

PROFESSIONAL ADAPTATION OF NEW EMPLOYEES WITHIN THE ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

Along with integration, adaptation to the workplace plays a very important role for both the individual and the organization.

Adaptation occurs when there is a change at the organizational level (changing the job position, changing the value objectives, technological developments, etc.), or when it occurs directly at the individual.

The individual can change their conceptions, their opinion about the company, their motivation, or when the employee has reached another point of maturity or professional career and wants to change his or her job.

Organizations select those people who have similar abilities and aptitudes, and if they were wrongly selected, they will at some point leave the organization due to inadequate work.

Adaptation in work refers to learning how to respect the behavioral model specific to the integrating environment.

The individual becomes aware of all their obligations (discipline at work, labor safety rules, manufacturing technology, behavior in the workgroup and in the collective, etc.), and gradually gets used to them.

Key words : new employee , adaptation, job , organization

INTRODUCTION

Adapting to the work is manifested by the satisfaction of the individual to the working environment and satisfaction to place the work to the individual contribution to achieving its goals.

The satisfaction and the ability to provide satisfaction have resulted in a lasting working relationship. The dimension of this duration can be predicted by the correspondence between the professional personality and the working environment .

The professional personality and the work environment can be described by the same size structure, which can be measured by means of common variables .

Adapted , it was enunciated by Dawis and Lofquist around two fundamental concepts:

a) the work environment, which means the organizational context that governs the work activities (objectives, resources, tasks, regulations, etc.)

b) professional personality (work personality), which means the resources and individual characteristics of the employees in the work process.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methods used in this study were different: the historical method, the comparative method, the sociological method, the logical method and the analytical one, their aim was the systematic analysis of the information selected from the sources studied in order to develop personal points of view and conclusions about the stated objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The adaptation of the human factor to his profession takes place on a double path:

- from the outside through the human resources management
- from the inside by adapting the work factor to the requirements and conditions of the professional activity

The adaptation of the human factor to the requirements and conditions of the professional activity will be done through the following psychic subsystems:

- the cognitive subsystem
- the affective subsystem
- the motivational subsystem
- adaptation processes.

The adaptation processes consist of:

- „the acquisition of knowledge and skills that the work process demands
- integration into the environmental environment in all its aspects, starting from the physico-chemical environment to the process and ending with the social environment " ¹

The beginning of the adaptation process cannot be determined exactly, because some believe that this process takes place right from the moment of reading the employment announcement.

The adaptation program can last from several weeks to several months, so it varies between two extremes:

1. The simplistic approach of checking the fumigation of the essential information
2. Formally organized packages to ensure professional adaptation of video messages, group activities, etc. This is a more expensive procedure

¹Scholz, M.M. (2000). Managementul resurselor umane. București: Editura Economica. 19. Sulea, C. Pagina 2000 pagina 91

and is carried out outside the workplace, involving people who have a higher status in the respective organization.

It usually occurs at certain time intervals when several newcomers are registered.

Following the recruitment process, when the human resources specialist acquires information about the candidate's skills and capabilities, he or she can develop an individual development plan to facilitate the adaptation process. ²

Scholz believes that success and professional stability are part of the adaptation process, which is more complex than the integration process.

„Thus, the professional stability of an individual depends on:

- emotional stability. Instability is the main cause of maladaptation
- self - image
- the attitude towards work and towards the person. Smith, Bruner and White say that "an attitude is a predisposition to experiment, to be motivated and to act in relation to a class of objects and in a predictable way"³

Along with integration, adapting the workplace plays a very important role for both the individual and the organization.

Adaptation occurs when a change occurs at the organizational level (changing the job description, changing objectives, values, technological developments, etc.), or when it appears directly to the individual.

The individual can change their conceptions, their opinion about the company, their motivation, or when the employee has reached another point of maturity or professional career and wants to change his or her job.

Counterproductive behavior, antisocial behavior, workplace deviance or dysfunctional component are names used in the literature to show a dark side of organizations, namely counterproductive behaviors in a workplace.

"Counterproductive behaviors are voluntary actions of employees, at or in the workplace, whose results are appreciated by the organization as harming its interests.

The fundamental elements of this definition are:

- the counter-productive character
- the intentional character
- expressing the vision of the organization

²Martin, M. și Jackson, T. (2008). *Practica de personal*. București: Editura Codecs

³ Scholz, M.M. (2000). *Managementul resurselor umane*. București: Editura Economica.
19. Sulea, C. Pagina 2000

"The deviance of employees is defined as voluntary behavior that violates organizational norms and thus threatens the well-being of the organization and / or its members" ⁴

McGregor has two theories about human behavior:

1. The assumptions of the "X" theory on human behavior are:
 - the human being is averse to work and seeks to avoid it if possible
 - for this reason most people must be constrained, controlled, guided or threatened with punishments in order to deter them from making an effort to achieve the organization's objectives
 - the average human being prefers to be guided, wants to avoid responsibility, has relatively low ambitions and wants safety above all

2. The "Y" theory hypothesizes on human behavior
 - ordinary people do not have an inherent aversion to work: depending on conditions, it can be a source of satisfaction or punishment
 - people will exercise their self-direction and self-control in the service of the goals entrusted to them, when they feel involved
 - the average human being learns, under appropriate conditions, not only to accept but also to seek responsibility. Many people are able to contribute creatively to solving the problems of the organization, but some are not required" ⁵

Counterproductive behaviors in the workplace can be classified as follows:

1. Organizationally oriented behaviors: theft, sabotage, absenteeism, delays, alcohol and / or drug use, intentional mistakes
2. Interpersonal behaviors: gossip, verbal abuse
3. Minor / serious behaviors: spread of rumors, aggression, violence (Șulea, 2004).

⁴ Robinson, S.L., Bennett R.J. (1995). A typology of deviant workplace behaviours: A multidimensional scaling study. *Academy of Management Journal*, pagina 556

⁵ . Modrea, A. (2013). *Managementul resurselor umane*. Târgu Mureș: Editura Universitatea Petru Maior.

CONCLUSIONS

According to the literature, the stages of the integration process are: introducing the employee into the organization, accommodating the employee within the organization, training at the workplace and managing the role.

Also, the specialized literature provides us with a series of integration models, the most common being the map of the meeting, the seminar and the visits to the company.

Along with integration, adaptation to the workplace plays a very important role for both the individual and the organization.

Adaptation occurs when a change occurs at the organizational level (changing the job description, changing objectives, values, technological developments, etc.), or when it appears directly to the individual.

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STUDY ON THE NATURAL, SOCIAL AND ANTHROPIC FRAMES EXISTING IN THE BUDUREASA COMMUNE, BIHOR

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Abstract

The commune of Budureasa is situated in the south-east part of Bihor county, in the Beiuș valley. In this paper we present the natural, social and anthropic frames of Budureasa commune. The commune of Budureasa is composed of five localities: Budureasa, Burda, Saca, Săliște de Beiuș and Teleac.

Key words: religious edifices, hydrographic potential, demographic aspects, population structure by nationality, population structure by religion

INTRODUCTION

Fishing, hunting, outdoor walks are some of a wide range of leisure possibilities tourists have at their disposal when visiting Budureasa commune.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

General aspects. The commune of Budureasa is composed of five localities: Budureasa, Burda, Saca, Săliște de Beiuș and Teleac.

Budureasa commune is located in the southeastern part of Bihor county, at the foot of the western slope of the Bihor Mountains, bounded on the north by the village of Cresuia, belonging to the commune of Curățele, on the east by the spa-climatic resort of Stâna de Vale, on the south by the Ferice and Săud, belonging to Buntești commune, and to the west of the village Mizieș and the city of Beiuș, at a distance of 12 km.

County Road 764 make the connection between the city of Beiuș, the center of Budureasa commune and Stâna de Vale, crossing the gentle hills of Budureasa.

Budureasa commune is crossed by numerous streams from several directions, some of them permanent, others temporarily. From the east side of the village Budureasa flows into the Valea Mare (Valea Buduresei), Valea Cohului and Valea Poienii. Valea Budureasa, after crossing a good

part of the village, near the Universal Store receives the Valea Plaiului and then continues to the northwest, separating Budureasa village from Cărbunari. On the territory of the village Burda adjoins the Valea Hijului and Burzeaua.

Hydrographic potential.

Crossing the villages of Burda, Pocioveliște, Cura and Nimăiești, they pour their waters into the Valea Nimăiești that passes through Beiuș municipality, next to the National College "Samuil Vulcan" and the agri-food market, pouring into Crișul Negru.

Valea Buduresei presents some very beautiful and attractive places for those who want to bathe in clean, clear, flowing water, of which we mention: Pietrele Albe, Firusău, Lespezi, Topile, Iazul Zbeuti, Lădoi, Iazul lui Teodoraș and Dascal, Gropana and Batrâna.

The village of Saca has a church dedicated to, "Sf. Gheorghe" a historical monument. Although it is a small village, over time it was a true focal point of Romanian culture in which cult books for the church were written, important church works were copied. The church has collected a number of old Romanian prints.

In the village of Săliște de Beiuș, in the eastern part of it, is the birthplace of the late poet Gheorghe Pituș. From the commune center, locals or tourists arriving on our lands can reach by bus to Stâna de Vale, Peștera Urșilor , Băile Felix, Oradea, Peștera Meziad and so on.

Demographic aspects.

According to the census conducted in 2011, Budureasa commune population was up to 2581 people, down from the previous census in 2002, when it had registered 2685 inhabitants.

Most residents are Romanians (74,97%). The main minorities are Romani (23,47%). For 1,56% of the population, ethnicity unknown.

By nationality, the population structure is shown in Table 1 (Source: INS 2013)

Table 1

Structura populației după naționalitate/Population structure by nationality

Nationality	Number inhabitants	%
Total	2581	100
Romanians	1934	74,97
Romani	606	23,47
Unknown	41	1,56

Sursa: INS 2013

In terms of confessional structure, most of the inhabitants are Orthodox (89,30%), Pentecostals (9,72%). For 0,98% of the population, the religious affiliation is unknown.

Population structure based on religion is presented in Table 2 (Source: INS 2013)

Table 2

Structura populației după religie/Population structure by religion

Religion	Number inhabitants	%
Total	2581	100
Orthodox	2305	89,30
Pentecostals	251	9,72
Unknown	25	0,98

Sursa: INS 2013

Tourism.

Stâna de Vale has excellent conditions of accommodation and spa treatment. From here you can choose tourist routes to Padiș, Cetățile Ponorului, Focul Viu, Valea Galbenă, Micău, Vlădeasa, Bohodei, Piatra Tâlharului, Piatra Grăitoare, Moara Dracului, Săritoarea Ieduțului, Valea Iadului, Casacada Vălul Miresei, Barajul Floroiu.

Stâna de Vale is a rest and treatment resort, located in Bihor county, located in the commune of Budureasa commune, in the Vladeasa Massif, at an altitude of 1100 m, being the center of precipitation in Romania.

The resort of Stâna de Vale is an ideal environment for spending a holiday in the middle of nature, and the pure air, without dust and allergic particles, rich in ozone. With relatively low atmospheric pressure, it offers the possibility of treatments such as in the case of asthenia, endocrine disorders, respiratory disorders, weakened body, physical and intellectual overloads, anemia, rickets and growth disorders in children.

The picturesque natural setting offered by the forests of huge firs and ferns, the meadows and meadows in the surroundings of the Bihor mountains, are the main attractions for tourists.

Pedoclimatic and vegetation factors create optimal conditions for the treatment of respiratory diseases, cardiovascular diseases and neuroses.

The main treatment factors in Stâna de Vale that attract thousands of tourists every year are the oligomineral and ferruginous waters, the tonic bioclimate, characterized by low atmospheric pressure, intense solar radiation and high ionization of the air.

The tourist attractions on the territory of Budureasa are:
Wooden Church “Sfântul Gheorghe” in the Saca village, 1724 construction, historical monument; *Natural reservation “Complexul Carstic din Valea Ponorului”* (168 ha.); *Natural reservation “Peștera Smeilor de la Onceasa”* (0,50 ha.), a monument of nature; *Natural reservation “Sistemul Carstic Peștera Cerbului - Avenul cu Vacă”* (45 ha.); *Natural reservation “Vârful Buteasa”*(2 ha.); *Natural reservation “Molhașurile din Valea Izbuțelor”* (80,02 ha.); *Natural reservation “Fâneața Izvoarelor Crișul Pietros”* (1 ha.); *Natural reservation “Vârful Cârligați”* (10 ha.); *Natural reservation “Piatra Grăitoare”* (5 ha.); *Natural reservation “Cetatea Rădesei”*(20 ha).

CONCLUSIONS

The commune of Budureasa is situated in the south-east part of Bihor county, in the Beiuș valley. The commune of Budureasa is composed of five localities: Budureasa, Burda, Saca, Săliște de Beiuș and Teleac. The Budureasa commune has many religious edifices, customs and crafts, natural sights very appreciated among tourists.

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ON DIFFERENTIAL SUBORDINATION RESULTS FOR P-VALENT FUNCTIONS

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Abstract

In this paper we derive some applications of first order differential subordination and superordination results involving a generalized multiplier transformations.

Key words: multiplier transformations, differential subordination, differential superordination.

INTRODUCTION

1.

Denote by U the open unit disc of the complex plane:

$$U = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z| < 1\}.$$

Let $\mathcal{H}$ be the class of analytic functions in U and for $a \in \mathbb{C}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let $\mathcal{H}[a,n]$ be the subclass of $\mathcal{H}$ consisting of functions of the form

$$f(z) = a + a_n z^n + a_{n+1} z^{n+1} + \dots, z \in U.$$

Let $\mathcal{A}(p,n)$ denote the class of functions $f(z)$ normalized by

$$f(z) = z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} a_k z^k, (p, n \in \mathbb{N} := \{1,2,3,\dots\})$$

which are analytic in the open unit disc. In particular, we set

$$\mathcal{A}(p,1) := \mathcal{A}_p \text{ and } \mathcal{A}(1,1) := \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_1.$$

Let

$$\mathcal{A}_* = \{f \in \mathcal{H}(U), f(z) = z + a_{n+1} z^{n+1} + \dots\}$$

with $\mathcal{A}_1 = \mathcal{A}$.

We denote by Q the set of functions f that are analytic and injective on $\bar{U} \setminus E(f)$, where

$$E(f) = \{\zeta \in \partial U : \lim_{z \rightarrow \zeta} f(z) = \infty\}$$

and are such that $f'(\zeta) \neq 0$ for $\zeta \in \partial U \setminus E(f)$.

Since we use the terms of subordination and superordination, we review here those definitions.

Let $f, F \in \mathcal{H}$. The function f is said to be subordinate to F or F is said to be superordinate to f , if there exists a function w analytic in U , with $w(0)=0$ and $|w(z)| < 1$, and such that $f(z) = F(w(z))$. In such case we write $f < F$ or $f(z) < F(z)$.

If F is univalent, then $f < F$ if and only if $f(0)=F(0)$ and $f(U) \subset F(U)$.

Since most of the functions considered in this paper and conditions on them are defined uniformly in the unit disk U , we shall omit the requirement " $z \in U$ ".

Let $\psi : \mathbb{C}^3 \times \bar{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, let h be univalent in U and $q \in Q$. In [6] the authors considered the problem of determining conditions on admissible function ψ such that

$$(1.2) \quad \psi(p(z), zp'(z), z^2p''(z); z) < h(z)$$

implies $p(z) < q(z)$, for all functions $p \in \mathcal{H}[a,n]$ that satisfy the differential subordination (1.2).

Moreover, they found conditions so that the function q is the "smallest" function with this property, called the best dominant of the subordination (1.2).

Let $\varphi : \mathbb{C}^3 \times \bar{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, let $h \in \mathcal{H}$ and $q \in \mathcal{H}[a,n]$. Recently, in [7] the authors studied the dual problem and determined conditions on φ such that

$$(1.3) \quad h(z) < \varphi(p(z), zp'(z), z^2p''(z); z)$$

implies $p(z) < q(z)$, for all functions $p \in Q$ that satisfy the above differential superordination.

Moreover, they found conditions so that the function q is the "largest" function with this property, called the best subordinant of the superordination (1.3).

For two functions

$$f(z) = z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} a_k z^k \text{ and } g(z) = z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} b_k z^k,$$

the Hadamard product of f and g is defined by

$$(f * g)(z) := z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} a_k b_k z^k.$$

MATERIAL AND METHOD

2. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

We begin our investigation by recalling here a generalized differential operator defined in [3].

Definition 2.1. [3] Let $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$. For $m \in \mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, $\lambda \geq 0$, $l \geq 0$, we define the multiplier transformations $I_p^m(\lambda, l)$ on $\mathcal{A}(p, n)$ by the following infinite series

$$(2.1) \quad I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) := z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} \left[\frac{p+\lambda(k-p)+l}{p+l} \right]^m a_k z^k.$$

It follows from (2.1) that

$$(2.2) \quad (p+l)I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) = [p(1-\lambda) + l]I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) + \lambda z(I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z))'.$$

Remark 2.1 For $p=1$, $l=0$, $\lambda \geq 0$, the operator $I_1^m(\lambda, 0) \equiv D_\lambda^m$ was introduced and studied by Al-Oboudi [1] which reduces to the Sălăgean differential operator [8] for $\lambda = 1$. The operator $I_1^m(1, l) \equiv I_l^m$ was studied recently by Cho and Srivastava [4] and Cho and Kim [5].

In this paper, we will derive several subordination results involving the operator $I_p^m(\lambda, l)$. In order to prove our main results, we also need the following result.

Lemma 2.1 [6] Let q be univalent in U , $\gamma \in \mathbb{C}^*$ and suppose

$$\operatorname{Re} \left[1 + \frac{zq''(z)}{q'(z)} \right] > \max \left\{ 0, -\operatorname{Re} \frac{1}{\gamma} \right\}.$$

If h is analytic in U , with $h(0) = q(0)$ and

$$h(z) + \gamma zh'(z) < q(z) + \gamma zq'(z),$$

then $h < q$, and q is the best dominant.

3. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 3.1. Let q be univalent in U , with $q(0) = 1$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}^*$, $m, \beta \in \mathbb{N}_0 = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ and suppose

$$\operatorname{Re} \left\{ 1 + \frac{zq''(z)}{q'(z)} \right\} > \max \left\{ 0, -\frac{p+l}{\lambda} \operatorname{Re} \frac{1}{\alpha} \right\}.$$

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$ satisfies the subordination

$$(3.1)$$

$$\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \frac{\alpha}{z^p} \left(I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right) < q(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l}zq'(z),$$

then

$$\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} < q(z)$$

and q is the best dominant of (3.1).

Proof. We define the function

$$(3.2) \quad h(z) := \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p}.$$

Differentiating (3.2) with respect to z and using the identity (2.2) in the resulting equation we have

$$\frac{zh'(z)}{h(z)} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \left\{ (p+l) \frac{I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)}{I_p^m(\lambda, l)} - [p(1-\lambda) + l + \lambda p] \right\}.$$

Therefore, we obtains

$$\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \frac{\alpha}{z^p} \left(I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right) = h(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l}zh'(z).$$

The subordination (3.1) from the hypothesis becomes

$$h(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l}zh'(z) < q(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l}zq'(z).$$

We apply now Lemma 2.1 with $\gamma = \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l}$ to obtain the conclusion of the theorem. $\square$

If we consider $m = 0$ in Theorem 3.1 we obtain the following result.

Corollary 3.1 Let q be univalent in U , with $q(0) = 1$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}^*$ and suppose

$$\operatorname{Re} \left[1 + \frac{zq''(z)}{q'(z)} \right] > \max \left\{ 0, -\frac{p+l}{\lambda} \operatorname{Re} \frac{1}{\alpha} \right\}.$$

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$ satisfies the subordination

$$(3.3) \quad (1-\alpha) \frac{f(z)}{z^p} + \alpha \frac{I_p^1(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} < q(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l}zq'(z),$$

then

$$\frac{f(z)}{z^p} < q(z)$$

and q is the best dominant of (3.3).

We consider a particular convex function $q(z) = \frac{1+Az}{1+Bz}$ to give the following application to Theorem 3.1.

Corollary 3.2 Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$, $A \neq B$ such that $-1 \leq B < A \leq 1$ and $\operatorname{Re} \alpha > 0$.

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$ satisfies the subordination

$$(3.4) \quad (1 - \alpha) \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \alpha \frac{I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} < \frac{1+Az}{1+Bz} + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} \frac{(A-B)z}{(1+Bz)^2}$$

then

$$\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} < \frac{1+Az}{1+Bz}$$

and $q(z) = \frac{1+Az}{1+Bz}$ is the best dominant of (3.4).

Taking $q(z) = \frac{1+z}{1-z}$ in Theorem 3.1 we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 3.3 Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ and $\text{Re } \alpha > 0$. If $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$ satisfies the subordination

$$(3.5) \quad (1 - \alpha) \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \alpha \frac{I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} < \frac{1+z}{1-z} + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} \frac{2z}{(1-z)^2}$$

then

$$\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} < \frac{1+z}{1-z}$$

and $q(z) = \frac{1+z}{1-z}$ is the best dominant of (3.5).

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DEVELOPMENT OF SOME INCLUSION BACKGROUNDS

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Abstract

Inclusive education involves a permanent process of improving the school institution, with the purpose of exploiting the existing resources, especially of human resources, to support the participation in the education process of all students within a community. The guiding principle should aim to provide equal education for all children, providing additional assistance and support to children in need.

In order to be able to track the progress of each educated person, the evaluation procedures must be revised, which must be incorporated in the ordinary educational process, in order to permanently inform the students and teachers both on the level of learning achieved and on the difficulties, but also to help the students to overcome them. Inclusive school represents a unit of education that ensures education for all children, the most effective means of combating discriminatory attitudes; it is the school that does not select and does not exclude, being an open, tolerant, friendly and democratic one; by its heterogeneity, it is natural, valuing all students; it adapts to the diversity of educational needs and to the particularities of learning and development.

Inclusive School puts the spotlight man, as being original, unique and unrepeatable.

Key words : inclusive education, principle, progress, educational process

INTRODUCTION

School learning is an ongoing process that is completed by classroom interactions and highlights the accumulation of each student. For personality development of psychosocial competence building, learning is more important than the product, not the students can be considered a problem, if not adjust rates proposed school learning. Inclusive school policies would lead to a school that seeks to include all students in the community and where there is an effective integration program for all. The inclusive approach is found not only at the level of the education system but also at the level of the teaching process. The main features of the inclusive teaching process are those related to its adaptation to the differences between children. Teachers with a wealth of personal and social life experience use relationships with parents and other community members to improve the methods used in teaching-learning in the classroom. Relationships between teachers are a source of learning and a continuous exchange of experience. It is the teacher who organizes the

learning situations in which all the students are involved and he / she can capitalize on the potential of each one, in a positive and flexible way.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the ontent of teaching students with intellectual disabilities , it is necessary to follow a few types of instructional approaches :

a. Visual approach – The most recommended teaching approach for students with intellectual disabilities is to use visual prompts. Students often show strong points in concrete thinking, repetitive memory and understanding of visual-spatial aspects and difficulties in abstract thinking, social knowledge, communication and attention. Pictorial and written directions can often help the student to learn, communicate and develop self-control. One of the benefits of using visual prompts is that students can use them as long as they need to process information. Unlike these, the oral information is transient: once said, the message is no longer available, the oral information may raise problems for students who have difficulty in language processing and who need extra time. In addition, it may be difficult for the student with the ESC to assimilate relevant information and simultaneously be able to block background stimulation. Using visual prompts we allow the student to focus on the message. Visual timepieces and visual symbols vary in complexity from simple and concrete to abstract. The content varies from object or real situation , to color photography, color image, black and white image, and finally to the graphic symbol and the written language. Objects are the simplest form of help. Graphic symbols, although far in the spectrum / continuum of visual representations in terms of complexity and abstraction, have proved successful in the case of students with CES. There are now numerous software packages that provide quick access to graphic symbols and the ability to create custom symbols for free or at affordable prices. Visual prompts can be used in a variety of ways in the classroom. However, in order to be successful, they must match the level of understanding of the student, that is, by making sure that they are at the appropriate point on the continuum of the complexity we talked about earlier. Using graphic with lines to support learning when the student needs color photographs to understand, will only generate frustration for all participants in the educational act.

b. Other approaches - we keep accurate, positive praise while the student is learning, accurate information about what they are doing right or right; for example, *you solved these math problems very well* . Generalized praise can lead to unintended learning, which is difficult to revise. Students with CES can learn through trials, so directing praise to

very specific behavior is a very important aspect: "*Mihai, you are very good at analyzing the bad stories*". Learning based on unrealistic associations may occur if students erroneously correlate with what they hear. Speaking exclusively "*Bravo Mihai !*" when Mihai stands up while doing the math problem, it can result in a correlation between standing and general praise. Reinforcers can be anything from praise to tangible objects , which enhance the student's behavior , is to learn. Students with ESC cannot be motivated by common reinforcements that work with other students. They may prefer time spent alone, time to talk to a person favorite school, a trip to the cafeteria, an exercise routine (eg walking), time to play a desired object, a game, a rut take preferred, elements that provide sensory stimulation or window state.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Students with CES may be particularly vulnerable to anxiety and intolerant to feelings of frustration if they are unable to perform their assigned tasks. Increasing the level of difficulty and supporting learning (especially with visual information, rather than just oral explanations) will help minimize student frustration. It is particularly important to respect the dignity of the students with CES , including through the type of materials chosen for the training. Even if the training needs to be significantly altered, the learning materials must be appropriate to the student's age. There is indicated to underestimate the comprehension of the student based on appearances and equally not appropriate to relate, permanent , standard typical students. Each student is unique and has a threshold from which learning can occur effectively. A dedicated teacher can observe the learning threshold and can generate a fundamental change in the learning curve of a student with ESC.

Given that students with CES may be frequently frustrated by their inability to understand themselves, they need training and practice to make choices that are beneficial to themselves. We need to keep in mind that many aspects of their lives can be well structured and controlled by adults. Sometimes , students continue to choose an activity or object because they do not know how to choose another. Thus , individual methods must be developed to give students the opportunity to choose in the absence of an ability to communicate. Direct learning to do chores can be a useful method, choice should be limited to one or two preferred activities , until the student understands the concept of choice, as open-ended laws will not enhance the student's ability to make choices and can cause frustration.

When provide instruction for pupils with SEN should avoid it loped long oral information, training oral and visual representations clues should help the students to understand. Students with CES may need more time to respond than other students. This may be related to cognitive and / or motor difficulties. Students with special needs may need to process each component of the message or requirement and , therefore, need additional time to respond. Providing extra time in general, and sufficient time between instruction and student responses are some important tactics for supporting students with CES.

In general, we render abstract ideas and conceptual thinking using specific examples , so that the concept is not accidentally learned as being applied in one way. Teachers and parents may need to stage complex tasks into sub-tasks and consolidate them into small steps that can be learned. For each step of a complex task, the student must have the skills necessary to complete it, these sub-skills can be learned and strengthened in turn. Life skills, social skills and academic skills can be analyzed and addressed as tasks and sub-tasks, with each step learned and then linked to the next sub-task of the chain.

In order to achieve the full success of the integration of children with special educational needs into a mass / inclusive school, it is necessary to go through several distinct stages in order to ensure the optimum conditions for a new form of school organization and curriculum. applied by the respective school:

- ❖ sensitization - the first stage that aims to prepare the school environment (starting with the school management, continuing with the teachers, the students, the administrative staff, the parents of the children);

- ❖ training - is the stage in which the people in school involved in didactic activities and who show openness towards inclusive practices are co-opted in a training program in which they learn principles, methods and techniques appropriate to the instructional-educational activities with the deficient or difficult students, thus for each child to receive knowledge in forms accessible to their own learning abilities and requirements;

- ❖ analysis on the school environment and decision - making - this is the stage that involves the reorganization of the institutional structures, a new way of managing and allocating school resources, revising the attitude of all school employees towards the educational act under the new conditions imposed by the inclusive principles and practices.

The promotion of inclusive education in mainstream schools implies, from the teaching and specialist staff, a series of qualities such as:

- ❖ the responsibility of recognizing the level of professional competence and the desire to improve the working capacities in the inclusive education conditions;
- ❖ critical and constructive attitude through concrete and realistic proposals to support the integration of children with special educational requirements in the classes where they operate;
- ❖ total involvement in the teaching process, so as to satisfy to the maximum the educational requirements of the students in the classroom;
- ❖ treating students with dignity, respect and consideration regarding the particular situation in which children with special educational requirements are;
- ❖ belief that inclusive education involves necessarily work in teams of specialists: teachers, educators, support teachers, counselors, social workers, psychologists specializing in activities with different groups of children with special needs etc. .

CONCLUSIONS

The play is designed taking into account the level of learning of all students, lessons encouraging the participation of all students, stimulating understanding and acceptance of differences. The students are actively involved in their own learning process, assimilating through cooperation. Evaluation contributes to the growth of performances, teachers having the role of planning, teaching and evaluating in partnership, the theme for home contributes to the success of learning of all students, all students participate in activities organized outside the classroom. The differences of students are used as resources for teaching and learning, life experience of personnel being put in value the most, involving various funds to support learning and participation of the students. The resources of the school are distributed fairly so that they support inclusion, promoting the education and participation of all children in mass education.

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INTERACTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING-LEARNING IN THE TEACHING OF THE EXERCISE COMPANY

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Abstract

The school of the future will surely be a cybernetized school, a "living" computer lab, interdisciplinary, which will prepare early children to become problem solvers, creators again and able to make optimal decisions in the face of increasingly unusual and unusual situations of current social life and perspective. Alvin Toffler says - the fundamental objective of "supra-industrial" education - "must be to increase the adaptability of the individual , so that he can adapt quickly and easily to the permanent novelty. And the faster the pace of change, the more attention is required to discern the type of events that will occur. " Interactive group methods are a way of modern stimulations of personal learning and development from an early age are teaching tools that favor the exchange of ideas, experiences, and knowledge. Interactivity involves learning through communication, through collaboration, it produces a confrontation of ideas, opinions and arguments, it creates learning situations centered on the availability and willingness of children to cooperate, on their direct and active involvement, on the mutual influence within the micro-groups and on social interaction of the members of a group.

Key words: exercise company , interactive teaching methods, educational process, skills methods .

INTRODUCTION

Method of teaching / learning each other 's a strategy learning instructional techniques to study the text. Once they are familiar with the method , the students interpret the role of the teacher, instructing their colleagues; a development of the student-student dialogue takes place ; and it can carry groups or with the whole class, the method focuses on four learning strategies used by anyone who makes a study of text on various topics. These strategies are: predicting, summarizing, asking questions, clarifying data. The resume means exposure to what is most important in terms that it is to read. Asking questions refers to the listing of a series of questions about the information read; he who asks the questions must of course know the answer. Clarification involves discussing unknown terms, more difficult to understand, appeal to various sources, and resolving misunderstandings. Predictability refers to expressing what students think will happen next, based on what they have read. The stages of the method involve explaining the purpose and describing the

method and the four strategies; group organization; team work; achievement of mutual learning; to pray, additions, comments.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Methods of interactive teaching and learning are mosaic method pyramid technique as lotus, starburst, palaloped thinking, teaching and mutual learning, exchange pair, cause and effect diagram technique 6/3/5 method FRISCO, brainstorming .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mosaic method (jigsaw) - (English , jigsaw puzzle means mosaic) or "method interdependent groups" - as he calls Neculau A. (1998) is based on team learning (team-learning). Each student has a task of study in which he must become an "expert"; it also has the responsibility of transmitting assimilated information to other colleagues. Stages and phases: 1. Preparation of the study material: The teacher establishes the study topic and divides it into 4 or 5 sub-themes. Optionally, it can establish for each sub-topic, the main elements that the student must emphasize, when studying the material independently. These can be formulated either in the form of questions, or in the affirmative, or an elliptical text that can only be completed when the student is studying the material. (Make an expert sheet that passes the 4 or 5 sub-themes proposed and will be offered to each group). 2. Organizing the team in learning teams of 4-5 students (depending on their number in the classroom). Each student in the team receives a number from 1 to 4-5 and has the task of studying independently, the sub-topic corresponding to its number. He must become an expert in the given problem. For example, students with the number 1 of all the learning teams formed, will deepen the sub-theme with the number 1. Those with the number 2 will study the sub-theme number 2, and so on. Independent phase: Each student studies his sub-theme, reads the corresponding text. This independent study can be done in the classroom or it can be a homework, done before the mosaic is organized. 3. Formation of expert groups: d fter which have undergone independent working phase, with the same number were combined experts, An expert group to consider the matter together. Thus, students with number 1 leave the initial learning teams and gather at a table to deepen the sub-theme with number 1. So do the other students with numbers 2, 3, 4 or 5. If the expert group has more than 6 members, it is divided into two smaller groups. Discussion phase in the expert group: The students present an individual report on what they have studied independently. Discussions take place based on the data and

materials available, new elements are added and the way in which the new knowledge will be transmitted to the other members of the initial team is also established. Each student is a member of a group of experts and is part of a learning team. From the point of view of the physical arrangement, the workgroups of the expert groups must be placed in different places of the classroom, in order not to disturb each other. The common purpose of each group of experts is to train as best they can, having the responsibility of their own learning and the teaching and learning of colleagues from the initial team.

4. Return to the initial learning team - Phase of the team report: The experts transmit the assimilated knowledge, retaining the knowledge that their colleagues, experts in other sub-topics, transmit. The mode of transmission must be short, concise, attractive, and may be accompanied by audio-visual media, various materials. Specialists in a sub-theme can demonstrate an idea, read a report, use the computer, illustrate ideas with diagrams, drawings, photographs. Members are encouraged to discuss, ask questions and make notes, each with their own ideas plan.

5. Evaluation Demonstration phase: The groups present the results of the whole class. At this point, students are ready to demonstrate what they have learned. The teacher can ask questions, ask for a report or essay or give each student an evaluation sheet to solve. If oral assessment is used, then each student will be asked a question to which they must answer without the help of the team.

The “Change the pair” method is based on the work of the students in pairs as follows: the class is divided into two equal groups as the number of participants; two concentric circles are formed, the pupils facing each other in pairs. The teacher asks a question or gives a task in pairs. Each pair discusses and then communicates ideas. The outer circle rotates clockwise, thus changing partners in pairs. Students have the opportunity to work with each member of the class. Each one is involved in the activity and contributes to solving the task.

Method stages: The stage of organizing the collective into two equal groups. Each student occupies a chair, either in the inner circle or in the outer circle. The teacher can give the students the freedom to choose their place or they can organize the group by having the children number two by two. Thus, those with the number 1 will sit in the inner circle facing the outside, and those with the number 2 in the outer circle facing the students in the inner circle. Standing face to face, each student has a partner. If the number of students is odd, the teacher may also participate in the activity or two students may work in tandem.

Presentation and explanation of the problem: The teacher offers the cases for study, the problems to be solved or the teaching situations and explains the importance of the solution.

Work in pairs: Students work two for two for a few minutes. Then the students from the outer circle move a place to the right to

change their partners, thus creating a new pair. The game is continued until the initial partners are reached or the questions are completed. The stage of analyzing ideas and drawing conclusions: At this moment, the class is grouped and the ideas emitted are analyzed. The teacher draws together with the students a diagram of the conclusions drawn. 4. *The pyramid* method or the "snowball" method is based on combining the individual activity with the cooperative one, within the groups. It consists in incorporating the activity of each member of the collective into a broader collective approach, meant to lead to the solving of a given task or problem. Phases of carrying out the pyramid method: 1. Introductory phase: the teacher sets out the data of the problem in question; 2. Phase of individual work: students work on their own to solve the problem for five minutes. At this stage, the questions related to the subject are noted. 3. Work in pairs: students form groups of two students to discuss the individual results reached by each one. Answers to individual questions from colleagues are requested and, at the same time, they are noted if new ones arise. 4. The reunion phase in larger groups. Usually, two large groups are made up, approximately equal in number of participants, composed of the smaller groups previously existing and the solutions reached are discussed. At the same time, it answers the remaining unresolved questions. The phase of reporting solutions in the collective - the whole class, gathered, analyzes and concludes on the ideas issued. They can be put on the board so that they can be viewed by all participants and compared. The answers to the unresolved questions up to this phase are also clarified, with the help of the manager (teacher); The decision-making phase - the final solution is chosen and conclusions are drawn on the steps taken and on the participation of the students / students in the activity.

The cause and effect diagram offers the possibility of highlighting the sources of a problem, event or outcome. The diagrams are used by the group as a creative process of generating and organizing the major (main) and minor (secondary) causes of an effect. Rules of organization and stages of the cause and effect diagram are as follows: divides the class into teams of laborers; to determine the issue to be discussed which is a particular event or event - the effect. Each group has an effect to analyze; the debate was held in each group to discover the causes that led to the effect discussed. The cases are registered on paper or on the board; reconstruction of the cause and effect diagram as follows: - the main axis of the diagram passes the effect; - the main causes of the effect correspond to the branches of the main axis corresponding to the 6 questions: WHEN ?, WHERE ?, WHO ?, WHY? (it happened); - as (secondary) arising from the principal is written on a smaller subset that is deducted from the major causes; Examining the list of causes generated by

each group: examining the partners; evaluating the way in which the major and minor causes were distinguished and their correct placement in the diagram, the major ones on the main branches, the minor ones on the secondary ones, relating and / or arising from them; evaluating the diagrams of each group and discussing them; establish the conclusions and the importance of the major causes. The technique of LOTUS (Flower of lily) implies the deduction of connections between ideas, concepts, starting from a central theme. The central issue or theme determines the 8 secondary ideas that are built around the main one, like the petals of the lily flower. The 8 secondary ideas are passed around the central theme, and then they become the main themes for 8 other flowers of lily. For each of these new central themes, 8 new secondary ideas will be built. Thus, starting from a central theme, new study themes are generated for which new connections and new concepts need to be developed. STAGE ART FLOWER lily targeting the construction of the diagram; writing the central theme in the center of the diagram; The participants think about ideas or applications related to the central theme. These are passed in the 8 "petals" (circles) that surround the central theme, from A to H, in the sense of clockwise; the use of the 8 ideas deduced, as new central themes for the other 8 quadrants. ("Lily flowers") ; It is the stage of building new connections for the 8 new central themes and recording them in the diagram - in this way as many quadrants are completed. ("Lily flowers") ; the idea evaluation stage - the diagrams are analyzed and the results from the qualitative and quantitative point of view are appreciated ; The issued lectures can be used as a source of new applications and study topics in future lessons. The Lotus technique can be successfully used in groups, being adaptable to broad age categories and domains. There is also the possibility of developing an individual Lotus, as an exercise in stimulating creativity and self-evaluation. For example, the central theme might be the question: "What would you like to study?", Which could be proposed 8 areas and for each one would be recorded the contents that correspond to the subject's interest.

Brainstorming , "delayed assessment" or "brain storm" is an interactive method of developing new ideas resulting from the discussions between several participants, each of which comes with a lot of suggestions. The result of these discussions results in the choice of the best solution to solve the debated situation. As a method of discussion and group creation, brainstorming (brain = brain, storming = stormy) was systematized in 1948 by professor at the University of Buffalo (USA), Alexander Osborn. The results of the experiments were published by Osborn in 1961 in the paper Appliedimagination. The method of "brainstorming" or "cascading ideas" aims to issue as many solutions, ideas, as possible on how to solve a problem, hoping that by combining them, the optimal solution will be

obtained. The way to get these ideas is to stimulate creativity within the group, in a non-critical, non-inhibiting atmosphere, a result of the postponement of the evaluation moment. In other words, the participants are released from any constraints, they communicate without fear that they will say something wrong or inappropriate, which will be appreciated as such by the other participants. The purpose of the method is to free the imagination, the unusual and original ideas, the unconventional opinions, provoking a chain reaction, constructive, to create "ideas on ideas." In this sense, an idea or suggestion, apparently unrelated. with the problem in question, it can provide premises for the emergence of other ideas from the other participants. Osborn's method is based on four fundamental rules of creative thinking: deliberate searching of ideas, postponing the judgment of ideas, large number of ideas, fertile exchange of ideas. Brainstorming takes place in a meeting of a very small group (maximum 30 people), preferably heterogeneous in terms of training and occupations, under the coordination of a moderator, who plays the role of both animator and as a mediator. The optimal duration is 20-45 minutes. Specific to this method is the fact that it comprises two moments: one of ideas production and then the moment of their evaluation (critical appraisal phase). The rules for conducting brainstorming are as follows:

- Knowledge of the issue discussed and the need to solve it, based on the clear and concise presentation from the moderator of the discussion;
- Carefully selecting the participants based on the principle of heterogeneity in terms of age, preparation, without antipathy;
- Ensuring a suitable place (no noise), spacious, bright, designed to create a stimulating atmosphere, conducive to the discussion of ideas;
- Admission and even encouraging formulating ideas as bold as unusual times, leaving participants imagination, spontaneity and creativity;
- In the first phase, the emphasis is on quantity, on the formulation of as many response variants and as diverse;
- The construction of "ideas on ideas", in the sense that, an answer can provoke associations and combinations for issuing a new cognitive-innovative approach;
- Discrete, accurate and complete recording of the discussions by a person specially designated to fulfill this role (or on the tape), without hindering the participants or the discussion;
- The evaluation is suspended and will be carried out later by the coordinator, with or without the help of the participants;
- Harnessing the ideas that come after the "incubation" period in a new session one , the next day the participants can meet again;

Starburst (starbursting) , (eng. "Star" = star; eng. "Burst" = explode), is a new method for the development of creativity, similar to brainstorming. It starts from the center of the concept and spreads out, with questions, like a stellar explosion. How to do it: Write the idea or problem on a sheet of paper and ask as many questions as possible about it. A good starting point is those of the type: What ?, Who ?, Where ?, Why ?, When ?. The list of initial questions can generate unexpected ones that may require even greater concentration to answer them. The aim of the method is to get as many questions and so many connections as strengthen concepts. It is a way of stimulating individual and group creativity. Organized in a group, the stellar explosion facilitates the participation of the whole group, stimulates the creation of questions to questions, as the brainstorming develops the construction of ideas on ideas. The steps of the method aims proposals a problem; organizing the collective into preferential groups; work in the team by elaborating a list with more and more diverse questions ; bad results of group work; it is the settlement of the most interesting questions and the appreciation of the work in cooperation. Optionally, it is possible to proceed to the elaboration of answers to some of the questions. The stellar explosion method is easy to apply to any age and to a wide range of domains. It is not expensive and does not require detailed explanations. The participants get caught up quickly in the game, on the one hand it is a way to relax and, on the other hand, a source of new discoveries.

The method Hat thinking ("Thinkinghats" - Edward de Bono) is t is an interactive technique for stimulating creativity participants based on the role-playing based on the selected hat. There are 6 thinking hats, each with a color: white, red, yellow, green, blue and black. The members of the group choose their hats and will thus interpret the precise role, as they see fit. The roles can be reversed, the participants are free to say what they think, but to agree with the role they play. The color of the hat is what defines the role. Thus , the White Hat: • Offers an objective look at the information; • It is neutral; • It is focused on objective facts and clear images; • It is under the sign of objective thinking; Red hat: • It frees the imagination and feelings; • Provides an emotional perspective on events; • Red can also mean anger or anger; • It unlocks the affective states;

The black hat: • Expresses caution, care, warning, judgment; • Give her r spectators dark, sad, bleak the situation in question; • It is the perspective of negative, pessimistic thinking; Yellow hat: • Provides the r spectators positive and constructive on the situation • Yellow symbolizes sunshine, brightness, optimism; • It is optimistic, constructive thinking on a logical basis; The green hat: • Expresses new ideas, stimulating creative thinking; • It is the fresh green of the grass, of the vegetation, of the abundance; • It is the symbol of fertility, of the production

of new, innovative ideas; Blue hat: • Expresses control of the thought process; • Blue is cold; it is the color of heaven that is above all, all-seeing and all-knowing; • Supervises and supervises the smooth running of the activity; • It is the concern to control and organize; Participants need to know very well the meaning of each color and to represent each hat, thinking from its perspective. Not the hat itself matters, but what it means, what induces the color of each one. The 6 thinking hats can be viewed in pairs: White hat - red hat ; Black hat - yellow hat ; The green hat - the blue hat . How is this method used? The 6 thinking hats are divided to the students and the case is presented for discussion so that each one can prepare their ideas. The hat can be worn individually - and then the student plays the role - or more students can respond under the same hat. In this case, the students of the group interpreting the role of a thinking hat cooperate in ensuring the best interpretation. They can wear each hat of the same color. Being aware that: The blue hat clarifies white hat informs green hat generates new ideas .

The 6/3/5 technique is similar to brainstorming. New ideas, however, are written on paper sheets circulating among participants, which is why it is also called the brainwriting method. The technique is called 6/3/5 because there are: - 6 members in the working group, who write down on a sheet of paper how many - 3 solutions each, for a given problem, for - 5 minutes. The steps of method 6/3/5: 1. Divide the class into groups of 6 members each. 2. Formulate the problem and explain the working method. Students each receive a sheet of paper divided into three columns. 3. Conduct group activity. The pins of the standing stage consists of a combination of individual collective activity. For this problem, each of the 6 participants, has to write down on a sheet, 3 solutions in the table with 3 columns, in a maximum time of 5 minutes. The sheets then migrate from left to right until they reach the original owner. The one who received the colleague's sheet from the left, reads the solutions already noted and tries to modify them in a creative way, by new formulations, adapting them, improving them and reconstructing them continuously. 4. Analyze the solutions and retain the best ones. Centralize the obtained data, discuss and evaluate the results.

11. Philips 6/6 was developed by literature professor J. Donald Philips (where his name comes from) who tested it at the University of Michigan. It is similar to brainstorming and the 6/3/5 method, but it is individualized by limiting the discussion of the 6 participants to 6 minutes. This fact aims to intensify creative production, as in the case of method 6/3/5. The stages of the Philips 6/6 method: 1. Establishment of groups of 6 participants (4 members + 1 secretary + 1 group leader). The secretary of each group also has the task of writing down the ideas of the

colleagues. The leader is the one who leads the debate within the group and presents the conclusions. 2. Handing over the topic / issue to be discussed in particular, by each group and motivating its importance. 3. Conduct discussions based on the theme, within the group, for 6 minutes. These can be free, in the sense that each member proposes an answer and in the end the most important ideas are retained or they can be progressive discussions in which each participant exposes within his group a variant that is analyzed and then moves on to the other ideas. 4. Collecting the solutions developed - The leaders of each group set out the ideas to which they arrived or they are handed over in writing to the coordinator of the group (the teacher). 5. The collective discussion, the collective decision regarding the final solution, based on the hierarchy of variants

12. The Frisco method is based on the interpretation by the participants of a specific role, covering a certain dimension of personality, approaching a problem from several perspectives. Thus, the group will have to play each turn, the role exuberance role of pessimist and optimist role. The method was proposed by the Four Boys of Frisco research team (the four boys in San Francisco), and its purpose is to identify complex and difficult problems and solve them in simple and efficient ways. It is based on directed brainstorming and asks the pupils / students empathic abilities, critically least then emphasis on stimulating thinking, imagination and creativity. The stages of the Frisco method: it involves solving the problem - the teacher or the students notify a situation-problem and propose it for analysis; the organization of the collective - the roles are established: the conservative, the exuberant, the pessimistic, the optimistic and who will interpret them. Roles can be approached individually or, in the case of large groups, the same role can be played by several participants simultaneously, forming a team. Stage of collective debate: each interprets the chosen role and supports his point of view in accordance with it. The one who is conservative has the role of appreciating the merits of the old solutions, deciding for their maintenance, without excluding the possibility of possible improvements. The exuberant looks to the future and issues ideas seemingly impossible to apply in practice, thus ensuring an imaginative-creative, innovative framework and stimulating the other participants to look at things in this way. It is based on a contagion phenomenon. It is the pessimist who does not have a good opinion about what is being discussed, censoring the initial ideas and solutions proposed. It highlights the aspects of any improvements. Optimist illuminates the shadow left by the pessimist, encouraging participants to look at things from a real, concrete and achievable perspective. He finds realistic foundations and the possibilities of realizing the solutions proposed by the exuberant., Stimulating the participants to think positively. The stage of systematizing

the ideas issued and the conclusion on the solutions found. At this stage, the elaboration of the main ideas and the formulation of the conclusions regarding the solution of the initial problem were set. It is like "Thinking Hats" both in terms of deployment and in terms of benefits and lim and communication.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, these methods are welcomed in the educational activity, because it helps us a lot - both teachers and students - to see with real eyes the real life and, implicitly, the role of the school in the training and professional training at high parameters of the young woman generations. Through the exercise company, students have a different perspective on the business environment and more confidence in their own capabilities and opportunities that the future offers. They know better the realities of the labor market and they will know what is the way to choose a successful profession or business.

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THE ROLE OF THE RURAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGROTOURISM

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Abstract

The Romanian rural environment is not a serial product, because it bears the imprint of the unhackneyed, of the original and as a result it arrives itself in front of the urban communities.

Romania has great possibilities for agro-tourism development which can be a way of increasing the standard of living and civilization of the Romanian village, and its inhabitants, through hospitality, can compete with the inhabitants of other European states.

Key words: agrotourism, rural environment

INTRODUCTION

In the rural area an economic activity has appeared complementary to the agriculture called agrotourism, a form of manifestation of rural tourism.

Many tourists are hesitating in spending a holiday in the countryside, although here we can also find a natural environment characterized by value and landscape variety to which is added a valuable cultural, historical and ethnographic heritage. On the other hand, the rural localities through the less degraded environment, through the tourist resources it has can represent a space for the discharge of the big tourist agglomerations.

Spending a holiday in the rural area can also be financially attractive because the agro-tourism respectively the rural tourism is addressed to the population with average and modest incomes. In Romania, tourists with incomes above average practice agro-tourism and rural tourism on the occasion of the two major religious holidays over the year (Christmas and Easter) because the Romanian rural environment is the preserve of the traditions and customs of the ancestors.

The rural environment and the agrotourism support each other through the following aspects:

- agrotourism offers the inhabitants of rural areas jobs;
- the rural environment represents the support for new businesses, including agro-tourism;

- by practicing agrotourism, the anthropic tourist resources of great value of the rural environment are emphasized: handicrafts, gastronomy, customs and traditions;
- agrotourism determines the increase of the income of the inhabitants of the rural area;
- the rural environment through the infrastructure it has determines whether or not the agritourism is practiced.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

For agrotourism the rural environment plays an important role. In order to be able to capture the close connection between them it is necessary to do an x-ray of the rural environment so that we can capture the interdependence between the two.

In Romania many villages can constitute spaces for practicing agrotourism because they have natural, ethnographic and socio-economic qualities that turn them into tourist products of great originality.

In order to become a tourist village any rural locality must benefit from minimum conditions such as:

- location in a picturesque natural environment, without sources of pollution;
- accessibility by various means of transport;
- water supply, electricity, sewerage, ie the presence of municipal facilities;
- the presence of households with comfort.

The lack of the "modernism of the urban civilization", the aging and conservative population, are elements that have led to the preservation of a well-defined cultural identity by which the Romanian village differs from the tourist villages in other European countries.

Agrotourism in Romania in its current meaning can be practiced because we still meet isolated traditional villages with dominant agricultural activities compared to the rural localities in the EU that have changed much their appearance and functions.

At the national level agrotourism can be practiced in many geographical areas and regions, respectively where the organization of the peasant household, the architecture and the popular creation, the customs and traditions are kept unaltered by the rural communities: Apuseni Mountains, Maramureș, Bucovina, Mărginimea Sibiului, Transilvania, Dobrogea etc.

The identification of the Romanian rural potential that is suitable for the development of agrotourism is achieved through two aspects:

1. conducting a study on the natural and cultural heritage of an area;
2. identification of peasant households that can be introduced to the agrotourism circuit.

The specificity of an agro-tourist area or region is given by the **traditional architecture** that puts its mark on the aspect of a household. Any peasant household comprises several categories of construction, each with a well-defined utility: housing construction, food preparation and consumption, water resources, agriculture practice (barns), grain storage, animal shelter, etc. (Cândea M, Simon T, Bogan E, 2012)

By attenuation of the urban, modern influences, the peasant farms are kept and preserved as original as possible, so that they can enter in the circuit of agrotourism and rural tourism.

Some peasant households in the Apuseni Mountains still have **traditional technical installations**, true objects of national heritage: mills, hand tools, pives.

At the national level, we find beautiful peasant households in Bucovina (wooden furniture, woolen fabrics), Maramures (icons on wood and glass, rugs, high wooden gates), Bihor (dowry boxes, wall covers), etc.

In Romania, agrotourism and rural tourism are successfully practiced in rural areas of Transylvania too, where **cultural diversity** has an important role. In this segment can be noticed rural localities from Cluj, Sibiu, Braşov, Bistriţa-Năsăud counties.

In Transylvania, multiculturalism gave birth to village cultural landscapes that are identified by the way of organizing the peasant household and specific forms of cultural identity.

The special attraction of rural communities is the social life where we encounter various human concerns and phenomena related to the terrestrial and cosmic environment. All these are materialized through **multiple celebrations and rituals** characteristic of the Romanian people.

CONCLUSION

In the future for the Romanian rural environment, agrotourism and rural tourism can be ways of economic development, having an important role also in stopping the migration from the village to the city.

Agrotourism and rural tourism allow the conservation of rural areas and their ways of life.

Agrotourism, component part of rural tourism, plays an important role in capitalization of local tourism resources and consequently in raising the standard of living of the inhabitants.

The households must be promoted on geographical and ethnographic areas and regions, because by presenting the local and regional specific, are achieved a better knowledge and promotion of the Romanian cultural, ethnographic and historical heritage.

Agrotourism and rural tourism can stimulate the growth of the activity of other branches of the village environment: handicrafts, crafts, local industry of agri-food products.

Agrotourism and rural tourism play an important role in the development of the rural area, both locally and regionally.

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STUDY ON THE PURCHASING BEHAVIOR OF THE CONSUMER OF FAST-FOOD PRODUCTS

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to find out if the students of the University of Oradea consume fast food products, which are the reasons why students choose to consume these products, what kind of brands they prefer, which they consider to be the effects of consumption on health. For this I drew up a questionnaire that was applied to a number of 219 students of the University of Oradea of which 77% were female and 23% male, most of the participants being enrolled in the Faculty of Geography, Sport and Tourism, the Faculty of Socio-Human Sciences, the Faculty of Environmental Protection and the Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy. Most of the students come from urban areas - 63%, and 37% - from rural areas.

After analyzing the answers I found out that the favorite restaurant of the students of the University of Oradea is McDonald's, and the main reason for the consumption is the taste of the dishes.

Key words: fast-food, students, taste.

INTRODUCTION

Fast food is preferred by a large part of the population, some people becoming dependent on it. This type of food is generally preferred by hasty people who do not have time to dine at home or in a real restaurant. It can be consumed in the car, in the means of transport or while dealing with other activities. Therefore, one of the advantages of fast food is that they are not time consuming. One of the most obvious disadvantages is obesity. Fast food products contain many calories, a high dose of saturated fat, carbohydrates and salt. Excessive salt intake can especially affect hypertensive people. <http://www.ziare.com/>

According to a study conducted by GfK Romania in 2015 that investigated the consumption habits of Romanians outside the house, "fast-food shops selling burgers, shaorma, fried chicken and fried potatoes are preferred for purchasing food for consumption" on the go. ". 50% of the participants in the GfK study declare they have bought from such a place in the last four weeks.

Fast-food is mainly attended by men, while women rather opt for pastry or pretzels. Most of the customers of these locations are between 25-34 years old.

Pizzerias, including those with home delivery, are third in the list of preferences and have a younger audience, pizza being mainly consumed by those between 18 and 24 years old. Pizzerias are also the most common option for people with above average incomes, while people with very low incomes choose pastries.

The latter are as popular as the fast-food restaurants in the average localities (between 50,000 and 200,000 inhabitants), while pizzerias are preferred in the big cities, with over 200,000 citizens, except the capital". <https://www.gfk.com/>

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In this study we used as a research method a quantitative method based on the survey, and the instrument used was the questionnaire with closed questions.

The questionnaire had a number of 14 questions and was applied to a sample of 219 students of the University of Oradea.

The obtained results were analyzed to present the main findings regarding eating habits, frequency of consumption of fast food products, favorite brands, favorite products, motivation for choosing these products, amounts spent, etc. The questionnaire was applied in the period 2018-2019.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We will present in continuation the results that arise from the analysis of the answers to the questions of the questionnaire, regarding the purchasing behavior of the student of the University of Oradea, consumer of fast-food products.

At the question asked "Do you use to eat fast food?" of 219 respondents used to consume 79% fast food, while the remaining 21% answered negative.

Regarding the frequency of consumption of fast food products among students, 33% replied that they prefer to consume these products weekly, 28% of the respondents consume the fast food products monthly, 26% consume them rarely, 9% are those students who consume the products every 2-3 days, 3% consume daily, and the remaining 1% stated that they never consume these products (fig. 1).

At the question: "How healthy do you consider fast food to be?", 64% of the respondents consider that this fast food is unhealthy, 35% of them think that fast food is less healthy, only 1% they considered fast-food

products to be healthy. One respondent considers fast food to be very healthy.

Fig.1. Frequency of consumption

Regarding the prices of fast food products, 82% of those surveyed believe that the prices of these preparations are accessible; 14% of them think the prices are high and only 4% of them think the prices are low (fig.2).

Fig.2. The prices of the products

Fast food restaurants preferred by students are: Mc Donald's - 56%, KFC - 36%, Mc Neil - 5% and Burger King - 3% (tab.1).

Table 1.

Favorite brands				
Fast-food	Mc Donald's	KFC	Mc Neil	Burger King
Number of students	122	78	12	7
%	56%	36%	5%	3%

Source: Processed data

What causes students to consume fast food products? 64% of the respondents consider that it is the taste that determines them to consume these products, 15% - the need, 11% - the accessibility, 7% - the advertising, 2% - the curiosity, 1% - the environment.

The amounts of money allocated by students for the purchase of fast food products are: under 50 lei - 66% of respondents, between 50 and 150 lei - 29% of respondents, between 150-300 lei - 2%, and over 300 of lei - 3% (tab.2).

Table 2.

The amount of money spent monthly on fast-food (in RON)			
Under 50	Between 50-150	Between 150-300	Over 300
145 students	63 students	5 students	6 students
66%	29%	2%	3%

Source: Processed data

Regarding the age of the respondents, 68% are young people between the ages of 18-22, they frequent these places for reasons, such as: lack of cooking experience, accessibility, parents' money, being influenced by the groups of friends from whom they make part. 24%, are between 22 and 25 years old; 6% - between 25-30 years, 2% are those over 30 years.

The students who participated in this survey attend the courses of fourteen of the fifteen faculties of the University of Oradea. 19% of the respondents are students of the Faculty of Geography, Sport and Tourism; 16% are representatives of the Faculty of Socio-Human Sciences, the Faculty of Environmental Protection has a participation of 15%, the Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy - 13% and the Faculty of Economic Sciences - 12%. From the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Information Technology 7% of the respondents participated, from the Faculty of Letters 6% were pronounced and 5% of the students are enrolled in the Faculty of History, International Relations, Political Sciences and Communication

Sciences. Managerial and Technological Engineering, Construction, Cadastre and Architecture, Art, Law and Orthodox Theology had a rather small participation in the questionnaire, with a contribution of 4%.

Fig.3. Monthly income

Considering the monthly incomes available to students more than one third of the students - 36% have a monthly amount between 500-1000 RON. About a quarter of them (25%) have a monthly income below 500 RON. In contrast, 39% stated that they have the opportunity to spend monthly amounts over 1000 RON (fig.3).

CONCLUSIONS

Following the evaluation of the questionnaires I came to several conclusions: of the 219 students, only 1% doesn't consume fast food products at all; 3% consume daily, 33% of them consume weekly, 28% - monthly, 26% - rarely. The student favorite restaurant is McDonald's (56%). 64% of the respondents consider that the main reason for consuming these products is the taste of the preparations. Even though 64% of the respondents consider this food unhealthy, the majority choose to consume it. Although 61% of the students have incomes lower than 1000 Ron, 82% of them think that the prices of these preparations are affordable, and 4% consider them even low. 92% of the respondents are between 18 and 25 years old.

Fast-food restaurants have registered an increasing trend in Romania in recent years; even though Romanians are beginning to realize that fast-food products are unhealthy, they are consuming them in increasing

quantities, with McDonald's profits registering an increase of 11% in 2018 compared to 2017.

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STRATEGIES OF DEVELOPMENT IN AGRO-TOURISM SERVICES IN MOUNTAIN AREA OF BRASOV COUNTRY

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Abstract

The characteristics of the agro-tourism defined by the services sector, imposes the knowledge of its own evolution rendered by: the nature and the characteristics of the services in the rural area, which are shaped by forms. These forms give a certain specificity to several aspects, these being: the objectives and the evolution of the forms of services in Romania: the validity of these services (through intangibility, inseparability, variability and perishability); specialization and diversity of rural services in Romania; the specific forms of the competition relations between the services market and the goods market in the rural area; the personnel providing services from the rural area; the role and behavior of the consumer, etc.

Brasov County, is the place where agro-tourism has its core and one in which the number of accommodation places in tourist and agro-tourism pensions is the most significant in the country.

The mountainous relief of the county allows the seasonal practice of winter sports, on the territory of Brasov county being three tourist resorts of national interest - Poiana Brasov, Predeal and Rasnov - all three being set up in the Postavarul Massif. According to the law, the non-agricultural activities specific to the mountain area supported by the state are: mountain tourism, agrotourism and ecotourism, through the specific services.

Key words: mountain tourism, rural services

INTRODUCTION

Rural tourism in general and mountain agro-tourism in particular are considered as promising options for the future, because this way can be achieved an economic development of the localities with predominantly agricultural and forestry specificity, with favorable consequences on attracting and maintaining the population in the rural environment, boosting the agricultural activity. in the disadvantaged regions from the point of view of social and cultural development, limiting the effects of social isolation, especially for the inhabitants of the villages or mountain hamlets.

The rural tourist pension is characterized by a functional specificity of the agrotourism services, and for this reason the relationships and the policy of the chain of the rural agrotourist services, are focused on the

identification of the agrotourist supply chain (products / services, itineraries, economic agents, operations, flows). etc.), along with the analysis of the regulatory mechanisms within the chain in the assembly of the integrating system and the integrating environment in the rural area.

By law, for the development of tourism and agro-tourism in the mountain area, the Romanian state, provides investments in the tourism infrastructure and tourist leisure: renovation / rehabilitation of accommodation units, campsites / harbours / shelters / chalets, creation of new means for spending leisure time, marking the mountain tourist routes, creating the thematic routes / paths, placing the interpretive panels, as well as the indicators. In order to increase the economic potential of the mountain area, the Romanian state provides the financing of projects in the mountain area to promote ecotourism and agro-tourism activities in order to extend the global tourism offer and to favor the creation of jobs in these areas. In farms, sheepfold and agro-pensions, food for tourists, in the form of fresh or processed products, must come from their own farm or from other farms in the area, except those that cannot be made within them. Individuals, individual businesses and family businesses, authorized according to the law, which carry out tourism activities in structures of reception of the type of pensions and agro-tourism farms, can benefit from granting from the local councils of some areas of the available lands, according to the law, for their construction, development and exploitation. The young people from the mountain area can request and receive wood material to build tourist reception structures: agrotourism pensions, rooms and / or hosting apartments. Considering the fact that in this county the agrotourism is well represented, we thought of a strategy that does not necessarily mean an increase in the number of accommodation places but of the services offered by the pensions in the area.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For this work I used statistical data offered by the national institute of statistics and the statistical department of Brasov. The paper covers well the field of qualitative research, seen as a first-order alternative, but also as a necessary complement to the quantitative methods.

For the research method I used qualitative exploratory research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Accommodation infrastructure in Brasov county is represented by hotels, pensions (urban, rural and agrotouristic), inns and motels, villas and tourist cottages, bungalows, holiday villages, campsites, tourist houses, student camps.

Tabel I

Touristic accommodation capacity, existing in Brasov county (places)

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Hotels	5740	6128	6652	7591	8791	9918
Hostels	0	125	147	207	445	962
Motels	429	316	343	431	748	772
Villas cottages	916	905	900	1010	1476	1764
Tourist cottages	655	612	682	801	752	1005
Bungalows	50	78	78	96	88	88
Holiday villages	106	106	106	72	72	72
Campsites	2196	640	1962	874	874	870
Tourist houses	22	0	0	0	0	240
Tourist boarding houses	2801	2996	3146	3556	3947	4719
Agrotourism pensions	2639	2772	2676	3067	4402	5024

Source:<https://statistici.insse.ro/shop>

Regarding the tourist accommodation capacity in the county, it is noticed an increasing trend starting with 2009, in 2013 registering with 73.3% more accommodation places. In 2013, the existing places in hotels increased by 12.82%, the pensions (tourist and agro-tourism) supplemented their places with 16.69%, the places in tourist villas increased by 19.51%, the largest extension registering the tourist cottages, whose places increased by 33.64%.

The number of places in the tourist and agro-tourist pensions has an increasing tendency during the analyzed years, considering that here is the most developed agro-tourist area, the Moieciu area.

The tourists arriving in Brasov county prefer, in proportion of over 60%, the hotels, aspect explained both by the superior accommodation capacity that they have, and by the various facilities made available to the clients. 23% of the tourists from Brasov county are staying in pensions (tourist and agro-tourism), the other types of accommodation units recording very little of the tourist circulation in the county.

The development strategy must be based on several key action paths, with an impact on the tourist activity:

- forming a team of members of the local authorities to remove the political and administrative barriers;
- the support of training institutions for tourism specialists;
- material support for the development of the county as a tourist destination;
- developing the capacity of tourist reception in accordance with the transport infrastructure,

- qualified human resource according to the requirements;
- setting up an agency around an important and experienced actor, with negotiating power, who will be able to support marketing efforts in order to attract the targeted market segments and to ensure customer satisfaction.

The main objective of the strategy is to increase the number of overnight stays and to increase the average length of stay in tourist and agrotourism pensions.

Ecotourism has grown in recent years, along with the awareness of the fragility and complexity of the environment. Although, at a general level, ecotourism is considered to involve only activities in nature (mountain climbs, hiking, nature observation, etc.), it also includes cultural activities. The most important aspect of ecotourism is obtaining the benefits for the local community: creating jobs, using local resources, involving the local community in making decisions regarding the development of the tourist activity. Thus, the rural areas of Brasov county, which also have cultural attractions, can be micro-destinations conducive to the development of ecotourism. Starting from the basic principle of ecotourism, responsible travel in relatively unaltered natural areas, it is found that Brasov county has several micro-tourist destinations exploited not properly and to its potential.

Although, at first glance, ecotourism cannot be a consistent source of income, given that it is a form of tourism that is addressed to individual tourists or small groups, it is a niche that must be developed coherently. Businesses in the sphere of ecotourism have a real chance of being successful in the long run if the laws of the market (applying recognized operating standards) and sustainable development are respected. A policy of ecotourism development in Brasov county must be developed, that emphasizes on educating tourists, conserving the environment, empowering and actively involving the local community. Thus, economic operators in areas close to the protected natural areas should be integrated into an appropriate management that combines the increase in the number of tourists with nature conservation and protection. The strategy for developing the ecotourism must start from consulting the local population, the investors, the tour operators, the NGOs active in the area. The main way of managing the natural areas should be to inform and educate the visitors, mainly at the destination, by: clear information messages, in an accessible language, qualified personnel, visiting leaflets, panels at the entrance to the protected areas. Obviously, attracting tourists for ecotourism must be done through targeted marketing actions within the tourism product promotion centers.

CONCLUSIONS

The natural environment, still slightly altered, formed, in a balanced way, from a high mountain step, one of the lower mountains and one of the valleys and depressions, is the physical support for the development of ecotourism activities. In the current territory of Brasov county there are a multitude of protected areas, some presenting elements of uniqueness, which justify the practice of ecotourism. Piatra Craiului National Park, whose territory overlaps with that of Zarnesti-Piatra Craiului ecotourism destination (according to the Criteria for the designation of Ecotourism Destinations in Romania elaborated on the basis of the European Ecotourism Certification Standard - The European Ecotourism Labeling Standard - EETLS and the Global Criteria for Sustainable Tourism). The park is notable for its spectacular rocky steep slopes (Zarnestilor Saddles) and the karst relief (Dambovicioarei Cave and Gorge), but also for rare or endemic elements of flora (*Dianthus callizonus*) or fauna (black goat). Near the city of Zarnesti there is also the only sanctuary for bears in Romania, LiBearty, dedicated to bears that have been rescued from captivity, but which can no longer be reintegrated into their natural environment. Both Piatra Craiului National Park and Bucegi Natural Park also contain anthropic areas, on the territory of the communes Fundata, Moieciu, Bran, where the meadows and scattered households create a typical landscape of mountain villages. This landscape is, in itself, an attraction for photography enthusiasts, which makes these areas, periodically, the "hosts" of tourist photography camps.

In the territory of Brasov county there are several areas propitious for the practice of ecotourism, both in terms of accessibility and diversity of natural and cultural heritage: the Bran-Moieciu-Fundata corridor, Buzau customs, Fagaras country, Bunesti area. A defining characteristic is the presence of the anthropic natural landscape, which generates an idyllic atmosphere: mountain or hill meadows, separated by forest or orchard curtains, the presence of sheep or cattle herds, maintaining traditional agricultural architecture and techniques.

The diversification of the services within the pensions could attract more tourists and could increase the number of days of accommodation for the current tourists.

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RESEARCHES ABOUT THE BUTTERFLIES (INSECTA,LEPIDOPTERA) FROM TINCA AREA (BIHOR COUNTY,NORTH-WESTERN PART OF ROMANIA)

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Abstract

In this work there are presented data about the fauna of butterflies from Tinca area(Bihor,Romania) identified during 2000-2019. There were identified 114 species belonging to 6 families and 62 genera. Some species are very rare at national level, being protected: Parnassius apollo jaraensis Kert. (probably accidental or vagrant specimens in Tinca area), Euphydryas aurinia Rott., Euphydryas maturna L., Lycaena dispar rutila Wern., Leptidea morsei major Gr., Maculinea arion L., Nymphalis vau-album Den. et Schiff., Parnassius mnemosyne L., Neptis hylas L., Arethusana arethusana Schiff.

Key words: butterflies, Tinca area, Bihor, Romania

INTRODUCTION

The Tinca area is located at the confluence of Miersiguluplain and Holodului depression, in the south-western part of Bihor county, Crişana region, in the north-western part of Romania. The average altitude is 110m, the climate is temperate-continental moderate. The drainage is represented by Crişul Negru river and his affluents: Valea Pustei, Valea Nouă, Rătăşel, and Rogoaze lake. The vegetation belongs to the oak s vegetative stage. Tinca village includes five villages: Tinca, Râpa, Gurbediu, Belfir and Girişu-Negru.

A synthesis about the butterflies at national level was published by different authors (Stănoiu et al., 1979; Rakosy, 2013; Szekely, 2008) and a book and data about the butterflies from Tinca area were published by Ilie (2013, 2014a, b, c, 2015, 2016, 2017).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The researches about the butterflies from Tinca area were performed during 2000-2019. The collecting was performed with the entomological

net. For the identification of the butterflies we used different guides (Rakosy, 2013; Szekely, 2008). Some species were exactly identified after only the analysis of genitalia, using the guide of Rakosy (2013): *Carcharodus flocciferus* Zel., *Pyrgus alveus* Hubn., *Pyrgus armoricanus* Ob., *Cupido argiades* Pall., *Cupido decolorata* Staud., *Plebeius argus* L., *Plebeius idas* L., *Plebeius argyrognomon* Berg., *Melitaea aurelia* Nick., *Melitaea athalia* Rott., *Melitaea trivialis* Den. et Schiff., *Hipparchia fagi* Scop., *Hipparchia semele* L.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

During 2000-2019, there were identified the following species in Tinca area:

Hesperiidae family

Erynis tages Linnaeus, 1758 –Euro-Siberian species

Carcharodus alcae Esper, 1780 –Eurasian species

Carcharodus flocciferus Zeller, 1847 –Eurasian species

Pyrgus malvae Linnaeus, 1758 –Eurasian species

Pyrgus armoricanus Oberthur, 1910 –Eurasian species

Pyrgus alveus Hubner, 1803 –Palearctic species

Carterocephalus palaemon Pallas, 1771 –Holarctic species

Thymelicus lineola Ochsenheimer, 1808 –Holarctic species

Thymelicus sylvestris Poda, 1761 –Western-Palearctic species

Hesperia comma Linnaeus, 1758 –Holarctic species

Ochlodes sylvanus Esper, 1777 –Eurasian species

Papilionidae family

Zerynthia polyxena Denis et Schiffer, 1775 –Pontomediterranean species

Parnassius mnemosyne Linnaeus, 1758 –Eurasian species

Parnassius apollo jaraensis Kertész, 1922 –Eurasian species

Iphiclides podalirius Linnaeus, 1758-Eurasian species

Papilio machaon Linnaeus, 1758 –Holarctic species

Pieridae family

Leptidea sinapis Linnaeus, 1758 -European species

Leptidea morsei major Grund, 1907-Euro-Siberian species

Anthocaris cardamines Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species

Aporia crataegi Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species

Pieris brassicae Linnaeus, 1758-Euro-Siberian species

Pieris rapae Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species

Pieris napi Linnaeus, 1758-Holarctic species

Pontia edusa Fabricius, 1777-Eurasian species

Colias erate Esper, 1805-Euro-Siberian species
Colias croceus Fourcroy, 1785-Eurasian species
Colias hyale Linnaeus, 1758-Euro-Siberian species
Colias alfacariensis Ribbe, 1905-Eurasian species
Gonopteryx rhamni Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species Riodinidae family
Hamearis lucina Linnaeus, 1758-European species
Lycaenidae family
Lycaena alciphron Rottemburg, 1775-Eurasian species
Lycaena phlaeas Linnaeus, 1758-Holarctic species
Lycaena dispar rutila Werneburg, 1864-Euro-Siberian species
Lycaena virgaurea Linnaeus, 1758-Euro-Siberian species
Lycaena tityrus Poda, 1761-Eurasian species
Lycaena thersamon Esper, 1784-Eurasian species
Thecla betulae Linnaeus, 1758-Eurasian species
Neozephyrus quercus Linnaeus, 1758-Western –Palearctic species
Callophrys rubi Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species
Satyrium w-album Knoch, 1782-Euro-Siberian species
Satyrium pruni Linnaeus, 1758-Euro-Siberian species
Satyrium spini Fabricius, 1787-Western-Palearctic species
Satyrium ilicis Esper, 1779-Western-Palearctic species
Satyrium acaciae Fabricius, 1787-Southern-European species
Leptotes pirithous Linnaeus, 1758-Mediterranean-African-tropical species
Cupido minimus Fuessly, 1775-Euro-Siberian species
Cupido decolorata Staudinger, 1886-Eastern-European species
Cupido argiades Pallas, 1771-Euro-Siberian species
Cupido alcetas Hoffmannsegg, 1804-Euro-Siberian species
Celastrina argiolus Linnaeus, 1758-Holarctic species
Pseudophilotes schiffermuelleri Hemming, 1929-Eastern-Mediterranean-Western-Asian species
Scolitantides orion Pallas, 1771-Eurasian species
Glaucopsyche alexis Poda, 1761-Euro-Siberian species
Maculinea arion Linnaeus, 1758-Euro-Siberian species
Plebeius argus Linnaeus, 1758-Euro-Siberian species
Plebeius idas Linnaeus, 1758-Holarctic species
Plebeius argyrognomon Bergstrasser, 1779-Euro-Siberian species
Aricia agestis Denis et Schiffermuller, 1775-Palearctic species
Cyaniris semiargus Rottemburg, 1775-Euro-Siberian species
Polyommatus thersites Cantener, 1835-Euro-Western-Asian species
Polyommatus icarus Rottemburg, 1775-Palearctic species
Polyommatus daphnis Denis et Schiffermuller, 1775-Euro-Western-Asian species
Polyommatus bellargus Rottemburg, 1775-Euro-Western-Asiatic species
Polyommatus coridon Poda, 1761-Euro-Western-Asiatic species
Nymphalidae family
Argynnis paphia Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species
Argynnis pandora Denis et Schiffermuller, 1775-Southern-European-

Central-Asian species

Argynnis aglaja Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species
Argynnis adippe Denis et Schiffermuller, 1775-Palearctic species
Argynnis niobe Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species
Issoria lathonia Hubner, 1819-Eurasian species
Brenthis daphne Bergstrasser, 1780-Euro-Siberian species
Boloria euphrosyne Linnaeus, 1758 –Euro-Siberian species
Boloria selene Denis et Schiffermuller, 1775–Holarctic species
Boloria dia Linnaeus, 1767-Euro-Central-Asian species
Vanessa atalanta Linnaeus, 1758-Holarctic species
Vanessa cardui Linnaeus, 1758 –Cosmopolitan species
Inachis io Linnaeus, 1758-Euro-Siberian species
Aglais urticae Linnaeus, 1758-Eurasian species
Polygonia c-album Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species
Araschnia levana Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species
Nymphalis antiopa Linnaeus, 1758-Holarctic species
Nymphalis polychloros Linnaeus, 1758-Western –Palearctic species
Nymphalis xanthomelas Esper, 1781-Eastern –Palearctic species
Nymphalis vau-album Denis et Schiffermuller, 1775-Holarctic species
Apatura ilia Denis et Schiffermuller, 1775-Euro-Siberian species
Apatura iris Linnaeus, 1758-Eurasian species
Neptis hylas Linnaeus, 1758-Euro-Siberian species
Neptis rivularis Scopoli, 1763-Euro-Siberian species
Euphydryas maturna Linnaeus, 1758-European species
Euphydryas aurinia Rottemburg, 1775-Palearctic species
Melitaea cinxia Linnaeus, 1758-Eurasian species
Melitaea phoebe Denis et Schiffermuller, 1775-Palearctic species
Melitaea trivia Denis et Schiffermuller, 1775-Eurasian species
Melitaea didyma Esper, 1778-Eurasian species
Melitaea aurelia Nickerl, 1850-Eurasian species
Melitaea athalia Rottemburg, 1775-Euro-Siberian species
Melitaea ornata Cristoph, 1893-Eurasian species
Pararge aegeria tircis Godat, 1821-Western-Palearctic species
Lasiommata megera Linnaeus, 1767-Western-Palearctic species
Lasiommata maera Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species
Lopinga achine Scopoli, 1763-Euro-Siberian species
Coenonympha arcania Linnaeus, 1767-European species
Coenonympha glycerion Borkhausen, 1788-Euro-Siberian species
Coenonympha pamphilus Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species

Pyronia tithonus Linnaeus, 1767-European species
Aphantopus hyperantus Linnaeus, 1758-Euro-Siberian species
Maniola jurtina Linnaeus, 1758-Palearctic species
Erebia medusa Denis et Schiffermuller, 1775-Euro-Siberian species
Melanargia galathea Linnaeus, 1758-Euro-Western-Asian species
Minois dryas Scopoli, 1763-Euro-Siberian species
Hipparchia fagi Scopoli, 1763-Euro-Western-Asian species
Hipparchia semele Linnaeus, 1758-European species
Arethusana arethusa Schiffermuller, 1775-Euro-Siberian species
Brintesia circe pannonica Fabricius, 1775-Eurasian species

There were identified 114 species belonging to 6 families and 62 genera. In Romania, the fauna of diurnal butterflies comprises 210 species (Rakosy, 2013). From these, in Tinca area there were identified 114 species (54.28%).

The butterflies identified in Tinca area belongs to six families (Rakosy, 2013): *Hesperiidae*-11 species (9.64%) compared to 23 species at national level (47.82%); *Papilionidae*-5 species (4.38%) compared to 10 species at national level (50%); *Pieridae*-13 species (11.40%) compared to 21 species at national level (61.90%); *Riodinidae*-1 species (0.87%) compared to 1 species at national level (100%); *Lycaenidae*-34 species (29.82%) compared to 60 species at national level (56.66%); *Nymphalidae*-50 species (43.85%) compared to 95 species at national level (52.63%).

Physical-geographic position and relatively small distance from Codru-Moma Mountains (30-35km) caused the existence of a rich and diverse butterfly fauna.

From the point of view of the zoogeographic spread, the following categories of species were identified: European – 7 (6.14%), Euro-Siberian 31 (27.19%), Eurasian-31 (27.19%), Holarctic – 13 (11.40%), Palearctic – 26 (22.80%), Pontomediterranean – 1 (0.87%), south-European – 1 (0.87%), Mediterranean-African-tropical – 1 (0.87%), east-Mediterranean-western-Asian – 1 (0.87%), south-European-central-Asian – 1 (0.87%), Cosmopolitan – 1 (0.87%).

The fauna of diurnal butterflies from Tinca area includes also rare or very rare species at national level, protected by legislation: *Euphydryas aurinia* Rott., *Euphydryas maturna* L., *Lycaena dispar rutila* Wern., *Leptidea morsei major* Grund., *Maculinea arion* L., *Nymphalis vau-album* Den. et Schiff., *Parnassius mnemosyne* L., *Parnassius apollo jaraensis* Kert.-one specimen,

Râpa village, May 20, 2015; one specimen (probably the same specimen), Râpa village, June 15, 2015; *Zerynthia polyxena* Den. et Sciff., *Arethusana arethusa* Schiff., *Neptis hylas* L.

Absence or fragmentation of habitats, pollution, intensive farming, deforestation, mechanical mowing, excessive grazing and the production of fires are causes of population decline or even the disappearance of butterfly species.

CONCLUSIONS

During 2000-2019, in Tinca area there were identified 114 species belonging to six families and 62 genera. Ten species are rare at national level being protected by legislation. Strong human impact is cause of population decline or even the disappearance of butterfly species.

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DETERMINATION OF ANTIOXIDANT PROTECTION SUBSTANCES IN FOOD BY LABORATORY METHODS

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Abstract

Because a substantial percentage of food borne diseases outbreaks are caused by home prepared food, is very important to determine their knowledge and food safety correlated with preparation practices. The occupational reactions in the food industry are also related with the knowledge about non-food, food derived or food related sensitizing materials (allergenic materials associated with food processing, manufacturing, transport, trade, transport, retail).

Key words: food safety knowledge, preparation practices, occupational reactions, allergens.

INTRODUCTION

The demographic conditions and the lifestyle have changed significantly in the last 30 years all over the world and in Romania especially in the last 10 years. They influenced the assortments of food products available to the buyers, as well as the way they were prepared at home. It is known that a food can be valuable not only for its caloric power.

It has long been demonstrated that a "caloric" diet can be devitalized by aging, processing, storage, fermentation or cooking. Protective nutrition is broadly reducing in nature and generally exhibits antilipoperoxidative action, associated with the ability to inhibit lipooxygenase. In the case of phenolic compounds, the reducing activity increases with the number of hydroxyls in the lateral cycle.

Protective feeding, as an oxide-reducing system, plays a role in the mechanism of hydrogen transfer. Through this action, it intervenes through different metabolic, respiratory, cellular processes. So far, there has been no agreement on how to express a food in reducing activity units. Under current conditions, the need for active substances is more important than the excess energy supply.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

There are no known effective methods for rapidly determining the presence of antioxidant (reducing) protective substances in foods. All the protective foods studied contain a certain group of substances permanently, which condition the physico-chemical, biological properties, including antimicrobials. For example, a number of compounds with antioxidant properties (polyphenols, vitamins: B, C, E, K, amino acids with sulfur) are among the permanent components present in the protection diet of vegetarians. A rapid method has been developed to determine the reducing capacity of protective foods by oxidizing them with potassium permanganate. The reaction with potassium permanganate allows a qualitative characterization of the protective products from foods containing antioxidants.

The oxidation rate is expressed in time (in seconds), during which a 0,1N potassium permanganate solution is bleached, in an environment containing the product to be investigated.

Food protective factors (antioxidants), in aqueous alcoholic environment, etc., discolor the 0.1N potassium permanganate solution. The property of the food protection factors to oxidize condition the antioxidant properties of food protection.

Determination of the oxidation rate of the food

0,1 g food, finely chopped, weighed accurately, put into a 50 ml flask, adding 10 ml distilled water at 20 °C, 40 °C, 70 °C, 90 °C, depending on the temperature at which we want to achieve extraction. After one hour, filter paper is filtered. Take 2 ml of the filtered solution with the pipette, place in a 50 ml beaker, add 20 ml of 20% sulfuric acid solution. After one minute, a drop (0,04 ml) of 0.1N potassium permanganate solution is introduced into the acidified solution and a stopwatch is followed by the disappearance of the pink color of the solution. The analysis is performed at the solution temperature of 18 - 20 °C. The working method is repeated by different dilutions 1:10; 1:20; 1:30.

They are foods that act as a protector (that is, they discolor the 0,1N KMnO₄ potassium permanganate solution) and at higher dilutions (shown in Table 1).

Table 1

Aliments with a protective role which decolour
the potassium permanganate

Material to be investigated	Suspension (g/100ml)	Dilution	Bleaching time of 0,1N KMnO ₄ solution (sec) (oxidation index)			
			Extraction temperature			
			20 ^o C	40 ^o C	70 ^o C	90 ^o C
Whole wheat flour	1	1:10	2 immediat	2,2 immediat	2,2 immediat	2,6 immediat
	1	1:20	4	4,3	4,4	4,5
White flour	1	0	8s	30s	45s	55s
	1	1:10	pink color persists	pink color persists	pink color persists	pink color persists
Palinka vol. 45%	-	0	50	-	-	-
White wine (from supermarket)	-	0	45	-	-	-
Honey 1,8 ^o refractometric	16,6	0	1	-	-	-
Honey 2 ^o refractometric	16,6	0	18	-	-	-
Alcohol vol.96%		0	56	-	-	-
		1:2	3,40s	-	-	-
		1:10	does not fade	-	-	-
White wine 7 ^o refractometric		0	3 immediat	-	-	-
		1:10	3 immediat	-	-	-
		1:20	16,5	-	-	-
		1:30	79	-	-	-
Distilled water			does not fade	-	-	-
Sugar	1	0	does not fade	-	-	-
Beef meat	1	0	does not fade	does not fade	does not fade	does not fade
	1	1:10	does not fade			

Material to be investigated	Suspension (g/100ml)	Dilution	Bleaching time of 0,1N KMnO ₄ solution (sec) (oxidation index)			
			Extraction temperature			
			20 ^o C	40 ^o C	70 ^o C	90 ^o C
Nettle leaves (Folium Urticae)	1	0	2,6	2,61	2,62	2,65
	1	1:10	8,6	8,55	8,7	8,7
Chamomile flowers (Flores Chamomillae)	1	0	immediat	immediat	immediat	immediat
	1	1:10	immediat	immediat	immediat	immediat
Caraway (Fructus Carvi)	1	0	2,7	2,9	3	3
	1	1:10	4,5	4,56	4,6	4,8
Marjoran	1	0	2,5	2,5	2,45	2,5

(HerbaMajoranae)	1	1:10	6,8	6,5	6,5	6,7
Rattles (Herba Hyperici)	1	0	3,2	3,12	3,13	3,5
	1	1:10	5,4	8,3	7,4	8,5
Marigold (Calendula Officinalis)	1	0	immediat	immediat	immediat	immediat
	1	1:10	immediat	immediat	immediat	immediat

Table 2

Aliments with a protective role which decolour
a potassium permanganate solution

Material to be investigated	Suspension (g/100 ml)	Dilution	Bleaching time of 0,1N KMnO ₄ solution (sec) (oxidation index)			
			Extraction temperature			
			20°C	40°C	70°C	90°C
Pork meat	1	0	Does not fade	-	-	-
	1	1:10	Does not fade	-	-	-
Fish meat „Hake”	1	0	7	-	-	-
	1	1:10	15	-	-	-
White bread	1	0	3	-	-	-
	1	1:10	60	-	-	-
Black bread	1	0	0	-	-	-
	1	1:10	25	-	-	-
Yogurt	1	0	immediat	-	-	-
	1	1:10	immediat	-	-	-
Sweet sheep case	1	0	immediat	-	-	-
	1	1:10	20	-	-	-
Cheese „Dalia”	1	0	10	-	-	-
	1	1:10	95	-	-	-

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) For all the products studied and which contain protective factors, the disappearance of pink in less than 30 seconds is characteristic.

2) The reaction rate depends on the dry matter content of the product investigated in the solution. In the case of protective food tea, the solution was instantly discolored, when the solution contained 4%, 1% finely chopped product. The disappearance of the pink color is delayed when the solution is diluted. The faster the pink color disappears (up to 30 seconds) and at different dilutions, the more protective the food.

3) The degree of activity of the extracts depended on the temperature at which the extraction was made. In general, the oxidation rate is higher for cold aqueous and alcoholic extracts than at temperatures of 400 °C, 700 °C, 900 °C. It is obvious the destructive effect of the high temperature for certain active components.

4) In the insoluble part of the investigated materials, the quantity of active substances is insignificant, only in very high suspensions a reaction of discoloration of the potassium permanganate solution 0,1 Normal can be observed.

5) In the case of fresh foods, the oxidation rate is high (the solution is immediately discolored - about 2 seconds). In the case of prolonged storage, the oxidation rate decreases, for example the protective food tea, after two years of storage it has the oxidation rate over 30 sec. (in some samples the pink color persisted even longer). Therefore, the duration of storage of certain foods under certain conditions substantially influences its properties.

6). There was no profound difference between the oxidation rate of the plants harvested from different climatic zones. Even if the antioxidant properties differ slightly, they do not go beyond the norm. As a speed of oxidation the samples of the yellowfin (*Callendula Officinalis*) are insignificant: those collected in the cities area (10-11 sec.). Those collected from the unpolluted mountain area (2 sec.).

7) After the oxidation rate the quality of the product can be deduced. It is observed that the whole flour has a much greater antioxidant capacity than the white one. They have no protective effect: white sugar, alcohol, pumice, meat (the solution of potassium permanganate does not discolor or the disappearance time of pink is greater than 30 sec.).

8) The antioxidant properties of a large number of foods have been studied and verified. The most active are fresh foods but the oxidation capacity is characteristic of all samples. Although there is no single value for this index, there are certain limits of variation on the samples. If the pink color disappearance time is less than 30 sec. food can be considered protective.

CONCLUSIONS

Both in the industrial processing, as well as in the commercial environment, or in the service of mass sharing (restaurants, etc.), but also at home, we are exposed to various risk factors for more or less professional illness.

In order not to be exposed to these factors or to minimize their effect, it is important that our level of perception, understanding and defense against these risk factors is always awake and equipped with the necessary knowledge.

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DIFFERENTIAL SANDWICH RESULTS FOR P-VALENT FUNCTIONS

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Abstract

In this paper we derive some applications of first order differential subordination and results involving a generalized multiplier transformations. Applying the techniques of differential subordination and superordination we also establish a differential sandwich-type theorem.

Key words: multiplier transformations, differential subordination, differential superordination.

INTRODUCTION

1.

Denote by U the open unit disc of the complex plane:

$$U = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z| < 1\}.$$

Let $\mathcal{H}$ be the class of analytic functions in U and for $a \in \mathbb{C}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let $\mathcal{H}[a,n]$ be the subclass of $\mathcal{H}$ consisting of functions of the form

$$f(z) = a + a_n z^n + a_{n+1} z^{n+1} + \dots, z \in U.$$

Let $\mathcal{A}(p,n)$ denote the class of functions $f(z)$ normalized by

$$f(z) = z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} a_k z^k, (p, n \in \mathbb{N} := \{1,2,3,\dots\})$$

which are analytic in the open unit disc. In particular, we set

$$\mathcal{A}(p,1) := \mathcal{A}_p \text{ and } \mathcal{A}(1,1) := \mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_1.$$

Let

$$\mathcal{A}_* = \{f \in \mathcal{H}(U), f(z) = z + a_{n+1} z^{n+1} + \dots\}$$

with $\mathcal{A}_1 = \mathcal{A}$.

We denote by Q the set of functions f that are analytic and injective on $\bar{U} \setminus E(f)$, where

$$E(f) = \{\zeta \in \partial U : \lim_{z \rightarrow \zeta} f(z) = \infty\}$$

and are such that $f'(\zeta) \neq 0$ for $\zeta \in \partial U \setminus E(f)$.

Since we use the terms of subordination and superordination, we review here those definitions.

Let $f, F \in \mathcal{H}$. The function f is said to be subordinate to F or F is said to be superordinate to f , if there exists a function w analytic in U , with $w(0)=0$ and $|w(z)| < 1$, and such that $f(z) = F(w(z))$. In such case we write $f < F$ or $f(z) < F(z)$.

If F is univalent, then $f < F$ if and only if $f(0)=F(0)$ and $f(U) \subset F(U)$.

Since most of the functions considered in this paper and conditions on them are defined uniformly in the unit disk U , we shall omit the requirement " $z \in U$ ".

Let $\psi : \mathbb{C}^3 \times \bar{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, let h be univalent in U and $q \in Q$. In [6] the authors considered the problem of determining conditions on admissible function ψ such that

$$(1.2) \quad \psi(p(z), zp'(z), z^2p''(z); z) < h(z)$$

implies $p(z) < q(z)$, for all functions $p \in \mathcal{H}[a,n]$ that satisfy the differential subordination (1.2).

Moreover, they found conditions so that the function q is the "smallest" function with this property, called the best dominant of the subordination (1.2).

Let $\varphi : \mathbb{C}^3 \times \bar{U} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, let $h \in \mathcal{H}$ and $q \in \mathcal{H}[a,n]$. Recently, in [7] the authors studied the dual problem and determined conditions on φ such that

$$(1.3) \quad h(z) < \varphi(p(z), zp'(z), z^2p''(z); z)$$

implies $p(z) < q(z)$, for all functions $p \in Q$ that satisfy the above differential superordination.

Moreover, they found conditions so that the function q is the "largest" function with this property, called the best subordinant of the superordination (1.3).

For two functions

$$f(z) = z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} a_k z^k \text{ and } g(z) = z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} b_k z^k,$$

the Hadamard product of f and g is defined by

$$(f * g)(z) := z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} a_k b_k z^k.$$

MATERIAL AND METHOD

2. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

We begin our investigation by recalling here a generalized differential operator defined in [3].

Definition 2.1. [3] Let $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$. For $m \in \mathbb{N}_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, $\lambda \geq 0$, $l \geq 0$, we define the multiplier transformations $I_p^m(\lambda, l)$ on $\mathcal{A}(p, n)$ by the following infinite series

$$(2.1) \quad I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) := z^p + \sum_{k=p+n}^{\infty} \left[\frac{p+\lambda(k-p)+l}{p+l} \right]^m a_k z^k.$$

It follows from (2.1) that

$$(2.2) \quad (p+l)I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) = [p(1-\lambda) + l]I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) + \lambda z(I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z))'.$$

Remark 2.1 For $p = 1$, $l = 0$, $\lambda \geq 0$, the operator $I_1^m(\lambda, 0) \equiv D_\lambda^m$ was introduced and studied by Al-Oboudi [1] which reduces to the Sălăgean differential operator [8] for $\lambda = 1$. The operator $I_1^m(1, l) \equiv I_l^m$ was studied recently by Cho and Srivastava [4] and Cho and Kim [5].

In this paper, we will derive several subordination and superordination results involving the operator $I_p^m(\lambda, l)$. In order to prove our main results, we also need the following result.

Lemma 2.1 [2] Let q be convex in U , $q(0) = a$ and $\gamma \in \mathbb{C}$, $\text{Re } \gamma > 0$.

If $h \in \mathcal{H}[a, 1] \cap Q$, the function $h(z) + \gamma zh'(z)$ is univalent in U and

$$q(z) + \gamma zq'(z) < h(z) + \gamma zh'(z),$$

then

$$q(z) < h(z)$$

and q is the best subordinant.

The authors established earlier the following theorem

Theorem 2.1. Let q be univalent in U , with $q(0)=1$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}^*$, $m, \beta \in \mathbb{N}_0 = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ and suppose

$$\text{Re} \left[1 + \frac{zq''(z)}{q'(z)} \right] > \max \left\{ 0, -\frac{p+l}{\lambda} \text{Re} \frac{1}{\alpha} \right\}.$$

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$ satisfies the subordination

$$(2.3) \quad \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \frac{\alpha}{z^p} \left(I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right) < q(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} zq'(z),$$

then

$$\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} < q(z)$$

and q is the best dominant of (2.3).

3. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 3.1. Let q be convex in U , with $q(0) = 1$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$, $\text{Re } \alpha > 0$.

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$ such that $\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} \in \mathcal{H}[q(0), 1] \cap Q$ and

$$\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \frac{\alpha}{z^p} \left(I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right)$$

is univalent in U and the following superordination holds

(3.1)

$$q(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} zq'(z) < \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \frac{\alpha}{z^p} \left(I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right),$$

then

$$q(z) < \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p}$$

and q is the best subordinator of (3.1).

Proof. We define the function

$$(3.2) \quad h(z) := \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p}.$$

Differentiating (3.2) with respect to z and using the identity (2.2) in the resulting equation we have

$$\frac{zh'(z)}{h(z)} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \left\{ (p+l) \frac{I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)}{I_p^m(\lambda, l)} - [p(1-\lambda) + l + \lambda p] \right\}.$$

Therefore, we obtain

$$\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \frac{\alpha}{z^p} \left(I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right) = h(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} zh'(z).$$

The subordination (3.1) becomes

$$q(z) + \frac{\alpha}{\beta+1} zq'(z) < h(z) + \frac{\alpha}{\beta+1} zh'(z).$$

The conclusion of this theorem follows by applying Lemma 2.1., with $\frac{\alpha}{\beta+1} = \gamma$.

Taking $m = 0$ in Theorem 3.1 we obtain the following result.

Corollary 3.1 Let q be convex in U , with $q(0)=1$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$, with $\text{Re } \alpha > 0$.

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$ such that $\frac{f(z)}{z^p} \in \mathcal{H}[1, 1] \cap Q$ and

$$(1-\alpha) \frac{f(z)}{z^p} + \alpha \frac{I_p^1(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p}$$

is univalent in U and the following superordination holds

$$q(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} zq'(z) < (1-\alpha) \frac{f(z)}{z^p} + \alpha \frac{I_p^1(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p},$$

then

$$q(z) < \frac{f(z)}{z^p}$$

and q is the best subordinator.

Corollary 3.2 Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$, $A \neq B$ such that $-1 \leq B < A \leq 1$ and $\operatorname{Re} \alpha > 0$. If $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$ such that

$$\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} \in \mathcal{H}[1, 1] \cap Q$$

and

$$(1 - \alpha) \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \alpha \frac{I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p}$$

is univalent in U and satisfies the superordination

$$\frac{1+Az}{1+Bz} + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} \frac{(A-B)z}{(1+Bz)^2} < (1 - \alpha) \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \alpha \frac{I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p}$$

then

$$\frac{1+Az}{1+Bz} < \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p}$$

and $q(z) = \frac{1+Az}{1+Bz}$ is the best subordinator.

Corollary 3.3 Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ and $\operatorname{Re} \alpha > 0$. If $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$ such that

$$\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} \in \mathcal{H}[1, 1] \cap Q$$

and

$$(1 - \alpha) \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \alpha \frac{I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p}$$

is univalent in U and satisfies the superordination

$$\frac{1+z}{1-z} + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} \frac{2z}{(1-z)^2} < (1 - \alpha) \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \alpha \frac{I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p}$$

then

$$\frac{1+z}{1-z} < \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p}$$

and $q(z) = \frac{1+z}{1-z}$ is the best subordinator.

Theorem 3.2. Let q_1, q_2 be convex in U , with $q_1(0) = q_2(0) = 1$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$, $\operatorname{Re} \alpha > 0$ and q_2 satisfies the inequality

$$\operatorname{Re} \left[1 + \frac{zq_2''(z)}{q_2'(z)} \right] > \max \left\{ 0, -\frac{\lambda}{p+l} \operatorname{Re} \alpha \right\}.$$

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$ such that $\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} \in \mathcal{H}[1, 1] \cap Q$ and

$$\frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z)}{z^p} + \frac{\alpha}{z^p} \left(I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l)f(z) - I_p^m(\lambda, l)f(z) \right)$$

is univalent in U and satisfies

$$q_1(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} z q_1'(z) < \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l) f(z)}{z^p} + \frac{\alpha}{z^p} \left(I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l) f(z) - I_p^m(\lambda, l) f(z) \right) < \\ < q_2(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} z q_2'(z),$$

then

$$q_1(z) < \frac{I_p^m(\lambda, l) f(z)}{z^p} + \frac{\alpha}{z^p} \left(I_p^{m+1}(\lambda, l) f(z) - I_p^m(\lambda, l) f(z) \right) < q_2(z)$$

and q_1, q_2 are the best subordinant and the best dominant respectively.

Considering the operator $\frac{f(z)}{z^p}$ we obtain the corresponding sandwich corollary.

Corollary 3.4 Let q_1, q_2 be convex in U , with $q_1(0) = q_2(0) = 1$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$, $\operatorname{Re} \alpha > 0$ and q_2 satisfies the inequality

$$\operatorname{Re} \left[1 + \frac{z q_2''(z)}{q_2'(z)} \right] > \max \left\{ 0, -\frac{\lambda}{p+l} \operatorname{Re} \alpha \right\}.$$

If $f \in \mathcal{A}(p, n)$ such that $\frac{f(z)}{z^p} \in \mathcal{H}[1, 1] \cap Q$ and

$$(1 - \alpha) \frac{f(z)}{z^p} + \alpha \frac{I_p^1(\lambda, l) f(z)}{z^p}$$

is univalent in U and satisfies

$$q_1(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} z q_1'(z) < (1 - \alpha) \frac{f(z)}{z^p} + \alpha \frac{I_p^1(\lambda, l) f(z)}{z^p} < q_2(z) + \frac{\alpha\lambda}{p+l} z q_2'(z),$$

then

$$q_1(z) < \frac{f(z)}{z^p} < q_2(z)$$

and q_1, q_2 are the best subordinant and the best dominant respectively.

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ANALYSIS IN DYNAMICS OF TOURISM OFFER IN SUCEAVA COUNTY DURING 2009-2018

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Abstract

Analysis of absolute and relative dynamics of touristy accommodation capacity which exist in Suceava County, during 2009-2018, shown the fact that number of accommodation places increased in 2018 face to 2009 with 60.87%, when was recorded the highest increase face to reference year; face to previous year were recorded increases up to 12.00% (in 2017). Per ensemble the mean level of existent accommodation capacity recorded 9789.2 places, with an absolute mean increase of 510.88 places, respectively a relative increase of 5.4%. Analysis of absolute and relative dynamics of functional accommodation capacity revealed the fact that these one increased in 2018 face to 2009 with 41.03%; when was recorded the highest increase face to reference year from analysed period; face to previous year was recorded a slightly decrease in 2016 (with 0.55%), in the rest of period were recorded increases up to 7.77% (in 2011). Generally speaking, mean level of functional accommodation capacity recorded 2638189.1 places-days/year, with an absolute mean increase of 99224.55 places-days/year, respectively with a relative increase of 3.9%. Net utilization index of functional touristy accommodation capacity, in Suceava County during 2009-2018 recorded fluctuating values, the highest value, 29.63%, being recorded in 2018.

Key words: accommodation capacity; tourism; net utilization index of accommodation capacity

INTRODUCTION

Suceava County is situated in the North-East part of Romania, bordering at North with Ukraine, at East with Botoşani County, at South-East with Iaşi County, at South with Neamţ, Harghita and Mureş Counties and at West with Bistriţa-Năsăud and Maramureş Counties. Relief, which is diversified, is the most important characteristic of Suceava County, here being founded mountains, mountains depressions, hills, plateaus, plains, terraced valleys and meadows/floodplains. The main relief forms are placed in parallel stripes, with a North-South disposal. Mountain region includes massifs, groups of massifs and peak complexes separated by deep valleys or depression areas (*Bojoi I. et al., 1979*). The massifs from county area belong to Oriental Carpathians group. So, Călimani massif is individualized in relation with the other mountains, being the highest volcanic mountains on Romanian territory, the only ones which overcame an altitude of 2000 m in Pietrosul Călimani peak. On the left hand side of Bistriţa River, from North

to South there are Obcina Mestecănişului, Giumalău massif, Rarău massif, Stânişoarei peak. Suceava County is recommended as an important country touristic area. Besides the great attractiveness of mountain landscape, county's touristic potential is characterized by variety, density and value of religious and architectural monuments, by natural parks and remarkable ethnographical areas, many of them being unique in the world. Particularly noticeable Voroneţ, Suceviţa, Moldoviţa, Putna, Humor, Slatina and Dragomirna monasteries; Bogdana church from Rădăuţi, as well as the ones from localities Arbore, Pătrăuţi, Baia, Probota and Suceava, Seat Fortress from the county residence municipality, Salt Mine and Minor Basilica from Cacica (Neacşu N. et al., 2016). Spectacular evolution of tourism, under those two correlative sides of it, production and consumption, reveal the receptivity of this domain to society dynamics, (Minciu Rodica et al., 1991), and also tourism as activity belonging to services is defined as a useful activity, destined to satisfy a certain social need its evolution under the incidence of a complex factors system, differencing between them by nature, role and participation in different rates to determination of touristic phenomenon (SnakO. et al. 2001). Touristic potential and tourism technical-material base (which represents the ensemble of capital goods utilised in this domain, for obtain specific goods and services designed for touristic consumption) (Minciu Rodica, 2004; Brezuleanu S. et al. 2008) from Suceava County favours mountain tourism and trip makings, equestrian tourism, spa tourism, cultural tourism, religious tourism, eco-tourism, rural tourism and agro-tourism as well as business tourism and congresses.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Touristic boarding structure with functions for touristic accommodation is represented by any building or construction, which provides permanently or seasonally an accommodation service or any other specific services for tourists. There aren't included in the statistical research, the touristic boarding structure with functions of touristic accommodation with an installed accommodation capacity less than 5 places (*insse.ro; Băltăreţu Andreea-Mihaela, 2016*).

The existent touristic accommodation capacity (installed) represent the number of accommodation places for touristic usage registered in the last document for reception, homologation and classification of the touristic accommodation unit, exclusively supplementary beds which could be installed in case of necessity. The places afferent to structures of touristic accommodation with function of complementary touristic boarding (small houses, camping, etc.) to a basic touristic boarding structure (hotel, motel,

camping, etc.) and utilisation of those places are included in the basic structure (*insse.ro; Neacșu N. et al., 2012*).

Touristy accommodation capacity in function represent the number of boarding places available for tourists and provided by the touristy units, taking in account the number of days in which the unit is opened into a certain period of time. It is expressed in places/day. Are excluded places from rooms or units temporary closed due to the lack of tourists, for improvements or by any other reasons (*insse.ro*).

Utilisation index of functional touristy capacity is calculated by rate between numbers of realised overnights at functional touristy capacity from a certain period (*insse.ro; Bădiță Maria et al., 2005; Turcu Daniela and Weisz Janeta, 2008*).

$$I_n = (N/C_f) \times 100, \text{ where:}$$

I_n is the utilisation index of functional touristy capacity;

N is the number of overnights recorded into a certain period of time;

C_f is the functional touristy capacity.

Absolute indicators represent a basic form of dynamic series, based on which could be obtained general indicators (*Merce E. and Merce C.C., 2009; Petcu Nicoleta, 2005*).

Level indicators are the terms of a series formed by absolute indicators ($y_1 \dots y_t \dots y_{t-1}$).

Total level of terms $\sum_{t=1}^n y^t$, only for time interval series with absolute measures.

The absolute modifications:

- with fixed base ($\Delta_{t/1}$): $\Delta_{t/1} = y_t - y_1$ where, $t = 2, n$
- with in chain base (mobile or variable base) ($\Delta_{t/t-1} = y_t - y_{t-1}$)

$$\Delta_{t/t-1} = y_t - y_{t-1} \quad \text{where, } t = 2, n$$

Relative indicators:

It is a presentation way, mainly percentage.

Dynamic index:

- with fixed base ($I_{t/1}$): $I_{t/1}(\%) = \frac{y_t}{y_1} \times 100$
- with in chain base ($I_{t/t-1}$): $I_{t/t-1}(\%) = \frac{y_t}{y_{t-1}} \times 100$

Dynamic rhythm:

- with fixed base ($R_{t/1}$): $R_{t/1} = I_{t/1}(\%) - 100\%$
- with in chain base ($R_{t/t-1}$): $R_{t/t-1}(\%) = I_{t/t-1}(\%) - 100\%$, $t = 2, n$

Mean indicators:

- meanlevel of timeseries ($\bar{y}$): $\bar{y} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n y^t}{n}$
- meanlevel of absolute gain (decrease) ($\bar{\Delta}$): $\bar{\Delta} = \frac{y^n - y^1}{n-1}$
- mean index of dynamics ($\bar{I}$): $\bar{I} = \sqrt[n-1]{\frac{y^n}{y^1}}$

- meangrowth rate ($\bar{R}$): $\bar{R} = \bar{I} - 100$

Method of adjusted trends was utilised for adjusting the tourists' number in according with linear trend for period 2009-2018.

Linear model: $y = a + bt$.

R is the correlation between the predicted values by equation and the actual values. R square is utilised to indicate the variation of values face to trend lineR (Panțiru Mariana, 2006).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of touristy offer

Number of touristy units with functions of touristy accommodation on types of structures (hotels, hostels, apartment hotels, motels, tourist villas, tourist chalets, bungalows, holiday villages, camping grounds/camp sites, tourist halts, tourist cottages, tourist boarding houses and agro-tourism boarding houses) from Suceava County in those 10 analysed years (2009-2018) (tab. 1), increased from 235 structures in 2009, to 460 accommodation units structures in 2018 (with 95.74%). The most numerous types of tourist accommodation units were agro-tourism boarding houses followed by tourist boarding houses and hotels.

Table 1

Touristy units with function of touristy accommodation on types of structures from Suceava County during 2009-2018

Types of touristy units	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
	MU: Number									
Total	235	245	271	296	295	296	310	343	441	460
Hotels	29	30	34	36	42	45	46	46	48	48
Hostels	8	8	13	12	8	8	8	11	12	14
Apartment hotels	1	1	:	:	:	:	:	:	:	:
Motels	3	3	7	6	5	6	6	6	6	6
Tourist villas	18	19	18	16	14	14	15	16	17	18
Tourist chalets	4	7	14	13	12	13	14	13	13	14
Bungalows	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3
Holiday villages	:	:	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Camp sites	4	4	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	3
Tourist halts	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3
Tourist cottages	:	:	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	3
Tourist boarding houses	54	62	67	74	73	73	80	88	107	115
Agro-tourism boarding houses	110	107	109	130	132	127	129	151	225	232

Legend: ':' – missing data

Source: insse.ro

Tourist accommodation capacity existent on types of tourist receiving units from Suceava County during 2009-2018 (*tab. 2*) constantly increase in those 10 analyzed years from 7554 places in 2009 to 12152 places in 2018 (with 60.87%), the most significant accommodation capacity being founded in hotels followed by agro-tourism boarding houses and tourist boarding houses. Functional tourist accommodation capacity existent in Suceava County in the same period of time (2009-2018) (*tab. 3*) recorded increases with 41.03% in 2018 face to 2008 which indicates a good economical situation for tourism in Suceava County during analyzed period, the most significant existent tourist accommodation capacity being also founded in hotels followed by agro-tourism boarding houses and tourist boarding houses.

Table 2

Existent tourist accommodation capacity on types of touristy receiving units from Suceava County during 2009-2018

Types of touristy units	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
	MU: Places									
Total	7554	8033	8835	9447	9585	9650	10143	10610	11883	12152
Hotels	3144	3322	3510	3610	3926	4065	4193	4152	4298	4276
Hostels	292	266	417	437	239	237	237	340	350	381
Apartment hotels	32	32	:	:	:	:	:	:	:	:
Motels	111	111	263	262	214	292	292	280	257	269
Tourist villas	530	572	379	357	283	291	290	297	314	341
Tourist chalets	259	246	332	304	308	258	284	243	224	245
Bungalows	40	40	40	40	50	50	104	104	104	104
Holiday villages	:	:	82	82	82	82	86	86	86	86
Camp sites	230	230	224	220	220	246	246	244	244	216
Tourist halts	76	76	76	76	76	76	124	120	108	108
Tourist cottages	:	:	10	10	10	10	10	10	16	30
Tourist boarding houses	1102	1383	1534	1665	1715	1592	1725	1964	2171	2308
Agro-tourism boarding houses	1738	1755	1968	2384	2462	2451	2552	2770	3711	3788

Legend: ':' – missing data
Source: insse.ro

In 2018, functional existent tourist accommodation capacity (total) from Suceava County was of 3069443 places – days with a net utilization index for functional accommodation capacity of 29.63%.

From a comparative analysis of the accommodation units number and places number from touristy units with function of touristy accommodation between years 2009 and 2018 from Suceava County (*tab. 4*), result that in 2018 number of accommodation units increase significantly, with 95.74% face to 2012 and number of accommodation places increases in 2018 with 60.87% face to 2009.

Qualitative analysis of receiving units' structure on structural types, for those two analysed years, 2009 and 2018, show the fact the rate of agro-tourism boarding houses from the total of units increased, from 46.80% to 50.43% and the rate of tourist boarding houses from the total of tourist units also increased from 22.97% to 25%. The rate of hotels from the total of touristy units from Suceava County reduced from 12.34% in 2009 to 10.43% in 2018.

Table 3

Existent functional tourist accommodation capacity on types of tourist receiving structures from Suceava County during 2009-2018

Types of touristy units	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
	MU: Places-days									
Total	2176422	2263630	2439609	2594059	2642601	2686399	2780181	2764901	2964646	3069443
Hotels	1096689	1141347	1199286	1234081	1329994	1398169	1330435	1251026	1301704	1304429
Hostels	88791	89177	105945	107203	97838	54874	48371	58260	66594	69736
Apartment hotels	8736	:	:	:	:	:	:	:	:	:
Motels	23844	30387	73628	73055	80773	103176	105857	104593	98118	93288
Tourist villas	164625	145579	101860	87689	77010	81643	79128	70612	68397	77875
Tourist chalets	74498	75846	60502	67734	74130	73956	67102	69847	65650	56403
Bungalows	7340	6740	6120	6740	8580	10210	17172	17098	17234	19670
Holiday villages	:	:	:	:	:	:	4816	:	:	:
Camp sites	34756	29398	31692	22712	29088	18352	21432	17952	15688	18128
Tourist halts	9386	8046	8252	6992	5732	4918	23492	24192	23890	20436
Tourist cottages	:	:	920	1840	1220	:	:	366	12	2514
Tourist boarding houses	300606	370943	419498	441444	417341	407494	474472	527300	560909	588039
Agro-tourism boarding houses	367151	366167	431906	544569	520895	533607	607904	623655	746450	818925

Legend: ':' – missing data

Source: insse.ro

The most significant increases of accommodation places were recorded in the case of agro-tourism boarding houses where the rate of accommodation places increased from 23.00% in 2009 to 31.17% in 2018 and in the case of tourist boarding houses from 14.59% in 2009 to 18.99% in 2018. The share held by number of places from hotels in Suceava County decreased from 41.62% in 2009 to 35.18% in 2018.

For an accurate presentation of touristy offer of Suceava County, during 2009-2018, we analysed the existent touristy accommodation capacity and functional touristy accommodation capacity. Their level and dynamics are considered to be the effective offer for accommodation places which exist into touristy accommodation units. To analyse this indicator in dynamics we use the indicators of chronological series.

Analyzing the absolute and relative dynamics for existent accommodation capacity from Suceava County, during 2009-2018 (*tab. 5*), we could observe that number of places considerably increase in 2018 face to 2009 with 60.87%, when was recorded also the highest increase face to reference year. Face to previous year was recorded increases up to 12.00%

(in 2017). Per ensemble the mean level of existent accommodation capacity recorded 9789.2 places, with an absolute mean increase of 510.88 places, respectively a relative increase of 5.4%.

Table 4

Comparative analysis of accommodation units number and places number from touristy receiving structures with function of touristy accommodation between 2009 and 2018 from Suceava County

Unit type	2009				2018			
	Nr. units	%	Nr. places	%	Nr. units	%	Nr. places	%
Hotels	29	12.34	3144	41.62	48	10.43	4276	35.18
Hostels	8	3.4	292	3.86	14	3.04	381	3.13
Apartment hotels	1	0.42	32	0.42	:	-	:	-
Motels	3	1.27	111	1.47	6	1.30	269	2.21
Tourist villas	18	7.66	530	7.01	18	3.91	341	2.80
Tourist chalets	4	1.70	259	3.42	14	3.04	245	2.09
Bungalows	2	0.85	40	0.53	3	0.65	104	0.85
Holiday villages	:	-	:	-	1	0.22	86	0.70
Camp sites	4	1.70	230	3.04	3	0.65	216	1.77
Tourist halts	2	0.85	76	1.00	3	0.65	108	0.88
Tourist cottages	:	-	:	-	3	0.65	30	0.24
Tourist boarding houses	54	22.97	1102	14.58	115	25.00	2308	18.99
Agro-tourism boarding houses	110	46.80	1738	23.00	232	50.43	3788	31.17
Total	235	100	7554	100	460	100	12152	100

Legend: ':' – missing data

Note: calculus in according with insse.ro

Table 5

Absolute and relative modifications of the existent accommodation capacity, in period 2009-2018, in Suceava County

Years	Existent accommodation capacity (places)	Absolute modifications		Dynamics index (%)		Dynamics rhythm (%)	
		$\Delta_{t/1}$	$\Delta_{t/t-1}$	$I_{t/1}$	$I_{t/t-1}$	$R_{t/1}$	$R_{t/t-1}$
2009	7554	-	-	-	-	-	-
2010	8033	479	479	106.34	106.34	6.34	6.34
2011	8835	1281	802	116.96	109.98	16.96	9.98
2012	9447	1893	612	125.06	106.92	25.06	6.92
2013	9585	2031	138	126.88	101.46	26.88	1.46
2014	9650	2096	65	127.74	100.68	27.74	0.68
2015	10143	2589	493	134.27	105.11	34.27	5.11
2016	10610	3056	467	140.45	104.60	40.45	4.60
2017	11883	4329	1273	157.31	112.00	57.31	12.00
2018	12152	4598	269	160.87	102.26	60.87	2.26
	$\bar{y}$	$\bar{\Delta}$		$\bar{I}$		$\bar{R}$	
	9789.2	510.88		1.054 (105.4%)		5.4	

Source: calculus in according with insse.ro

To estimate the existent accommodation capacity for the next five years (2019-2023) we used the adjustment function $y = 481.88x - 960478$ obtained through graphical method in according with the linear trend. R

square was used to indicate the variations of values face to trend line ($R^2 = 0.9869$)(fig. 1).

Fig. 1 - Dynamics and estimation of existent accommodation capacity in period 2009-2023, Suceava County

Analysing the absolute and relative dynamics of functional accommodation capacity, from Suceava County, during 2009-2018 (tab. 6), we could observe that the number of places increased quite high in 2018 face to 2009 with 41.03%, when was recorded also the highest increase face to reference year.

Table 6
Absolute and relative modifications of the functional accommodation capacity, in period 2009-2018, in Suceava County

Years	Functional accommodation capacity (places-days)	Absolute modifications		Dynamics index (%)		Dynamics rhythm (%)	
		$\Delta_{t/1}$	$\Delta_{t/t-1}$	$I_{t/1}$	$I_{t/t-1}$	$R_{t/1}$	$R_{t/t-1}$
2009	2176422	-	-	-	-	-	-
2010	2263630	87208	87208	104.00	104.00	4.00	4.00
2011	2439609	263187	175979	112.09	107.77	12.09	7.77
2012	2594059	417637	154450	119.19	106.33	19.19	6.33
2013	2642601	466179	48542	121.42	101.87	21.42	1.87
2014	2686399	509977	43798	123.43	101.66	23.43	1.66
2015	2780181	603759	93782	127.74	103.49	27.74	3.49
2016	2764901	588479	-15280	127.03	99.45	27.03	-0.55
2017	2964646	788224	199745	136.21	107.22	36.21	7.22
2018	3069443	893021	104797	141.03	103.53	41.03	3.53
	$\bar{y}$	$\bar{\Delta}$		$\bar{I}$		$\bar{R}$	
	2638189.1	99224.55		1.039 (103.9%)		3.9	

Sursa: calcul după insse.ro

Face to previous year were recorded slightly decreases in 2016 (with 0.55%), in the rest of period being recorded increases up to 7.77% (in 2011). Per ensemble mean level of functional accommodation capacity recorded 2638189.1 places-days/year, with an absolute mean increase of 99224.55 places-days/year, respectively with a relative increase of 3.9%. If we compare mean dynamics of functional accommodation capacity (103.9%) with the existent one (105.4%), we could observe that the first one didn't overcome the second one, which means the fact that didn't increased the efficiency of tourist offer by renovation process or by increasing of tourist demand in Suceava County during analysed period (2009-2018).

Adjustment after linear trend of functional accommodation capacity for the next five years (2019-2023) was realised with adjustment function $y = 89099x - 2E+08$. R square was utilised to indicate the values' variations face to trend line ($R^2 = 0.9866$) (fig. 2).

Fig. 2 - Dynamics and estimation of functional accommodation capacity in period 2009-2023, Suceava County

In conditions in which influence factors in touristy activity will have the same rhythm in the next five years (tab. 7), in 2023, in Suceava County existent touristy accommodation capacity will be of around 14500 places, and functional accommodation capacity will be of around 3.5 mil. places-days.

Net utilisation index for functional touristy accommodation capacity which express the relation between functional accommodation capacity and effective utilization of it by tourists (overnights), (into a certain period),

in Suceava County, during 2009-2018 (tab. 8), recorded fluctuant values in those 10 analysed years (2009-2018), in 2018 being recorded the highest value of 29.63%.

Table 7

Estimation of accommodation capacity during 2019 – 2023, in Suceava County

Years	t(x)	Existent accommodation capacity (places)	Functional accommodation capacity (thousands places-days)
		$y = 481.88x - 960478$	$y = 89099x - 2E+08$
2019	11	12434.53	3143953
2020	12	12896.61	3223121
2021	13	13345.89	3292709
2022	14	13864.5	3373095
2023	15	14453.03	3469947

Table 8

Capacity and touristy accommodation activity in Suceava County

Years	Accommodation capacity		Arrivals	Overnights	In (%)
	Existent (places)	Functional (places-days)			
2009	7554	2176422	209725	479402	22,02
2010	8033	2263630	194365	460637	20,35
2011	8835	2439609	229519	556249	22,80
2012	9447	2594059	238611	586237	22,60
2013	9585	2642601	241629	577232	21,84
2014	9650	2686399	260684	583642	2172
2015	10143	2780181	310548	699491	25,16
2016	10610	2764901	342710	759754	27,48
2017	11883	2964646	385676	815732	27,51
2018	12152	3069443	430673	909535	29,63

Legend: In – utilization index for functional accommodation capacity

Source: calculus in according with insse.ro

CONCLUSIONS

Analyzing the absolute and relative dynamics for existent accommodation capacity from Suceava County, during 2009-2018 we could observe that number of places considerably increase in 2018 face to 2009 with 60.87%, when was recorded also the highest increase face to reference year.

Face to previous year was recorded increases up to 12.00% (in 2017). Per ensemble the mean level of existent accommodation capacity recorded 9789.2 places, with an absolute mean increase of 510.88 places, respectively a relative increase of 5.4%.

Analysing the absolute and relative dynamics of functional accommodation capacity, from Suceava County, during 2009-2018, we could observe that the number of places increased quite high in 2018 face to

2009 with 41.03%, when was recorded also the highest increase face to reference year.

Face to previous year were recorded slightly decreases in 2016 (with 0.55%), in the rest of period being recorded increases up to 7.77% (in 2011).

Per ensemble mean level of functional accommodation capacity recorded 2638189.1 places-days/year, with an absolute mean increase of 99224.55 places-days/year, respectively with a relative increase of 3.9%.

If we compare mean dynamics of functional accommodation capacity (103.9%) with the existent one (105.4%), we could observe that the first one didn't overcome the second one, which means the fact that didn't increased the efficiency of tourist offer by renovation process or by increasing of tourist demand in Suceava County during analysed period (2009-2018).

In conditions in which influence factors in touristy activity will have the same rhythm in the next five years, in 2023, in Suceava County existent touristy accommodation capacity will be of around 15000 places, and functional accommodation capacity will be of around 3.5 mil. places-days.

Net utilisation index for functional touristy accommodation capacity in Suceava County, during 2009-2018, recorded fluctuant values in those 10 analysed years (2009-2018), in 2018 being recorded the highest value of 29.63%.

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STUDY REGARDING THE IMPLIED ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION EXPENDITURE

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Abstract

The expenses for the protection of the environment constitute the economic measure of the answer given by the company for treating the problems generated by the state of the environment at a certain stage. Regional as well as local communities have a significant role in accepting and applying environmental protection measures.

Thus, it is considered that the field of environmental protection is a very important one for the population.

The environment is protected at great expense in the modern world.

The expenses with the protection of the environment include the expenses incurred to carry out the activities of surveillance and protection of the environment, but also those that refer to the prevention or repair of the damages brought to it.

The expenses that are made with the protection of the environment are lower when its degradation is prevented compared to the situation when it is repaired. In other words, in the protection of the environment, not therapy, but prophylaxis should be established as the basic rule. Environmental protection measures are becoming more and more necessary.

As a result of the depletion of natural resources, there is an upward evolution of the quantities of waste.

The paper presents a situation of the expenses for environmental protection.

The general situation related to the expenses for environmental protection in Romania was improved by increasing the available funds, as a result of the economic growth and also of the revenues to the state budget.

Keywords: environmental protection, expenditure, natural resources

INTRODUCTION

The environment means: wonderful scenery and recreational environment; fresh air and drinking water; investment opportunities with positive consequences on GDP growth and job creation; supplier of raw materials, energy, etc .; capacity to absorb and recycle waste; protector of life through forests and river basins; source of oxygen and ozone (Manoliu. M., Ionescu, Cris tina, 1998)

We attend more and more often, at actions where some of the raw materials, intermediate or final products, especially complex, are found in air, water and soil (EEA, 2008).

Pollution, by introducing into the environment matter or energy with harmful or harmful effects, alters ecosystems, diminishes biological resources and endangers human health ”(Munteanu, C., Dumitrașcu, Mioara, Iliuță, RA, 2011)

The environmental problems are particularly complex, because the causes are interdependent, which requires actions at all levels: local, national and regional authorities, each having its own role in increasing the responsibility for the protection of the environment (Comănescu Mihaela, 2010).

The problems regarding the protection of the environment are in the attention of some international institutions, which monitor the activity carried out by the countries in this field. It should be noted that, through the actions taken, especially in the last eight decades, Romania has some positive results, being ahead of countries in Europe and on other continents. (M arinescu, RT, 2018)

Environmental protection includes all the measures by which the economic and social development takes into account the ecological requirements of the development (Badea, Carmen Georgiana, Angheluț, P., S., 2017).

This refers both in technique and in practice to ensuring the necessary conditions for the preservation and improvement of the quality of natural factors, increasing natural wealth, ensuring better living and working conditions for present and future generations. From all points of view, environmental quality is the inseparable central element of quality of life.

Quality environment positively affects economic growth because, firstly, acts favorably on the main production factor - man, keeping health and exempt companies spending for medical assistance and, secondly, contribute to ensuring and activation natural factors of production - land with his riches. (Gheres Marinela, 2007).

Expenditure for environmental protection represents the economic measure of the response given by the company to address the problems generated by the state of the environment at a certain stage.

These include the expenses incurred for carrying out environmental monitoring and protection activities and those relating to the prevention or repair of the damages brought to it (Frășineanu I., Băloiu L., 2007) .

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research methods used by the authors consisted of consulting a bibliography from the specialized literature, collecting statistical data, documentary analysis, graphical representation, classification, comparative analysis.

Expenditure on environmental protection reflects the financing flows of the environment and includes payments for economic activities aimed at producing specific services for preventing, reducing or combating environmental damage.

These are grouped into: current investments and expenditures which in turn include internal current expenditures (salaries and social contributions, consumption of raw materials, fuels, energy, water and other auxiliary materials, research and development expenses, training, information, administration of and external current expenses (expenses for environmental protection services purchased from third parties and for environmental taxes paid) (INS, 2015).

The categories of producers are divided into: specialized producers, non-specialized producers and the public administration sector (INS, 2017). Each of these categories is composed of units specific to the respective activities.

Thus, from the category of specialized producers are: units for collection and treatment of waste water; the units for the collection, treatment and disposal of waste, recovery activities of recyclable materials; the units for decontamination services and units dealing with the wholesale trade of waste and scrap. (INS, 2014).

The non-specialized producers include: forestry units, economic units in the extractive, processing, production and supply of electricity and heat, gas, hot water and air conditioning; units for water capture, treatment and distribution; the construction units and the units that have transport activity. Within the category of the public administration sector are the units of central and local public administration.

The Public Administration includes all the units of the local and central public administration that produce or finance non-commercial environment protection services, intended for individual and collective consumption (INS, 2016).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From analysis DATEL or presented in Table 1, it is found that for between 2014-2018 environment costs of producers we specialize increased, peaking in 2015 (9,262,709 thousand).

Thus, in 2015 they were 2.35 times higher than in 2009 (3,929,598 thousand lei) .

Also, it can be seen that the expenses for the environmental protection of specialized producers decreased, the smallest decrease being in 2016 (5,138,758 thousand lei) .

Table 1

Evolution of expenditures for environmental protection by activity sectors
- RON tho using current prices-

Sectors of activity	The year				
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Non-specialized producers	6078229	9262709	4844684	5253304	6953322
Forestry, logging and related services	34.193	46.675	269.955	246.967	270.720
Extractive industry	596.107	553.873	474.329	620.704	1569569
Manufacturing industry	1539285	2940678	1269102	1357311	1367959
Production and supply of electricity and heat, gas and hot water	1662484	2612875	1202476	1582996	2,195.9 52
Water capture, treatment and distribution	2005086	2767395	1257777	1013776	1115525
Construction	88.008	117.977	146.059	135.482	144.852
Transport	153.066	223.236	224.986	275.056	259.281
Other activities		-	-	21.012	29.464
Specialized manufacturers	7145977	6229382	5138758	6203919	6.73243 million
Public Administration	3132485	4507534	5.5207 million	4310403	7.1805 million

Sources: www.insse.ro

Regarding the expenses for the environmental protection of the producers of the public administration sector, an increase of 2.29 times in 2018 is observed compared to 2014.

From the analysis of the expenses for the environmental protection of the non-specialized producers in 2018, it turns out that in the field of "production and supply of electricity and heat, gas and hot water" 31.6% of the expenses were registered, while in the sector "industry" 22.6% were extracted, while the "processing industry" sector spent 19.7% of the expenses of non-specialized producers.

Expenditures at national level include: investments, internal current expenses (current expenses incurred through own activities of environmental protection) and other public administration expenses (grants awarded, transfers), not including external current expenses (expenses for the purchase of environmental protection services). to third parties, as well as taxes paid as an environment)

In 2014, expenditures for environmental protection at national level were about 12.6 billion lei , rising to 15.6 billion lei in 2015, decreased to 9.0 billion lei in 2016 and again increased to about 14 , 7 billion lei in 2018 (table 2).

Table 2
Expenses for environmental protection by types of producers and categories of expenses

- RON thousand current prices -

Types of manufacturers	investments	Internal current expenditure	Internal current expenditure	Transfers
2014				
Non-specialized producers	3.08957 million	1332819	1.65584 million	-
Specialized manufacturers	372.637	5822854	950.486	-
Public Administration	792.469	1020643	1181316	138.057
2015				
Non-specialized producers	4.82857 million	2706216	1727923	-
Specialized manufacturers	775.695	4458577	995.110	-
Public Administration	1,140 , 763	1530528	1687356	
2016				
Non-specialized producers	1233658	1507782	2103244	-
Specialized manufacturers	285.600	3801206	1051952	-
Public Administration	1.4852 million	709.018	1166683	2.1598 million
2017				
Non-specialized producers	887.667	1,671 , 874	2693763	-
Specialized manufacturers	266.043	4449551	1488325	-
Public Administration	1152299	1073011	1272689	812.404
2018				
Non-specialized producers	1,657,409.00	1,947,580.00	3,348,333.00	-
Specialized manufacturers	400,913.00	4,833, 490.00	1,498,027.00	-
Public Administration	1,434,900.00	1,147,962.00	1,356,038.00	3,241,600.00

Sources: www.insse.ro

At national level (tables 2), the largest investments for environmental protection were registered in the field of wastewater management in the public administration, representing 78.0% of the total investments in the field of wastewater management.

Fig. 1. Environmental protection investments, by field and producer category, in 2018 (RON thousand current prices)
Sources: www.insse.ro

From the analysis of the national level for the year of investments 2018, the following aspects are found: the share of investments of non-specialized producers (figure 1) represented 47.4% in total investments for environmental protection ; the share of investment of their government represented 41.1% and that of investiții or professional producer accounted for 1 1.5%.

Fig. 2 . Evolution of the total expenditures for environmental protection by environmental domains
Sources: www.insse.ro

In 2018, by environmental domains (Figure 2), the highest expenditures were registered for waste management (44.1% of the total expenditures for environmental protection at national level), followed by the expenditures for other environmental domains (18, 7%) and the expenses for waste water management and air protection with 16.3% each .

The environmental protection actions eligible for support within the National Framework are as follows: Air protection, Waste water management, Waste management , Soil and groundwater protection, Protection of natural resources and biodiversity conservation, Other environmental areas (National framework for protection measures) environment, 2019)

Table 3 presents the environmental expenditures of producers well specialized in environmental areas , for between 2014 -2018 . Thus, the expenses with the management of the waste water decreased during the analyzed period by 1,158,803 thousand lei from 2,215,714 thousand lei in 2014 to 1,056,911 thousand lei in 2018 (decrease over 50%). The other categories of expenses had an upward evolution: expenses with waste management increase of 1.39 times, expenses with rotation of soil and groundwater , increase of 1.57 times, and expenses with other environmental areas, increase of 3, 66 times.

Table 3

Evolution of the expenses for environmental protection of non-specialized producers in environmental fields

- RON thousand current prices -

Environmental areas	The year				
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Air protection	1126659	2329749	425.516	332.750	1083325
Waste water management	2215714	2522504	1251416	997.224	1056911
Waste management	292.031	458.245	238.498	303.709	404.714
Protection of soil and groundwater	260.484	416.369	233.235	409.870	408.108
Protection of natural resources and conservation of biodiversity	130.698	79.984	183.471	152.720	172.992
Other environmental areas	130.698	1727935	409.304	363.268	478.939

Sources: www.insse.ro

From the analysis of the data presented in table 4 , it is found that for the period 2014-2018 the expenses for the environmental protection of the specialized producers registered a downward evolution , except for the expenses with the protection of the air that increased (increase with 5,766

thousands lei) . The expenses with the management of the waste decreased by 918,345 thousand lei during the analyzed period (from 5,928,533 thousand in 2014 to 5,010,188 lei in 2018), the expenses with p rotation of the soil and of the groundwater decreased by 3.58 times, and expenditures for other environmental domains fell 3.43 times.

Table 4

Evolution of the expenses for environmental protection of specialized producers in environmental fields

- RON thousand current prices -

Environmental areas	The year				
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Air protection	124.404	17.482	108.310	12.320	130.170
Waste water management	90.490	129.453	61.849	76.041	77.580
Waste management	5928533	4788232	3852293	4544257	5010188
Protection of soil and groundwater	14.091	20.795	8709	51.995	3941
Protection of natural resources and conservation of biodiversity	2,342	118	390	1679	2143
Other environmental areas	35.631	278.192	55.255	29.302	10.381

Sources: w ww.insse.ro

Regarding the expenses for the environmental protection of the public administration, they increased considerably between 2014-2018. Thus, expenses with air protection registered a significant increase of 11.22 times (from 104,476 thousand lei in 2014 to 1,171,770 thousand lei in 2018), while the expenses with other environmental fields increased by 30.1 times. On the other hand, expenditures for the protection of natural resources and the conservation of biodiversity fell considerably by 21.1 times in 2018.

Table 5

Evolution of expenditures for environmental protection of public administration on environmental domains

- RON thousand current prices -

Environmental areas	The year				
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Air protection	104.476	220.99	609.556	683.168	1.17177 million
Waste water management	825.777	817.465	1131556	815.948	1257969
Waste management	909.890	1.54517 million	937.092	1082693	1048138
Protection of soil and groundwater	9001	40.007	12.666	58.664	90.734

Protection of natural resources and conservation of biodiversity	27.068	110.871	25.878	868	1285
Other environmental areas	74.957	85.675	1.63727 million	396.373	2254566

Sources: www.insse.ro

In the coming period, efforts to improve environmental activities must constitute a concern valued for all the stakeholders involved in this area. According to estimates of the Department IU Environmental Protection and of European experts, it is estimated that over the next 20 years, to maintain environmental balances as close as environmental standards, Romania will have to invest over 20 billion euros.

CONCLUSION

The concerns in Romania for the protection of the environment, for the protection of natural beauty, as well as for preventing the abusive exploitation of nature, are not recent.

The analysis shows that the environment is a "factor of life", while the development of industry and other economic activities that has not always been of the highest quality have led to its degradation. In these conditions, it is necessary that in the next period a better organized and protected evolution will be ensured, so that the quality of the environment is protected. Also, emphasis should be placed on measures to protect the environment, and developments in the polluting branches should be sufficiently protected on the one hand, and on the other hand, the effects of polluting factors should be diminished.

Romania is facing serious environmental problems, INS to report at expenses of 14.7 billion lei in this sector in 2018.

It is noted that for the period 2014-2018, due to the reduction of the expenses for the environmental protection of the specialized producers, the expenses for the environmental protection of the non-specialized producers, but also those of the public administration sector, have registered an increasing trend.

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RESEARCH ON THE BEHAVIOR AND QUALITATIVE CHANGES OF FROZEN APPLES

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Abstract

Apples can freeze as such. During the freezing and thawing operations, a series of changes of the physico-chemical and organoleptic characteristics take place, which are mainly due to the color and structure-texture changes and the degradation of some components, especially of vitamin C.

Key words: apples, freezing, color change, structure-texture, organoleptic properties, vitamin C.

INTRODUCTION

Frozen apples are an appreciated assortment, being used in confectionery or compote preparation.

The freezing can be done in two variants: in the form of slices or rounds as such or in sugar syrup.

For freezing, varieties with light-colored, a sweet-sour taste, aromatic, firm, dense pulp, resistant to browning, have reached technological maturity.

For cold resistant varieties (Golden Delicious, Red Delicious, Starkrimson, Renet Baumann, etc.) the refrigeration is carried out at 0 ... +1°C (A. Ardelean, 2019).

A series of physico-chemical and organoleptic changes occur during freezing and storage.

The dehydration of frozen products is among the physico-chemical modifications, especially if the packaging is not efficiently enough. It must be impermeable to water vapor and sealed. Also, water losses occur during storage, especially for products stored in bulk or in permeable packaging for water vapor.

At the same time, the freezing modality influences the percentage of water lost from fruits. Studies have shown that by the method of rapid freezing, fruits lose less water compared to the slow freezing process (Gherghi A., 1998).

A consequence of the dehydration phenomenon is the weight loss of the frozen products.

Another negative effect of freezing is the modification of the texture by the loss of the consistency of the fruits, a phenomenon due to the losses of cellular liquid upon defrosting, as a result of the damage of the cell membranes, especially in the slow freezing variant. Also, the scalding operation performed for the purpose of enzymatic inactivation, causes changes in the structure of pectic substances in the cell membranes, affecting the consistency of the products (I. F. Radu, 1985, I. F. Radu, A. Gherghi, 1967).

Due to these changes, the structure-texture becomes looser, and weight loss due to water evaporation and cell juice leakage is observed on the bottom of the packages (I. Potec, et al, 1983, 1985, D. Beceanu, A. Chira, 2003, Gh. Mihalca, 1980).

Among the important chemical changes that take place during the technological flow are: soluble dry matter content, total acidity and vitamin C losses.

Organoleptic changes refer to diminished losses of aroma and taste due to the effect of the scalding operation, the degradation of some components and the losses of cell juice.

Research on the content of vitamin C has revealed that by freezing losses of vitamins occur, which are soluble in water, but the losses are much lower compared to other processing processes (Inoue K. et al., 1998, Neamțu G. et al., 1993, 1997). These vitamin losses are due to their solubility in scalding water and degradation during freezing.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research was carried out in 2019, at the Faculty of Environmental Protection Oradea.

The Golden Delicious apple variety, which is a winter variety, was used in the studies. Harvesting took place in mid-October.

The fruits have a light, crispy flesh, with a succulent, slightly acidic sweet taste and a specific aroma.

The research was carried out on fresh and frozen fruits for two months.

The operations of the freezing technological flow are the following: harvesting, storage, quantitative and qualitative reception, conditioning operations (sorting, washing, sorting, cleaning, dividing), antioxidant treatment, packaging, freezing, storage, delivery.

The cleaning consists in extracting the seed core, followed by the split into slices (8-12 pieces).

To strengthen the structure, the fruit slices were immersed in a solution of sodium chloride and calcium chloride 1%.

Antioxidant treatments are performed to avoid the phenomena of browning (oxidation), by scalding.

The scalding was done by immersion in water for 1-2 minutes.

The frozen fruit was packaged in 200g casseroles.

Freezing was performed in the freezer.

Storage is performed for all frozen products at -18°C . The storage time depends on the freezing method used: 3-5 months for the frozen apples as such.

The main chemical indicators analyzed for both fresh and frozen samples refer to soluble dry matter content, total titratable acidity and vitamin C content. For frozen samples the determinations were performed after thawing and appropriate preparation of the samples.

The soluble dry substance was determined refractometrically directly in the field with the Zeiss portable refractometer for the fresh products, so that the optimum harvest time was established based on this value (A. Ardelean, 2009).

The total titratable acidity was determined as follows: fresh products were milled, filtered and titrated with sodium hydroxide solution with the known factor, in the presence of phenolphthalein as a color indicator (A. Ardelean, 2015).

The vitamin C content is determined by iodometric method. Thus, 15 g of product to be assessed are weighed with the analytical balance from the intermediate sample which is grinded with 2 g of quartz sand and 10 ml of metaphosphoric acid until a homogenous paste is obtained. The mixture is passed through a calibrated flask of 50 ml and is brought to the sign with metaphosphoric acid. Then, the mixture is filtered and 10 ml are furtherly assessed. Two titration are further made.

The titration of the standard solution of ascorbic acid: in an Erlenmeyer glass, 10 ml of ascorbic acid, 20 ml of distilled water, two drops of hydrochloric acid solution 1M, 15 drops of amidon solution 1% are put together. They are all titrated with iodine solution until the change of colour into lavender blue.

The titration of the sample under study: the working technique is the one previously presented with the observation that the standard solution of ascorbic acid is replaced with 10 ml of sample to be filtered. Titration is also performed with iodine solution until the change of colour into lavender blue (C. Purcărea, 2005, 2008, C. Hura, 2006).

The organoleptic properties of fresh and frozen fruits were determined by sensory methods. Thus, the appearance of the fruits in terms of pigmentation and texture, but also taste and aroma were analyzed.

RESULTS AND DISSCUSIONS

Immediately after harvesting, analysis samples were performed, and the results present the average of the determinations.

The physical-chemical properties analyzed in fresh apples are presented in Table no. 1.

Table no. 1

The main indicators analyzed in fresh apples

Sample no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Samples average
Weight (g)	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
S.D.M. (%)	17	17,5	18	17,5	18	18,5	17,5	18	18,5	17,5	17,8
Total titratable acidity (malic acid)g/%	3,2	3,2	3,0	3,2	3,1	3,5	3,0	3,5	3,5	3,2	3,2
Vit. C (mg/100g)	5,9	5,8	6,0	5,8	5,9	6,0	5,5	5,9	5,7	5,5	5,8

The physico-chemical properties analyzed for frozen apples stored for two months are presented in table 2.

Table no. 2

The main indicators analyzed for frozen apples stored for two months

Nr. probă	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Samples average
S.D.M. (%)	15,5	15,0	16,0	15,0	16,5	16,0	15,5	16,0	16,0	15	15,65
Total titratable acidity (malic acid)g/%	2,9	3,0	2,7	2,8	2,9	3,1	2,6	3,0	3,1	2,8	2,89
Vit. C (mg/100g)	5,3	5,2	5,5	5,8	5,0	5,0	5,0	5,1	5,0	4,9	5,18

From the analysis of the obtained results, a decrease in the value of the total titratable acidity and of the vitamin C content is observed. The change in the total titratable acidity is due to the loss of a quantity of water by

freezing and as a result the concentration of the cellular juice takes place, which also caused the decrease in the soluble dry matter content.

The decrease in vitamin C content is due both to the losses recorded during the water scalding operation, as it is a water soluble vitamin, and due to its degradation during the freezing operation and during storage.

From the point of view of the weight of the samples, the decreases recorded are due to the losses of cell juice after the thawing operation. By the slow freezing carried out in the domestic freezers, non-uniform ice crystals are formed as an intra- and intercellular size, which, at the time of thawing, damages the thin epidermis of the split into slices.

From the sensory point of view, there was a decrease of the organoleptic characteristics, respectively taste and aroma, the changes being more noticeable in the samples deposited for four months. As for the texture, it has become looser for thawed products as a result of cell juice losses. The pigmentation has been preserved, the thawed fruits have an intense coloring similar to the fresh products.

CONCLUSIONS

From the analysis of the results obtained regarding the quality changes in the frozen and stored apple samples, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The soluble dry matter content (s.u.s.) slightly decreased for the samples stored for two months;

3. The total titrable acidity, expressed in malic acid, also decreased during the storage period.

4. Vitamin C content is reduced, primarily due to the scalding operation and due to chemical degradation during freezing and thawing.

5. Regarding the organoleptic properties, some changes are observed: the structure of the apple slices becomes looser, a phenomenon that is more intense in the case of slow freezing, due to the cracking of the cell membranes and the epidermis during the freezing and thawing operations. The taste and aroma lose their intensity compared to fresh fruits. This aspect is due to the water losses that result in some of the dissolved substances responsible for these properties. The pigmentation does not show any changes compared to the fresh products, which is why the fruits of this species can be frozen without sugar.

6. Apples are very suitable for preservation by freezing in the sugar-free version, considering the behavior of this species during the technological flow.

7. It is also recommended to use rigid casserole packages to preserve the integrity of apple slices.

8. The defrosting of the fruits is carried out at room temperature, so that the losses of cell juice are minimal.

9. It is recommended to continue research on freezing apples and other methods.

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ROMANIAN WALNUTS, SOURCE OF IMPORTANT NUTRIENTS

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Abstract

Walnut is a good source of macronutrients and micronutrients and other bioactive substances. Romania presents a long tradition being one of the leading walnut producers of EU. The aim of the study was to evaluate the mineral content and total polyphenols of the Romanian walnuts kernel originated from Banat region (western Romania). The study results show that the analyzed walnuts samples presents a high content of minerals (average value) like: potassium (404.50 mg/100 g kernels F.W.), magnesium (221.17 mg/100 g kernels F.W.), manganese (6.12 mg/100 g kernels F.W.), iron (3.67 mg/100 g kernels F.W.) and copper (2.28 mg/100 g kernels F.W.), but also high levels of total polyphenols 9.19 mg GAE/ g nuts kernel extract. Based on mineral composition and polyphenols content a database can be created for walnuts fingerprint profiles that can be used to identify the origin of undeclared walnuts cultivars.

Keywords: *Juglans regia L.*, polyphenols, minerals, fingerprint

INTRODUCTION

Among common foods and beverages, nuts are one of the most important sources of polyphenols, therefore, their effect on human health draws attention. In 2017, Romania was the leading walnut producer in the European Union and among the world's top-ten producers (FAS Europe Offices). The main production regions are in the Carpathian Mountains, as well as northwestern, northeastern, and southern regions of Romania. (https://agfstorage.blob.core.windows.net/misc/FP_com/2019/04/05/Nuts002.pdf)

Walnut is a good source of macronutrients and micronutrients and other bioactive substances. The nut kernel contains 15.8% protein, 13.7% carbohydrate, 4.1% water and 1.8% ashes (NUTS and HEALTH).

Nuts contain relevant micronutrients, such as folic acid, niacin and vitamins E and B6, gamma tocopherol, choline, and minerals such as magnesium, copper, zinc, selenium, phosphorus and potassium (USDA Database). They are also an excellent source of flavonoids, pectic substances, sterols, polyphenols and phenolic acids (TABASUM F., UMBREEN S. and HUSSAIN, S. Z., 2018).

Walnuts have well-known properties of antioxidant and anti-inflammatory bioactivity and several studies have evaluated the potential role of walnuts against cancer, cardiovascular and neurodegenerative diseases. Walnut kernels represent a high source of protein, fat, vitamins, minerals and polyphenols, which makes them indispensable for human nutrition. The diet that involves regular consumption of walnuts is associated with a reduced risk for both fatal coronary heart disease and non-fatal myocardium, heart attack (CHRZANOWSKI et al, 2011).

Other results showed that people who consumed nuts five or more times a week had a 50% lower risk of coronary heart disease compared to those who never consumed nuts (DAVIS et al, 2007).

Although walnuts are high in fat, a diet supplemented with nuts has a beneficial effect on blood lipids, lowering blood cholesterol and lowering the ratio of serum concentrations of low-density lipoproteins: high-density lipoprotein by 12%. Nuts contain about 10% α -linolenic acid that has been associated with an antithrombotic effect. Other benefits of walnuts include high magnesium, copper, folic acid, protein, potassium, fiber and vitamin E (TABASUM F., UMBREEN S. and HUSSAIN, S. Z., 2018).

The Romanian walnut varieties present rich mineral composition, especially high content of potassium, phosphorus, magnesium and iron (COSMULESCU et al, 2009).

Walnuts contain about 65% fat by weight, which makes them dense and calorie rich. However, even though nuts are high in fat and calories, studies specify that they do not increase the threat of obesity when replacing other foods in the diet. (<https://www.healthline.com/nutrition/foods/walnuts>)

The aim of the study was to generate the fingerprint of the analyzed walnuts assortments cultivated in Banat region, based on mineral and polyphenols content

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The walnuts kernels used for the study investigation were sampled from different private producers from Banat region. All the weighed samples were dried at 105 °C and grinded. The mineral content were determined by flame atomic absorption spectrometry as described by Bordean et al, 2014. All analysis were performed in triplicate (BORDEAN, et al, 2014).

The determination of the total content of polyphenols is based on the Folin Ciocalteu method. Spectrophotometric reading of the absorbance is performed at 750 nm after 2 hours of reaction. A calibration curve was constructed using gallic acid as standard, as described by Figueroa et al, 2016 and total polyphenols content (Pph) was expressed as milligrams of

gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per gram walnuts extract. The extraction was performed with 50% ethanol solution (FIGUEROA et al, 2016)

All reagents were of Ultra pure grade.

Statistical analysis

The statistical evaluation of the experimental data was done using MVSP 3.22 and PAST 2.14 software. (HAMMER et al, 2001)

The Simple linear correlation is used as a method to evaluate the degree to which two variables vary together, or a measure of the strength of the association between two variables. (https://www.ndsu.edu/faculty/horsley/Corr_revised.pdf)

The correlation coefficient “r” appreciates “the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two variables on a scatterplot” (RUMSEY et al, 2016)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that the mineral elements form the series: K> Mg> Mn> Fe> Cu, depending on their content in the walnut kernel, which is confirmed, also, by the research of Boaghi. 2018. (BOAGHI E., 2018).

Table 1.

Mineral composition and polyphenol content of studied walnut kernel samples

Walnut samples	Pph [mg GAE/ g nuts kernel extract]	Minerals [mg/100 g nuts kernel F.W.]				
		K	Mg	Fe	Cu	Mn
WA1	7.79 ± 1.13	435 ± 2.26	191 ± 2.16	3.12 ± 0.15	1.88 ± 0.12	4.23 ± 1.12
WA2	9.67 ± 1.35	357 ± 2.53	251 ± 1.88	3.45 ± 1.19	2.89 ± 0.88	7.63 ± 1.64
WA3	9.82 ± 1.88	389 ± 2.66	247 ± 1.08	3.61 ± 0.84	2.31 ± 0.57	4.56 ± 2.05
WA4	9.98 ± 1.65	410 ± 2.19	263 ± 1.75	4.10 ± 0.77	1.98 ± 0.55	7.42 ± 1.17
WA5	9.19 ± 1.03	441 ± 1.56	201 ± 2.13	3.85 ± 1.27	2.05 ± 1.05	5.99 ± 1.66
WA6	8.69 ± 1.12	395 ± 1.79	174 ± 3.22	3.90 ± 0.85	2.55 ± 1.84	6.87 ± 1.58

Legend: WA1, WA2, WA3, WA4, WA5, WA6 – walnut samples from Banat region; Pph = total polyphenol content, mg GAE = milligram Gallic Acid Equivalent; F.W. = fresh weight

Based on the linear correlation r of the experimental data, presented in table 2 we can affirm that both minerals, K and Mg present strong positive relationship with Fe, while Mg shows also, high positive relationship with Cu and moderate correlation with Mn. Pph shows moderate positive relationship with Cu.

Applying the graphic fingerprint profiling using MVSP we can observe that WA1 (using mineral and Pph content values) can be used as a basis to describe the mineral composition of the walnuts cultivated in the western part of Romania, WA2-WA6 presenting similar trend and small variations (Figure 1).

Table 2

The linear correlation r of the experimental data

0	Pph	K/10	Mg/10	Fe	Cu	Mn
Pph	0	0.30227	0.035992	0.22862	0.54936	0.3092
K/10	-0.50915	0	0.33118	0.96319	0.015212	0.33034
Mg/10	0.84082	-0.48357	0	0.72815	0.78382	0.54967
Fe	0.57893	0.024543	0.18328	0	0.9468	0.21997
Cu	0.3104	-0.89753	0.14514	-0.03548	0	0.28611
Mn	0.50294	-0.4843	0.31016	0.58767	0.52384	0

Fingerprint (Figure 2) relay usually on spectroscopic analysis and when it to compare and interpret huge amount of data or to identify the origin of different analysed product samples. The data of samples of unknown origin can be compared with the profiles existing in the database for simplifying the identification (BRERETON, 2013)

Fig. 1. Walnuts fingerprint profile based on Pph and mineral composition
 Legend: WA1, WA2, WA3, WA4, WA5, WA6 – Walnut samples from Banat region; Pph = total polyphenol content [mg GAE/ g nuts kernel extract], mineral composition = concentration of K, Mg, Fe, Cu, Mn [mg/100 g nuts kernel F.W.]

Fig. 2. Banat Region Walnut Fingerprint based on mineral composition and total polyphenol content

Legend: WA1, WA2, WA3, WA4, WA5, WA6 – Walnut samples from Banat region; Pph = total polyphenol content [mg GAE/ g nuts kernel extract], mineral composition = concentration of K, Mg, Fe, Cu, Mn [mg/100 g nuts kernel F.W.]

CONCLUSION

Romanian walnut samples represent a high source of minerals and polyphenols, which recommend them for daily use. The polyphenol content of the analyzed walnut samples is very high. There are possibilities to identify the origin of undeclared walnuts cultivars based on fingerprint profiles and fingerprints database, which reduces the number of time-consuming analysis.

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ELABORATION OF MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR A MEXICAN RESTAURANT

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Abstract

In order to be successful, a business must have a short, medium and long term strategic planning. The aim of this paper is to develop a set of marketing strategies that will help the company increase the economic profitability.

Key words: *strategic planning, marketing strategies, Mexican restaurant*

INTRODUCTION

The smooth running of a business involves the rigorous organization of the whole activity, together with its planning, setting clear objectives, developing long and medium term strategies, evaluating the results¹, etc.

Regarding the activity of a business, there are a more ways of planning, the most common ones being the operational and strategic planning. The most important type of planning for a company is the strategic type because the strategies are oriented to a long term, including all company's activity.²

The aim of this scientific paper is the elaboration of a set of marketing strategies that will help the restaurant adapt to the market that it is going to serve. An efficient marketing strategy is effective when it helps the company fulfill its objectives.³

¹ BerzinsG., *Strategic Planning*, University of Latvia,

² .DFANZ. Leading Accounting Association in Australia and New Zealand , *The Life Cycle of The Business Plan*, 2015

³ Arenas AriasY., *La importancia de realizar un plan de negocio para la creación de una empresa*, Universidad Militar Nueva Granda, Bogotá, Colombia, 2016

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The market

The “El Sombrero” particularly addresses those who do not have much time to eat and are always on the run and looking for something different, new, tasty, spicy relatively fast. These types of meals are for any type of clients of all ages. It is also addressed to married, unmarried people, with or without children, students, employees of companies and banks in the surrounding area, with minimum incomes, average and above average, with different lifestyles, people belonging to different social classes, etc.⁴

When it comes to behavioral criteria, the restaurant is aimed at those who have positive attitudes and reactions regarding fast food and the restaurants that serve this type of food. However, from a geographical point of view, most customers will be those who live or have work in the area, as well as the clientele segment and those who stroll through the city center and want to eat something quick and tasty in the restaurant or take-away food to consume outside of the restaurant.⁵

Regarding the demand for fast food products, it is obvious that there is a high demand. Romanians are consuming more and more of this type of fast food, thus the offer of a relatively new concept would be an opportunity that should not be overlooked. The fact that more and more people are traveling is an advantage for restaurants with a specific character. Most of the fast food consumers are probably tired of the products already on the market in Oradea, such as shaorma, kebab or burgers and they want something else, something different and something healthier and many of the El Sombrero's dishes are healthier because they contain less fat and not all the ingredients need to be fried in an oil bath. Most meals are made from raw or cooked vegetables. Sauces are also prepared in the restaurant's kitchen and are not purchased by trade⁵.

This extremely high demand for fast food has contributed to the decision of opening a Mexican fast food restaurant as customers will be able to enjoy the novelty of the product, the high quality of the services provided, the convenient price and the kindness of the staff when fulfilling duties⁶. In addition, the products will be manufactured from fresh and quality raw

⁴ TerwindtF., RajanD., *Strategic planning: Transforming priorities into plans*, World Health Organization, 2016

⁵ Istocescu A., *Management. Analiză comparativă: întreprinderile mici sau mijlocii versus organizațiile mari din România în condițiile societății bazate pe cunoaștere*

⁶ .World Bank Group, *Strategic Planning: A ten-step guide.*, United States of America

materials. That is why it can be said that the demand for the restaurant's products will be a daily one and there will be quite a large flow⁷.

The competition

The competition is represented by all the other fast food restaurants in Oradea, but the main and direct competitor who specializes in Mexican food is Taco Fresh. A competitive advantage would be the value for money, the dishes of the El Sombrero restaurant, the diversified range of products, the way of serving, the approach and the know-how (secret recipes).

The providers

The main raw materials needed for the finished products offered by the El Sombrero restaurant are: wheat flour and corn, maize, beans, chilli, jalapeño, tomatoes, tomatillos (green tomatoes), pumpkin, avocado, cumin, mint, oregano, parsley, meat (pork, beef, chicken), shrimp, rice, oranges, mango, onion, pepper, cilantro, thyme, pepper, salt, tortillas for fajitas and quesadillas (those for tacos will be made by the restaurant's chef), cheese, fruit etc.

All these raw materials will be purchased from the city's department stores (METRO, Selgros, Kaufland, etc.). If these raw materials will not be found in the city's department stores, specialized importers will be called upon.

In order to identify the market strategies of the Restaurant, I will be using the SWOT analysis, this representing a great method of identifying the general state of the market restaurant so that I would be able to elaborate a development plan, in which to emphasize the company's strengths and oportunities on the market and to exclude the weaknesses and emergence of potential threats.¹⁰

Table no1

The SWOT Analysis for the Mexican's Restaurant

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attractive price, affordable for all social categories; • Superior product quality; • Diversified product range; • The uniqueness of the menu; • The novelty of the products; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low awareness; • Small space (limited number of people), where the flow of customers will increase, the restaurant has 116 places; • New taste

⁷ JiménezY. B., *Aplicacion del proceso de planeación para una empresa de transporte de material y residuos peligrosos.*, Universidad de las Américas Puebla, Mexico, 2003

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Motivated and dedicated staff; 	
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demographic growth; Expansion of the space, if it is considered that the current space is too small for the flow of customers, measures will be taken; Extending the product range; Opening another premises under the brand El Sombrero in another part of the city or in another city Diversification of distribution services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Undecided customers Difficulties in marketing Change of legislation that could have negative effects on the business The emergence of new competitors in the market The already existing competition;

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Product strategy

The products and services marketed by the company are closely linked to public food. The finished products of the company are culinary dishes belonging to Mexican gastronomy that can be prepared quickly in a specialized professional kitchen for a fast-food restaurant. These dishes, although fast food, are appetizing and tasty and can be liked by anyone. The strengths of the products would be the taste, the authentic and unique taste, the appearance and the speed of their preparation.

The products offered by El Sombrero are based on ingredients such as corn, beans, chilli, tomatoes, tomatillos (green tomatoes), pumpkin, avocado, cumin, mint, oregano, parsley, pork, beef, chicken, shrimp, rice, oranges, mango, onion, cilantro, thyme and pepper. And among these preparations are: burritos, tacos, empanadas, quesadillas, fajitas.

Among the services provided by the company are those related to hospitality, which include kindness, speed, respect offered to customers, positivity of employees, offering a glass of milk accompanied by spicy preparations. Moreover, it is hoped that in the future free home delivery services will be offered.

The company will use the strategy of differentiation and diversification of the product range. It will use the differentiation from the competitors since there are already a large number of restaurants on the market in Oradea, together with the strategy of diversifying the range in order to satisfy a large number of tastes. Another strategy used will be quality, the company showing a permanent concern for the quality of the

products but also the strategy of innovation, with the help of which we hope to permanently improve the existing products.

Price strategy

The price determination was made according to the ingredients used for each particular product, so that the production cost was calculated for the first time, to which a commercial addition between 30-100% was added.

Finally, the company focused on the strategy of low prices with strong promotion because we want to attract as many customers as possible. The prices charged will be slightly lower than the prices the competition is charging.

Regarding certain offers and price reductions, these will be established in relation with the promotional strategy so that the result will be a positive one. To begin with, a 10% discount will be applied for the second product purchased and a point card will be offered for loyal consumers. The points will be able to be monthly capitalized by paying for a new purchase.

Placememt strategy

The products will be sold in their own space, so the strategy will focus on short distribution channels.

Promotion strategy

The following methods will be used in order to promote the restaurant:

- Media: print media, leaflets, posters;
- Direct advertising: mailing, bus-mailing, catalog (interactive), Facebook page, web page, recommendations, word-of-mouth;
- Product brand: Logo, Slogan;
- Packaging: Materials, format, illustration, design.

The annual costs regarding the promotion will be worth about 5,000 lei since El Sombrero will have a Facebook page through which the restaurant will be promoted and where the restaurant's program will be displayed and updated along with its menu. There will also be a website, the cost of which is 39.99 euros, and other costs will not involve because it will be created and arranged by the company administrator. Thus, regarding the other means of promotion (posters, leaflets, mailing, etc.) the costs are quite

low, only involving their printing and distribution, their designed will be made by the company's administrator, thus not requiring the call for specialized marketing firms.

CONCLUSIONS

The marketing strategies developed will help the "El Sombrero" restaurant achieve profitable economic results. The main advantages are those related to product quality, location, the uniqueness of the menu and the chef's experience. The main risks consist of low notoriety, strong competition and changing legislation. With the help of the marketing strategies developed, the company will succeed in realizing its potential and facing the threats on the market.

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DEPROTEINIZATION INFLUENCE ON SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF NITRATES AND NITRITES

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Abstract

Nitrites and nitrates are contaminants mostly for vegetal origin food through environmental factors or improper agricultural practices.

The main toxicological risk of nitrites is related to nitrosamine formation which was related to some cancer forms.

EU legislation sets Maximum Residues Level values for leafy vegetables and for baby food which are under sanitary-veterinary surveillance.

Several samples of lettuce, rocket salad, spinach and baby food were analysed in order to determinate their nitrites and nitrates content.

Griess spectrophotometric method using an aqueous and deproteinized extracts of the samples was applied. Rocket salad samples show the highest nitrate content (2368 and 2177 mg/kg) on both of the tested extracts.

All leafy vegetal samples have a nitrate content below the legal specific requirement, only frozen spinach was close to MRL. So even if there are no significant differences between the results obtained using different extracts, the deproteinization of the vegetal samples is mandatory for control purposes.

Key words: nitrates, nitrites, deproteinization, Griess method

INTRODUCTION

The foods are subject to contamination by chemical substances from different sources: raw material production, processing, packaging, handling, transportation and especially from environmental factors.

Regarding nitrites and nitrates, they contaminate mostly vegetal origin food due to inappropriate use of fertilisers or from polluted irrigation waters.

The storage conditions of vegetables influence their content of nitrites and nitrates (Chung et al., 2004).

Nitrites and nitrates are also admitted additives for processed meat products in order to preserve their colour and as antimicrobial agent.

Both optic and chromatographic methods are used in order to determinate those contaminants (Silalahi, et al, 2018, Khanfar et al, 2019, Scheeren et al, 2013).

Water or food contamination by nitrites can induce methemoglobinemia to babies, but the major risk of nitrites is related to the

formation of nitrosamines in the presence of secondary amines (Rostkowska, 1998).

Nitrosamines were found to be related to gastric and oesophageal cancer (Bambilla and Martelli, 2007, Jakszyn and González, 2006 a). For humans, the nitrates input are exogenous, but for nitrites it is preponderant endogenous due to the conversion of nitrates to nitrites in the gastric acidic environment (EFSA Journal, 2008).

Therefore, even if the toxic effect of nitrites is higher than the nitrates one, both European (CE 1881/2006) and national legislation (ANSVSA Order nr 97/2007) stipulates Maximum Residues Levels (MRL) for nitrates in order to avoid the accumulation of nitrites through a reduction process.

The MRL values refer to certain leafy vegetables such as spinach, lettuce and rocket salad depending on the cultivation area and period, as well as for baby food.

The presence of nitrates in food is subject to continuous monitoring and Romania is an important contributor to this issue, 20% of total analysed data was from Romania, second after Germany with 34% (EFSA, 2008).

The results from 2008 that refers to the precedent seven years pointed to rocket salad as the most affected vegetable by nitrates contamination.

So, the European legislation was amended by Regulation nr. 1258/2011 and this leafy vegetable was added among those under sanitary veterinary surveillance.

National studies about the intake of nitrites and nitrates through foods were conducted in Spain (Jakszyn et al, 2006 b), Estonia (Tamme et al, 2006) and Portugal (Rebelo et al., 2015).

The aim of this study was to verify the influence of the deproteinization of some vegetables samples on the nitrites and nitrates determination by a spectrophotometric method.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material

The tested materials consist in samples of vegetal origin chosen from the one listed with MRL values as follows: Fresh spinach (*Spinacia oleracea*) (FSP) and preserved, frozen spinach (PSP); Fresh Lettuce (*Lactucasativa*) – green house cultivated during winter (FLGW) and summer (FLGS); Fresh Lettuce (*Lactucasativa*) – field cultivated during winter (FLFW) and summer (FLFS); Iceberg Lettuce – green house (ILG) and field cultivated (ILF); Rocket salad (*Erucasativa*) – cultivated during winter (RW) and summer (RS); Baby food in jar, BF1 contains potatoes and spinach and BF2 contains rice, vegetables and spinach.

The above-mentioned codes are used all along this paper. The samples were purchased from local shops in Oradea during September 2018 – July 2019 and the experiments were conducted in the food control laboratory of the Food Engineering Department, Environmental Protection faculty.

Methods

The determination of nitrites was performed using the Griess spectrophotometric method (Hura, 2006). Freshly dried sodium nitrite was the standard for 0.005 and 0.01 mg nitrite.

The nitrates concentration was determined indirectly after the reduction of nitrates to nitrites with cadmium and the redetermination of nitrites in the reduced extract.

Two experimental variants were applied:

1- Aqueous extracts: 10 g of homogenised sample were mixed in a 250 ml flask with 100 ml hot water and kept for 30 minutes at 80°C. Then, water was added to the mark and after cooling, a clear extract was obtained by centrifugation 5 minutes at 5000 rot/min.

2 - Deproteinized extracts: to the same amount of sample and water as for (1) variant 5 ml saturated borax solution was added and heated for 15 minutes at 80°C, stirring it from time to time. After cooling at room temperature 6ml of 10.6% potassium ferrocyanure solution and 6 ml 22% zinc acetate solution were added. After 20-30 minutes the clear extract was again obtained by centrifugation.

From the filtrate obtained through the two above mentioned procedures, 10 ml were added to 10 ml of Griess reagent, stirred and let to rest for at least 20 min, but no more than 4 hours, in the dark, at room temperature. The absorbance was measured with a Shimadzu Mini UV-VIS spectrophotometer at 520nm wavelength towards a blank solution of the reagents. Two determinations were performed for each sample or standard.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first step of the experiment was to obtain the foods aqueous and the deproteinized extracts, then nitrites and nitrates were calculated for both series of extracts as explain above.

The results, as means +/- Sd are presented in Table 1.

The experimental results reveal for all the tested samples higher values using the deproteinized extract than the aqueous one.

The differences between nitrites and nitrates content determined using the two different extracts are from 3.97% to 15.89% (nitrites) and from 3.76% to 17.46% (nitrates).

Statistical analysis (t-test) reveals not-significant differences; however, there is no predictability or relationship between the samples type and the extent of the differences.

Referring to the aqueous extracts of tested leafy vegetables, the lowest nitrites content (0.79 mg/kg) was found in FLGS sample and the highest (2.96 mg/kg) in FPS.

For nitrates, the lowest content (325.6 mg/kg) was found in FLGS sample and the highest (2177; 2018mg/kg) in rocket salad, regardless of the cultivation period. As for deproteinized extracts, the lowest nitrites content (0.094 mg/kg) was found again in FLGS sample and the highest (3.375 mg/kg) in FPS.

Regarding nitrates, the lowest content (371.6 mg/kg) was found in FLGS sample and the highest (2368; 2097.2mg/kg) in rocket salad, regardless of the cultivation period.

Those results comply with the ones reported by scientific studies. Avasilcăi, 2012 found for indoor green salad an average content of 0.69 mg/kg of nitrite and 138.1 mg/kg nitrates.

Outdoor cultivated salad shown higher values, 2.24 mg/kg for nitrites and 1363.8 mg/kg for nitrates. Kmecl et al., 2017, sensitising a 13 years study in Slovenia, found values of 0.28 mg/kg nitrites and for nitrates 962 mg/kg lettuce.

In Estonia, a study from 2006 (Tamme et al, 2006) found an average under 5 mg/kg and for nitrites 2508 mg/kg for spinach.

Table1

Nitrites and nitrates content, mg/kg					
Sample code		NO2	NO3	NO2	NO3
		Aqueous extracts		Deproteinized extracts	
FSP	Mean	2.960	1076.16	3.375	1859.16
	Sd	+/-0.204	+/-87.99	+/-0.280	+/-24.61
PSP	Mean	1.456	1739.08	1.634	1817.10
	Sd	+/-0.218	+/-35.25	+/-0.147	+/-72.45
FLGW	Mean	1.894	470.97	2.138	550.11
	Sd	+/-0.400	+/-39.35	+/-0.564	+/-8.74
FLGS	Mean	0.791	325.58	0.094	371.62
	Sd	+/-0.136	+/-11.65	+/-0.022	+/-10.89
FLFW	Mean	1.684	1445.94	1.904	1617.03
	Sd	+/-0.390	+/-124.50	+/-0.397	+/-82.08
FLFS	Mean	1.294	897.16	1.411	1086.78

	Sd	+/-0.058	+/-37.67	+/-0.0803	+/-113.14
ILG	Mean	1.180	942.64	1.403	997.17
	Sd	+/-0.024	+/-78.72	+/-0.016	+/-122.08
ILS	Mean	1.466	928.60	1.649	1062.10
	Sd	+/-0.064	+/-57.19	+/-0.044	+/-20.59
RW	Mean	1.354	2177.04	1.411	2368.05
	Sd	+/-0.167	+/-145.31	+/-0.157	+/-158.98
RS	Mean	1.321	2018.37	1.403	2097.18
	Sd	+/-0.227	+/-131.08	+/-0.025	+/-38.58
BF1	Mean	0.339	36.82	0.413	38.58
	Sd	+/-0.013	+/-1.20	+/-0.014	+/-1.68
BF2	Mean	0.478	31.70	0.541	36.05
	Sd	+/-0.013	+/-2.27	+/-0.066	+/-1.52

We did not compare baby foods to the tested leafy vegetables because they are mixed foods and the MRL value is at least 10 times lower than for leafy vegetables, as we are going to discuss further on.

In Europe, the studies regarding this item found for nitrates values between 61 mg/kg in Portugal (Rebello et al., 2015) and 88 mg/kg in Estonia (Tammi et al, 2006), so the samples analysed in the present study shown a lower contamination by nitrates.

The comparison of the tested samples with the MRL values of nitrates for each category of samples is presented in the graph from the Figure 1

.As we can see, all experimental values are beneath the maximum admitted, no matter the type of extract used in the experiment.

However the ones obtained from deproteinized extract are always higher and in one case for preserved spinach it is very close to the MRL representing 91%.

Fig.1 – The comparison of experimental nitrates content to MRL

CONCLUSION

The experimental results of the study reveal the fact that aqueous extracts can be used in order to determinate the nitrites and nitrates content of leafy vegetal origin food as well as for mixed vegetal origin baby foods in routine verifications. However if the registered values are near the MRL values, the deproteinized extract should be used in order to avoid any discrepancy with the legal requirements. However, if the determination is related to a control activity, concluded with a control act, the deproteinization of the samples is mandatory.

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PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF LIPOSOMES LOADED WITH POLYPHENOLS EXTRACTED FROM CALLENDULAE FLOS

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Abstract

Liposomes have been used since 1960 in various fields such as: chemistry, mathematics, physics, biophysics, and biology. Since then they are successfully available in modern technology as an active transport molecule at the site of action. They are spherical vesicles, made up of one, or more, bilateral phospholipid layers. Phospholipids are the main component of the cell membrane, containing a hydrophilic and a hydrophobic part.

They are most often used as carriers for a large number of molecules. The cosmetic, pharmaceutical, agriculture and food industries have studied the use of liposome encapsulation to streamline the transport and delivery of different systems that can trap unstable components (flavors, antimicrobial substances, antioxidants, and bioactive elements) and make them more functional.

Calendula officinalis L. is used all around the world in the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industry for its antioxidant, antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, and antiviral properties. For external use, it is useful for treating skin inflammations, scratches, wound healing and burns.

At present, liposomes are widely used in the medical field. They are considered the most suitable carriers for the introduction and transport to the target organ of various agents, for example anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antibiotic, hormonal, antifungal, enzymatic, vaccines (in the aqueous or lipid phases). The use of different liposomes dimensions and compositions is done to ensure adequate time of delivery.

Key words: Liposomes; phospholipids; wound healing; *Calendula officinalis* L.; burns

INTRODUCTION

Polyphenols are bioactive compounds that have beneficial effects, being used mainly in the health, cosmetic and food industries. After being extracted from medicinal plants, they have several disadvantages: low water solubility, low physico-chemical stability, which leads to reduced bioavailability, bitter and astringent taste. In the present study, we encapsulated polyphenols from *Calendula officinalis* L. flowers extract into nanostructured liposomal systems to improve their characteristics.

Liposomes are small, artificial, spherical vesicles that can be created from natural, non-toxic cholesterol and phospholipids (Akbarzadeh A. et al.,

2013). Due to their low toxicity, biocompatibility and ability to trap both lipophilic and hydrophilic substances, liposomes are seen as drug delivery systems. The structure, chemical composition and size of liposomes can be controlled by the preparation method (Ahmed K.S. et al., 2018).

When phospholipids are dispersed in aqueous solutions, they have a strong tendency to form membranes and this is due to the amphipathic nature (Papahadjopoulos D, Kimelberg H.K., 1974).

Liposomes can have single or double lipid membranes, and their size can range from very small vesicles (0.025 μm) to large vesicles (2.5 μm). Both the size and the number of bilateral layers influence the amount of drug that has been incorporated into liposomes.

Compared to the micrometer-size carriers that are obtained by traditional techniques, nanoparticles have the advantage of having a larger interfacial surface, increase solubility and improve bioavailability, taste, aroma of bioactive compounds and the active principle released in a controlled manner (Singh H., 2016; Bochicchio S. et al., 2016; (Putheti S., 2015). There are two categories of liposomes, classified according to the size of the vesicle and the double lipid layers: multilamellar vesicles (> 500 nm; MLV) or unilamellar (> 100nm; LUV), unilamellar ones can be found in 3 forms: small unilamellar vesicles (20 -100 nm called SUV), intermediate (100-250 nm), or large unilamellar vesicles (> 250 nm, called LUV) (Pattni B.S. et al., 2015); (Jesorka A., Orwar O., 2008; Makino K., Shibata A., 2006; Irache J.M. et al., 2001).

When choosing the method of liposome preparation, certain factors are taken into account: the physico-chemical characteristics of the components of the liposome and the drug to be loaded, the toxicity and concentration of the substance to be loaded, the environment in which the liposomes will be dispersed, the additional processes what will occur during liposome administration, the size and half-life that is desired to be achieved, the costs and the large scale applicability for the clinical purpose (Bozzuto G., Molinari A., 2015; Gomez-Hens A, Fernandez-Romero J.M, 2006; Mozafari M.R. et al., 2008; Dua J.S. et al., 2012; Cagdas M. et al., 2014).

Due to its simplicity and low costs, many laboratories use the method of obtaining liposomes by hydrating the lipid film, in which the lipid components are dissolved in an organic solvent (Bulbake U. et al., 2017). This involves drying a lipid solution, forming a thin film at the base of the round bottom flask and then hydrating the film with an aqueous buffer, shaking for a certain period of time. The components to be encapsulated will be added in an organic solvent or aqueous medium, choosing the method based on their solubility.

To evaluate the liposomes size distribution, various techniques are used such as: microscopy, size exclusion chromatography (SEC), field flow

fractionation or even static or dynamic light scattering (Nogueira E. et al., 2015). The most direct method for determining the size of the liposome is performed with the help of an electron microscope that offers the possibility of visualizing the liposomes individually (Ho R.J.J. et al., 1986).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Materials: The liposomes loaded with polyphenols from the *Calendula officinalis* L. flowers extract were prepared by the hydration method from phosphatidylcholine, dipalmitoyl phosphatidylcholine, cholesterol purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy). We used flowers of *Calendula officinalis* L. harvested from the Crişana region, Bihor County. The compounds used are of adequate purity, attested by analysis bulletins issued by the manufacturer.

Preparation of liposomes

When preparing liposomes with different tips of lipids, those one must first be dissolved and mixed in an organic solvent to assure a homogeneous mixture of lipids. Most times, this process is carried out using chloroform to obtain a clear lipid solution for complete mixing of lipids. Once the lipids are mixed in the chloroform, the solvent is removed to yield a lipid film. For larger volumes, the organic solvent should be removed by rotary evaporation until a thin lipid film is present on the sides of a round bottom flask. The lipid film is truly dried and without residual organic solvent by placing the flask on a vacuum pump. Spinning the round bottom flask in the warm water bath maintained at a temperature of 40°C, allows the lipid to hydrate in its fluid phase with adequate agitation.

Hydration of the dry lipid film is achieved by adding an aqueous medium to the container of dry lipid and then agitating. The application of the lipid vesicles is generally determined by the hydration medium which can include distilled water, buffer solutions, saline, and non-electrolytes such as sugar solutions. To develop liposome vesicular systems, we used flowers of *Calendula officinalis* L. The flowers were carefully selected as to obtain an alcoholic extract by maceration with 30% (v/v) alcohol, plant-to-solvent ratio 1:5.

The liposomes were prepared from phosphatidylcholine (50 mg), dipalmitoyl phosphatidylcholine (50 mg), cholesterol (2,5 mg). The method chosen for preparation was the thin-film. This method produces micrometric structures, with an ultrasound-assisted process developed to prepare nanometric structures. The desired size of liposomes, is determinate during the production process, decreasing due to addition of ultrasound energy,

used to break the lipid bilayer into small pieces that close themselves in spherical structures.

At first lipids were dissolved in organic solvent (2 ml of chloroform), after mixing, the solution was transferred to a rotary evaporation, at 40°C, 80 rpm and 200 mBars the solvents were removed and the solution was vacuum-dried. A yellow film was formed on the sides of a round bottom flask. The dried lipid film, was hydrated at room temperature with 2 ml solution of phosphate buffer (0,25 M, at pH 6,5), and then mixed in a centrifuge at 60°C, 200 rpm for 20 minutes. After that, the suspension was homogenized through an ultrasound-assist process (25°C, for 30 minutes) leading to the nanoliposome formation. We used the ultrasound-assist process in nanoliposomes production, because the energy is used to break the lipid bilayer into small pieces which closes themselves in spherical structures producing SUVs. Finally, the suspension was recovered and then characterized.

DLS (Dynamic Light Scattering) and ZP (zeta potential) measurements were carried out to determinate the physicochemical and morphological properties of the nanoparticles.

Another method for the size determination on liposomes is scanning electron microscope (SEM) which produces images of a sample by scanning the surface with a focused beam of electrons. SEM can achieve resolution better than 1 nanometer.

Also, we used Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM, LEO 435 VP) which allows the visualization of dynamic changes that occur to vesicle as physical environmental parameters are changed. The characteristics of Scanning Electron Microscope used: Vacuum 2.17e-005 mBar, Detector SE1, Beam current 250uA, I Probe 200pA, Filament I Target aprox 2.180 A, EHT Target 20kV, Enlarge 1.06 KX, Reference scale 20.00 kV.

The entrapment efficiency was determined immediately after preparation, after 24 hours, 1 week, 2 weeks, 30 days and 60 days. The Folin-Ciocalteu test using gallic acid as a standard was used for evaluation. A testing system of six Franz diffusion cells and the UV spectrophotometric method were used to determinate the release of the polyphenolic complex from the liposomal nanoparticles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The size and the polydispersity index of the liposomes was made at 25°C, and after ultrafiltration (Pellicon® 2 Cassette Ultrafiltration) we separated the particles with nanometric dimensions smaller than 500 nm (Fig.1.).

(a) (b)
 Fig.1. DLS analysis of liposomal systems:
 a) Particle size distribution; b) Zeta potential measurement

The obtained liposomal systems showed high entrapment efficiency of $81.02 \pm 0.42\%$ and stability at 25°C for at least 60 days. Several kinetic models (order zero, order I, Higuchi) were used to investigate the mechanism of in vitro release of polyphenols. All the entrapped polyphenols were released in 24 hours ($98.15 \pm 0.22\%$).

CONCLUSIONS

All the achieved positive results endorse the use of pharmaceutical applications for nanoliposomes loaded with *Calendula officinalis* flowers because the evaluation demonstrated good entrapment efficiency ($\sim 80\%$), small size (less than 500 nm), low polydispersity index and good stability after 60 days at 25°C , avoiding the use of toxic solvents and drastic conditions.

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STUDY ON NUTRITIONAL QUALITY OF SOME SMOKED PRODUCTS FROM SILVER CARP (*HYPOPHTHALMICHTHYS MOLITRIX*) AND BIGHEAD CARP (*HYPOPHTHALMICHTHYS NOBILIS*)

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Abstract

The study aimed an analysis of the nutritional characteristics of smoked products from silver carp (*Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*) and bighead carp (*Hypophthalmichthys nobilis*). Sixteen products were analyzed, eight samples of smoked silver carp (A products) and eight of bighead carp (B products).

The proteins, lipids, collagen and water content was determined using the automated analyzer Food Check (infrared spectrophotometer); mineral substances were determined by calcination at 550 °C and the carbohydrates content and energy value were determined by calculation, using conventional formulas.

The most important differences between the products analysed, have targeted the content of lipids, with difference of 2.48 percentage points (4.13% for B products and 1.65% for A products). The salt content was higher for B products (4.54%), compared with A products (3.40%), with differences of 1.14 percentage points.

The obtained data were statistically processed by classical methods and through the test for analysis of variance ANOVA. Mostly significant ($p < 0.05$), distinct significant ($p < 0.01$) and very significant differences ($p < 0.001$) were observed between the smoked fish products analysed at the level of chemical composition and energy value, with exception of proteins, ash and carbohydrates content where not significant differences were observed ($p > 0.05$).

Key words: smoked products, proteins, lipids, ash, salt.

INTRODUCTION

Carp is one of the most widely cultured and traded species all over the world due to its fast growth rate, easy cultivation, high feed efficiency ratio and high nutritional value (Shi et al., 2014, Lazar et al., 2012, Kachele et al., 2017). The species' of fish markedly affects the proximate composition and amino acid profile of their muscle tissue (Pyz-Lukasik and Paszkiewicz, 2018). Depending on the species, fish muscle tissue contains 12.2–21.79% proteins (Ozyurt and Polat, 2006; Tzikas, et al., 2007; Hadjinikolova et al, 2008; Usydus et al, 2011; Ghomi, 2012; Ljubojevic et al., 2013), 0.08–13.1% lipids and 67.3–86.7% water (Ozyurt and Polat, 2006; Usydus et al, 2011; Naseri et al 2010; Karl et al, 2014).

The energy value of the muscle tissue of different fish species, which depends on the proportion of its basic components, ranged from 210.7 to 797.5 kJ/100 g (Usydus et al, 2011; Skalecki et al, 2013).

Silver carp is one of the most commonly raised freshwater fish species throughout the world due to its wide availability, low cost of aquacultural production, high feed efficiency ratio and nutritional values (Valipour et al, 2017). It is well known to be rich in proteins, polyunsaturated fatty acids, lipidsoluble vitamins and micronutrients (Siddaiah, et al, 2001, Rezaei and Shahbazi, 2018).

Bighead carp culture was first initiated in the areas along Yangtze River and Pearl River in the southern part of China, much later than the culture of common carp. It can also be found in some wild environments of Europe, South America and North America (Shi et al., 2013).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Sixteen products were analyzed, eight samples of smoked Silver carp (A manufacturer/ products) and eight of bighead carp (B manufacturer/ products). The samples were chopped and homogenized with an electric shredder.

The water, proteins, collagen and lipids content were determined using the Food Check Near Infrared Spectrophotometer (NIRS technology); the energy value was determined by calculation using conventional formulas and crude ash content was assessed after AOAC, 1990, by calcinations (at 550°C for 18 h after a preliminary carbonization).

The energy conversion factors were: 4.27 for proteins, 9.02 for lipids and 3.87 for carbohydrates (according to Atwater system/ FAO relations, 2003). The achieved results were statistically processed through the main descriptors computation: arithmetic mean, $\bar{x}$, standard deviation, s , coefficient of variation, $V\%$, and by analysis of variance test (ANOVA)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The chemical composition and energy value of Silver carp *Hypophthalmichthys molitrix* (A) and Bighead carp *Hypophthalmichthys nobilis* (B) are presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

The most important differences between the products analysed, have targeted the content of lipids, with difference of 2.48 percentage points (4.13% for B products and 1.65% for A products).

The average proteins content was higher for A products (21.83%), compared with B products (20.91%), with differences of 0.92 percentage points. The collagen content was higher for A products (4.5%), compared with the B products (3.45%), with differences of 1.05 percentage points,

probably and because the total proteins content was higher for this products (Fig 1.).

The water content was higher for A products (70.47%) compared with B products (69.08%) with differences of 1.39 percentage points. Also, the dry matter and inclusively the organic matter were higher for B products compared with A products.

Table 1.
Chemical composition and energy value of Silver carp *Hypophthalmichthys molitrix* (A)

Chemical components and energy value	$\bar{X} \pm s\bar{x}$	V%	Min.	Max.
Lipids%	1.65± 3.16	9.96	1.40	1.90
Proteins%	21.83± 1.52	2.31	21.10	22.60
Collagen%	4.50± 1.69	2.85	3.32	4.72
Water%	70.47± 0.87	0.75	69.10	73.20
Salt%	3.40± 2.43	5.88	3.10	4.70
Ash%	5.47± 2.36	5.58	5.03	5.70
Dry matter%	29.53± 1.34	1.80	28.80	29.90
Organic matter%	24.07± 1.74	3.02	23.19	24.87
Carbohydrates %	0.58± 5.97	9.37	0.29	1.47
Energy kcal/100g	110.37± 1.66	2.76	101.58	137.44
Energy kJ /100g	461.80±2.34	2.76	445.94	478.83

V%=coefficient of variation.

The salt content was higher for B products (4.54%), compared with A products (3.40%), with differences of 1.14 percentage points. The ash content was very close for the tow products analysed, a little bit higher for products A (5.47%) compared with B products (5.41%). The carbohydrates content was also close for the tow products analysed, a little bit higher for A products (0.58%) compared with B products (0.48%).

Table 2.
Chemical composition and energy value of Bighead carp *Hypophthalmichthys nobilis* (B)

Chemical components and energy value	$\bar{X} \pm s\bar{x}$	V%	Min.	Max.
Lipids%	4.13± 4.28	4.76	1.49	6.98
Proteins%	20.91± 1.47	3.22	18.19	21.47
Collagen%	3.45± 1.23	1.15	1.55	3.69
Water%	69.08± 2.12	0.47	66.40	73.20
Salt%	4.54± 1.49	3.66	2.35	5.34
Ash%	5.41± 1.25	7.11	4.13	5.89
Dry matter%	30.62± 2.56	2.31	27.80	33.70
Organic matter%	25.22± 1.32	1.09	22.43	27.69
Carbohydrates %	0.47± 3.56	6.21	0.33	1.07
Energy kcal/100g	128.36± 3.15	4.12	105.79	154.59
Energy kJ /100g	537.05±1.17	1.98	466.91	591.07

V%=coefficient of variation.

The mean carbohydrates content was higher for products B (128.36 kcal/100 g) this having more lipids in composition compared with A product (110.37 kcal/100 g), differences of 17.99 kcal/100 g (Fig. 2).

Mostly significant ($p < 0.05$), distinct significant ($p < 0.01$) and very significant differences ($p < 0.001$) were observed between the smoked fish products analysed (Table 3), at the level of chemical composition and energy value, with exception of protein, ash and carbohydrates content where not significant differences were observed ($p > 0.05$).

Fig. 1. Chemical composition of A and B products

Fig. 2. The energy value of A and B products

Table 3

The statistical significance of the differences for Silver carp *Hypophthalmichthys molitrix* (A) and Bighead carp *Hypophthalmichthys nobilis* (B)

ANOVA		A-B
Lipids	S	***
	P value	5.5E-05
Proteins	S	ns
	P value	0.0522
Collagen	S	*
	P value	0.0174
Water	S	**
	P value	0.0085
Ash	S	ns
	P value	0.8887
Salt	S	**
	P value	0.0051
D.M.	S	*
	P value	0.0285
O.S.	S	*
	P value	0.0344
Carbohydrates	S	ns
	P value	0.24224
Energy kcal/100g	S	***
	P value	2.53E-15

n.s.(not significant)= $p > 0.05$; *(significant)= $0.05 > p > 0.01$; **(distinct significant)= $0.01 > p > 0.001$; ***(highly significant)= $0.001 > p$.

Pyz-Lukasik et al, 2018 found mean values of 73.56% water, 15.98% protein, 8.93% lipids, 1.10% ash and 144.27 kcal/100 g energy value in the fresh muscle tissue of bighead carp. Shi et al 2013 found similar value for juvenile bighead carp. In the smoked products, nutrients are more concentrated (and in the present study), because some of the water is removed in the cold/hot smoking process and salt is added in different concentrations. Thus, Shehata et al, 2018, found the following mean values of water, proteins, lipids, carbohydrates, ash and energy value: 78.11%, 16.55%, 2.31%, 1.16%, 1.87%, 91.63±1.49 kcal/100g for raw grass carp; while it was recorded 48.22%, 23.38%, 13.88%, 8.14%, 6.38%, 251.05 kcal/100g for hot smoked grass carp fillets with 10% salt. On the other hand, Vujkovic et al 1999, analysing the composition of fatty acids and total lipids in the fresh muscle tissue of silver carp and bighead carp, showed that there is no significant difference either in the content of polyunsaturated n-3 and n-6 fatty acids, or in the n-6/n-3 fatty acids ratio in these two fish species. The lipids of both the silver carp and bighead carp from the spring harvest have significantly higher contents of the n-3 fatty acids and a significantly lower n-6/n-3 ratio than fish from the autumn harvest.

CONCLUSIONS

The analyzes performed revealed the most important differences between the products A and B at the level of lipids content, with difference of 2.48 percentage points (4.13% for B products and 1.65% for A products). The salt content was higher for B products (4.54%), compared with A products (3.40%), with differences of 1.14 percentage points. Mostly significant ($p < 0.05$), distinct significant ($p < 0.01$) and very significant differences ($p < 0.001$) were observed between the smoked fish products analysed at the level of chemical composition and energy value, with exception of proteins, ash and carbohydrates content where not significant differences were observed ($p > 0.05$).

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COMPARISON BETWEEN THE MAXIMUM DEGREE OF INCORPORATION OF ESSENTIAL FATTY ACIDS IN THE SANE COMPARED TO FRESH TELEME CHEESE

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Abstract

In order to obtain functional dairy products, we tried to obtain acid dairy products and cheeses enriched in essential fatty acids. For this has been added in the sheep milk raw fish oil. The homogenization of the mixture was followed by the incorporation of the essential fatty acids from the fish oil into the milk fat globule. For manufacturing, it was chosen from the class of acid dairy products to obtain the sane and from the cheese class to obtain telemea cheese. The concentration of added fish oil in milk was .,05%; 0,10%; 0,15%. The classic manufacturing technology was used in the manufacturing regime.

The products were analyzed from a sensory point of view and after two days after the manufacture the disappearance of the taste and aroma of the fish was detected in all the samples. Three essential fatty acids that are present in both sheep's milk and fish oil were taken into consideration. In sane proportion, linoleic acid increased from 2,68% to 3,24%; of linolenic acid from 1% to 1,3% and γ -linolenic acid from 0,84% to 1,21%. In teleme cheese, the proportion of linoleic acid increased from 2,58% to 2,82%; of linolenic acid from 0,31% to 1,09% and γ -linolenic acid from 0,85% to 0,99%.

The maximum limit of incorporation of the three essential fatty acids was reached in the case of sane for linoleic acid was not reached, for linolenic acid at 0,6055 added fish oil and for γ -linolenic acid at 1,3200%. In the case of teleme cheese, the maximum incorporation limit was reached for the three essential fatty acids at the following concentrations of fish oil added to the raw material milk: for linoleic acid of 0,1600%, linolenic acid of one, 0,1716% and for acid γ -linolenic of 0,4668%.

Key words: lactation products, fish oil

INTRODUCTION

Milk and dairy products are indispensable foods for life. They contain all the components and in optimal proportions that favor the normal functioning of the human body.

Milk casein is a protein that enters the structure of the clot in cheese manufacture. β -casein is part of the casein case and has the beneficial effect of regulating metabolic and physiological processes together with serum proteins. It also improves immune balance compared to a food that contains only whey protein (N. Rafiee-Tari,2019).

The digestion of milk components takes place gradually in the gastrointestinal tract. Most of the protein decomposition in cheese (75%) occurs in the intestinal digestion phase. The release of fat from cheese occurs mostly in the gastric and intestinal digestion stages, and the fat globules have become more spherical after the gastric phase. Proteolysis was produced for the gastric and intestinal phases (Kristīne Žolnere, 2019).

Food preservation technology can be achieved by adding "positive" bacteria to inhibit the growth of unwanted microorganisms. The results suggest that bacteriocin production of *L. plantarum* and *L. casei* lactic bacteria is an effective conservation strategy (Jianpeng Li, 2019).

Phenylactic acid is a natural antibacterial compound resulting from the phenylalanine catabolism. It is metabolized with lactic acid and metabolized by glycolytic enzyme, lactate dehydrogenase, during fermentation. The addition of *Lactobacillus plantarum* improved the production of phenylactic acid by 1,7 times. *Lactobacillus brevis* and *Leuconostoc lactis* have determined an increase of about 1,5 times. These results suggested that the addition of specific lactic acid bacteria from starter cultures may increase the content of phenylactic acid and has the effect of increasing food preservability (Sera Jung, 2019).

Supplementing with fatty acids rich in oleic acid from the diet of dairy cows is a way to reduce the supply of saturated fatty acids from milk. This fact also improves the quality of dairy products (butter, cheese) which become creamier and are accepted by consumers. (Oonagh Markey, 2019).

Due to the use of oils rich in unsaturated fatty acids increase the whiteness of the product due to light reflection (Morna Anamaria, 2018).

Essential fatty acids play many important roles in human biology. Essential fatty acids ω -3 and ω -6 are the precursors of eicosanoids, hormones with local action that play a role in mediating inflammatory processes. Through the production of these eicosanoids, for the most part, essential fatty acids influence human health and disease. All studies have previously confirmed that there is a relationship between supplementation with essential fatty acids and improved dry eye effect. (Elana S, 2010).

The effect of a treatment effect of omega-3 fatty acids for depression in adults is beneficial. Further study of essential fatty acids as an independent and adjuvant therapy for adult depression is indicated, including a more sophisticated investigation of response to certain doses. (Anna-leila, 2006).

Recently, demonstrated shown that supplementation with ω -3 polyunsaturated fatty acids, obtained from fish oil (ω -3 LCPUFAs) during gestation reduces the risk of asthma in children, but the mechanisms involved are not known (Daniela Rago, 2019).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

To obtain the two dairy products for analysis, sheep milk collected in April was used. It has a lower fat and higher protein content. In order to enrich the dairy products in essential fatty acids, in the raw material milk, a fish fillet from cod liver was added. In order to include the fish oil inside the fat globules the milk mixture with fish oil was homogenized at 70 ° C and the pressure of 200 bar. The classic technological process was used to obtain the products. In order to avoid the oxidation of the essential fatty acids, the maturation of the cheese samples was accelerated by increasing the maturation temperature by approximately 2-3 ° C. In order to remove the oxidation of the essential fatty acids, the maturation of the cheese samples was accelerated by increasing the maturation temperature by approximately 2-3 °C.

The raw material milk was analyzed from a physico-chemical point of view. The acidity determination was performed by the titratable method and expressed in both °T and grams of lactic acid%. The fat percentage determination was performed by the acid-butyrometric method and the density determination by the areometric method. Also, the analysis of the physico-chemical parameters of the milk was carried out with the help of the lactostar apparatus, which also determines the percentage of protein, lactose, non-fat dry substance in milk, in addition to the usual parameters.

The analysis on technological flow was carried out by tracking the parameters of the process operations but also of the milk parameters, especially the evolution of the acidity of the samples. Finished products were analyzed from the sensory and physical-chemical point of view. Was followed in this particular flavor and aroma of the products are influenced by the addition of fish oil. The physico-chemical was determined, the dry matter by the drying method in the oven, the percentage of fat by the acid-butyrometric method, the percentage of salt by the Mohr method.

Chromatography analyzed 19 fatty acids from milk samples but also from dairy products obtained. It has focused on the analysis of the evolution of the three essential fatty acids that are specific to both sheep's milk and fish oil. The results of the analyzes were statistically validated using the comparison method between the samples and the control sample, Anova. The ROC (Receiver Operator Characteristic) curves were used to establish the maximum point of incorporation at the optimum percentage of fish oil added to the raw milk.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this work it was analyzed by embedding the essential fatty acids from fish oil added to the raw milk in the milk product acid, sane, compared to fresh teleme cheese. Fish oil was added in increasing percentages of 0,05%; 0,10%; 0,15%. The coding of the samples is presented in the table 1.

Table 1

No. cr.	Add fish oil %	Sample code		
		Milk raw material	Sane	Fresh teleme cheese
1	0	L ₀	S ₀	Tp ₀
2	0,05	L _{0,05}	S _{0,05}	Tp _{0,05}
3	0,10	L _{0,10}	S _{0,10}	Tp _{0,10}
4	0,15	L _{0,15}	S _{0,15}	Tp _{0,15}

The concentrations in essential fatty acids of milk samples and milk products are shown in table 2.

Table 2

No. cr.	Sample	Concentration in essential fatty acids of samples		
		linoleic acid	linolenic acid	γ -linolenic acid
1	L ₀	2,55	0,97	0,92
2	L _{0,05}	2,68	1,00	0,84
3	L _{0,10}	2,75	1,06	0,96
4	L _{0,15}	3,01	1,10	0,96
5	S ₀	2,68	1	0,84
6	S _{0,05}	2,79	1,12	0,95
7	S _{0,10}	2,9	1,25	1,04
8	S _{0,15}	3,24	1,3	1,21
9	Tp ₀	2,58	0,31	0,85
10	Tp _{0,05}	2,87	1,24	0,95
11	Tp _{0,10}	2,80	0,84	1,07
12	Tp _{0,15}	2,82	1,09	0,99

As can be seen from table 2, with the addition of fish oil, the concentration of essential fatty acids in both the sane and the fresh teleme cheese increases. Figure 1 shows the evolution of the essential fatty acids in the samples of raw material milk, those of sane and fresh teleme cheese. In general, there is a marked increase in the health samples compared to the cheese samples.

Fig. 1. Variation of essential fatty acids in milk and dairy products

From the statistical analysis the maximum limit of incorporation results, taking into account the three fatty acids analyzed. As shown in Table 3, the concentration in fish oil corresponding to the maximum incorporation limit is within the established fish oil concentrations (0,905%; 0,10%; 0,15%).

Table 3

Concentration in fish oil of raw material milk at the theoretical threshold of incorporation of essential fatty acids

	Concentration in fish oil of raw material milk at the theoretical threshold of incorporation of essential fatty acids		
	linoleic acid	linolenic acid	γ -Linolenic acid
Fresh teleme cheese	0,1600	0,1716	0,4668
Sane	-	0.6505	1.3200

CONCLUSIONS

The addition of fish oil in the raw material milk used in the manufacture of sane and fresh teleme cheese has the effect of enriching them in essential fatty acids. There is, for all that, a limit to the incorporation of fish oil into the milk fat globule. This shows that enrichment in essential fatty acids is more effective in the case of sane compared to the fresh telemea cheese.

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RESEARCH ON THE PERFORMANCE, STABILITY AND ROBUSTNESS OF THE AUTOMETED SYSTEM, TO THE FOOD EQUIPMENT WICH CAN BE USED GEOTHERMAL WETER AS A HEETING AGENT

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Abstract

The autometion of industrial processes in the food industry involves ensuring optimum opereting regimes for them after a pre-established schedule. Autometion ensures the management of hard-to-reach processes that evolve in challenging environments, or processes with a high risk factor; The problem of the synthesis of management systems based on the use of the PID controller pursues essentially a leading purpose expressed by the requirement that the quality size pursue a specified character reference size in the context Disturbance. This is achieved by drawing up a decision on the proper evolution of the order size, the elaboretion resulting from the processing of the measured informetion and possibly, where possible, the disturbance; The controlled process must be known to be able to predict how it will respond to different input signals and disturbances affecting it. This is achieved by aggretegreting the entire knowledge of the process into a model of its own. The process identificetion phase is essential to be able to design a performance control algorithm; The performance indicetors proposed to the adjustment system must be specified in the terms of concise methemetical formulas involving the system directly variable. Et the food industry machines, trying to introduce geothermal weter as a warming agent, the analysis of the performance, stability and robustof the PID controller is particularly important.

Key words: geothermal wheter, food machinary, PID controller with two degrees of freedom.

INTRODUCTION

The controller With two degrees of freedom shown in Figure 1, It is used in food industry machines, which can use geothermal water as heating agent and shall consist of a comparetor and the K-type clearing. Block G on the direct peth shapes the execution element and the autometed process. (A. Bara 2001, C. Pantea et all 2010, H. Silaghi et all 2009 The transducer is represented by the H block. The transfer function of a PID K-type clearing has the following general form:

$$K(s) = \frac{U(s)}{E(s)} = Kc \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_i s} + T_d s + q \frac{T_d}{T_i} \right) \quad (1.)$$

PID algorithm with zero influence factor $q = 0$, named ideal, is the preferred. (C. Popescu et all, 2001, Borangiu Th et all 1986, Carmen Jover et all 2006

Figure 1. Standard adjusting loop

The shape of the algorithm, called the parallel PID algorithm, is preferred by some companies because it is linear in parameters K_p , K_i , K_d . (Crispin Allen 1990, E.F. Zanoelo et al, 2008, Dionissios P. Margaris et al, 2006). In this case, the proportional action (amplification) K_p , full action (automatic restoration) K_i/s and $K_d s$ derivative action are clearly highlighted..

$$\text{Parallel PID: } K(s) = k_p + \frac{k_i}{s} + k_d s \quad (2.)$$

The PID Series algorithm (interactive) corresponds to the value of $q = 1$ of the influence factor and is obtained after several simple transformations in the general relationship:

$$\text{PID serie: } K(s) = k_c \left(1 + \frac{1}{T_i s} \right) \cdot (T_d s + 1) \quad (3.)$$

PID compensators are easily transformed into P compensates if $T_d = 0$ and $T_i = \infty$, in compensating PI if $T_d = 0$, or the PD offset if $T_i = \infty$. The ideal PID compensators differ from those series only if all three actions P, I and D are present. (A. Bara 2001, C. Pantea et al 2010, H. Silaghi et al 2009)

The response of the PI compensator to a unit step error is $U = K_c (1 + t/T_i)$. When the proportional effect of the algorithm repeats (doubles). This is why you are measured in seconds/iteration. A ramp error causes the $U = K_c (t + T_d)$ response of the PD compensator. If the proportional effect of the algorithm doubles and in this way can be determined the constant derivative time. (Astrom K.J et al, 1984, J. W. Tester et al 2006, Setel Aurel et al 2010)

In the technical documentetion or manuals The PID algorithm is usually presented in one of the ideal forms, parallel or series. (Astrom K. J 2002, Burkhard Sanner 2006, F. S. Blaga 2009, Dionissios P et al 2006, C.

Volosencu 1997) However, the actual algorithm used by the controller et the helm of the process is different because the Tds term, corresponding to the derivate action, thet appears in the PID compensator transfer function is not physically achievable.

Analogue trade controllers use, for this reason, the approximete:

$$T_{ds} = \frac{T_d s}{\alpha T_d s + 1} \quad (4.)$$

Modern, numerically implemented controllers have the block diagram shown in Figure 1. (Iancu Carmen 2010, Iancu Carmen 2010, K. Leiviskä et all, 2005) The K-error compensator is full-type I and has the transfer function:

$$Ks = \frac{Kc}{T_i s} = \frac{k_i}{s} \quad (5.)$$

D block including derivate action is PD type with transfer function:

$$D(s) = Kc \left(1 + \frac{T_d s}{\alpha T_d s + 1} \right) \quad (6.)$$

In the expression of the Td transfer function is the constant of the derivate time. The value of α is between 0.1 and 1. (Astrom K.J et all, 1984, J. W. Tester et all 2006, Setel Aurel et all 2010, Angel Vidal et all, 2010)

The transfer function of the F prefilter in Figure 1. It is for the PID controller, as a rule, of the form:

$$F(s) = bT_i s + 1 + c \frac{T_d T_i s^2}{\alpha T_d T_i s + 1} \quad (7.)$$

or its numerical equivalent obtained by approximating s.

METERIAL AND METHOD

The proposed design method is based on the sensitivity functions S (s) and T (s). The Hu (s) transfer function of the autometric system in Figure 1. Follow-up is given by the following relationship if the ideal transducer H = 1 is considered.

$$H_u s = \frac{Y(s)}{R(s)} = \frac{K(s)G(s)}{1 + K(s)G(s)} \quad (8.)$$

The function S (s) of auto sensitivity function shows how much the Hu (s) tracking function changes when the autometric system transfer function G (s) changes slightly with dG (s).

$$S(s) = \frac{\frac{dH_u(s)}{H_u(s)}}{\frac{dG(s)}{G(s)}} = \frac{dH_u}{dG} \frac{G}{H_u} \quad (9.)$$

From previous relationships results from the derivation of the sensitivity function S (s).

$$S(s) = \frac{1}{1 + K(s)G(s)} = \frac{1}{1 + L(s)} \quad (10.)$$

In which L (s) = K (s) G (s) is the open-loop transfer function.

In addition to the sensitivity function S (s) is also defined as the complementary sensitivity function T (s) of the automatic system and the standard adjusting loop using the:

$$T(s) = \frac{K(s)G(s)}{1 + K(s)G(s)} = \frac{L(s)}{1 + L(s)} \quad (11.)$$

In which L (s) = K (s) G (s) is the open loop transfer function. From the relationship it is noted that for the ideal transducers that have H (s) = 1 The complementary sensitivity function T (s) is identical to the transfer function (7) of the automatic system.

Between the two sensitivities the relationship are:

$$S(s) + T(s) = 1 \quad (12.)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using the S (s) and T (s) functions can evaluate the performance of the system automatically by determining the output, error, and order of the block in Figure 1.

$$Y(s) = T(s)R(s) + S(s)P(s) - T(s)N(s) \quad (13.)$$

$$E(s) = R(s) - Y(s) - N(s) = S(s)[R(s) - P(s) - N(s)] \quad (14.)$$

$$\begin{aligned} U(s) &= K(s)E(s) = K(s)S(s)[R(s) - P(s) - N(s)] = \\ &= \frac{T(s)}{G(s)} [R(s) - P(s) - N(s)] \end{aligned} \quad (15.)$$

Considering previous relationships, different performances can be taken into account regarding the operation of R-reference and attenuation of P disturbances, measurement noise N, modelling deficiencies and saturation of the element of Run. The standard performance indicators refer to the second order system with the following sensitivity functions:

$$T(s) = \frac{\omega_0^2}{s^2 + 2\zeta\omega_0s + \omega_0^2} \quad (16.)$$

$$S(s) = 1 - T(s) = \frac{s(s + 2\zeta\omega_0)}{s^2 + 2\zeta\omega_0 s + \omega_0} \quad (17.)$$

When designing the controller, a certain stability is required provided that the hodograph of the Open loop transfer function $L(j\omega) = K(j\omega)G(j\omega)$ pass through certain points determined by P_m , G_m and M_s . If the process is known and it is necessary that the hodograph of $L(j\omega)$ for an PI controller to pass through a point in the Nyquist diagram determined by the amplification edge or phase mode, the $U + jV$ coordinates are obtained:

$$L(j\omega) = K(j\omega)G(j\omega) = \left(K - j \frac{K_i}{\omega} \right) (a(\omega) + jb(\omega)) = u + jv \quad (18.)$$

From this relationship you can determine the parameters of the PI controller according to the process and the coordinates of the point in the Nyquist chart plan.

$$K = \frac{a(\omega)u + b(\omega)v}{a^2(\omega) + b^2(\omega)} \quad (19.)$$

$$K_i = \frac{[a(\omega)v - b(\omega)u]\omega}{a^2(\omega) + b^2(\omega)} \quad (20.)$$

CONCLUSIONS

All points within a range delimited by a curve satisfy the stability condition corresponding to the P_m , G_m or M_s point.

Figure2. The robustness of stability in the Nyquist plan

A point that is found on both curves corresponds to an open loop $L(j\omega)$ transfer function that passes through both P_m and G_m points. Point A has coordinates $(K_c, k_i = K_c/T_i)$ that determine the PI controller. The TD

constant of the PID controller is determined with the relationship $T_d = 0, 25T_i$. For different values of Ω , an automatically drawn curve [13] in the $K_c, K_i = K_c/T_i$ plan is derived.

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STUDY OF ABERDEEN ANGUS POPULATION TAKEN INTO THE OFFICIAL CONTROL OF MEAT PRODUCTION FROM S.C. COSMI VAS IMPEX S.R.L., FOR IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract

The development of the Aberdeen Angus breed in Romania began in 1999 following an exchange of experience between Romanian specialists, Dr. Popescu Alexandru, Dr. Pachițanu Vasile and Dr. Buzdugan Lucian, who participated in documentation visits to universities, breeding farms and fattening, frozen semen production centers and slaughterhouses in the United States at the invitation of specialists from the State Department of Agriculture.

The paper aims to analyze the main breeding indicators and the production performance of the Aberdeen Angus breed of cattle included in the Official Meat Production Control operated on the S.C. farm. Cosmi - Vas Impex S.R.L and comparing the results obtained with those of the specialized literature, in order to improve it.

The reproduction indicators studied were: the calving interval (Calving interval), the age at first calving and the interval in days from parturition until the first artificial sowing or fecundation (Service period) for 2017 and 2018.

The production performances studied have been: birth weight, average daily gain corrected at 200 days and 365 days for 2017 and 2018.

The obtained results showed values that are included in the specialized literature, therefore, the birth weight for 2017 was 32.25 ± 0.30 kg, the average daily gain being 781.62 ± 31.58 g / day at the age of 200 days and 812.62 ± 35.28 g / day to that of 300 days.

Key words: Aberdeen Angus, birth weight, calving interval.

INTRODUCTION

Raising beef is a viable alternative to the dairy cow, due to the shortage of beef in the European Union, the increase in the price of meat, the large areas of unused grassland at national level and the low maintenance costs.

In the context of a meat shortage in the European Union, the increase of production can not only be based on the increase of the exploited herds,

but it must be based on the modification of the genetic potential of the bovine populations and the improvement of the production characters, together with the improvement of the operating conditions, so that to obtain superior productions, both quantitatively and qualitatively, that meet the needs of consumers (Bishop MD et al., 1994, Schlee P., et al., 1994b).

The development of the Aberdeen Angus breed in Romania began in 1999 following an exchange of experience between Romanian specialists, Dr. Popescu Alexandru, Dr. Pachitanu Vasile and Dr. Buzdugan Lucian, who participated in documentation visits to universities, breeding farms and fattening, frozen semen production centers and slaughterhouses in the United States at the invitation of specialists from the State Department of Agriculture (Veleac C., 1999).

The first massive importation from Germany of Aberdeen Angus bulls took place in 2008, in Sibiu county, where Samuel Widmer and Stefan Jung laid the foundations of the Karpaten Meat farm by modernizing the premises of a zootechnical complex from the post-December period.

The ever-increasing demands for beef coupled with lower milk prices and the introduction of milk quota have prompted farmers in Romania to reorient to the Aberdeen Angus breed due to the remarkable adaptability to the pedoclimatic conditions of our country, the low maintenance costs, very good recovery. and forage, the slaughtering efficiency of over 65%, the achievement of spores of between 1000 and 1450 g / day and the obtaining of meat having special organoleptic qualities (Vasconcellos, L. P. de M. K . et. al., 2003)

The import of biological material and the establishment of pure-bred farms as well as the acquisition of artisans through the use of artificial seeding and semen from internationally valuable bulls have led to the increase of the national herds and the need to organize the control of the performances that represent the basis. the program to improve the exploited herds.

The Aberdeen Angus breed is native to the counties of Aberdeen and Angus in northeast Scotland and was formed by breeding local bulls and infusing it with other breeds: Galloway, Ayrshire, Guernsey and Shorthorn. The founders and breeders of the breed are considered H. Watson and William Mc. Combines that at the end of the XVIII century by the contribution of numerous breeders consolidate and improve the breed (Velea C., 2012).

In this paper, we proposed to analyze the main breeding indicators and the production performance of the Aberdeen Angus breed cattle included in the Official Meat Production Control operated on the S.C. Cosmi - Vas Impex S.R.L farm and comparing the results obtained with those of the specialized literature, in order to improve it.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The biological material analyzed was represented by the Aberdeen Angus, Fleckvieh, German Bălțată, Bălțată with Romanian black, Brună and Pinzgau breeds and mixed with Aberdeen Angus (tab. 1).

Comparing the data from 2017 and 2018, it is observed that the number of males category 0-6 months remains constant, 6-12 months and 12-18 months register a decrease of 1, respectively 2 heads, 18-24 months and bulls register an increase of 1, respectively 5 heads. In total, the number of people increased in 2018 by 9 heads.

Table 1

The breed structure of the herd, 2017-2018

Year	Breed							Half breed	Total
	AA	FV	BG	BR	BNR	BS	PZ		
2017	210	13		2		4		49	278
2018	247	10	1	2	2	4	2	54	322

The female herd category 0-6 months and 12-18 months registered a decrease of 2 heads in 2018, and the 6-12 months and the cows category registered an increase of 4, 33 heads respectively. Overall, the female population registered an increase of 35 heads in 2018 (tab. 2).

Table 2

Age structure of the head, 2017 - 2018

Year	Sex	Vârsta						Total
		0-6 months	6-12 months	12-18 months	18-24 months	Cows	Bulls	
2017	♀	12	52	13	25		2	104
	♂	11	35	10	26	92		174
2018	♀	12	51	11	32		7	113
	♂	9	36	9	30	125		209

The main breeding indicators and the production performance of the cattle studied were: calving interval (calving interval), age at first calving and days between parturition and until the first artificial sowing or fecundation (Service period), weight at birth, the average daily gain corrected to 200 days and 365 days for 2017 and 2018.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Regarding the average weight at birth in 2017 for the whole lot studied, it was 32.25 ± 0.30 kg, the absolute values ranging from 27 to 39 kg.

From this point of view, the population is very homogeneous, the coefficient of variation V% having the value of 7.56%.

Comparing the results obtained for the group of females and males, one can observe their homogeneity, the differences between the average weight at birth being insignificant.

Depending on the sex of the product it is observed that the smallest and the highest weight are registered in the lot of females, 27 respectively 39 kg.

The data obtained regarding the birth weight are comparable to the data in the specialized literature which indicates an average birth weight of 30-35 kg. (tab. 3).

Table 3

Estimators for birth weight (Kg), 2017 - 2018

Anul	Sex	n	$\bar{X} \pm s\bar{x}$	V%	Limita (kg)	
					Min	Max
2017	♀	37	32,43±0,36	6,84	29	37
	♂	28	32,00±0,51	8,51	27	39
	Total	65	32,25±0,30	7,56	27	39
2018	♀	42	30,17±0,36	5,56	26	40
	♂	38	30,05±0,38	6,18	24	35
	Total	80	30,11±0,26	2,91	24	40

In 2018, the average birth weight for the entire studied group was 30.11 ± 0.26 kg, the absolute values ranging from 24 to 40 kg.

The coefficient of variation V% has a value of 2.91% and from this point of view the population is very homogeneous.

The data obtained regarding the birth weight are comparable to the data in the specialized literature which indicates an average birth weight of 30-35 kg (tab. 3).

Comparing the results for 2017 and 2018, it can be seen that in 2017, the average birth weight is higher compared to 2018, but the lot is more homogeneous in 2018, the coefficient of variation V% being 2.91%. In

2017, the minimum weight registered was 3 kg higher than in 2018 and the maximum weight with 1 kg less (tab. 3).

Regarding the average daily increase, it is observed that in 2017 at the age of 200 days for the whole studied group the average was 781.62 ± 31.58 g / day, the absolute values ranging between 464 and 1185 g / day. From this point of view, the population is very heterogeneous, the coefficient of variation V% having the value of 22.86%.

Comparing the results obtained for the group of females and males, we can observe their heterogeneity, the coefficient of variation being 18.02% for females and 21.31% for males, the average daily increase of the group of females 867.19 ± 36.87 g / day being superior to the group of males that recorded an average of 670.30 ± 38.17 g / day.

These results are in contradiction with the values in the literature, knowing that males have higher daily average increases than females.

These results can be explained by the fact that the weighed batches were different in terms of age and date when the weaning occurred.

Depending on the sex of the product it can be observed that the smallest daily average increase is recorded in the male group 464 g / day and the highest increase in the female group 1185 g / day.

The data obtained regarding the average daily increase are not comparable with the data in the specialized literature which indicate a daily average increase between 1000-1450 g / day (tab. 4).

Table 4

Estimators for the average daily gain corrected at the reference age 200 days (g / day),
2017-2018

Year	Sex	n	$\bar{X} \pm s\bar{x}$	V%	Limit (g/zi)	
					Min	Max
2017	♀	14	670,30±38,17	21,31	464	914
	♂	18	868,19±36,87	18,02	615	1185
	Total	32	781,62±31,58	22,86	464	1185
2018	♀	18	837,37±73,28	37,13	371	1465
	♂	9	763,12±31,45	31,45	449	1248
	Total	27	812,62±35,28	35,28	371	1465

In 2018, the average daily increase corrected for the entire studied group was 812.62 ± 0.26 g / day, the absolute values ranging from 371 to 1465g / day. The coefficient of variation V% has a value of 35.28% and

from these points of view the population is very heterogeneous. And in 2018, the average daily increase is lower than the one mentioned in the literature.

Comparing the results for 2017 and 2018, we can see an increase in the average daily increase in 2018 (tab. 4.).

Also in 2018 the average daily increase at 365 days for the whole studied group was 902.51 ± 17.62 g / day, the absolute values ranging from 779 to 991 g / day.

The value of the coefficient of variation 7.31% indicates that the studied lot is very homogeneous. Depending on the sex of the product it is observed that the smallest and the highest daily average increase is recorded in the male group 886 g / day, respectively 991 g / day.

The average daily gain recorded by the weighed lot is lower than the average daily gain mentioned in the literature (tab. 5).

Table 5

Estimators for the average daily gain at the reference age 365 days 2018

Year	Sex	n	$\bar{X} \pm s\bar{X}$	V%	Limit (g/day)	
					Min	Max
2018	♀	7	945,47±13,20	3,69	886	991
	♂	7	859,55±23,60	7,26	779	953
	Total	14	902,51±17,62	7,31	779	991

The average age at first childbirth in 2017 is 24.57 ± 0.23 months, the absolute values ranging from 23 to 26 months, the studied population being very homogeneous $V\% = 3.47$ (tab. 6).

Table 6

Estimatorii pentru vârsta la prima fătare 2017 și 2018

Year	n	$\bar{X} \pm s\bar{X}$	V%	Limit (mounth)	
				Min	Max
2017	14	24,57±0,23	3,47	23	26
2018	34	23,47±0,30	7,36	21	29

The average age at first birth in 2018 is 23.47 ± 0.30 months, with absolute values ranging from 21 to 29 months. And in this case, the herd is very homogeneous $V\% = 7.36$.

The results obtained are comparable with those of the specialized literature, the age at first calving being considered between 23-26 months and the optimal interval for introduction to reproduction 14-17 months or the minimum weight of 350 kg.

Calving interval (CI) represents the interval between two consecutive calves. It is observed that in 2017, the interval between two successive calves was 365 ± 6 days, the absolute values ranging between 306 and 498 days, the coefficient of variation $V\% = 11.42$ indicates that the studied population is heterogeneous.

In 2018, the interval between two successive calves was 398 ± 5 days, the absolute values ranging from 308 to 466 days. From this point of view, the population was very homogeneous, the coefficient of variation being $V\% = 9.21$. At the same time, there is an increase in the interval between two successive calves in 2018.

Comparing the data from the specialized literature that indicates an optimal range of 360 - 380 days, it turns out that in 2017 the value falls within the optimal limit, while in the year 2018 increase of this interval can be an indicator of reproductive function disorders, low feeding level or maintenance conditions (tab. 7).

Table 7

Estimatorii pentru caracterul Calving interval 2017 și 2018

Year	n	$\bar{X} \pm s\bar{x}$	V%	Limit (days)	
				Min	Max
2017	53	365 ± 6	11,42	306	498
2018	49	398 ± 5	9.21	308	466

The service period (SP) represents for multiparous, the interval in days from parturition and until the first mount or fertile sowing and for primiparous, the time interval from birth to first calving.

This indicator is important for the management of the farm and the breeding activity indicating how the cows were kept during the advanced gestation period and in the post-breeding period and the breeding youth.

The optimal period of service in cows is 45-90 days and is an important period, in which the animal recovers after parturition and the uterine involution takes place.

Following the statistical processing of the data, for the population studied in 2017, a Service period of 67 ± 6 days was obtained, and a value of the coefficient of variation of 58.12, which indicates a very heterogeneous population. In 2018, the Service period for the studied

population was 109 ± 5 days, with absolute values ranging from 21 to 168 days. The population is also very heterogeneous (tab. 8).

Table 8

Estimators for Service period 2017 și 2018

Year	n	$\bar{X} \pm s\bar{x}$	V%	Limita (zile)	
				Min	Max
2017	46	67±6	58,12	21	210
2018	44	109±5	32.04	21	168

Considering that the optimal value of the service period mentioned in the specialized literature is between 45-90 days, the data obtained in 2018 indicate possible disorders of the reproductive function or are due to the body's exhaustion after calving.

CONCLUSIONS

Following the study of the Aberdeen Angus cattle herd from the S.C. farm Cosmi Vas Impex S.R.L., the following conclusions can be drawn:

➤ for the birth weight character, the average obtained for 2017 and 2018, of 32.25 ± 0.30 kg, respectively 30.11 ± 0.26 kg, falls within the limits mentioned in the specialized literature, 30-35 kg;

➤ for the character of daily average increase, the average obtained both at the reference age 200 days for the year 2017 and 2018, 781.62 ± 31.58 g / day and 812.62 ± 35.28 g / day, respectively at 300 days for the year 2018, 902.51 ± 17.62 g / day, are below the average mentioned in the literature, 1000-1450 g / day;

➤ for the character of age at first calving, the average obtained in 2017 and 2018, 24.57 ± 0.23 months and 23.47 ± 0.30 months, fall within the limits mentioned in the specialized literature, 23-26 months;

➤ for the Calving interval character, the average obtained in 2017, 365 ± 6 days, falls within the limits mentioned in the specialized literature, 360-380 days. In 2018, the average increases to 398 ± 5 days, indicating the appearance of dysfunctions in the way of animal maintenance;

➤ for the character of Service period, the average obtained in 2017, of 67 ± 6 days, falls within the limits mentioned in the specialized literature, 45-90 days. In 2018, the average increases to 109 ± 5 days, indicating the appearance of dysfunctions in the way of animal maintenance.

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ANALYSIS OF THE RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF KETCHUP ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT HYDROCOLLOIDS AND TEMPERATURE

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Abstract

The present paper presents the analysis of the effect of temperature on the rheological properties of house made ketchup with different content of thickening agents. The viscosity data showed that all the samples under examination were non-Newtonian fluids, which was indicative by the pseudo-plastic (shear thinning) nature of tomato ketchup.

The results of this study showed that ketchup supplemented with hydrocolloids (xanthan, guar, CMC) behaves as a non-Newtonian thinning liquid, in the temperature range of 30-60°C. Increased gum concentration increased the apparent viscosity compared to control; however, the effect of xanthan gum on viscosity was greater than that of guar and CMC gums.

Key words: Ketchup, rheology, temperature, hydrocolloids

INTRODUCTION

Tomato is one of the most important vegetable products mainly marketed in a processed form i.e. pastes, concentrates or ketchup (Mazaheri Tehrani and Ghandi, 2007). Ketchup is a vegetable sauce produced from tomato concentrate and sugar, vinegar, salt, and different spices. Poland is the third largest market of consumption of ketchup in Europe, after Germany and Great Britain (Ochmańska, 2006).

Ketchup is a descriptive term for a number of different products, which consist of various pulps, strained and seasoned fruits; the variety made from tomatoes being the most popular condiment. Tomato ketchup is a heterogeneous, spiced product, produced basically from either cold or hot extracted tomatoes; or directly from concentrates, purees or tomato paste (Sahin and Ozdemir, 2004).

Knowledge of the rheological properties of fluid and semisolid foodstuffs is important in the design of flow processes in the quality control, storage and the processing stability, and in understanding and designing texture (Vercet et al., 2002; Mazaheri Tehrani and Ghandi, 2007, Hilma E., 2018). Viscosity of the continuous phase is mostly affected by thickening substances, especially polysaccharide hydrocolloids used to produce a ketchup (Gujral et al. 2002; Sahin and Özdemir 2004; Koocheki et al. 2009).

Ketchup is non-Newtonian, shear-thinning fluid, with yield stress. It also shows thixotropy and viscoelastic properties (Bottliglieri et al. 1991; Varela et al. 2003; Sahin and Özdemir 2004; Sharoba et al. 2005; Koocheki et al. 2009). The viscosity of tomato ketchup is a major quality component for consumer acceptance.

Usually viscosity is considered an important physical property related to the quality of food products. Therefore, reliable and accurate rheological data are necessary for designing and optimization of various food processing equipment such as pumps, piping, heat exchangers, evaporators, sterilisers, filters and mixers (Crandall and Nelson, 1975; Tanglertpaibul & Rao, 1987; Stoforos & Reid, 1992; Vercet et al., 2002).

Rheological properties of ketchup depend not only on the amount of tomato paste used and its rheological characteristics but also on the kind and amount of added thickening substances. Hydrocolloids are water-soluble, high molecular weight polysaccharides that serve a variety of functions in food systems including enhancing viscosity, creating gel-structures, film formation, control of crystallization, inhibition of syneresis, improving texture, encapsulation of flavours and lengthening the physical stability (Dziezak, 1991; Glicksman, 1991; Garti and Reichman, 1993; Dickinson, 2003). Generally, gums and stabilisers have non-Newtonian rheology and they impart non-Newtonian character to the emulsions even when the amount of the dispersed phase is low (Ford et al., 1997). For consumers' acceptability, the long-term stability of sauces is also very important. Thus, hydrocolloids are widely used in the food industry.

The most often used thickening agents are polysaccharide hydrocolloids such as: guar gum, xanthan, tragacanth, pectins, and sodium alginate (Gujral et al. 2002; Varela et al. 2003; Sahin and Özdemir 2007; Koocheki et al. 2009). These substances essentially improve sensory and rheological properties of ketchup. Guar and xanthan gums and their mixtures are found to be the most successful in decreasing serum separation of tomato ketchups (Varela et al. 2003; Sahin and Özdemir 2007).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The present paper presents the analysis of the effect of temperature on the rheological properties of house ketchup with different content of thickening agents. The objectives I have pursued in this paper were: to establish the influence of the thickening agent on the viscosity; analysis of the ketchup viscosity variation as a function of temperature; analyzing the variation of ketchup density as a function of temperature; pH determination; ketchup stability analysis. The vegetable material used was the ketchup made in the house.

The ingredients used for the preparation of homemade ketchup can be found in table 1.

Table 1

Ingredients used to make homemade ketchup

Raw materials	MU	Raw quantity
Tomatoes	g	1000
Sugar	g	75
Salt	g	10
Vinnegar	ml	25
Onion	g	50
Garlic	g	5
Cinnamon	g	5
Black pepper	g	0.15
Sodium benzoate	g	0.25
Hydrocolloids ¹	g	

Healthy and ripe tomatoes were purchased from the local market, sorted by color, size and lacking in bruises/green spots. The tomato pulp was placed in a laboratory vessel. The spices (cinnamon, black pepper) were wrapped in a cloth and dipped in tomato paste. The onion and garlic were added directly over the tomato pulp.

The mixture was then heated to a moderate temperature and stirred constantly until it reached a temperature of between 75°C and 80°C, at which time vinegar and salt were added. Finally, sodium benzoate was added as a preservative. Hydrocolloids were then added to each 100 g of ketchup at different levels and stirred for 2 minutes. The final level of each hydrocolloid by weight in the ketchup samples was 0.5%, 0.75% and 1%. Each sample was immediately poured into glass containers and then stored at ambient temperature (20°C - 22°C) for 24 hours before analysis.

The physical properties of ketchup were evaluated after the addition of three commonly used food thickening agents: guar, xanthan and CMC of different concentrations (0.5%, 0.75% and 1%) and four temperatures (30, 40, 50 and 60°C). Ketchup without supplements served as a control. For physical determinations, I prepared 10 samples as follows: ketchup with 0.5% (2.89 g) guar gum, ketchup with 0.75% (4.33 g) guar gum, ketchup with 1% (5.78 g) guar gum, ketchup with 0.5% xanthan gum, ketchup with 0.75% xanthan gum, 1% ketchup 1% xanthan gum, ketchup with 0.5% CMC, ketchup with 0.75% CMC, ketchup with 1% CMC gum.

Different concentrations of gums were added to the samples. These were stirred continuously until boiling. Upon completion, the samples were poured into glass jars, and then stored at ambient temperature (20 - 22°C)

¹ Gums are added to concentrations of 0,5%, 0,75% ans 1%.

for 24 hours before analysis. The hydrocolloid-free sample was considered as a control.

In order to achieve the objectives, taking into account the physical properties of the analyzed product, I made the following determinations: pH determination; density determination; viscosity determination and stability of the samples. The pH determination was performed using the Inolab WTW pH meter, pH 720. The viscosity analysis was performed after one day storage at ambient temperature using the Brookfield viscometer. In the preparation of ketchup I used a hand mixer with 7 steps, power 250 W, Hausberg brand.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The rheological assessments of ketchup were made after one day storage at ambient temperature. Thickening agents: guar, xanthan and CMC were added in ketchup at different concentrations (0.5%, 0.75% and 1%).

The prepared samples were allowed to equilibrate for 10 minutes at the desired temperature (30, 40, 50 and 60°C), after which they were used in the determinations listed above.

The first determination consisted of measuring the ketchup viscosity as a function of temperature.

Fig. 1. Variation of ketchup viscosity as a function of temperature with thickening agents 0.5%

The ketchup viscosity in which 0.5% Xanthan gum was added depends on both the measurement temperature and the dissolution temperature of the gum. The viscosity decreases with increasing temperature. This behavior is completely reversible between 30 and 60°C. Although the viscosity decreases, the dissolution temperature increases up to 40°C. Between 40 and 50°C, the viscosity increases with a higher temperature.

At temperatures above 50°C, the viscosity decreases with increasing temperature. This unique behavior is associated with the conformational changes (the ordering-disturbance transition) of the xanthan molecule.

The highest viscosity was recorded at 60°C, by the addition of 0.5% CMC - a more active thickening agent, CMC is a ionic polymer and forms

complexes with the soluble proteins in tomatoes, which increases the product's viscosity.

The following samples analyzed were those with the addition of 0.75% concentration thickening agents.

Fig. 2. Variation of ketchup viscosity as a function of temperature with thickening agents 0.75%

The control sample recorded, with increasing temperature, the lowest viscosity compared to the samples with thickening agents, so the values increased for all samples containing hydrocolloids compared to the control. Therefore, the control had the lowest temperature dependence and the ketchup containing 0.75% CMC the highest, at 40°C.

The addition of 0.75% **Guar gum** resulted in a significant increase in the apparent viscosity of tomato ketchup. When adding **Xanthan** gum 0.75% the consistency of the ketchup fluctuates, the highest being at 50°C, 308 cP. At temperatures above 50°C, the viscosity decreases with increasing temperature. This unique behavior is associated with the conformational changes (the ordering-disturbance transition) of the xanthan molecule.

The last samples were analyzed with the addition of 1% concentration thickening agents.

Fig. 3. Variation of ketchup viscosity as a function of temperature with thickening agents 1%

An increase in the viscosity of the samples with respect to the control was observed in fig.3, as the temperature increased, which indicates that the 1% ketchup samples have higher pseudo-plasticity at high temperatures. The viscosity of the sample with xanthan and guar 1% compared to the control sample was statistically more significant at $P < 0.05$. This was

mainly due to the addition of guar gum and xanthan which, in turn, increases the ketchup's consistency and viscosity. The viscosity was highest for the xanthan 1% sample.

The viscosity data showed that all the samples under examination were non-Newtonian fluids, which was indicated by the pseudo-plastic (shear thinning) nature of tomato ketchup. The addition of different levels of gum has led to a significant increase in the apparent viscosity of the tomato ketchup. The viscosities of the samples increase in proportion to the increase of the gum concentration.

The results of this study showed that ketchup supplemented with hydrocolloids (xanthan, guar, CMC) behaves as a non-Newtonian thinning liquid, in the temperature range of 30-60°C.

Increased gum concentration also increased the apparent viscosity compared to the control; however, the effect of xanthan gum on viscosity was greater than that of guar and CMC gums.

Consistency increased with the concentration of the three hydrocolloids, indicating that the addition of these gums stabilizes the consistency of the ketchup. The activation energy is generally found to decrease with the use of the gum substitute compared to the control sample. Ketchup containing 1% CMC had the lowest temperature dependence which means it had the greatest stabilizing effect on ketchup.

The **ketchup pH** variation according to temperature differs from sample to sample, but it ranges between 4-6, low acid ketchup. pH is a very important factor that influences the quality of tomato ketchup, so the pH values varied: between 4.71-4.74 for the CMC sample of different concentrations; between 4.65-4.73 for the xanthan sample; between 4.6-4.86 for guar sample; between 4.65-4.82 for control.

The density of ketchup at different temperatures does not have major discrepancies between values. **The sample with the addition of 0.5% CMC gum** recorded a value close to the ideal value of the ketchup of $\rho = 1.092 \text{ g/cm}^3$. **The xanthan gum sample 0.5%** has lower values than the rest of the samples, both at low and high temperatures, as the ketchup has expanded, the volume has increased, and therefore the density has decreased.

All samples were stable, they did not show separation of the visual phase after 7 days. Consistency indices increased with the concentration of all three hydrocolloids, indicating that the addition of these gums stabilizes the ketchup's consistency.

CONCLUSIONS

The viscosity data showed that all the samples under examination were non-Newtonian fluids, which was indicated by the pseudo-plastic (shear thinning) nature of tomato ketchup. The addition of different levels of gum has led to a significant increase in the apparent viscosity of tomato ketchup. The viscosities of the samples increase proportionally with the increase of the gum concentration.

The viscosity of xanthan solutions depends on both the measurement temperature and the dissolution temperature. The viscosity decreases with increasing temperature. This behavior is completely reversible between 30 and 60°C. Although the viscosity decreases, the dissolution temperature increases to 40°C. Between 40 and 50°C, the viscosity increases with increasing temperature. At temperatures above 60°C, the viscosity decreases with increasing temperature. This unique behavior is associated with the conformational changes (the ordering-disturbance transition) of the xanthan molecule. The viscosity of xanthan solutions is independent of pH changes.

The samples with guar gum have pseudo-plastic or thin behavior. The degree of weight-plasticity of guar solutions increases with the concentration and the molecular weight. Guar gum provides the thickening and increase of viscosity in aqueous solutions due to the large hydrodynamic volume and the specific intermolecular nature. The viscosities of the guar gum samples increase proportionally with the increase of guar gum concentration.

CMC is an ionic polymer and forms complexes with food-soluble proteins, which results in increased product viscosity. Protein complexes are stable at low pH (3-5.5) and at high temperatures. The results of this study showed that ketchup supplemented with hydrocolloids (xanthan, guar, CMC) behaves as a non-Newtonian thinning liquid, in the temperature range of 30-60°C.

Increased gum concentration also increased the apparent viscosity compared to the control; however, the effect of xanthan gum on viscosity was greater than that of guar and CMC gums. Consistency increased with the concentration of the three hydrocolloids, indicating that the addition of these gums stabilizes the consistency of the ketchup.

The activation energy is generally found to decrease with the use of the gum substitute compared to the control sample. Ketchup containing 1% CMC had the lowest temperature dependence which means it had the greatest stabilizing effect on ketchup. pH does not change significantly, at the addition of thickening agents, therefore neither the preservability nor the nutritional quality of the product is affected.

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THE INFLUENCE OF THE STORAGE PERIOD UPON THE QUALITY OF FRESH FRUITS

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Abstract

Fresh fruits are one of the indispensable components of man's| rational nourishment. The nourishing value of the freshly eaten fruits is due to the chemical components of the latter which are easily accessible to the human body and to which a series of taste and olfactory excitative factors are added which make the fruits be savoured with pleasure any time during the day or any time during any season.

Fruit storage represents an assembly of technological operations performed with the aim of maintaining the quality of the fruits for the freshly estate consumption, an admissible time interval according to each fruit species and type, as well as for expanding the consumption period.

The study related to the influence of the storage period upon the quality of fresh fruit has been performed in laboratory conditions, for three species of fruits: strawberries, apricots and raspberries, each one having two variants of work and which have benn refrigerated and kept at a temperature of approximately 2°C.

Key words: perishable fruits, refrigeration, fruit quality, controlled atmosphere, period of storage

INTRODUCTION

The majority of fruits are considered functional food as they contain one or more substances that have the role to diminish the risk of a disease or the role to improve the way the human body functions. (Banu C., 2010).

The ability to store fruits is influenced by their specific features, by the features ability to regenerate, by their chemical composition and by the relation between the chemical elements, by the maturation degree, by the intensity of the metabolical processes, etc. Very perishable fruits (strawberries) or easily perishable fruits (apricots, raspberries) which have a very sensitive tissue at any mechanical trauma have got a high content of water and a high metabolical activity. (Marca Gh., 2004).

The fruit storage must ensure the prolongation of the storage time of fruit quality. In order to maintain a high biological and nourishing value of fresh vegetal products there must be a permanent control of the physiological and metabolical processes. The decrease of the respiratory metabolism of the fruits leads to the prolongation of the storage period. Fruit storage must ensure the prologation of the fruit quality storage time. (Tuțulescu F., 2013).

The most important factor that makes a fruit able to be stored in a freshly estate is the fruit's active natural immunity, as well as each type of fruit's specific metabolism. The passive immunity has also got an important role being determined by the specific features of the epicarp, by the structural and texture like features and by the maturation degree. (Banu C., 2009).

When at low temperatures a lot of physical transformation appears in food products, determined especially by the heat and mass transfer during the chilling process. As a consequence of the fact that fruits are chilled, unwanted transformations of the natural pigments may appear as well as consistency and form modifications. (Niculiță P., Mona Popa, 2002).

Temporary storage of the strawberries is done in frigorific warehouses at a temperature of 0-2 °C, relative humidity of the air being 85-90% and a powerful ventilation. The storage period is of 3-6 days according to the fruit's health degree, the maturation degree at which the fruit has been harvested, the moment and the way the fruit has been harvested. (Lazăr V., 2006).

The storage of the apricots is done in frigorific warehouses that have a normal atmosphere as well as in warehouses that have controlled atmosphere. The introduction of the fruits in the warehouses is to be done in the shortest time possible after they have been harvested and with as little handling as possible. (Potec I. et al., 1983).

The controlled atmosphere links the effect of the low temperature, of the high relative humidity, of the high content of carbon dioxide and of the low content of oxygen, factors which inhibit the breathing and the sweating process. The intensity of the sweating process of the agricultural products is higher during the period immediately after the harvest. As the water from the fruits disappears, the juice from the fruits' cells gets concentrated, the osmotic pressure increases and the intensity of the breathing process decreases. (Burzo I., 1986).

The optimum conditions for apricots which can be realised only in frigorific warehouses are; temperature -0,5...+0,5°C and RH of 85-90%, the storage period being of 10-15 days according to the harvesting moment. When establishing the storage period one has to keep in mind that in 10-15 days even fruits that had been kept at a temperature of +1°C may lose their flavor and some of their tasty features and that between 4-7 °C these losses become even more obvious. (Beceanu D. și Chira A.).

Raspberries are stored for a very short period of time, for 2-3 days, in frigorific conditions at a temperature of -0,5-0°C and at a relative humidity of 85-90%, some species being able to be kept even for 7 days. A modern way of transporting them and storing them is their intensive treatment with CO₂, which reaches a level of up to 20%. CO₂ manifests a

repressor effect upon the main micro organisms which alter the raspberries during their capitalization period.(Beceanu D. et all, 2008).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In order to analyse the quality of the fruits according to the period of their storage we have taken into consideration 3 types of fresh fruit: strawberries, apricots and raspberries, each of them containing two variants of work, the fruits having been purchased from the fruit market.

The fruits were stored refrigerated at a temperature of about 2°C, for a period of 3 days for the raspberries, 7 days for the strawberries and for the apricots in the Faculty of Environmental Protection's laboratory called: Food Preservation Methods

The determinations have been performed the moment the fruits have been purchased and after the 3 day storage period for the raspberries and 7 day storage for the strawberries and apricots:

- 1.Determining the organoleptic characteristics;

- 2.Determining the chemical-physical indicators of the fruits: the soluble dry substance, acidity, content of C vitamin.

In order to determine the organoleptic characteristics: taste, consistency, smell, color and form, we have used as indicators grades from 1 to 10 and the proportionality factors have been the following: taste – 3, consistency -3, smell – 2, color – 1 form – 1.

inorder to determinethe quantity of soluble dry substance from the fruits, expressed in brix degrees, we have used the refractive method.

In order to determine the quantity of acidity, expressed in grams of malic acid/100ml we have treated the samples with a solution of NaOH in the presence of Phenolphthalein as an indicator.

In order to determine the amount of C vitamin existent in the fruits we have treated the C vitamin with a solution of iodine having amidone as an indicator. In the presence of the iodine the C vitamin oxidizes, iodine decreases and it is expressed in mg/100ml.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Determining the organoleptic characteristics of the fruits

The qualifications obtained for the 3 types of fresh fruits and after these fruits have been stored and refrigerated are registered in table 1.

In what the organleptic characteristics are concerned we have noticed the following: fresh fruits have got grades between 9 and 10, having specific form and color, their texture and consistency were ferm, they had specific smell and taste and while they were stored they got grades between 7 and 9.

Table 1

Organoleptic notes				
No. of samples	Type of fruit	Organoleptic note		
		Fresh fruit	Fruits stored for 3 days	Fruits stored for 7 days
1.	Strawberries V1	9	-	7
2.	Strawberries V2	9,5	-	8,5
3.	Apricots V1	9,5	-	8
4.	Apricots V2	10	-	9
5.	Raspberry V1	10	9	-
6.	Raspberry V2	9,5	8	-

During storage the organoleptic characteristics register lower grades: the raspberry got the grades 9 at V1 and 8 at V2 after 3 day storage and after 7 day storage the strawberry got a 7 for V1 and the apricots got a 9 for V2.

The raspberry is a very perishable fruit which can be stored for a very short period of time in refrigeration conditions that is why the determinations have been done after this fruit has been stored for only 3 days because after this period of time this fruit is not good for consumption.

The fruits have well preserved their color in comparison to the fresh ones, due to the lack of air which leads to the oxidation of the fruits.

The texture and the consistency of the strawberry and apricot pulp present signs of softening as the fruits have been matured by transforming the carbohydrates and protopectin into pectin. In the raspberry's case its texture became soft due to its over maturation during storage.

The pulp has a lower content of juice due to water losses and the taste and flavor lost their intensity.

1. Content of soluble dry substance

The content of soluble dry substance of the analyzed fruits is presented in table 2.

Table 2

The content of soluble dry substance of the fruits				
No. of samples	Type of fruit	Fruit storage period		
		Fresh °Brix	Pstored for 3 days °Brix	Stored for 7 days °Brix
1.	Strawberries V1	8,1	-	7,5
2.	Strawberries V2	10,9	-	13,6
3.	Apricots V1	7,2	-	9,00
4.	Apricots V2	12,5	-	13,5
5.	Raspberry V1	7,5	7,00	-

6.	Raspberry V2	11,1	10,5	-
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From the data analyzed we can notice that fresh fruits present variations of the content of dry substance, even within the same species of fruit, as well as after the storage period.

At the fresh strawberries the content of soluble substance has the value of 8,1°Brix at V1 and 10,9°Brix at V2.

After having been stored for 7 days, sample V1's soluble substance decreases to 7,5 °Brix, and at sample V2, the content of soluble substance increases to 13,6 °Brix.

At fresh apricots the content of soluble substances has been of 7,2 °Brix for sample V1 and of 12,5 °Brix at sample V2, and after 7 days of storage their content increases to 9°Brix at sample V1 and to 13,5 °Brix at sample V2.

At the fresh raspberry the content of soluble substance has been of 7,5 °Brix for V1 and of 11,1 °Brix for V2, and after a 3 day storage the content of the soluble substance decreases to 7,00 °Brix for V1 and to 10,5 °Brix in the case of V2.

During storage the poli carbohydrates are hydrolytically degraded into mono carbohydrates having as a result the content's increase in soluble carbohydrates which are later degraded because they get oxydized and the total quantity decreases.

2.2.The acidity content of the analyzed fruits

The measurable content of acidity for the three types of analyzed fruits is presented in table 3.

Table 3

No. of samples	Type of fruit	Period of fruit storage		
		Fresh g malic acid/100 ml	Stored for 3 daysg malic acid/100 ml	Stored for 7 daysg malic acid/100 ml
1.	Strawberries V1	0,80	-	0,70
2.	Strawberries V2	0,70	-	0,60
3.	Apricots V1	0,90	-	0,70
4.	Apricots V2	0,70	-	0,60
5.	Raspberry V1	1,20	1,10	-
6.	Raspberry V2	1,10	0,90	-

From the presented data one can notice that the acidity of the fresh fruits has got values between 0,70 g malic acid/100 ml at the strawberries V2 and at apricots V2 and of 1,20 g malic acid/100 ml at the raspberry V2.

For the refrigerated fruits the acidity presents lower values, being between 0,60 g malic acid /100 ml at strawberries V2 and apricots V2, and it is of 1,10g malic acid/100ml at V1 for raspberry.

It can be noticed that the higher values of acidity are registered for the fruits that have got a lower content of soluble dry substance within each species, the values being the same for the fresh fruits as well as for the ones kept refrigerated.

2.3.Content of C vitamin

The content of C vitamin for the 6 variants of analyzed fruits is presented in table 4.

Table 4

No. of samples	Type of fruit	Fruit storage period		
		Fresh mg/100g	Stored for 3 days mg/100g	Stored for 7 days mg/100g
1.	Strawberries V1	53,90	-	46,60
2.	Strawberries V2	58,64	-	51,26
3.	Apricots V1	11,36	-	8,33
4.	Apricots V2	13,27	-	10,56
5.	Raspberry V1	19,55	17,62	-
6.	Raspberry V2	24,61	21,34	-

The content of C vitamin in the fresh fruits presents variations between 11,36mg/100g at apricots V1 and 58,64 mg/100g at strawberries V2.

After the fruits have been stored for 3 days and for 7 days respectively in what the apricots are concerned the content of their C vitamin decreases from 11,36mg/100g to 8,33mg/100g in case of V1 and from 13,27mg/100g to 10,56 mg/100g, in case of V2; at strawberries the content of C vitamin decreases at V1 from 53,90 mg/100g to 46,60mg/100g, and at V2 from 58,64 mg/100g to 51,26mg/100g; in what the raspberry is concerned the content of C vitamin in the fresh fruit is of 19,55mg/100 g at V1 and it decreases after 3 days of storage to 17,62mg/100g, and at V2, from 24,61 mg/100g, it decreases to 21,34mg/100g.

The content of C vitamin decreases while the fruits are stored as the C vitamin is soluble in water and at a long contact with the air it decomposes itself.

CONCLUSIONS

Fruits form one of the indispensable elements of man's sensible nourishment. The nourishing value of the fruits eaten in their raw estate is due to their chemical components which are easily accessible to the human body, to which a series of visual, olfactory and taste excitatives are added which make the fruits be consumed with pleasure any time of day or any season.

Fresh fruits have a high content of water (75-95%) which gives them freshness and softness but at the same time they present an unwanted environment which can lead to unwished reactions that can affect their chemical composition as well as their quality.

Carbohydrates which exist in a percent of 75% from the dry substance are greatly represented by simple sugars. The presence of simple carbohydrates in fruits and in vegetables contribute to the shortening of their storage period as the simple sugars are organic substances that can be easily decomposed by their own enzymes or by the enzymes of micro organisms.

In what the organoleptic characteristics are concerned fresh fruits have got grades between 9 and 10, having specific form and color, their consistency and texture were firm, they had characteristic smell and taste. And between the storage period they got grades between 7 and 9.

The content of dry substance presents variations at the fresh fruits, even within the same species of fruit, as well as after the fruits have been stored. The content of soluble dry substance is between 7,2°Brix at fresh apricots V1 and 12,5 °Brix at fresh apricots V2, and after the storage it is between 7,5 °Brix at strawberries V1 and 13,5 at apricots V2.

In the case of refrigerated fruits the acidity presents lower values between 0,60 g malic acid /100 ml at strawberries V2 and at apricots V2, and it reaches 0,90g malic acid/100ml at raspberry V2.

Fruits that have got a lower content of soluble dry substance register higher values of acidity within each species in what the fresh fruits are concerned as well as in what the refrigerated fruits are concerned.

The content of C vitamin decreases while fruits are stored as the C vitamin is soluble in water and after a long period of contact with the air it decomposes itself.

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DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS BETWEEN STAPHYLOCOCCI AND STREPTOCOCCI BY THE LATEX AGGLUTINATION TEST

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Abstract

The bacteria of the Staphylococci type are cocci gram-positive, isolated disposed, in pairs, in short chains and clusters, irregular, with variations in dimensions and the capacity to retain, the gram, immobile and non sporulated. Most of the species are catalase-positive. The streptococci are spherical or oval cocci, gram positive, placed in chains under pair, immobile and non sporulated. Nutritive demanding, discretionary anaerobe, some carboxiphilic, are better developed at reduced tensions of the oxygen, even anaerobe. They are catalase and oxidase negative and don't reduce the nitrates. They ferment the glucose with production of lactic acid and always without gas. The Staphylococci are not nutritive demanding, are cultivated on the majority of usual mediums and tolerate concentrations of over 5% NaCl, and some species are catalase-positive and discretionary anaerobe, but they grow better aerobic. Once the isolated was characterized preliminary "cocci gram positive" with the tendency to form chains and catalase negative, they have to be submitted to the physiological and serological tests of identification.

Keywords: catalase, oxidase, ferments, anaerobe

INTRODUCTION

*The Staphylococci are omnipresent germs. They are found on the level of the teguments and mucous of the human being (especially on the level of the nasopharynx, of the gastro-intestinal and urogenital tube), and in other mammals and birds. The human species of coagulase-negative (SCN) staphylococci colonize especially the nostrils and teguments. *S. aureus* colonizes transitionally the tegument areas or the wet mucous. The colonizing of the newborn with *S. aureus* begins on the level of the umbilical blunt, of the tegument surfaces, of the perineum area. Afterwards, the transmitting of short or long duration to the old child and to the adult was frequently found on the level of the nasopharynx. Approximately 15-30% of the healthy adults are nasopharynx bearers of *S. aureus*. In the medical staff and in the patients with a long hospitalization, the rate of the transmission reaches 40-70% and even 90%, which explains the numerous infections associated to the medical nursing (named also nosocomial infections) with *S. aureus*.*

The cellular wall of *S. aureus* is characteristic to the gram-positive bacteria. The majority of the strains of *S. aureus* have on their surface an enzyme connected to the cellular wall, named “clumping factor” or connected coagulase that transforms the fibrinogen in fibrin. It should be mistaken for the “free coagulase”, secreted in the exterior of the bacterial cell and which is characteristic to the *S. aureus* species. In the majority of the strains of *S. aureus*, the peptidoglycan is covered by the protein A, which has the property to connect in a nonspecific way the antibodies by the Fc fragment. The capsule, present only in some strains, increases the antiphagocytic properties of the staphylococci, being a factor of virulence.

The *Streptococcus* type, very complex, was classified using multiple criteria that consider the hemolysis, antigenic structure, clinical aspects etc. – Depending on the type of hemolysis on blood agar they are divided in: β -hemolytic streptococci, produce colonies surrounded by a clear area of complete hemolysis, characteristic for *Streptococcus pyogenes* and other pathogen species. α -hemolytic, produce a partial hemolysis with the appearance of a green coloration of the medium (viridans hemolysis), characteristic to the viridans streptococci and pneumococci α' -hemolytic, produce incomplete hemolysis, with nonlysed erythrocytes non hemolytic (γ -hemolytic). - Lancefield antigenic classification. *Streptococci* were divided based on the antigenic structure – depending on the C glycan from the cellular wall, in serologic groups written with the letters A-H and K-W, - non groupable streptococci – those without group antigen: *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and streptococci viridans. From the clinical point of view the streptococci are classified in: - *Streptococcus pyogenes* (β -hemolytic streptococcus of group A) – is the main human pathogen from the streptococci, being associated to some infections with location, invasive, generalized, and to some allergic complications resulting after repeated infections - *Streptococcus agalactiae* - is part of the group B and is isolated from the vaginal flora. It is involved in the meningitis and septicemias of the newborn. – the streptococci of group C, G and F colonize sometimes the nasopharynx, being the cause of some sinusitis, bacteremias or endocarditis. – non enterococci streptococci of group D (*Streptococcus bovis*) are part of the normal flora of the intestine and are the cause of some endocarditis. They can produce bacteremias in patients with carcinoma of colon. - *Streptococcus pneumoniae* – the non-enclosed version of this species is present in the normal flora of the upper respiratory tube. The enclosed, pathogen versions are the major cause of meningitis in children and of pneumonia.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

It were processed the samples from the patients from Sante laboratory, from Oradea. The species of *Staphylococcus* and *Streptococcus* isolated were identified based on the morphologic, cultural aspect, of the production of coagulase, the presence of hemolysin, the enzymatic activity and the production of acid following the fermenting of some sugars. The API galleries used for the definitive identification of *Staphylococcus* and *Streptococcus* strains were ID 32 STAPH and STREP. For the identification of the *Staphylococcus* and *Streptococcus* strains we used also the Pastorex Staph-Plus kit: the reaction is of latex-agglutination on the slide that shoes simultaneously the presence of “clumping factor” (the factor of affinity for fibrinogen), protein A, and the latex test for streptococci, the test uses the latex suspension specific for groups: A,B,C,D,F,G, for the identification of correspondent Ag group specific it is needed previously an enzymatic extraction.

1. The latex kit of identification of *Streptococci*

Equipments and reagents

Sterile loops

Thermostat

The latex kit

Preparing and preservation of reagents

The latex kit is kept at 2-8°C, before the utilization is kept to heat at the room temperature.

Preparing the biologic material.

The pure young culture on non-selective medium.

Execution of the procedure

With a sterile loop are sampled 2-6 colonies, then discharged in 0.4 ml of extraction enzymes and is hatched 10 min at 35-37°C, is disposed on the agglutination plate a drop of extract and a drop of latex reactive.

2. The latex kit of identification of *Staphylococci*

Principle

The test uses a latex suspension specific sensitized that will agglutinate with those colonies of Staphylococci that include: clumping factor or/and protein A and capsular polysaccharides of *Staphylococcus Aureus*.

Necessary materials

The reactive test contains:

- Sensitized latex particles
- Sodium azide as preservation medium
- The negative control includes non-sensitized latex particles
- Cards for agglutination
- Plates with test strains

- Pipettes
- Sterile loops

Procedure

- Is left the kit to accommodate to the room temperature
- Is homogenized the latex reactive
- Is dispersed 1 drop of reactive on the agglutination card
- Are transferred 2-3 suspect colonies and is mixed the mixture
- Is followed the appearance or the absence of the agglutination in 20 seconds

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In staphylococci strains, the presence of the connected coagulase was showed with a kit that allows the testing of the strains as a screening test for the detecting of this enzyme.

Fig. no.1 *Staphylococcus Aureus*

Fig. no. 2. *Staphylococcus Aureus*

Fig. no. 3 *Streptococcus*.

Fig. no. 4 Kit agglutination of streptococci

The positive reaction indicates the presence of the factor of aggregation by the appearance of some small clots, as a consequence of the precipitation of the plasmatic fibrinogen in fibrin, under the action of this enzyme for 2-3 minutes. The negative reaction is represented by the absence of such clots.

By the precision of the results, a strain of *S. aureus SSP. Aureus* was used as a positive control and a strain of *S. epidermidis* as a negative control. The results were the following: - *S. aureus SSP. aureus*: 60 possessed strains factor de aggregation ,72,04%; - *S. intermedius*: 73 possessed strains factor de aggregation, 62,27%;

The direct detecting of the streptococcus antigen by the latex kit of agglutination has as ascendant result for the streptococci of group A, 65%, 20% for the streptococci of group G, respectively, the rest of 15% for the streptococci of group B,D,C,F.

DISCUSSIONS

The clinical importance and significance of a staphylococcus coagulase-negative is supported by the isolation of this microorganism in a dominant ratio or in pure culture and by the repeated isolations of the same strains, from blood, urine or other samples. In the case of the systemic nosocomial infections that appeared in the wards with risk, the interpretation of the involvement of some staphylococcus coagulase negative in the infectious syndrome can be oriented by the correlation between the isolated bacteria from the catheter and the presence of the same bacteria in blood cultures.

The microscopic aspect, as a series of fenotypical types, under the aspect of the colonies on non selective mediums, beside a restrained set of enzymatic tests, allow the preliminary identification of the species most frequently isolated from staphylococcus infections.

On the staphylococcus strains, the presence of the connected coagulase was accomplished with the help of a kit that allows the testing of the strains as a test of screening for the detection of this enzyme. The positive reaction indicates the presence of the factor of aggregation by the appearance of small clots, following the precipitation of the plasmatic fibrinogen in fibrin, under the action of this enzyme in a period of 2-3 minutes. The negative reaction is represented by the absence of such clots. The staphylococcus strains that synthetize the connected coagulase, and the protein A produced a positive reaction, because this enzyme, in contact with the sensitized latex particles with IgG and fibrinogen, has agglutinated this mixture.

In the study “Evaluation of RapiDEC Staph for identification of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, and *Staphylococcus saprophyticus*”, accomplished by W M Janda, K Ristow, and D Novak, is specified the fact that, RapiDEC Staph is a test for the presumptive identification of the main human staphylococci species, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, and *S. saprophyticus*. The test includes control cupules for the detection of fluorogenic of coagulase and chromogenic substrates for alkaline phosphatase and beta-galactosidase. These tests identify *S. aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, and *S. saprophyticus*, respectively. The positive results with both chromogenic substrates offer a presumptive identification of *S. xylosus* or *S. intermedius* (*S. xylosus*-*S. intermedius*).

The cupules of testing are inoculated with a suspension of the body, and the reactions are read after an incubation of 2h. RapiDEC-Staph was evaluated with 303 clinical strains and of stock. The identifications were compared with those obtained by the test of coagulation of the tube, a test of coagulation of the diapositives of latex (StaphAUREX), another system of commercial identification (Staph-TRAC) and additional conventional tests. RapiDEC-Staph identified 100% correct from 130 *S. aureus* strains, 70,3% of 74 *S. epidermidis* strains, and 81,3% of 32 *S. saprophyticus* strains. Four of the five isolations *S. xylosus* were named *S. xylosus-S. intermedius*. Non identified *s. epidermidis* and *s. saprophyticus* strains were named "*Staphylococcus spp.* " among 62 other coagulase-negative staphylococci, 4 were wrongly identified as *s. epidermidis* and 7 were wrongly identified as *s. saprophyticus*. While the sensitivity and specificity of the test of fluorogenic coagulation for *S. aureus* were of 100%, the incapacity to detect the activity of the alkaline phosphatase in more isolations *S. epidermidis* has determined less correct identification by the RapiDEC-Staph test for these species.

Once the isolated was characterized preliminary “cocci gram positive with the tendency to form chains and catalase negative”, have to be submitted to physiological tests and serologic tests of identification. The introduction of streptococci in the algorithm of identification is made based on the aspect of the hemolysis: the β hemolytic streptococci versus non β hemolytic streptococci.

The reagents of agglutination from latex are used on a wide scale in the microbial diagnosis, the identification and serotyping. *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (pneumococcus) is a major cause of morbidity and mortality on the global level. The world organization of health recommended the latex agglutination as an alternative method to “golden standard” of testing for pneumococci, serotyping.

The study “Detection of group B streptococcal antigen in early-onset and late-onset group B streptococcal disease with the Wellcogen Strep B latex agglutination test”, accomplished by D L Ingram, D M Suggs, A W Pearson, showed the fact that the test of agglutination of latex Wellcogen strep B (Wellcome Diagnostics, Dartford, England) was evaluated as a method of detecting of the streptococcus antigen from Group B in urine, cephalorachidian fluid and serum from newborn with early debut (less or equal with 7 days of age) and streptococcus disease Group B with late start. The urine was the best source of antigen that was detected in 100% of six newborn with early streptococcus disease Group B, which had urine available in the first 12 hours of disease and in 88% of the 17 newborn infected with streptococcus from Group B with urine available in the first 48 hours of disease. The antigen was not detected in any group of patients

without streptococci disease of group B, with the exception of the urine of a patient with meningitis *Proteus Mirabilis*. The latex test Wellcogen strep B from the tested lot compares favorably with a test of agglutination from latex available non-commercial.

CONCLUSIONS

A gradual diagnosis, consisting of the performing of multiple tests of differentiation whose results, corroborated, allow the differentiation of the species of staphylococci with an acceptable degree of precision, is the solution agreed in the present by most of the laboratories.

The fast identification of the species of *S. Aureus* can be made with the help of the tests of agglutination. The sensitized reagents with fibrinogen and immunoglobulin G pairs the connected coagulase, respectively protein A from the wall of *S. Aureus*, which has as macroscopic expression the agglutination of the mixture of reactive and the culture with *S. Aureus*. The precision of this test is between 70% and over 90%.

Reactions of reverse agglutination that use as support particles for specific antibodies of group, either staphylococci with protein A, or particles of latex. Numerous types of kits are sold for the agglutination on the slide. Comparing to the classic test of precipitation, the tests of agglutination on the slide were faster, economical for a sensitivity and specificity at least equal.

The kit with the antisera A,B,C,F,G allows the identification of most of the β hemolytic streptococci involved in the urinary infections. The rare strains that don't react with these sera can be characterized biochemically following to be confirmed by the reference laboratory.

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF HONEY FROM BEAR GARLIC (*ALLIUM URSINUM*) FLOWERS FROM BIHOR COUNTY

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Abstract

Honey is a natural product of animal origin very important in human diet from many points of view. It is defined as “the sweet substance produced by honeybees from the nectar of blossoms or from secretions on living plants, which the bees collect, transform and store in honeycombs”. It plays an important part in our nutrition and it is well-known for its positive effects on health. *Allium ursinum* L. (Ramson or wild garlic) is a perennial plant, widely distributed in Europe. The plant is valued by beekeepers, as well, since bear garlic flowers can serve as pollen and nectar sources for honeybees, completing the spring bee pasture. In Bihor county, in the forest of Săldăbagiu grows wild bear garlic and a beekeeper from this county has managed to obtain honey from the flowers of this plant in 2016 and 2017. In this study, certain physico-chemical and biochemical parameters of honey from bear garlic from this region were investigated.

Key words: floral honey, wild garlic flowers, physico-chemical parameters, bioactive compounds.

INTRODUCTION

Honey is defined as “the sweet substance produced by honeybees from the nectar of blossoms or from secretions on living plants, which the bees collect, transform and store in honeycombs” (Codex Alimentarius Commission, 2002). Naturally, honey has been traditionally recognized as a valuable source of energy. It has also been recognized for its antimicrobial characteristics, possessed excellent antioxidant activity and is such a natural product with a number of therapeutic properties (Alvarez-Suarez et al., 2010; Basualdo et al., 2007, Bousaid et al, 2014).

It is a concentrated aqueous solution of invert sugar, that contains a mixture of other carbohydrates, amino and organic acids, minerals, aromatic substances, pigments, waxes and pollen grains to make it complex (Ajlouni and Sujirapinyokul, 2010; Manzanares et al., 2011; Rashed and Soltan, 2004).

Wild or bear garlic (*Allium ursinum* L.) is a perennial plant, widely distributed in Europe, occurring in various deciduous woodlands, preferring

damp shadow places, meso- and eutrophic, neutral to moderately acid soils of the hilly and the mountainous vegetation belt (Kovacs et al, 2007).

Allium ursinum L., has been used for centuries in folk medicine, food flavoring and as an ingredient for local dishes (Sapunjieva et al, 2012). In 1992 *Allium ursinum* was declared the "Medicinal Plant of the Year" by the Association for the Protection and Research on European Medicinal Plants.

The usable part of the plant is usually its delicate and fragile leaves, which should be collected in the first phase of blooming (Błażewicz-Woźniak and Michowska 2011), but Bear garlic has a rounded head of star-like flowers. In bear garlic the flowers are a clear white.

The plant is valued by beekeepers, as well, since bear garlic flowers can serve as pollen and nectar sources for honeybees, completing the spring bee pasture (Farkas et al, 2012).

Flowering in late April, early May, it provides an excellent spring bee pasture with good nectar flow. Its flowering period overlaps with oilseed rape (*Brassica napus*), but the nectar flow is uneven and does not give as much as rape, even in favourable weather (Nagy, 2005).

Rate of nectar secretion was influenced by both, floral age and environmental factors, from which relative humidity was the most important, being significantly and inversely related to nectar production. Similarly, environmental factors were found to affect the nectar production of ramson, ranging from 0.16 to 0.42 mg nectar/flower/day, with an average of 52.13% sugar content (Peter, 1975). In their study, Farkas et al, 2012, sugar value was 0.14–0.25 mg in sunny weather, but remained below 0.1mg in changeable, cool weather.

The aim of this study is to investigate some physico-chemical and biochemical parameters of honey from bear garlic (*Allium ursinum*) flowers from Bihor county, in year 2016 and 2017.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In Bihor county, in the forest of Saldabagiu grows wild bear garlic and a beekeeper from this county has managed to obtain bear garlic honey (BGH) from the flowers of this plant in 2016 and 2017.

A number of 6 honey samples were analyzed, 3 sample from each year. All samples were obtained directly from the same beekeeper of Bihor county (BGH 2016 and BGH 2017).

In each sample, we determined physico-chemical parameters: colour, water, ash, total acidity, HMF, and biochemical parameters: total sugar proline, total polyphenols (TP), total flavonoids (TF), antioxidant activity (AA) with FRAP method and the ascorbic acid content with spectrophotometric method.

Physico-chemical parameters

Physical-chemical parameters, like: colour, water, pH, acidity, ash, electrical conductivity, were analysed according to the Romanian Standard Analysis Methods (National Standard, 2009) and Harmonised methods of the IHC (Bogdanov, 2009), or with specific methods.

Colour - Since the colour of honey partly reflects the content of pigments with antioxidant properties (carotenoids, flavonoids, etc.), honey was diluted to 50% (w/v) with warm water (45–50°C), sonicated for 5 min and filtered to eliminate large particles.

Colour of honey samples was measured with 2 methods:

a. Colour intensity -ABS 450

The net absorbance ABS450, was defined as the difference between spectrophotometric absorbance at 450 and 720 nm (Shimadzu UVMini-1240 spectrophotometer), (Bereta, 2005)

$$\text{ABS 450} = A_{450} - A_{720}$$

b. Colour analysis with Pfund scale

The color of honey was determined by spectrophotometric measurement of the absorbance of a 50% honey solution (w/v) at 635 nm.

The honeys were classified according to the Pfund scale after conversion of the absorbance values (White, 1984).

$$\text{mm Pfund} = -38.70 + 371.39 \times \text{Abs } 635$$

where mm Pfund is the intensity of honey colour in the Pfund scale; Abs is the absorption of honey solution.

Water and total sugar - of the tested samples were determined with digital refractometer KRUSS model AR 2008.

pH – HATCH SensyION 378 multiparameter meter was used to measure the pH of a 10% (w/v) solution of honey prepared in ultrapure water.

Total acidity - by titration method (Bogdanov, 2009).

Ash content -The honey is ashed at a temperature no higher than 600°C and the residue weighed.

Electrical conductivity (EC) – Currently the measurement of electrical conductivity is the most useful quality parameter for the classification of honeys which can be determined by relatively inexpensive instrumentation. This has been confirmed by the data published by Persano Oddo and Piro, 2004. This parameter was measured for a 20 % (w/v) solution of honey suspended in ultrapure water, with HATCH SensyION 378 multiparameter meter.

HMF content was determined by spectrophotometric method (White, 1979). Each of the honey samples was divided into 2 clarified aliquots; water was added to one of the aliquots and absorption was read at $\lambda=284$ and 336 nm. This was compared to a second solution in which this absorption was eliminated by the addition of sodium bisulphate. Results were expressed in milligrams of HMF per kilogram of honey.

Biochemical parameters

Proline - The content of proline is defined as the colour developed with ninhydrin compared with a proline standard (SIGMA-ALDRICH, USA) and expressed as a proportion of the mass of honey in mg/kg. Proline and ninhydrin (REDOX, Romania) form a coloured complex. After adding 2-propanol (MERCCK, Germany), the extinction of the sample solution and a reference solution at a 510 nm wavelength is determined (Bogdanov, 2009).

Extraction of antioxidant components - Antioxidant components from honey were extracted with water (10% solution) and with methanol/water mixture

Total polyphenols (TP) content was determined by using the Folin-Ciocalteu (1927) colorimetric method developed by Singleton and Rossi (1965). A diluted extract (0.5 ml) or phenolic standard was mixed with 2.5 ml Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and after 5 minutes 2.0 mL sodium carbonate (7.5%). The absorption was read after 2 h at 20°C, at 750 nm. For the preparation of calibration curve 0.5 ml aliquot of 0.2, 0.4, 0.8 and 1.2 $\mu\text{M}/\text{ml}$ aqueous gallic acid solution were used as the standard and expressed as mg of gallic acid equivalent (GAE).

Total flavonoids (TF) The total Flavonoid compounds content was measured with AlCl_3 colorimetric assay (Atanassova et al, 2011). The absorbance was measured at 510nm. As standard we used quercitine.

Ascorbic acid content was determined through xylene-extraction (Ranganna, 1986) using a spectrophotometer.

Antioxidant activity – FRAP assay (Berzie and Stain, 1996) using the calibration curves for $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0 to 1000 μM) and Trolox (0 to 250 μM). Results were expressed as the correspondent of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and Trolox activity for 10% honey solution activity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After performing the calculations, it was found that in the analyzed honey samples in both years the colour was Extra light amber (table 1).

The honey samples had fluid consistency, was homogeneous, viscous, without signs of crystallization, without impurities. The flavor is of bear garlic, medium sweetness and, sometimes, a light bitterness.

The colour of honey was determined with 2 methods.

Table 1.

Mean values of the results obtained after colour intensity determination of the honey samples from the two years of study

Sample	Abs 450	Abs720	A450	Colour	A635	Pfund	Colour
BGH 2016	0.758	0.259	0.499	extra light amber	0.211	39.77	extra light amber
BGH 2017	0.834	0.268	0.566	extra light amber	0.235	48.57	extra light amber

The content of water, total sugar, ash, electrical conductivity total acidity and HMF respect the limits established for honey in the Romanian and the International Regulatory Standards.

Proline content was higher than 200 mg/kg honey, which proves that no sugars were added to the analyzed samples (table 2.).

Table 2.

Mean values for physical-chemical parameters determination

Sample	Acidity °T	Total sugar %	Water %	Electrical conductivity mS/cm	Ash %	Proline mg/kg	HMF mg/kg
BGH 2016	3.2	81,5	16,9	0.136	0,1	387.6	1,40
BGH 2017	3.5	79.2	19.2	0.158	0,17	303.2	1.20
STAS* 784/3-89/	Max 4	Max 83	Max 20	0.8	Max 0,5	Min 200	Max 1,5

The results obtained after performing analysis for studying the content of some bioactive compounds in honey samples from both years were inserted in table 3 and figure1.

Since no studies were found for bear garlic honey characterization, the data obtained by us were compared with those obtained for the acacia honey and the multifloral honey from April-May.

Table 3.

Sample	Total polyphenols mg GAE/kg honey	Flavonoids mg Quercetin/100g honey	FRAP value for a 10% honey solution ($\mu\text{mol FeSO}_4$)	Vitamina C mg/100g honey
BGH 2016	46.7±0.9	8.9±0.1	335.5±1.3	8.65±0.4
BGH 2017	38.65±0.8 ***	7.5±0.1 ***	309.0±1.1 ***	7.16±0.3 **

The total phenolic content of the tested honey samples, was 46.7 GAE/kg for year 2016, and 38.65 GAE/kg for 2017. These values are lower than results obtained for accacia and multifloral honey, by Beretta et al, 2005 (55.2±2.8 mg of GAE/kg of honey). Similar results were obtained by Bertoneclj et al., 2012, (from 25.7 to 67.9 mg of GAE per kg of honey) and Mărghitaş et al., 2009, who determined the total phenolic content in Romanian acacia honey to be in the range from 2.0 to 39.0 mg of GAE per kg of honey.

Total Flavonoid content has similar pattern with those determined by Meda et al. (2005) in various Burkina Fasan honey types in the range from 0.17 to 8.35 mg of QE per 100 g of honey.

Antioxidant activity was 335.5 $\mu\text{M FeSO}_4$ in 2016 in comparison with 309 $\mu\text{M FeSO}_4$ in 2017, and similar with results obtained by Saric et al 2012.

Ascorbic acid content had close values for the two years, respectively 8.65 and 7.16 mg/kg of honey.

Fig.1 Graphical representation of mean values of vitamin C, total polyphenol and flavonoid content in the studied bear garlic honey samples

CONCLUSIONS

Bear garlic honey colour was extra light amber.

Physical-chemical parameters of bear garlic honey respect the limits established for honey in the Romanian and the International Regulatory Standards.

The studied antioxidant compounds content in Bear garlic honey has similar values like multifloral honey collected in April-May.

All the tested honey samples present a good quality, consistent with the legislative requirements and a high antioxidant activity.

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ON THE USAGE OF POTASSIUM SORBATE (E202) IN DIFFERENT SORTS OF MARGARINE AND ESTIMATION OF ITS POTENTIAL DAILY INTAKE

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Abstract

Sorbic acid and its sorbates are food preservatives widely used, in manufacturing more than 80 food products categories, according to Codex Alimentarius. Their role is to prevent the development in food of dangerous microorganisms, especially from moulds and yeasts categories, as well as to preserve certain sensorial traits of the food.

The aim of this paper was to identify and quantify the potassium sorbate (E202) presence in certain commercially available margarines and to estimate the hypothetical daily dietary intake in three consumers' categories (adult women and men and children), in comparison with the maximal admitted levels specified by the en-force regulations.

Thus, the potassium sorbate inclusion rate reached 133-138 mg additive/100 g margarine, which represented 66-69% of the maximal inclusion threshold (200 mg E202/100 g margarine).

The intake levels were calculated at 0.440 – 0.460 mg potassium sorbate/kg body weight in women and children, respectively at 0.495 – 0.518 mg E202/kg body weight in men.

Such levels represented just 1.76-2.07 % of the maximal admitted daily intake in humans (25 mg potassium sorbate/kg body weight).

Key words: potassium sorbate, margarine, inclusion rate, daily dietary intake

INTRODUCTION

Many concerns raise among the modern consumers, which became more exigent to the quality of food, mainly to those potential direct or indirect risks that could threaten them though the daily intake of food improved by adding chemically synthesized ingredients (Hura C., 2008). The sorbates family (sorbic acid and its salts) play a significant role in the food industry, due to their properties involved in food sensorial properties preservation or in prolonging its shelf life (Banu et al., 2010).

They act efficiently against moulds and yeasts, while the action against bacteria is lower. However, at a pH below 6.5, sorbates could have a slight inhibitory effect against *Clostridium botulinum*. Their fungicide effect is significant, mostly on some mould species that are known as mycotoxins producers (Oşan A., 2010).

In certain food categories rich in fats, such as margarine, butter, mayonnaises, salad dressings, the sorbic acid and the sorbates inhibit the development of moulds, preventing thus the subsequent lipolysis and rancid alterations (Orănescu E., 2008).

In most of the cases, the sorbic acid and the sorbates are considered as non-harmful for humans, because most of their compounds are assimilated and metabolised successfully by the organism.

There were also reports of persons with accentuated sensibility and allergic reactions to foods containing a certain amount of sorbates (in their composition or on the surface). Mucosal membrane irritations and skin rash are the most known side effects of sorbates (A. M. Fărr, 2000).

Another negative effect of sorbates is that they drain out the B₁₂ vitamin available in the organism. Moreover, it was emphasised that calcium sorbate could have a pronounced mutagen actions, despite the fact that doses and conditions of usage were not specified in the studies reporting the undesirable effect (Orănescu E., 2008).

According to Gouget C. (2012), the sodium sorbate (one of the most used chemical preserving additives in food industry) could interact with the nitrates and could induce congenital malformations.

Other authors reported that using this sorbate could lead to severe illness chronic conditions, such as: asthma, atopic rash, rhinitis and digestive disorders (Mihai G., 2013).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The aim of the research was to quantify the potassium sorbate used in producing five sorts of margarine commercially available (*Rama- M1, Becel – M2, Auchan- M3, Linco – M4, Delma – M5*) and to report this content to a hypothetical intake, through an estimation of consumers dietary patterns. Sorbic acid and its sorbates used in margarines were assessed through the spectrophotometric method (AOAC, 1990) using a VWR – UV6300PC double beam spectrophotometer.

The results were compared to the dosage admitted for inclusion in such food category (2000 mg potassium sorbate/kg of fat emulsions with more than 60% total lipids; 1000 mg potassium sorbate/kg of fat emulsions with at least 60% total lipids) (Codex Alimentarius, F.A.O., 2019). Starting from an estimated dietary daily consumption of margarine (20g in women, 30 g in men and 10 g in children), the daily intake quantity was obtained for each of the three category of consumers (adults, women of 60 kg body weight, men of 80 kg body weight and children of 30 kg body weight, as well).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Potassium sorbate (E202) concentrations quantified in the five studied margarine sorts are presented in table 1.

There were not identified exceeding doses, in comparison with the maximal admitted inclusion limit, i.e. 200 mg sorbate/100 g product.

The first margarine sort (M1) had an average content of 132 ± 7.21 mg potassium sorbate/100 g, while in the second investigated sort (M2), a slight increase was detected, in comparison with the former one (134 ± 7.21 mg potassium sorbate/100 g).

The last three sorts (M3, M4, M5) presented also close values of potassium sorbate per 100 g product (M3= 138 ± 5.20 mg E202; M4= 137 ± 5.74 mg E202; M5= 135.50 ± 8.06 mg E202).

In comparison with the maximal allowed inclusion threshold (tab. 1), in M1 samples was calculated a 66% sorbate inclusion rate, therefore 34% less E-202 vs. the maximal possible dosage.

Table 1

Average values of the potassium sorbate contents in the five sorts of margarine

Analysed product	Analytical value (mg/100 g) Mean	Mean standard error	Variation coefficient v%	Legal Inclusion threshold (mg/100 g)	% vs. legal threshold
Margarine M1	133.00	± 7.21	17.28	200	66
Margarine M2	134.00	± 3.61	8.51	200	67
Margarine M3	138.00	± 5.20	11.91	200	69
Margarine M4	137.00	± 5.77	13.26	200	68.5
Margarine M4	135.50	± 8.06	18.82	200	67.75

In the second product (M2 margarine, the inclusion rate represented 67% of the maximal admitted one, 33% less than the standard; in M3 margarine, potassium sorbate reached 69% of the maximal allowed dosage (31% less); in M4 margarine, the analytical values revealed a 68.50% sorbate content out of the 200 mg/100 g maximal regulated threshold (31.5% less). In the last analysed sort (M5), the potassium sorbate level reached 67.75% of the maximal admitted one (32.25% less vs. the whole admitted potential inclusion level).

Data referring to the potassium sorbate hypothetical daily intake were derived from the estimated margarine portion to be consumed daily by the three categories of consumers (20 g in adult women, 30 g in adult men and 10 g in children) (table 2).

Table 2

Estimation of the potassium sorbate (E-202) daily intake (mg/kg body weight) from the five sorts of margarine

Consumer category	Sort of margarine				
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5
Maximal allowed intake	25	25	25	25	25
Adult woman, 60 kg body weight	0.440	0.447	0.460	0.457	0.451
<i>% of daily maximum allowed intake</i>	1.76	1.78	1.84	1.82	1.80
Adult man, 80 kg body weight	0.495	0.503	0.518	0.514	0.508
<i>% of daily maximum allowed intake</i>	1.98	2.01	2.07	2.05	2.03
Child, 30 kg body weight	0.440	0.447	0.460	0.457	0.452
<i>% of daily maximum allowed intake</i>	1.76	1.79	1.84	0.82	1.81

In women having 60 kg body weight, the daily intake of potassium sorbate was estimated between 0.440 – 0.460 mg potassium sorbate/kg body weight, which represented 1.76-1.84% of the maximal admitted daily intake (25 mg potassium sorbate/kg body weight).

In men with an average body weight of 80 kg, the daily intake was calculated between 0.495 – 0.518 mg E-202, that corresponded to a dosage of 1.98 – 2.07 % of the maximal admitted daily intake.

In the last category, represented by children with an average weight of 30 kg, the values were similar to those identified in adult women (0.440 – 0.460 mg potassium sorbate), corresponding to a proportion of 1.76 – 1.84 % of the maximal dosage (25 mg potassium sorbate/kg body weight).

CONCLUSIONS

Potassium sorbate (E202) inclusion rate in the five commercially available margarine products was 31-34% lower than the maximal admitted level (200mg potassium sorbate/100 g product).

Estimation of the daily intake of E202 (mg/kg body weight) through the consumption of one margarine portion, in accordance with the consumer type (30 g in men, 20g in women and 10g in children), revealed values that represented 0.82-2.07% of the maximal intake dosage in humans (25mg E202/kg body weight)

Usage of potassium sorbate in this food product category is justified, hence it prevents the development of moulds that could lead to lipolysis and rancid degradations, knowing that the consumption of margarine is increasing (basing of financial affordability and practical reasons in domestic food preparation), despite the fact the product itself is not a healthy one.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF UTILIZATION THE MALT MASH IN THE BAKERY

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Abstract

Using the new recipes and biotechnologies, using the flour as basic raw material, the bakers obtain a various range of products for the purpose of satisfying the larger and more diversified demands of the population. The reinforcing of the flour is wide spread practice, in the last period using on a large scale byproducts coming from different industries. The malt flour, obtained from the malt mas by specific procedures, byproduct resulted from the industry of beer, is the object of the present paper. Being introduced in the bakery products it fortifies the products due to its content in antioxidants, in phenolic compounds respectively, with an important role in prevention of some diseases. Its behavior in the bakery products is different depending the percentage used and the technology applied

Key words: beer, malt mash, malt flour, fermentation

INTRODUCTION

The bakery still remains an open subject to the researches because the science in the field of food industry evolves, being found new techniques of manufacture of bread, of its baking and also, the more and more utilization of different food fortifiers, being tested on the pilot level for the obtaining of innovating products designated for the human consumption with nutritional properties higher than of the classic products (Bei M, 2016).

The malt mash, the main waste resulted in the largest quantity in the beer factories, being obtained at the end of the phase of filtration of must in the department of boiling from the mash of saccharified barley, phase that has as purpose the separation of the particles in suspension and the sediments made in the mash-saccharification from the clear malt must. Practically this was used for decades as fodder for animals. Mussatto and the collaborators in 2005, following the accomplished studies, has concluded that annually are gathered quantities approximated to 85% from the total of waste generated by different industries.

Huige in the paper published in 1994 specifies that the chemical composition of the beer must is different depending on the diversity of barley used, on the process of malt manufacturing applied, the conditions of

obtaining the beer must and the type and quality of the auxiliary materials added, specifying that it is rich in fibers, proteins, minerals and antioxidants, compounds that are not used enough in the process of obtaining the beer, which correlated with the small price and the availability of supply represents real sources of nutrients and antioxidants.

Goupy and the collaborators in the paper published in 1999, specifies that approximately 80% from the phenolic compounds present in the beer come from malt and the rest comes from hop. These compounds represent a real source of natural antioxidants, capable to foreclose and treat different inflammatory affections, cardiovascular diseases, neurodegenerative diseases, even cancer, presenting an anti-tumor activity characterized by the inhibition of the proliferation of a variety of cancer cells (Domocoş D., 2018).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The fresh malt mash obtained is difficult to be stored due to its high content of water, approximately 75%, the high potential of anti-oxidation and due to a strong enzymatic activity, thus, it is necessary its fast exploitation. In order to be introduced easily in the composition of pre-mixtures, the malt mash was dried in the oven for 6 hours, at the temperature of 78°C, until it has a content of 10% water, it was milled and then the 6 pre-mixtures from white flour and different percentages of malt flour were made (10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%, 35%). The 6 versions of pre-mixtures were used for the obtaining of bread using traditional manufacturing recipes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The form of the products is similar, shaped, increased in the case of some experimental versions with small quantity of malt flour and less increased in case of the versions where it was used more malt flour. Also the volume of the products obtained was smaller for the bread obtained from premix with larger quantity of malt flour. This aspect can be explained by the retention of water by the fibers of malt flour, being known that it contains over 40% fibers compared to the wheat flour for example, which contains approximately 0,6%.

The aspect of the bread peel where it was introduced malt flour has presented the defect of cracking of the peel even from the phase of fermenting being maintained afterwards in the finished product. The larger the malt flour percentage in the composition of the pre-mixture the more pronounced was this defect. Also here it can be mentioned the fact that the color of the peel of the bakery products is different varying more between

the versions depending on the quantity of malt flour introduced in the pre-mixture, this being darker in color once the percentage of malt flour increases.

The aspect of the bread crumb presents a similar evolution depending on the type of pre-mixture from which the product was obtained. Thus, the breads with smaller content of malt flour are well baked, when beating the peel it produces a clear sound, elastic bread crumb, when it is pushed it comes back to the initial form, uniform, dry at touch while those with larger content present baked aspect, when beating the peel it produces a muffled sound, when it is pushed it comes slowly back to the initial form, when cut with the knife it is clean.

The porosity of the bread crumb from the versions where the malt flour percentage introduced in the pre-mixture was smaller, it presents a structure of the pores with oval form, well defined, uniform on the whole surface, compared to the samples where the quantity of malt flour introduced was greater, it presents a dense core, with acceptable porosity, small and dense pores. The rheological structure of the core is strongly affected by the introduction of the malt flour in a quantity greater than 20% of the total flours.

Regarding the taste of the products was observed it is present a mild or more intense smell of bran, depending on the percentage of malt flour introduced. The humidity considered in the 6 samples is different because the more the percentage of malt flour in the product the product retains more water. For this reason the superannuation of the product is accomplished in a shorter time, it is losing the specific taste, the smell becomes unpleasant after 24 hours at the room temperature.

CONCLUSIONS

The bakery products enriched with active biologic compounds, coming from the malt mash flour are designated to a wide category of consumers, healthy persons, preoccupied for the maintaining of the health condition and persons that suffer of mild impairment of the digestive tube, diabetics, hypertensive, overweight persons.

The functional bread obtained is a natural product, without preservatives, flavors or synthetic colorants. The bakery products present special sensorial qualities given by the pleasant aspect and specific flavor.

Due to the high content of fibers included in the malt mash flour, during the kneading it retains a greater quantity of water which makes the finished products to have a crispier peel by the evaporation of the water when it is baked.

We recommend the introducing of the dry malt mash in the peoples alimentation because by its composition it can have benefic effects on the

consumers like the following: it can prevent the increase of cholesterol favoring the elimination of the fat from the body, it can prevent the appearance of the coronary diseases, it can regulate and accelerate the intestine transit, it can prevent cancer, the gastro-intestinal diseases, the diabetes and the forming of gall bladder calculi.

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„UPS AND DOWNS” IN THE LOCAL IMPLEMENTATION OF NATIONAL PROGRAMS AND INTERVENTIONS FOR PROMOTING HEALTHY EATING AND PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN SCHOOLS AND KINDERGARTENS IN BIHOR COUNTY

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Abstract

Food represents a constant challenge and concern of health professionals, of those who work in the food field, of teachers and educators in schools and kindergartens, and of the decision-makers regarding the cross-sectoral collaboration for a better state of health of the population. Many diseases can be prevented or their onset may be delayed, through a few changes in lifestyle, consisting essentially of adopting a healthy diet, water consumption and promoting physical activity. The alignment of the Romanian legal framework with the European Union requirements led to the approval of the school nutrition programs in educational establishments, initially centered on the distribution of milk and bakery products (sub roll), subsequently adding the fruits (apple) and implementing educational measures to complete the distribution program. These programs have responded to a social need, promoting the consumption of dairy products, bakery products and fruits, ensuring a daily snack, for children and adolescents, but it also have disadvantages related to waste, the monotony of a snack and dysfunctions in the food distribution chain. Through the national program of evaluation, promotion of health and health education, some of the preschoolers and pupils have access to correct information, appropriate to the age and level of understanding regarding healthy nutrition, water consumption, benefits of physical activity, behaviors at risk for health, all being fundamental components for a healthy lifestyle.

The evaluation of the interventions for the implementation of the county action plans for healthy eating and physical activity in children and adolescents within the National Program of Evaluation, Promotion of Health and Health Education, has been successfully implemented in Bihor County (2014 – 2019).

Key words: public health, eating behavior, food, educational programmes

INTRODUCTION

Nutrition, a major component of the individual's health, has an impact on public health and on the level of socio-economic development of communities.

What „preschoolers and schoolers are eating in educational units” represents a constant challenge and concern for the health professionals and other professional categories: those who work in the food field, regarding

the marketing of quality and "safe" products for health, of the teachers in the education process and learning of the young generation, of the decision makers regarding the legislative framework that regulates healthy eating and the optimal conditions for serving meals in the educational establishments.

There is undeniable scientific evidence that a healthy diet, calorically and nutritionally balanced, is the basis of the harmonious growth and development of the human body, contributing to the well-being of the individual, in order to prevent many chronic diseases, that represent a major threat today. Thus: overfeeding, shows the growth of incidence of diseases such as diabetes, obesity, various tumors, cardiovascular diseases, with major impact on the health and well-being of the individual but also on the public budget. On the other hand, child malnutrition and anemia among children are another challenges facing the health system.

Many of these diseases can be prevented or their appearance may be delayed by some changes in lifestyle, consisting essentially in adopting a healthy diet, water consumption and promoting physical activity. Behavior regarding nutrition, water consumption and physical activity should be cultivated through education, as early as possible.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In order to improve feeding habits in children, Romania has adopted European models in accordance with the provisions of the European Union, (EU) Regulations of the European Parliament and of the Council amending the (EU) Regulations, regarding the aid scheme for the provision with fruits and vegetables, bananas and milk, of the educational institutions. The alignment of the Romanian legal framework with the EU requirements led to the approval of the *school nutrition programs* in educational establishments, initially centered on the distribution of milk and bakery products (sub roll), subsequently adding the fruits (apple) and implementing educational measures to complete the distribution program.

The last approved program is „Romanian Program for schools for 2017-2023” with the following components:

- a) distribution of fresh fruits and / or vegetables, natural milk and / or dairy products without the addition of powdered milk, bakery products;
- b) educational measures accompanying the distribution of products.

It was performed the global analysis of the school programs for the distribution of dairy products, bakery and fruits, developed in Bihor county, highlighting the positive and negative aspects in the implementation over time, as well as the implementation of Law no. 123/2008 for a healthy diet in pre-university education units.

A component, through which the state acts in the education for a healthy nutrition of children and young people in kindergartens and schools,

is the national program of evaluation, promotion of health and education for health. The program aims to promote the health and well-being of the students, the optimal functioning from a somatic, physiological, mental, emotional, social point of view and the formation of a healthy lifestyle. Thus, preschoolers and students have access to correct information, appropriate to the age and level of understanding, regarding healthy eating, water consumption, physical activity benefits, risk behaviors for health, all being fundamental components for a healthy lifestyle.

Since 2011, information-education-communication activities regarding healthy eating among children and adolescents in Romania have been carried out in Bihor County, by the staff of the Health Promotion Department from the Bihor Public Health Directorate and by other categories of trained persons for disseminating the specific correct messages, as: teachers, doctors and school nurses. All activities were targeting preschoolers, students and indirectly parents.

The activities proposed for the purpose of adopting healthy behaviors by children and adolescents, are aimed to:

- increase consumption of fruits and vegetables
- consume breakfast daily
- optimize / encourage water consumption
- increase involvement in physical activities at least 60 minutes / day

In Bihor County, this program is an integral part of the County Plan of Action (County Framework Plan for 2011 - 2015 „Increasing access to primary preventive services for children and adolescents” and the County Action Plan „Be active for health” for the period 2015 -2020) proposed by the Bihor Public Health Directorate, and assumed with the county partners: Bihor County School Inspectorate, Bihor County Council, Bihor County Association of Representative Parents Councils and Bihor County Sport and Youth Directorate.

The activities carried out by the teachers in schools, are extracurricular, optional and include a significant number of beneficiaries year by year. These are:

- theoretical activities: lessons, presentations, discussions, stories, watching video documentaries, movies, cartoons, poems, riddles, songs; meetings with doctors;

- practical activities: drawings, exhibitions, panels, posters, masks and objects from vegetables and fruits; preparation of a healthy breakfast; preparing salads from vegetables / fruits; visits to gardens / orchards, to the market;

- monitoring the behavior of children by using the monitoring files.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initially the program „Sub roll and milk”, represented an answer to a social, real and important need, having several dimensions:

- the need to supplement the nutritional deficiencies of children from families in severe poverty – „there are children for whom sub roll and milk are their first / only meal per day”; on the other hand, „there are children who do not consume milk at home because it is expensive.”

- the need to counteract certain eating behaviors with negative effects on the health of children: the habit of eating nothing in the morning; the habit of eating foods high in carbohydrates and / or fats; lack or insufficient percentage of dairy products in children's nutrition.

Positive aspects of the implementation of programs for dairy products, bakery products and fruit:

- promoting the consumption of dairy products and fruits

- providing a snack between breakfast and lunch for preschoolers and schoolchildren

- encouraging the consumption of fresh fruit – the program showed that most of the students who received an apple also consumed it

- universality and accessibility of programs through: *equity*, meaning that those who contribute to the financing of the program are not excluded, and by *avoiding the effects of discrimination*.

Negative aspects of the implementation of programs for dairy products, bakery products and fruit:

- the wastage generated by the behavior of the students who use the sub roll, milk and apple for a purpose other than the one dedicated to them: „*they fight with them*”; „*they throw them in the garbage or on the street*”; „*I take it home and give it to birds or dogs*”.

- the monotony of a snack that is the same every day - the children who throw the sub roll, the milk or the apple declare that they do it because they are bored to eat the same thing every day.

- the distribution of products, both in terms of transportation to school and in-school distribution: there are schools where daily delivery cannot be ensured; the lack of storage conditions or the effort to keep distribution costs as low as possible, generates a series of practices that affect the purpose of the program and the quality of the products; especially in the case of large schools, with over 1000 students, the distribution of these products is a problem, which requires time and effort every day and which often falls to teachers. There is a certain frustration between teachers who say they are „prepared to be teachers, not to distribute food products”.

The school feeding offers (canteen, school kiosk, catering) were regulated by Law no. 123/2008 for healthy eating in pre-university

education units, whereby all food suppliers in the educational establishments, have the obligation to comply with certain provisions regarding foods not recommended for preschoolers and schoolchildren, respectively the principles underlying a healthy nutrition for children and adolescents.

The educational units, through the changes of structure (reduction of personnel, frequent changes that they have undergone in time) were not worried nor encouraged to improve their quality and the sustainability of the services of serving meals in educational units, these being partially replaced by offers from commercial school kiosk or catering, with negative impact on the nutrition of children and young people, because uncontrolled menu, not respected meal schedule, poor quality of food products etc.

The evaluation of the interventions for the implementation of the county action plans for healthy eating and physical activity in children and adolescents within the National Program of Evaluation, Promotion of Health and Health Education, has been successfully implemented in Bihor County for 2014 - 2019 (Table 1).

The implementation of the educational program was favorable appreciated by teachers and other professional categories in the educational units, who were actively and voluntary involved in the implementation of the project. The informative-educational materials, as guides and worksheets, were considered: - "useful, important and well made"; positive appreciation of behavior monitoring records were also expressed, these being considered appropriate to the age and level of understanding of preschoolers / students.

Table 1

Indicators of interventions implementation of the county action plans for healthy eating and physical activity in children and adolescents in Bihor County for 2014 – 2019

School year	2014- 2015	2015- 2016	2016- 2017	2017- 2018	2018- 2019
Indicators					
Educational Units	69	73	83	110	90
urban/rural	31 / 38	39 / 34	45 / 38	51 / 59	49 / 41
Pre-schoolers	5074	5427	6094	7941	6359
Pupils	5930	7869	10756	14182	10872
IEC Activities	4173	8488	10313	13886	12650
Informed parents	11551	13065	17205	21853	18011
Teachers / other persons implicated	791 / 93	939 / 104	1118 / 172	1427 / 170	1299 / 140

1/3 of the students enrolled in the Bihor County education system participated in the activities, benefiting from the specific information.

The parents agreed to the participation of the preschoolers and the schoolchildren in the activities within the project and even more, they were gladly involved in some activities.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the positive and negative aspects of the school programs by the decision makers and the specialists / professionals could generate a series of corrective actions in their development.

The positive impact of informative - educational activities among preschoolers, pupils and parents has led to an increase in awareness of the role and importance of adopting and maintaining healthy behaviors.

The implementation of the strategy on the healthy nutrition of children and young people in kindergartens and schools in everyday life, requires a collective, cross-sectoral effort involving health specialists, staff from educational establishments, economic agents, parents, decision-makers – „actors” to provide healthy nutrition and support to children and adolescents.

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THE EFFECT OF CUTTING AT THE APPLE TREE CULTIVATED IN SUPER INTENSIVE SYSTEM REGARDING CROPS CULTIVATION AND FRUIT GROWING IN CHERESIG- BIHOR COUNTY GROWING CONDITIONS

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Abstract

In the ecological conditions in the Cheresig area were experienced several apple varieties, planted at distances of 4x3, 4x2 and 4x1 m, falling to hectare 833, 1250 respectively 2500 trees. The increase in thickness of the trunk compared to trees planted at 4x3 m is decreasing with 11-21% at trees planted at 4x2m, respectively 4x1m. Fruit production is superior at Romus 2 and H-3-11-41P variety, with 38-40% good results realizing also Prima and Florina varieties. The distances of plantation positively influence fruit production, increasing the number of trees from 833-1250 per hectare, increasing fruit harvest with 36-110%. Reduction of tree vigor and production increase while planting a larger number of trees per hectare makes possible the promotion in conditions from Cheresig of Florina, Prima, Romus 2 and H-3-11-41P, varieties in intensive and superintensive culture system with densities up to 2500 trees per hectare.

Kei words: apple varieties, increase in thickness of the trunk, distances of plantation, fruit production

INTRODUCTION

The promotion in that concerns the growing of some sorts that prove generic resistance to diseases, is an issue of actual importance on which depends the success of biological pomiculture and the production of competitive fruits. Meanwhile, the correct application of the other technological verges inside the ecologically founded agricultural system imposes the knowledge of the fruit – sorts reaction to these verges.

To this purpose, under the ecological conditions of Cheresig (medium multiannual temperature of 10,3 c and the annual precipitation sum of 635 mm) an experiment has been made in which, besides the disease resistance fruit – sort (besides a standard sort Jonagold) were tried tree planting distances according to the intensive and superintensive apple – growing system.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research sorts, Florina and Prima, alongside with Romus 2 and Romus 3 have joined the experiment when hybrids (later acknowledged as apple - sorts) as well as the Jonagold sort and the H – 3 – 11 – 41P hybrid have been engrafted on the M106 motherplant and planted in a brown soil with a clay content of 40%.

The planting distance were of 4m between rows and of 3, 2 and 1 in the row constituting as many variants with nutrition space given when planted.

The grown – like – form was freely flatamed and the soil has been planglied.

The fitosanitarian treatments consisted of those applied during the repaus, during vegetation only the insects being fought against.

The observation comprised both the tree growing and the fruit production.

RESULTS AND DISSCUSION

The growth in thickness of the tree is presented in Table No.1. On the basis of the medium data, one will notice in the table that the shorter planting distance reduce the vigour of a tree with 11 – 21% (as trees have been planted at distances of 2 and 1 m comparative to those planted at a 3 m distance).

These data allow us to state that no matter what the vigour of tree sorts and mother plants, by reducing the planting distance, the trees diminish their vigour with up to 34% in the case of Jonagold in what concerns the tree sort, the less vigorous is Romus 2 fact which justifies its planting at short distances.

The tree sorts Romus 2 and florin have a greater vigour, but this is not at a limit, which should exclude their planting at 2, respectively 1 m distance.

Tree fruit production presents in table No.2 gives us information about the productive potentiality of tree sorts and their behavior under these circumstances depending on their space at planting.

Regarding the second aspect (distances) we can notice a situation opposite the growing vigour in the sense that reducing the distance between trees on the row, the production grows on an average with the six tried tree sorts from 12,4 t/ha for the kinds with the trees planted at 4x3 m to 16,9 and 21,1 t/ha by simply reducing the distance on the row at 2 and 1 m. Romus 2 sort is the most productive one which goes over 23 and 27 t/ha when the trees were planted at 4x3 and 4x2 while at 4x1m distance the h – 3 – 11 – 41P is more productive, giving 47 t/ha. As it is normal, the Jonagold sort

gave the lowest production that is 8,8 t/ha without any treatments against diseases.

It is to be remarked the Florina tree sort, which reaches an average production of almost 20 t/ha on the tree distances of planting.

By planting a large number of trees, the production of this tree sort doubles and triples increasing from 8,3 t/ha for the kind with 833 trees to 17,2 t/ha for the kind with 1250 trees/ha and to 27,6 t/ha when 2500 trees/ha were planted.

CONCLUSIONS

The tree sorts and the hybrids with genetic resistance to diseases (*Venturia* and *Podosfera* species) analysed under the conditions of Cheresig and planted at distances of 4x3, 4x2, 4x1 have involved differently in respect of the vigour of trees and of the obtained production of fruits.

After eight years, the Romus 2 sort has not reached at covering the reserved place by the planting at 4x3 because of its reduced vigour, a fact that imposed it to be planted at smaller distances.

The production of fruits has enormously increased as more trees/ha have been planned, the production being of 12,4 t/ha for the sort with 833 trees, of 16,9 t/ha when 1250 trees/ha were planted. The weakest response was given by Romus 2 which has not offered a significant production according to the number of planted trees although is offered the best average crop of 26,4 t/ha on the trees planting distances on a row.

The Florina and Prima sorts gave an average production of 19,8 and 17,2 t/ha, which is over the average of tree – sorts or very close to it.

The results referring to the vigour of tree – sorts and to the production of fruits make us recommend their expansion in planting and the promotion of the superintensive system with planting of over 1560 trees/ha.

Taking into account the making of the fruits, the proportion will be more reduced for the summer and bigger for the Prima and florin sorts in autumn and winter.

These five sorts with genetic resistance to diseases may constitute the sort for future orchards, intensive and superintensive orchards in the biological pomiculture system.

The growth in thickness was much obvious at the trees with a bigger place of nutrition (4x3 m = 833 trees/ha) and it has been diminished with up to 21% as the place of nutrition was reduced by planting 1250 and 2500 trees/ha. According to the place of nutrition, the much vigorous sorts: Prima, Florina and Romus 2 have occupied it in the first four years since planting and they have been kept in the limits of distances reserved at planting by yearly cuttings.

Table .1

The growth in thickness of the trunk at some sorts and hybrids of apple depending on the place of nutrition reserved at planting

Nr. crt.	The apple sort (hybrid)	V1=4x3m=833 trees/ha		V2=4x2m=1250 trees/ha		V3=4x1m=2500 trees/ha		The average sort x distance	
		cm	%	cm	%	cm	%	cm	%
1.	Jonagold	42	111	34	100	28	93	35	103
2.	Florina	40	105	34	100	27	90	34	100
3.	Prima	40	105	36	106	31	103	36	106
4.	Romus 2	40	105	38	112	33	110	37	100
5.	Romus 3	31	82	27	79	30	100	29	85
6.	H - 3 - 11 - 41P	35	92	38	112	30	100	34	100
The Medium	cm	38	100	34	100	30	100	34	100
	%	100	-	80	-	79	-	-	-

DL	5%= 4,5	4,1	3,6	4,1
DL	1%= 6,9	6,2	5,5	6,2
DL	0,1%= 11,1	9,9	8,8	9,9

Table 2

The production of fruits at some sorts and hybrids of apple depending on the place of nutrition reserved at planting

Nr. crt.	The apple sort (hybrid)	V1		V2		V3		The average distance x sort, hybrid	
		4x3m – 833 trees/ha		4x2m – 1250 trees/ha		4x1m – 2500 trees/ha		T/ha	%
		T/ha	%	T/ha	%	T/ha	%		
1.	Jonagold	6.3	51	8.3	49	11.5	42	8.8	47
2.	Florina	8.3	67	17.2	102	27.6	106	19.8	105
3.	Prima	14.6	118	15.1	89	22.0	84	17.2	91
4.	Romus 2	23.4	189	27.2	16	28.7	110	26.4	140
5.	Romus 3	10.8	87	14.2	89	19.7	75	14.9	79
6.	H – 3 – 11 – 41P	11.4	92	19.3	117	47.2	181	25.9	138
The average sort x distance		12.4	100	16.9	100	26.1	100	18.8	100
The different of V1%			100	4.5	136	13.7	210	-	-

DL 5%= 1,5
DL 1%=2,2
DL 0,1%= 3,6

2,0
3,0
4,9

3,1
4,7
7,6

2,3
3,4
5,5

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STUDIES ON SOME PATHOLOGICAL ISSUES THAT APPEARED IN A FARM OF AMERICAN BISON

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Abstract

Bison is part of the bovine family, originally from Asia, which has reached both America and Europe. There are two subspecies - Bison (American prairie bison) and Bison Atabascae (Canadian forest bison). The European brother also had two subspecies, Bison Bonasus Caucasicus and Bison Bonasus Karpathicus.

Key words: bison, diseases, natality

INTRODUCTION

Bison growing is still a niche business in Romania. It does not require special halls and farm-type spaces, but it does require fenced pastures to ensure optimal living conditions and productive pasture management. The cost of such an investment depends on the number of animals and the area of pasture which will be surrounded by perimeter fences with wire mesh and professional electric fences.

Feeding of animals is done naturally in summer, by grazing in the ad libitum system, in winter by the administration of fan and minerals. Due to this mode of growth the nutritional value of the bison meat is higher. Bison are handled as little as possible, they are not domesticated, they spend their lives in the pasture without being locked up in a stable. Treatments and vaccinations are applied only in case of need. Bison is clearly a better choice with far less fat and calories, less cholesterol, but higher amounts of protein, iron and vitamin B12 than beef, pork and chicken.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The studies were conducted at Euro Buffalo Bison Farm in Salonta, Bihor County. The entire number of animals from the farm was studied, starting with the year of establishment of the farm (2012) until 2018, which at the present time numbered about 851 copies. The number of fetuses, dystocias, neonatal mortality, respectively occurrence of all episodes of animal diseases were studied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In 2012, the American bison farm began to be popularized by an import of 37 animal heads from Austria. In 2013, these animals were abducted, resulting in 25 offspring. The low birth rate of 36% was due to the accommodation and acclimatization of the mature specimens.

As a result, the number of American bison from the Salonta farm increases during 2013 from 37 cows imported in 2012, to 78 heads, to which we can add the young born in 2012. Also at the end of the year we count 38 calves from females imported from Poland and 25 calves from females imported in 2012.

In 2014 the females gave birth to 76 calves, of which 6 heads died, the cause of death being their crushing by adults.

Also in May, a number of 61 females from France and Belgium are purchased, these animals are 2 years old. Due to the reduced body development, it was decided to introduce them to the mountain.

In 2015, there were 87 born heads, a relatively small number of newborns, which is due to the still unfinished acclimatization process of American bison arriving from other parts of Europe.

In 2016, in March the calves begin to exist on the females existing on the farm, most of the calves run until the end of June, but late calves have been noticed from the point of view of the year (autumn and winter months).

This year resulted in 98 calves, of which about 18 were lost (chicks unborn at birth, or crushed by adult congeners).

Also this year, there is a purchase of 96 American bison from Bulgaria. Of these animals 75 survive, the remaining 21 heads die because of their poor maintenance, unsupported transport, or die after calving, their body being very weak. The surviving animals give birth soon (1-2 months) to viable and unviable products. In the deceased animals, a massive infestation of intestinal, pulmonary, hepatic, chronic pneumonia, with pulmonary lobes entering the stages of gray hepatization, peritonitis and traumatic pericarditis was found following the necropsies. Animals imported from Bulgaria have undergone parenteral de-parasitization and vitamin treatment.

Fig. 1. Presentation of the accumulation of sero-purulent fluid in the thoracic and intracardiac cavity

Fig. 2. Presentation of the areas of pulmonary sclerosis due to insufficient oxygenation of the lung

In 2017 we have a number of 131 calves born, of whom 121 survive, mortality due to the causes mentioned above.

The birth rate in 2018 is 78%, a percentage that is due to reproduction problems manifested by dystocia, followed by partial or total placental retention at a lot of American bison located on a common plot. This lot consisted of primeparous animals aged 2-2.5 years. The facade took place about two weeks before the deadline, the products being unviable or dying within a few hours postpartum. It was found that the process of product development did not end, manifested by the presence in the oral cavity of very soft teeth, the small size and weight of the products, the impossibility of performing the sucking act from the mother, to live made products.

CONCLUSIONS

As it is observed during the period studied, the bison generally did not have serious illnesses if they received adequate maintenance.

Major problems arose in 2016 at the group imported from Bulgaria due to the maintenance conditions of the animals in the farm of origin. In 2018, in the batch of primiparas following the laboratory analysis of the samples (dead fetus, portions of placenta, blood samples from the dead fetus and mother, vaginal secretions from females), the suspicion of infectious disease was excluded. Following the findings it was concluded that the females were introduced too early for breeding although they showed good body development. That is why we recommend that the females of American bison raised on farms be introduced to the herd only after the age of two, taking into account their health and their body development, respectively.

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MORPHOPRODUCTIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE POPULATION OF PHEASANT (PHASIANUS COLCHICUS COLCHICUS) FROM THE BIHOR COUNTY AREA

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Abstract

The study presents the partial results regarding the morphoprodutive properties of the birds of the order Galliformes, the genus Phasianus, the species Phasianus colchicus colchicus from the territory of Bihor county. The study was carried out in three private farms in Oradea, as well as in the territory of Bihor county, being analyzed 205 specimens from the population of pheasants, respectively 29 males and 176 females. The analyzed parameters refer to morpho-productive index: body weight in young female and male birds, weight in adult birds, food consumption in both young and adult birds, age of sexual maturity, numerical egg production and egg curve.

Key words: Morphological and production index, dynamics, body weight, pheasant males and females.

INTRODUCTION

The pheasant has its origins on the Asian continent. In Europe, it is widespread, both in the natural environment, in the hilly and valley areas, as well as in specialized farmers. In the western part of the country, namely in Bihor county, there are small populations of pheasants in the breeding poultry farms. Farmers appreciate the outstanding quality of the meat, which is sweet and juicy, as well as the value of these birds as exemplars of exhibition. At the same time the County Forestry Department has a number of farms in which young people are obtained for the continuous popularity of the forest areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The paper presents data collected from private breeders, namely: in farm C1, 64 heads (6 males and 58 females), farm C2, 82 heads (11 males and 71 females), farm C3.59 heads (8 males and 51 females). Birds of both sexes, at different ages (hatching, in juvenile age, reaching sexual maturity, during active reproduction period) were used as biological material.

The working materials and devices used are: digital technical and analytical scales, scrapers, Petri dishes and flat glass plates, small capacity incubators (50-200 eggs / series), portable ovoscope, camera, computer

equipped with computer software table, depending on the experimental method approached.

The results obtained were compared with the reference values in the literature (Sauveur B., 1988; Usturoi M. G., 1999; Vacaru-Opriş I. et al., 2002).

The data obtained experimentally were centralized and statistically processed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The birds from the studied populations are classified, from the age of one day and up to the age of 45 weeks, in the youth category, following to enter the breeding activity at 46 weeks of life.

In adults, the evolution of body weight has gone through a curve characterized by a slow growth.

The adult pheasants continued their growth reaching an average weight of 1381.9g at the age of 57 weeks, under the conditions in which the populations became very heterogeneous (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. – Dynamic of the body weight in the adult pheasant males

In females it has been reached a weight of 1002.8g / head at the end of the productive period (fig. 2). The values obtained were lower than in the literature (Vacaru-Opriş I, 2002). C2 for both sexes.

Fig. 2. – Dynamic of the body weight in the adult pheasant females

The earliest population was in farm C2, while the most recent birds were found in farm C3 (table 1).

Table1.

Age of sexual maturity onset in the 3 studied Pheasant population

Specification	C2	C3	C5	Average population
Age of laying the first egg (days)	318	323	320	320,3

CONCLUSIONS

The specimens of the population of *Phasianus colchicus colchicus*, existing in the private farms in Bihor County, were characterized by a higher growth rate in the first 10 weeks of life, increasing daily feed consumption but also achieving high values for food conversion.

The multiplication of the common pheasant herds in private breeders is uncertain because part of the existing herd is strictly controlled by the state farms that produce the biological material for the repopulation of the hunting fund.

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STUDY REGARDING THE USE OF MULBERRY LEAVES BY BOMBYX MORI - ZEFIR HYBRID

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Abstract

In order to assess how efficient is the use of Mulberry leaf by the Bombyx mori Zefir larvae hybrid, some determinations were made regarding the nutritional value and digestibility of the worm leaf administered as food (leaves from a Japanese variety, Kokuso 21), during a series of summer growth. The results showed that ongoing vegetation and growth process of this hybrid, the Mulberry leaves suffer an aging phenomenon, revealed by diminishing its chemical composition quality. According to this, most of the nutritional substances from Mulberry leaves, except cellulose, manifest a continuous decline during the growth period. The digestibility of these nutritional components registered a value of 55.22%, the raw energy value was 4216 kcal/kg dry substance, the digestive energy was 2103 kcal/kg (DS), while the metabolic energy was 1935-1959 kcal/kg (DS). The efficiency of converting ingestion into silk had a value of 10.33% and the digestion was 16.37%.

Key words: leaves, Mulberry, larvae, energy, use.

INTRODUCTION

Besides the continuous improvement of the growth technologies, one of the main concerns of the specialists in sericulture is represented by the production of biological material of high genetic value as the Bombyx mori larvae with an increasing productive potential, more resistant to the environmental factors and to diseases and to use nutrients offered by the Mulberry to the best of their advantage.

Thus, from this point of view, the performances of the used larvae in intensive breeding systems have greatly increased, but at the same time, in order for them to be able to reach their full potential, it is necessary to improve all the factors involved in the breeding process. From the multitude of factors that directly influence the growth process of the larvae and the economic results obtained, it is encountered also nutrition.

The quantity and especially the quality of the worm leaf used in feeding of larvae, directly influence the growth rate, their health and vitality, but also the quantitative and qualitative production of silk. In turn, the quality of the leaf is also influenced by many factors related to the

pedoclimatic conditions, season, variety of the mulberry, the way of harvesting and storage etc.

The knowledge of the nutritional value and of the influence factors, as well as the way in which *Bombyx mori* larvae are harnessed to kill the nutrients in the wormwood, has attracted the attention of a significant number of researchers.

At the end of the last century, Romania could be considered an important point on the map of European sericulture. Thus, in her record, Romania can boast in this field with a quite complex literature, as well as with the creation of new varieties and valuable hybrids of worm, as *Bombyx mori*, all being the result of some decade research work of Romanian specialists (*Dolis M., 2008; Lazăr S. and Vornicu O.C., 2013; Pătruică S., 2013*).

For this reason, we consider appropriate to bring a modest contribution to the study of using the mulberry leaf, derived from indigenous varieties, by larvae of breeds or hybrids created in Romania.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research was done during the growth period of the silkworm larvae from summer series, the biologic material being represented both by silkworm larvae and mulberry leaves which were administrated.

The animal biologic material was the Romanian simple hybrid of silkworm *Zefir*.

The vegetal biologic material used in the research was represented by *Kokuso 21* a mulberry variety which derives from the crossing between *Naganua*, *Gariin* and *Shiso* varieties. It is a variety of Japanese origin with whole leaf which has adapted fairly well to the climatic conditions from the south of Romania. In plantations of the intensive type may be produced from the first years a high quantity of leaves with a high protein content.

Working methods aimed to determine the nutritive value of the mulberry leaves taking into account the chemical composition and the digestibility of its components.

The chemical composition was determined using the „Proximate Analysis” scheme and the digestibility (approximate digestibility) through „*in vivo*” method- simple digestibility with a single period control (<http://www.fao.org>).

The chemical analyses were done on samples previously dried to 65°C and grinded. The obtained results were processed and noted in tables being expressed in both fresh and dried leaves (*Halga P. et al., 2005*). The collected samples moisture determination was done by drying them into the hot air oven for 4-5 hours at 105°C (*Regulation (EC) no. 152/2009 SR ISO 6496:2001*).

The ashes content was determined using the incineration of the samples method (*Regulation (EC) no. 152/2009 SR EN ISO 2171: 2010*).

To determine the protein content (CP), the Kjeldhal method was used (*Regulation (EC) no. 152/2009 SR EN ISO 5983-2: 2009 AOAC 2001.11*).

The fat content (EE) was determined using Soxhlet method; its principle is based on the fat property of dissolving in the organic solvent (such as, petroleum ether) (*Regulation (EC) no. 152/2009 SR ISO 6492: 2001*).

The crude fiber (CF) was determined by the sample acid-basic hydrolyze, after which from the leaf is removed the hydrolysable part, on the filter paper remaining only the cellulose and minerals; by calcination are determined the minerals and the crude cellulose is calculated through difference (*Regulation (EC) no. 152/2009 SR EN ISO 6865: 2002*).

Nitrogen free extract was calculated through difference from fresh leaf or dried one. In the first case, from 100 were decreased the percentages of water, protein, fat, cellulose and ashes. In the second case, from the dry matter percentage were decreased the percentages of crude protein, extract etherate, crude fiber and ash.

In order to determine the nutritive matter digestibility from mulberry leaves which were administered in silk larvae feeding, it was respected the digestibility principle “in vivo”, with a single control period. There were calculated the digestibility coefficients ($DC\% = \frac{\text{Digest}}{\text{Intake}} \times 100$).

Based on the quantity of administered leaves, the leftover waste, excrete and on the data obtained from chemical analyses firstly, were found out the intake nutrients or ingest (the difference between administered quantities and the ones leftover) and finally the intake of the nutritive substances or digest (difference between ingest and faeces). Expressing in percentage the digest from ingest, were obtained the digestibility coefficients, which shows how much from the leaves nutrients are digested into the digestive system of the larvae.

Based on the digestible coefficients, there was calculated the digestible content for each nutrient it represents the result between the crude chemical content and the digestible coefficient which was divided to 100.

The obtained values were summed obtaining in the end the total digestible nutrients (TDN) from the mulberry leaves. The fat content was multiplied with 2.25 because it is considered that the fat has 2.25 times more energy than the others intake nutrients.

Also, because the nutritive value was expressed in TDN/kg, and the calculated values were reported to 100 g, it was multiplied with 10.

For energy value, The working methods used were mainly the specific ones used to determine the raw energy (use of specific computation

equations and regression coefficients recommended by the OKIT system), digestible (calculation equation recommended for monogastric species) and metabolizable (equations recommended for monogastric animals and birds) contained (Halga P. et al., 2005).

The efficiency of the use of nutrients in the worm leaf by the larvae was expressed by the amount of ingested/digested dry matter required for increasing 1 gram of body mass/weight (silk wrap), respectively by the efficiency of conversion of ingested substances (ECI%)/digested (ECD%) in body mass/weight (Matei A., 1995; Rahmathulla V.K. et al., 2002; Sarkar A., 1993).

The main experimental data obtained were statistically processed being calculated the arithmetic average, variance, the average standard deviation and the variability coefficient coefficient (Sandu, 1995; Cucu et al., 2004; Maciuc et al., 2015).

During the silkworm larvae growth, the research objective was to establish the nutritive values of the mulberry leaves depending on its maturity and silkworm larvae age, respectively. This was accomplished through digestibility trials.

There were organized an experimental lot formed from 150 larvae, which were grouped in three repetitions of 50 larvae each. In the calculations during the research were used the average values obtained in all three repetitions, the data being extrapolated to all 50 silkworm larvae.

In each repetition were used trays with paper sized accordingly with the larvae's age and size.

To each repetition had been administered the same quantity of mulberry leaves from which previously were collected samples for chemical analyses.

Daily and at the same time from each repartition were collected, weighted and registered the leftover mulberry leaves and the excreta.

The number of leftovers mulberry leaves from each repetition were summed, the result being than divided to 3, obtaining the average quantity of leftover leaves from the 50 larvae; the value being representative for the entire lot. This value was used to calculate the digestibility coefficients of the nutrients from mulberry leaves. Similarly, was done in the case of the excreta.

From each repetition were collected samples of leftover, excreta respectively, which were homogenized in order to obtain an average sample for each lot; those samples were chemically analyzed.

Also, there were organized three reserve repetition with 50 larvae raised separately, but under the same conditions.

During the experiment was watched the larval mortality from each lot and if necessary the dead larvae were immediately replaced with ones from reserve lot.

Also, the groups were weighed at the beginning of growth (after hatching) and at the end (before budding), the difference between the two weights, divided by the number of larvae in each group, representing the increase in body mass accumulated by a larva.

From the separated lot were extracted 10 larvae, whose content was determined in dry matter; thus, multiplying the average dry substance content of larvae, calculated from the separated lots, with the increasing body mass of the larvae in the experimental lots, it was determined the average increasing of body mass of a larva.

After gobbling, 15 cocoons were harvested, from which the silk wrapper was separated, weighed and its dry matter content determined, thus obtaining the average dry wool content of the silk wrapper.

The larvae growth was held during 31st of July and 31st of August, respecting the breeding technology recommended by the specific literature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The values regarding the mulberry leaves chemical composition evolution throughout growth period of the silkworm larvae were centralized and statistically processed (table 1).

The average values obtained for each nutrient separately are set in the limits presented by specific literature, where the data regarding the crude chemical composition of the mulberry leaves varies according to each author, to the research period, to the varieties of mulberry, etc.

Table 1

The chemical composition evolution of the Kokuso 21 variety mulberry tree leaves during the silkworm larvae growth (%)

The larvae age	Water	DM	CP		EE		CF		NFE		Ash	
			F*	DM**	F*	DM**	F*	DM**	F*	DM**	F*	DM**
I	72.09	27.91	6.31	22.61	0.79	2.83	4.74	16.98	12.33	44.18	3.74	13.40
II	71.66	28.34	6.28	22.16	0.88	3.11	4.88	17.22	12.34	43.54	3.96	13.97
III	70.31	29.59	6.23	21.05	1.14	3.85	5.31	17.95	12.64	42.72	4.27	14.43
IV	70.13	29.87	6.04	20.22	1.16	3.88	5.44	18.21	13.09	43.83	4.14	13.86
V	68.86	31.14	6.15	19.75	1.25	4.01	5.93	19.04	13.41	43.07	4.40	14.13
$\bar{X}$	70.63	29.37	6.20	21.16	1.04	3.54	5.26	17.88	12.77	43.46	4.10	13.96
$S_{\bar{X}}$	-	0.575	-	0.547	-	0.237	-	0.368	-	0.261	-	0.169
Cv%	-	4.381	-	5.782	-	14.975	-	4.599	-	1.342	-	2.713
Min	-	27.91	-	19.75	-	2.83	-	16.98	-	42.72	-	13.40
Max	-	31.14	-	22.61	-	4.01	-	19.04	-	44.18	-	14.43

* fresh leaves; ** dry matter

The average relative humidity of the mulberry leaves during the research was 70.63%, and a decreasing evolution being registered average values between 72.09% (at the first determination corresponding to the first age of the silkworm larvae) and 68.86% (to the last determination when the silkworm larvae are in the age Vth). The dry matter represented $29.37 \pm 0.575\%$.

The mulberry leaves humidity influences its consumption by the silkworm larvae. The larvae, especially in the early stages of life, prefers young leaves with a high percentage of water. In the data presented by different authors, the average humidity of the mulberry leaves varies between 65-75% (*Doliş M., 2008*).

Compared with the common Mulberry (69.80-73%), the selected varieties have more water content (*Bura M. et al., 1995*). The dried substance from the worm leaf, harvested in the same period, can record, depending on the variety/hybrid, different values, for example, between 23.61% and 27.56% (*Matei A., 1995*).

Also, if the spring moisture of the mulberry leaf is 71.85-77.81%, then it decreases to 68.42-75.64%, in the summer period, respectively to 64.10-73.64%, in the fall (*Ifrim S., 1998*).

The crude protein had an average value of 6.20% ($21.16 \pm 0.547\%$ from DM). It is noticed a progressive decreasing of the protein content throughout the studied period, the content decreasing being with 2.86 percentage points, from 22.61% to 19.75%, respectively.

The protein content in the mulberry leaves may be considered a real indicator of the leaf's quality. The protein intake from mulberry leaves strongly influences both the silkworm larvae growth and development and, especially, the silk production of the larvae.

The raw leaf protein is estimated to have an average value of 6.16% in the fresh leaf, 20.97% in the dry substance and 24.36% in its organic substance (*Doliş M., 2008*). The raw leaf protein values can vary depending on the season, the time of day, the variety/hybrid of the dude: 32.40% in spring, 28.21% in summer and 24.53% in autumn (*Borcescu A., 1966*), 26.80% in the morning and 29.10% in the evening (*Mărghitaş L. A., 1995*), between 22.55% and 25.73% depending on the variety (*Matei A., 1995*).

The fat content from the mulberry leaves was in average 1.04% in the fresh leaves, and $3.54 \pm 0.237\%$ in DM. It is the only nutrient with a high variability, of 14.975%.

The fat content increased uniformly throughout the silkworm larval growth, from 0.79% to 1.25% when it was expressed in fresh leaves, or 2.83% to 4.01% respectively, when it was reported to the dry matter.

The limits presented by specific literature regarding the fat content in mulberry leaves are 2.85-6.07% (*Pop E.C., 1967*).

The crude cellulose was in average 5.26% in fresh leaves, $17.88 \pm 0.368\%$, respectively when in was reported to DM. Throughout the research, for a month, the crude cellulose increased with 2.06 percentage points, from 16.98% to 19.04%, respectively.

The cellulose is highly responsible for aging processes of the mulberry leaves. As the cellulose content grows, the leaf becomes tougher and rougher, being more difficult to be consumed by the silkworm larvae.

For this reason, in the silkworm larvae's growth are considered the most valuable mulberry varieties, the ones that have a lower cellulose content.

The values obtained for crude cellulose from mulberry leaves were comparable with the ones from specific literature. The crude cellulose quota varies between 12.33-14.38% to the common mulberry tree and between 10.43-13.70% to different selected varieties (*Craiciu E., 1966*). Throughout the mulberry vegetation period, the cellulose content from leaves increase from 14.47 to 21.16% (*Pop E.C., 1967*).

Nitrogen free extract represented in average $43.46 \pm 0.261\%$ from the dry matter of the mulberry leaves; the average values decreased from the first determination to the third, from 44.18% to 42.72%, then was an increasing to the fourth determination, being 43.83%, decreasing to the last analyses to 43.07%.

The ash represented in average 4.10% in the fresh leaves and $13.96 \pm 0.169\%$ from dry matter.

The minerals from the mulberry leaves throughout the research registered a continuous increase from analyze to another. The average values varied from 3.74% to 4.40% to fresh leaves and from 13.40% to 14.13% from dry matter. An exception was registered to the third determination which had a higher value than the fourth one.

The increasing in mineral content from mulberry leaves throughout the research was 0.90%.

The obtained data regarding the mineral content are in conformity with the ones from specific literature, 9.13-17.38% (*Pop E.C., 1967*), 11.52-12.80% (*Matei A., 1995*) and 8.7 - 13.15% (*Bura M. et al., 1995*).

Knowing the raw chemical composition of the mulberry leaf, using the specific calculation equations, it was possible to assess the nutritional value of the mulberry leaf based on its content of raw energy, which was, on average, over the entire studied period, of 1238 Kcal/kg, in fresh leaf, respectively 4216 Kcal/kg, in the dry matter (table 2).

Table 2

Raw average energy of Mulberry leaf

Specification	%		Caloric equivalent	Kcal/100g		Kcal/100g	
	*	**		*	**	*	**
CP	6.20	21.16	5.72	35.46	121.04	354.6	1210.4
EE	1.04	3.54	9.50	9.88	33.63	98.8	336.3
CF	5.26	17.88	4.79	25.20	85.65	252.0	856.5
NEF	12.77	43.46	4.17	53.25	181.23	532.5	1812.3
						1238	4216

By recording the quantities of the worm leaf administered, the non-consumed and excreted residues and also determining their chemical composition (table 3), its digestibility coefficients could subsequently be calculated (table 4) and also the content of digestible substances in the leaf (table 5).

Table 3

Data needed to calculate digestibility coefficients

The larvae age	Specification	Quantity (g)	Chemical composition (%/g)					Ash
			DM	CP	EE	CF	NEF	
I	Frunză	15.5	27.91	6.31	0.79	4.74	12.33	3.74
	Resturi	5.01	66.9	14.32	1.99	14.62	27.04	8.93
	Excretă	0.16	67.96	20.69	8.78	1.39	28.11	8.99
II	Frunză	26	28.34	6.28	0.88	4.88	12.34	3.96
	Resturi	8.78	60.51	13.61	1.92	13.97	21.03	9.98
	Excretă	0.79	65.95	14.08	3.71	5.21	29.98	12.97
III	Frunză	77	29.59	6.23	1.14	5.31	12.64	4.27
	Resturi	24.01	61.73	8.75	3.22	15.97	25.01	8.78
	Excretă	3.91	66.56	17.99	1.41	5.82	26.01	15.33
IV	Frunză	242	29.87	6.04	1.16	5.44	13.09	4.14
	Resturi	68.17	59.06	11.61	1.66	15.22	23.88	6.69
	Excretă	20.31	62.28	12.88	3.08	11.56	26.64	8.12
V	Frunză	1000	31.14	6.15	1.25	5.93	13.41	4.4
	Resturi	269.41	58.87	12.16	1.88	14.67	25.03	5.13
	Excretă	120.41	59.63	9.03	3.81	12.92	24.99	8.88

Following the complex phenomenon of digestion, nutrients are transformed into simple substances, which can thus be absorbed through the epithelium of the digestive tract, at different levels, thus being retained in the organism of silk larvae, representing practically the difference between the amount of substances ingested through food and the amount of appropriate substances found in droppings. Because not all the substances found in excrement are of dietary origin, some of them are of endogenous

origin, which can be obtained by this difference, indicating only apparent digestibility. If you admit the fact that at *Bombyx mori* excretions are also found in their excrement, which complicates the establishment of the digestibility of nutrients in the wormwood even more accurately, the use of the approximate digestibility term seems to be more correct (Miranda J.E. and Takahashi R., 1998; Rahmathulla V.K. et al., 2004; Rath S.S. et al., 2003; Sabhat A. et al., 2011; Tzenov P., 1993).

During the whole period studied, the digestibility of the dried substance from the worm leaf had a digestibility of 55.22%. The highest digestibility was recorded in larvae of age I (88.84%), after which, by the end of the larval period, there was a decrease of 35.83 percent.

Table 4

Digestibility coefficients of *Zefir* hybrid

The larvae age	Specification	DM	CP	EE	CF	NEF
I	Leaves	4.3261	0.9781	0.1225	0.7347	1.9112
	Leftovers	3.3517	0.7174	0.0997	0.7325	1.3547
	Ingest	0.9744	0.2607	0.0228	0.0022	0.5565
	Excreta	0.1087	0.0331	0.014	0.0022	0.045
	Digest	0.8657	0.2276	0.0088	0.0000	0.5115
	DC%	88.84	87.30	38.60	0.00	91.91
II	Leaves	7.3684	1.6328	0.2288	1.2688	3.2084
	Leftovers	5.3128	1.195	0.1686	1.2266	1.8464
	Ingest	2.0556	0.4378	0.0602	0.0422	1.3620
	Excreta	0.521	0.1112	0.0293	0.0412	0.2368
	Digest	1.5346	0.3266	0.0309	0.0010	1.1252
	DC%	74.65	74.60	51.33	2.37	82.61
III	Leaves	22.7843	4.7971	0.8778	4.0887	9.7328
	Leftovers	14.8214	2.1009	0.7731	3.8344	6.0049
	Ingest	7.9629	2.6962	0.1047	0.2543	3.7279
	Excreta	2.6025	0.7034	0.0551	0.2276	1.017
	Digest	5.3604	1.9928	0.0496	0.0267	2.7109
	DC%	67.32	73.91	47.37	10.50	72.72
IV	Leaves	72.2854	14.6168	2.8072	13.1648	31.6778
	Leftovers	40.2612	7.9145	1.1316	10.3755	16.279
	Ingest	32.0242	6.7023	1.6756	2.7893	15.3988
	Excreta	12.6491	2.6159	0.6255	2.3478	5.4106
	Digest	19.3751	4.0864	1.0501	0.4415	9.9882
	DC%	60.50	60.97	62.67	15.83	64.86
V	Leaves	311.4000	61.5000	12.5000	59.3000	134.1000
	Leftovers	158.6017	32.7603	5.0649	39.5224	67.4333
	Ingest	152.7983	28.7397	7.4351	19.7776	66.6667
	Excreta	71.8005	10.8730	4.5876	15.5570	30.0905
	Digest	80.9978	17.8667	2.8475	4.2206	36.5762
	DC%	53.01	62.17	38.30	21.34	54.86
I-V	Leaves	418.1642	83.5248	16.5363	78.557	180.6302
	Leftovers	222.3488	44.6881	7.2379	55.6914	92.9183
	Ingest	195.8154	38.8367	9.2984	22.8656	87.7119
	Excreta	87.6818	14.3366	5.3115	18.1758	36.7999
	Digest	108.1336	24.5001	3.9869	4.6898	50.9120
	DC%	55.22	63.08	42.88	20.51	58.04

In the specialty literature, the main explanation for reducing the digestibility of nutrients from the worm leaf as a whole, during the growth period of the silk larvae, would be as seen from the data in table 1, precisely the qualitative degradation of the leaf, in terms of chemical composition. Digestibility of the dry substance from the worm leaf decreases from 71.07% in age I, to 39.99% (for male larvae), 48.26% (for female larvae) in age V (Rath S.S. *et al.*, 2003). The worm leaf administered to the larvae of the fifth age has an approximate digestibility between 27.99% and 32.44% (Rahmathulla V.K. *et al.*, 2002).

The raw protein had a digestibility coefficient for the entire studied period of 63.08%. The raw protein digestibility decreased progressively during the studied period, with 25.13%, respectively from 87.30%, in the first larval age, to 62.17%, in the last one.

The high digestibility of age I could be explained by the rich content in amides, simple nitrogenous substances, which are found in the young leaf and which are digested much easier than the protein nitrogenous substances, which have the weight in the old leaf.

In the specialty literature, for raw leaf protein, the value of digestibility coefficients is between 69.21% and 78.92% (Borcescu A., 1966), 60.06% and 74.69% (Petkov N., 1980), 71.62% and 93.48% (Matei A., 1995).

The raw fat from the worm leaf had the minimum digestibility value of 38.30%, in the larvae of the fifth age and maximum of 62.67%, in the larvae of the fourth age.

The results of the digestibility tests regarding the raw fat in the worm leaf are generally inconclusive, as many of these can come from the intestine of the larvae and not from the leaf, which is why, we cannot speak of a determination of the digestibility of the fat itself but of the "ethereal extract", which also contains very large quantities of pigments. Thus, the big differences regarding the evolution of the digestibility of the raw fat during the studied period could be explained.

The limits presented by specific literature regarding the fat content in mulberry leaves are 2.85-6.07% (Pop E.C., 1967). The values of the digestibility coefficient for raw fat are between 63.28% and 74.19% (Petkov N., 1980).

During the whole larval period, the digestibility of the raw cellulose from the mulberry leaf was 20.51%, being null in age I, after which it increased progressively, reaching the end of the period studied up to the value of 21.34%. This increase in the digestibility of raw cellulose, as the larvae grow older, is in line with the development of the enzymatic equipment in their digestive tract. Thus, if at age I, in the digestive tract of

the larvae, the enzymes involved in the process of cellulose digestion are as non-existent, then they gradually increase, reaching the peak at age V, at which point the weight of raw cellulose from the worm leaf it is also bigger. This aspect, however, negatively influences the digestibility of the raw leaf protein, which during the same period, is experiencing a reduction.

At the beginning of the last century, some authors (*Acqua, 1930 – cited by Dolis M., 2008*) found that the leaf cellulose passes undigested through the digestive tract of the larvae and later it was concluded that this substance has a digestibility of approx. 20% (*Legay, 1955 - cited by Dolis M., 2008*). Recently, some authors state that in the first two ages, raw cellulose would not be digested, but only from the third (8%), its digestibility reaches 21.13% in the third period (*Matei A., 1995*).

Unclaimed extractive substances from the worm leaf had a digestibility over the entire studied period of 58.04%, the digestibility coefficients registering decreasing values, from 91.91%, in the case of the larvae of age I, at 54.86%, in the case of those of fifth age.

According to Matei, 1995, for the extracts not recorded from the leaf of the worm, the digestibility coefficients for the whole larval period record average values between 63.40% and 94.97%.

From the data in table 3 it can be observed that the digestibility of the nutrients of the worm leaf showed a medium variability for dry matter, raw protein and high for raw fat and raw cellulose.

Knowing the value of digestibility coefficients, it was possible to calculate the digestible content for each nutrient separately, then the content of digestible substances in the leaf, so when the report was made to the fresh leaf, 134.05 g of Total Digestive Substance/kg were obtained, and when the report was made on the dried substance from the leaf of the mulberry, its nutritional value was 456.54 g TDS/kg (table 5).

The determination of the digestible energy content of the worm leaf administered in the feed of silk larvae was made based on the relative digestible content of the nutrients contained in it, using the calorific equivalents recommended for monogastric animal species (table 6). In the case of the fresh leaf, the digestible energy content was 617.50 Kcal/kg, and in the case of the dry substance, 2102.75 Kcal/kg.

The calculation of the metabolic energy from the worm leaf administered in the feed of silk larvae was done by multiplying the digestible content of each nutrient with the energy equivalents recommended for monogastric (pig) animal species. Considering, however, the specificity of the silkworm's digestion, respectively the similarity with the digestion of the birds, for the estimation of the metabolic energy from the worm leaf, the energetic equivalents recommended for the birds were used (table 7).

Table 5

The nutritional value calculation of the mulberry leaves (g TDN/kg)

Specification	Raw chemical composition %		Digestibility coefficients	Digestive content %		G Total Digestive substance /kg	
	*	**		*	**	*	**
CP	6.20	21.16	63.08	3.91	13.35	39.11	133.48
EE	1.04	3.54	42.88	0.45	1.52	10.03	34.15
CF	5.26	17.88	20.51	1.08	3.67	10.79	36.67
NEF	12.77	43.46	58.04	7.41	25.22	74.12	252.24
Total						134.05	456.54

* Reported to the fresh leaves; ** reported to DM

Table 6

Digestive energy of Mulberry leaf

Specification	Digestive content %		Caloric equivalent (Kcal/g)	Kcal/kg	
	*	**		*	**
CP	3.91	13.35	5.78	226.00	771.63
EE	0.45	1.52	9.42	42.39	143.18
CF	1.08	3.67	4.40	47.52	161.48
NEF	7.41	25.22	4.07	301.59	1026.45
Total				617.50	2102.75

* Reported to the fresh leaves; ** reported to DM

Table 7

Metabolic energy of Mulberry leaf

Specification	Digestive content %		Caloric equivalent (Kcal/g)		Kcal/kg			
	*	**			*		**	
			swine	birds	swine	birds	swine	birds
CP	3.91	13.35	5.01	4.26	195.89	166.57	668.84	568.71
EE	0.45	1.52	8.93	9.50	40.19	42.75	135.74	144.40
CF	1.08	3.67	3.44	4.23	37.15	45.68	126.25	155.24
NEF	7.41	25.22	4.08	4.23	302.33	313.44	1028.98	1066.81
Total					575.56	568.44	1959.80	1935.16

* Reported to the fresh leaves; ** reported to DM

The average content in metabolic energy from the fresh mulberry leaf was 575.56 Kcal/kg, when the recommended energy ratios for pigs were used, respectively 568.44 Kcal/kg, when the recommended coefficients for birds were used. In relation to the dry matter of the leaf, the content in metabolic energy was on average 1959.80 Kcal/kg, when the recommended energy coefficients for pigs were used, and 1935.16 Kcal/kg, when the recommended coefficients for birds were used.

In order to determine the efficiency of use of the nutrients in worm leaf by the silk larvae, except for the intake and digestion, which were calculated during the course of the digestibility tests, it was necessary to

determine the average growth rate of the larvae and the mass of the silk shell. The data necessary for calculating the efficiency of the use of the worm leaf by the larvae, as well as the results obtained in this respect, were centralized in table 8.

Table 8

Efficiency of using Mulberry leaf by *Bombix mori* Zefir larvae hybrid

Average body mass gained during the whole larvae stage (g)	Living larvae	5.089
	Dry matter	0.921
Silky shell mass (g Dry Matter)		0.401
Dry Matter of ingested leaf (g)		3.884
Dry Matter of digested leaf (g)		2.450
Ingested Dry Matter/Body mass Dry Matter (g)		4.217
Dry matter ingested/ Body mass Dry Matter (g)		2.660
Dry matter ingested/Silky shell Dry Matter (g)		9.685
Dry matter digested/ Silky shell Dry Matter (g)		6.110
CEI body mass %		23.71
CED body mass %		37.59
CEI silky shell %		10.33
CED silky shell %		16.37

From the data of this table it is observed that in the case of the *Bombyx mori* Zefir larvae hybrid, for every gram of silk wrap is required 9.69 grams of dry matter ingested from the wormwood, respectively 6.11 grams of digested dry matter, resulting in an efficiency of conversion of silk intake (CEI) of 10.33%, respectively of digestion (CED) of 16.37%

The data obtained from the experience performed, regarding the efficiency of the use of the mulberry leaf by the larvae of *Bombyx mori*, are comparable with those presented in the literature (Matei A., 1995; Rahmathulla V.K. et al., 2002; Rath S.S. et al., 2003; Sarkar A., 1993; Tzenov P., 1993).

CONCLUSIONS

From those mentioned in the paper, the following conclusion may be drawn:

- Expressed to dry matter from the mulberry leaves, Kokuso 21 variety the average values were: CP – 21.16%, EE – 3.54%, CF – 17.88%, NEF – 43.42% and ash – 13.96%.

- At once with vegetation advancement and implicitly during each growth period of silkworm larvae, the mulberry leaf ages and its quality from the chemical composition point of view is decreasing. During the 30 days of the research, was noticed a decreasing of the moisture with 3.23% and of the CP with 2.86% and in the same time an increasing of the CF with 2.06%.

- During the whole period studied, the digestibility of the dried substance from the worm leaf had a digestibility of 55.22%. The dry matter digestibility decreased with 35.83%.

- Digestibility coefficients of the CP (63.08%) and of the NFE (58.04%) from the mulberry leaves decreased during the study with 25.13% and 37.05%, respectively.

- The CF digestibility, null at the beginning, increased progressively till the fifth larval stage when it was 21.34%.

- Nutritional value of the mulberry leaves was 456.54 g TDN/ kg DM.

- Throughout the studied period, the gross enrichment of the worm leaf was on average 4216 Kcal/kg, in the dry substance

- In the leaf, the content of digestible energy was, in the case of dry matter, 2102.75 Kcal/kg.

In relation to the dry matter of the leaf, the content in metabolic energy was on average 1935.16 – 1959.80 Kcal/kg.

In the case of the Zefir hybrid, for each gram of silk wrap, 9.69 grams of dry matter ingested from the mulberry tree are required, respectively 6.11 grams of digested dry substance, resulting an efficiency of conversion of ingestion (CEI) into silk of 10.33%, respectively of the digestion (CEI) of 16.37%

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GENOMIC SELECTION IN LIVESTOCK IMPROVEMENT – A BRIEF OVERVIEW OF DAIRY CATTLE

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Abstract

Many countries use molecular tools and genomic selection in breeding programmes to reach rapid rates of genetic gains, especially in dairy cattle in developed countries. This paper provides a brief overview on genomic selection in dairy cattle. Some aspects related the status of genomic selection application in livestock improvement are showed. Following the examples provided by other countries, genomic selection should be considered for animal breeding improvement strategies in Romania too.

Key words: dairy cattle, genomic selection, genomic prediction, selection indices.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing number of the world’s population result in a higher food demand, especially meat and dairy products, so that animal production had to face a significantly increment. Advances in genetics and the use of modern genetic tools in breeding programmes led to a rapid genetic progress towards the development and highly specialized breeds related to the production traits (Woelders et. al., 2006). The breeding programmes need to be adapted to the actual status of progress registered in the genetic area. The objectives of livestock production should consider a better characterization of population and various breeds, for implementing of suitable livestock breeding and improvement programmes (Hoffmann et. al., 2010). Breeds characterization at phenotypes level and their interaction with production systems and at genetic level is essential. Anyway, the available information related to the genetic traits of each breed still need to be approached. Characterization of the population and individual genetics, next to the further development of livestock breeding and improvement programmes is a critical element (FAO, 2011). Traditional selection stands

for recording lots of cows across many farms, opposite to genomic selection, targeting more detailed information from cooperating farms, so that such similar strategies could be useful in less developed countries (Cole, VanRaden, 2017).

Genomic technologies use DNA information on a large scale to predict the performance potential of cattle and also concur to efficient herd management to increase productivity, genetic improvement, health and welfare, shortening the generation interval (Hart, 2017). Breeding indices are important tools in modern dairy cattle breeding, providing a way to combine information related many traits into a single value, for ranking animals and making breeding decisions (Cole, VanRaden, 2017). Genomic selection help farmers to select animals for the next generation of replacements within the herd rather than relying on phenotypic assessment alone, facilitating an earlier identification of the elite animals within the herd (Hart, 2017).

The information from animal pedigree next to genetic markers increase the reliability of genomic estimated breeding values (GEBV) (Hart, 2017). The reasonable cost of genomic evaluation compared to those of embryo transfer, multiple ovulation, or sexed semen technologies, stands for applying both methods to enhance both profit and genetic gains (Hart, 2017). The ideal breeding objective for dairy cattle is still a popular topic, and also there is no single selection objective to be considered best for all populations or all herds within a population (Cole, VanRaden, 2017). Overall, genomic selection facilitate a better selection of animals for herd and also a better accuracy in breeding pair selection (Hart, 2017).

Thus, the present paper provides an overview on genomic selection use in dairy cattle, highlighting at the same time the perspectives and the priorities for considering such methods for breeding and improvement programmes in Romania.

SELECTION INDICES AND TRAITS

The use of a selection index is to improve one or more traits, by ranking and choosing mates based on a combination of one or more traits, the selection objective in modern breeding programs aiming typically a measure of lifetime profitability and the selection criterion usually comprises traits included in national milk recording programs (Cole, VanRaden, 2017). Genomic technology enables to breed cattle according to specific goals, such as for higher milk yield or higher fertility in young bulls (Hart, 2017). Farmers need to understand only the function of each subindex instead of dozens of traits (Cole, VanRaden, 2017).

Indices are constructed based on a series of subindices. Indices revision can be directed to include new or additional traits in some

subindices. The lifetime net merit (NM\$) indice was constructed from production (PROD\$), longevity (LONG\$), fertility (FERT\$), conformation (TYPE\$), calving ability (CA\$) and lately, new health subindex (HEALTH\$) (Cole, VanRaden, 2017). The Ideal Commercial Cow Index (ICCS; Genex, 2006) was constructed based on the production efficiency (PREF\$), health (HLTH\$), fertility and fitness (FYFT\$), milking ability (MABL\$), and calving ability (CABL\$) subindices. The Irish EBI Index (ICBF, 2017) comprises 7 subindices like milk production, fertility, calving performance, beef carcass, cow maintenance, cow management, and health. In the past, the proposed indices were typically reviewed by groups of experts, and information related to the derivation of the indices was provided to ensure confidence in the values. Recently, genetic evaluations for novel traits and new selection indices are computed and distributed by companies (i.e. CRV (Arnhem, the Netherlands), Genex (Shawano, WI), Zoetis (Parsippany-Troy Hills, NJ)), but transparent review processes may be lacking (Cole, VanRaden, 2017).

Selection indices vary within and across countries due to different economic conditions, traits recorded and specific breeds (table 1).

Table 1

Selection indices used in various countries

Index abbreviations	Index specification	Country
GDM	genes diffusion merit	France
RZG	total merit index	Germany
£PLI	profitable lifetime index	Great Britain
PFT	production, functionality and type index	Italy
ICO	total genetic merit index	Spain
BW	breeding worth	New Zealand
ISEL	total selection index	Switzerland
NVI	Netherlands cattle improvement index	The Netherlands
EBI	economic breeding index	Ireland
NTM	Nordic total merit	Denmark, Finland, Sweden
TPI	total performance index	U.S.A.
GM\$	grazing merit	
CM\$	cheese merit	
NM\$	net merit	
LPI	lifetime profit index	Canada
NTP	Nippon total profit	Japan
PD11	Israeli 2011 breeding index	Israel
HWI	health weighted index	Australia
TWI	type weighted index	
BPI	balanced performance index	

Prior to genomic testing use on a farm, it is important to ascertain the traits that will be selected to achieve on farm goals (Hart, 2017). Recording important new traits on a fraction of cows can quickly benefit the whole population through genomics. The number of traits included in a typical selection criterion has grown over time, from 1 or 2 yield traits to many non-yield traits, including fertility, health, and fitness traits (Cole, VanRaden, 2017). Usually, selected traits differ slightly in various countries, but there are common trait groups defined (table 2).

Table 2

Common group traits and selected traits in various countries

Common trait group	Example of traits included in the common trait group
yield	milk volume
	fat yield
	protein yield
longevity	productive life
fertility	nonreturn rate
	days open
udder health	SCS
	clinical mastitis
calving traits	dystocia
	stillbirth
milking traits	milking speed
conformation	udder conformation
	feet score
	leg score

For example, the genomic profile of a heifer use the key indexes: the profitable lifetime index (£PLI) and type merit, harboring production traits such as: milk kg, fat kg, protein kg, fat %, protein %, as well as health and fitness traits as follows: mammary composite, feet and legs composite, temperament, ease of milking, locomotion, condition score, TB advantage, lifespan, SCC, fertility. The profitable lifetime index (£PLI) provides an economic breeding index for UK herds (Hart, 2017).

The first USDA index, predicted difference dollars (PD\$), included only milk and fat yield in the traits, whereas the 2017 revision of the lifetime net merit (NM\$) rely on 33 different traits included in various subindices.

The traits that should be included in future selection indices is still a concern, some traits showing a growing interest to dairy farmers. Some countries are showing interest to include specific traits in their selection indices, but some do not. Traits as health and fitness, feed intake, fertility, genetic diversity, milk composition, omics data, or other traits maybe adopted for individual breeding programs, could be considered for future

selection indices in various countries (Cole, VanRaden, 2017). New traits and strategies are still demanding for livestock improvement.

GENOMIC SELECTION APPLICATION IN DAIRY CATTLE

Genomic selection is a form of marker-assisted selection (MAS), in which genetic markers covering the whole genome are used so that all QTL are in linkage disequilibrium with at least one marker (Yadav et al., 2018).

In developed countries, genomic selection (GS) lead to rapid rates of genetic gains especially in dairy cattle, resulting in a higher proportion of genomically proven young bulls for breeding (Mrode et. al., 2019).

Developing countries are facing issues related small holder systems with small herd sizes or the existence of breed associations, resulting in some degree of data and pedigree recording and genetic evaluation or even the lack of performance and pedigree recording; also, some countries still had to face the lack of breeding structures such as artificial insemination companies, to drive breed improvement programs. Therefore presently, in developing countries most genotyping activities are undertaken by breed organizations or associations, or are a result of several development projects (Kosgey, Okeyo, 2007, Carvalheiro, 2014, Brown et al., 2016, Silva et al., 2016, Mrode et. al., 2019).

Genomic selection in dairy cattle has been used to discover the markers and improvement of the traits associated with milk production, cow health, udder health, and cow conformation, Australia being the leader on genomic selection in dairy cows, along with other countries like US, Canada, China, etc. (Yadav et al., 2018). In practice, genomic selection refers to selection decisions based on genomic estimated breeding values (GEBV) (Yadav et al., 2018). The accuracy of genomic prediction in dairy cattle shows values exceeding 0.8 for production traits and 0.7 for fertility, longevity, somatic cell count and other traits (Wiggans et al. 2011). Using SNP effects from one breed to calculate GEBV in another breed vice versa was not satisfactory. SNP estimates calculated from a Holstein-Friesian reference population did not produce accurate GEBV in Jersey bulls, and the correlations ranged from -0.1 to 0.3 (Yadav et al., 2018).

Implementing genomic selection in dairy cattle has resulted in increased genetic gain in many countries, so that related dairy genomic predictions, many countries collaborate to assemble large reference sets, being three consortiums established (Eurogenomics, including the Netherlands, Germany, France, the Nordic countries, Spain, and Poland; The North American Consortium including USA, Canada, Italy, and Great Britain; and a “rest of the world” consortium consisting of a number of remaining countries) (Yadav et al., 2018). Worldwide, approximately 2 million dairy cattle have been genotyped for purposes of genomic

prediction, from which 934,780 Holstein, 120,439 Jersey, 19,588 and 4,767 Ayrshire in USA (Wiggans, personal communication referred in Meuwissen et. al., 2019).

Lately, the genetic selection of dairy heifers can be a better option than selection for young bulls alone, as a part of selection for breeding (Hart, 2017). In many countries, most of the genotyped animals are now heifer calves and even if genotyping young bull calves results in the greatest genetic gain, genotyping is now sufficiently cheap to be applied to heifer calves for the choosing which heifers to retain in the herd or the bulls to which to mate, to minimize inbreeding (Pryce, Hayes 2012).

Next-generation sequencing and associated technologies facilitated breed composition, parent verification, genome diversity and genome-wide selection sweeps assessment, such data being used in breeding programs aiming genomic selection. (Mrode et. al., 2019). In 2007, the first draft of bovine genome enabled the Illumina Company, in collaboration with an international consortium to develop a chip for genotyping over 54,000 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) simultaneously, that was used to genotype existing progeny-tested bulls (Boichard et. al, 2016). Such technology showed genomic breeding values enough accurate to replace progeny testing and allowing young bulls semen with genomic evaluation only the dissemination (Boichard et. al, 2016). Cross validation approaches implemented in most studies show accuracies of 0.20–0.60, meanwhile genotyping based on a mixture of HD and LD chips, followed by imputation to the HD lead to accuracies of 0.74–0.99 (Mrode et. al., 2019).

The genomic best linear unbiased prediction (GBLUP), single-step GBLUP (ssGBLUP) and SNP-BLUP methods are very similar to traditional BLUP, the pedigree relationships being replaced by genomic relationships. (Habier et al., 2007, Goddard et al., 2011, Vitezica et al., 2011, Legarra et al., 2014, Yadav et al., 2018, Meuwissen et. al., 2019,).

Genomic prediction studies in developing countries are mostly target dairy and beef cattle, usually with small reference populations (500–3000 animals) and are mostly cows, the input variables tending to be pre-corrected phenotypic records and the various Bayesian methods use are feasible in addition to GBLUP (Mrode et. al., 2019). Various commercial chips vary related the efficacy of imputation in dairy cattle breeds in terms of the impact on the accuracy of imputation and genomic prediction, based on different reference populations and different imputation algorithms (Browning, Browning, 2016, Das et al., 2016, Aliloo et al., 2018).

The number of genotyped animals tend to be limited, are mostly females, therefore having a major impact on both the size and structure of the reference and validation populations (Mrode et. al., 2019). Nowadays, genomic selection is used on a large scale in dairy cattle industry and with

the advancement it may be used for the improvement of all the livestock population (Yadav et al., 2018).

CONCLUSIONS

In developing countries genomic selection could use the advantages of various dairy sires already genotyped and phenotyped, from developed countries, but also need to find solutions for efficient and satisfactory performance and pedigree recording next to genetic evaluation, for breeding and improvement programs.

A strength collaboration between developing and developed countries, next to the ability of Governments to enable policies, statutory and regulatory frameworks, by putting in place farmers, institutions, breed organizations and associations, artificial insemination companies could stand for breeding and improvement programmes in dairy cattle.

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IDENTIFICATION OF ENTEROPATHOGENIC *E. COLI* AND THE ANTIGENIC STRUCTURE

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Abstract

Enterobacteriaceae is the bacteria that includes many of the most familiar pathogen agents or pathogen conditioned as would be *Salmonella*, *Shigella*, *E. Coli*. Following the genetic studies, they were placed in *Proteobacteria* having their own order, *Enterobacteriales*.

E. Coli, in the human intestine, represents dominant flora of the large intestine having an important role in the maintaining of its normal physiology and in the synthesis of some proteins from the groups B and K. Eliminated in the external environment with the excrements it contaminates the water, the soil, the food. Inside the species are distinguished numerous versions that express characteristics of pathogenicity, versions named pathovars, patotypes. *E. Coli* is pathogen by virulence and/or toxigenicity. The determinants of pathogenicity are various. Depending on the determinants of pathogenicity that the strains of *E. Coli* are having can cause different affections. The *enterobacteriaceae* of the *Escherichia* type are mainly saprophyte or conditioned pathogen. There are patotypes of *E. Coli* involved in the human pathology as the diarrhea patotypes, uropathogen and other types are. The intestinal infections or infectious enterocolites are determined by the five diarrhea patotypes, each having serologic subgroups and determining distinct clinical manifestations.

Key words: pathogenicity, toxigenicity, infections

INTRODUCTION

Enterobacteriaceae is a microorganism that can be found in the environment which evolved in order to compose the normal intestinal flora.

Enterobacteriaceae are non demanding germs, they grow on simple media. They are aerobe germs, facultative anaerobe that need for an optimum growth, temperatures of 22-37°C. On the non selective media will form colonies of grey color of the "S" type, "M" type. On the blood agar, some species determine β hemolysis.

It is a resistant bacteria in the environment. Destroyed by the usual antiseptics and disinfectants and by the colorants as malachite green, crystal violet.

It presents a special capacity of adapting to the modifications from the environment as would be the presence of some minerals, modifications of ph, temperature, osmolarity.

It can sense the presence or absence of some chemical substances or gases in the environment or of life and with the help of the cilia it can come closer or farther of them.

It can also become immobile and to produce adhesion fimbriae that would allow the adherence to the specific substrate.

Due to the temperature or osmolarity they modify the dimension of the pores by the modification of porins constituent of the external membrane. Thus it can increase the dimension of the pores to accumulate large molecules of nutrient or to eliminate inhibitor substances.

They poses a complex mechanism of regulation of the bacterial cell metabolism that allows it to assure an easy life. They synthetize only those enzymes necessary for the obtaining of some metabolites when they are present in the environment where it can use them.

It is a microorganism that develop the resistance towards the antibacterial substances by the elaboration of enzymes that hydrolyses the beta lactamases or by mutations that affect the porins thus becoming resistant to the aminosides.

The enterobacteriaceae present pils that assure the adherence to mucous, allowing the bacteria to colonize and multiply.

The mannose-sensitive pils are connected to the host cell in the same place as D-mannose.

They are important for the normal colonization of the gastric-intestinal tube. Other mannose-resistant pils are not connected to the host cell in the same place with the D-mannose.

There are pils that represent a major importance as factor of virulence, helping the microorganisms to determine affections outside their normal area of action.

The invasins are proteins that act locally destroying or invading the host cell, facilitating the growth and the spreading of the pathogen agent.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the accomplishing of the objectives proposed was used the retrospective study.

Collection and transport of samples

The collection has to be made as close to the beginning of the disease and before the beginning of any antimicrobial treatment.

- The collection from the stool made spontaneously – it is preferred and is indicated in all the forms of acute diarrhea when the emission of excrements is frequent.

- For bacterial and parasite examinations, the collection is made with the “spoon” of the coproculture tube, concerning the liquid parts and

especially, those mucous and/or sanguinolent, if they exist. The volume of the collection has to be of minimum 5 ml or 3-5 cm³, if the stool is formed³.

- For the isolations or virological exams is collected 5-10 cm³ of excrements or minimum 5 ml, if the stool is not formed³.

- The rectal collection – is recommended in:

- chronic shigellosis, where the curettage of the rectal mucous with the probe or the tampon offers greater chances to the isolation;

- the investigation of the carriers of Shigella and Salmonella, with the exception of the those with S. Typhi.

For this type of collection are used Nelaton probes (no.14-16) or adequate tampons, as the following: with the tampon, wet in saline isotone solution (not to be used lubricant gels), is penetrated the anal sphincter by slow rotation, introducing in the rectum approximately 15 cm. It will proceed identically also with the Nelaton probe, to which is adapted a syringe (10 ml) used for 1-2 aspirations. After the collection, the probes and tampons are introduced in sterile recipients that contain preservation medium, are labeled correspondently and are sent to the laboratory³.

The transport of the samples and their processing is made in maximum 1h, if they were collected in recipient without medium of transport (with transport at the room temperature), or can be kept up to 24h at room temperature, if they were collected in recipients that contain Cary-Blair medium of transport which assures a good viability of the bacterial intestinal pathogens. An exception to these rules are the samples collected for the suspicion of infection with Shigella spp, very sensitive bacteria, which needs seeding on the culture media immediately after collection^{3;4}.

For the viral etiology, the samples that are not processed immediately have to be kept at – 70°C³.

The isolation of the aerobe bacteria

- It is seeded the sample on two culture media, one weakly selective (Mac Conkey) and one moderately selective (Hektoen) and is incubated 24 h at 35-37°C, following the cultures at 24 and 48 h for the appearance of characteristic colonies. For the Vibrio type, the recommended selective medium is BSA (bile salts agar), and for yeasts – the Sabouraud medium with Cloramfenicol.

- In order to increase the chances of isolation, the sample is sub cultivated on media of enriching that favors the multiplication of the pathogen (ex. selenite broth sodium acid for Salmonella spp., alkaline peptone water or broth with taurocholate and peptone at pH=8,0-9,0 for Vibrio where, after incubation can be made smears and cultures from the superior part of the medium). It is incubated 24 h at 35-37°C, then are made transmissions on the culture mediums.

- The colonies characteristic to each type will be transplanted in order to identify on the level of species and agglutination with specific serums.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

Fig.1. *E. Coli*.

Fig.2. *E. Coli*.

E. Coli is a germ well adapted to its living environment. It is not demanding. It grows on simple mediums in which the glucose is the only organic constituent.

It is an aerobic germ, discretionary anaerobe that can have both fermentative and respiratory metabolism. On solid mediums it grows under the form of colonies of "S" type, and in the liquid medium it determines uniform disorder and adherent ring on the wall of the tube.

From the point of view of the metabolism and of biochemistry, *E. Coli* ferments the glucose and other carbohydrates with production of acid and gas. The majority of strains are oxidase-negative, are capable to reduce the nitrites in nitrates.

They don't produce urease, don't decompose the proteins with formation of H₂S, don't use the citrate as unique source of carbon. They decompose the lactose with emission of acid, decompose the proteins with formation of indole, give the positive methyl red reaction.

Some strains, usually those involved in urinary infections, determine the beta hemolysis of blood agar.

The antigen "o" or somatic one, is the antigen with specificity of group that corresponds to the polyside fixed on the lipopolysaccharides of the bacterial wall. It is thermo stable and acid-alcohol-resistant. By the reactions of agglutination there were identified 180 "o" antigenic blood groups that can present reactions of crossing with antigens of some strains of Klebsiella, Salmonella, Providencia, Vibrio, and others are common with the Shigella group.

The Antigen "H" or the flagella antigen is present only in the ciliate strains, it is made of a specific protein named flagellin. It has a specificity of type, it is thermolabile and is inactive in alcohol. By reactions of agglutination there were distinguished 56 "H" serotypes.

The Antigen "K" or the capsular antigen is of polysaccharide nature, has a specificity of type and was identified in the uropathogen strains of *E. Coli* and in strains involved in the case of newborn meningitis. The B antigen is an antigen of surface.

The strains of enteropathogenic *E. Coli* induce a watery diarrhea similar to that from the infections with enterotoxigenic *E. Coli*, affecting especially the children. enteropathogenic *E. Coli* doesn't produce enterotoxins TL or TS but only small quantities of Shiga-like toxin with enterotoxic and cytotoxic effect.

By the Bfp adhesins is connected to the intestinal epithelia on the level of the colon determining the destruction of the microvilosities with inflammatory response, without sign of invasion. As a consequence is

installed the malabsorption, the watery diarrhea, persistent, accompanied by fever and vomit.

The enterotoxigenic strains affect all the categories of age though it represents the major etiology of the children's diarrhea and of the tourists in the countries with scarce sanitation, named also "diarrhea of tourists".

Nataro and Kaper, presented the fact that, from its description, many cases and outbreaks of diseases associated to the diarrhea were associated to the EAEC strains, but the clinical characteristics and the results of these infections are diverse.

In 2002, Elias and others in the studies on the EAEC strains showed its heterogeneity.

Jenkins and others, 2006b, Okeke and others, 2010, offered information on the heterogenic pathogenesis of CEEA in the human being, but also the importance of the host.

Recently, Okeke and others confirmed the heterogeneity of the EAEC strains by the molecular phylogenetic analysis, because 96 types of sequence (ST) were identified using the impression of the multilocus sequencing (MLST) and isolated EAEC identified by the HEp-2 tests, mainly from a site, although 40% of the EAEC strains belong or were locus versions of three STS.

In this review we will discuss about the relevance for the public health of the infection with EAEC and its complexity due to the heterogeneity of the strains.

CONCLUSIONS

The diagnosis of laboratory is bacteriologic and is based on the identification of the strains of Escherichia Coli in the pathologic products.

The identification based on the biochemical characteristics is completed with the serotyping for EPEC and EHEC strains.

Numerous andesine, toxins and proteins associated with virulence were described, and also many factors that contribute to the inflammation induced by EAEC.

None of these factors is found in all the isolated EAEC and no single factor was ever involved in the virulence of EAEC.

EAEC producing Shiga toxins is increasing its pathogen potential and interest to find real pathogen factors that can define this prototype.

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EPIDEMIOLOGICAL AND CLINICAL ISSUES OF PATIENTS WITH THICK BITES AND FIRST STAGE LYME DISEASE, IN BIHOR COUNTY

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Abstract

Climate change affects the behavior of organisms, especially in case of migration of disease carrying insects (like mosquitoes, ticks). Higher temperatures, changing precipitation regime and various extreme weather events directly influence the distribution of serious cases and their number may increase.

Infectious diseases can spread quickly. Vector insects become resistant as these changes are frequent and increase the incidence of Lyme disease, West Nile, malaria and other (Mărculescu, 2016).

Bihor county, as border county is located in the area of vectors with upward trend in the last period.

Key words: Lyme disease, Borelliosis, tick bites, erythema migrans

INTRODUCTION

Borreliosis or Lyme disease, formerly known as *Erythema chronicum migrans*, Bannwarth syndrome, is part of the zoonosis category that occurs accidentally in humans (Chiotan, 2011; Crișan, 2015). It is produced by a *Borrelia burgdorferi sensu lato* spirochete that contains several pathogenic serotypes, transmitted to humans through ticks of the species *Ixodes* (Coipan, Vladimirescu, 2010; Drăghici, 2015).

The evolution of the disease (Cupșa, 2015; Voiculescu, 1980) comprises 3 stages:

- the first stage, characterized by the presence of the erythema migrans,
- the second stage, with skin, cardiac and neurological manifestations and
- the third stage, with persistent clinical evolution of the disease.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

There are studied a number of 1200 patients who presented at the emergency room of The Municipal Clinical Hospital „Dr. Gavril Curteanu” Oradea, Infectious Diseases section, between 01.01.2015-31.12.2018,

having been bitten by ticks in different parts of the body. The positive diagnosis of Lyme disease was supported by the presence of migratory erythema, respectively of the positive serology for Lyme disease (ELISA and Western-Blot) (Hoeprich et al., 2005; Mandell et al.,2019)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- The number of tick bites has increased significantly every year, the highest percentage being in 2018 with over 1/3 (34.58 %) of the total presentations to emergency room over the last 4 years (Table 1; Fig.1).

Table 1

The number of tick bites registered between 2015-2018					
Year	2015	2016	2017	2018	Total
Nr.	195	250	340	415	1200
%	16,25	20,83	28,34	34,58	100%

Fig.1. Evolution of tick bites registered between 2015-2018

-Not all patients with tick bites developed Lyme disease. 15.2% (183 persons) of the 1200 patients had positive serology for *Borrelia burgdorferi sensu lato* (Fig.2).

Fig.2. The presence of Lyme disease developed after tick bites

-The majority of patients reported only one tick bite, these being 80% of cases, the remaining 20% being bitten by two or more ticks in a very short period of time (Fig.3).

Fig.3. Distribution of cases according to number of tick bites

- The location of the tick bite was uneven, the most exposed area being the anterior and posterior thorax in 1/3 of the cases (33.3%) (Table 2; Fig.4).

Table 2.

Locations of the tick bites					
Upper limbs	Lower limbs	Thorax	Abdomen	Scalp	Total
26,67	24,83	33,3	19,5	1,66	100 %
320	298	400	162	20	1200

Fig.4. Distribution of tick bites according of the body region

- In patients diagnosed with Lyme disease, the most frequent location of erythema migrans has been reported in the abdominal area, although this part of the body is covered by clothing, which would protect from an eventual biting (Table 3; Fig.5).

Table 3.

Locations of the erythema migrans					
Upper limbs	Lower limbs.	Thorax	Abdomen	Scalp	Total
16,53	13,11	32,77	36,66	1,1	100 %
31	24	60	66	2	183

Fig.5. Distribution of the location of erythema migrans

- The appearance of the erythema migrans was the most frequent within the period 16-20 days from the time of the bite (73 cases), with a percentage of 38.9% of the cases (Fig.6).

Fig. 6. The time required of erythema migrans appearance

Fig.7. Gender distribution of the patients

Gender of the patients has no significant influence on the disease appearance (Fig.7).

Fig.8 The origin of the patients with Lyme disease

The percentage of patients from urban area was insignificantly higher in comparison with the patients from rural area (Fig.8).

CONCLUSIONS

1. Lyme disease is a disease with increasing incidence during the four years covered by the presented study.
2. The majority of patients reported only one tick bite, these being 80% of cases, in various body regions.
3. Erythema migrans has been reported with high percent in the abdomen area, who appeared after 11- 20 days from the time of bites.

4. Gender of the patients has no significant influence on the disease manifestation.

5. The percentage of patients from urban area was insignificantly higher in comparison with the patients from rural area.

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**CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE STUDY OF THE CLASS
PHRAGMITETEA AUSTRALIS R. TÜXEN et PREISING 1942
IN THE LOWER BASIN OF CRIȘUL NEGRU RIVER**

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Abstract

The grasslands from the lower basin of Crișul Negru river form an area with rich flora and vegetation suitable for a complex phytocoenological research and an ecologic and bio-economical study of the floor vegetation.

This work represents a phytocoenological study of the association Sparganietum erecti Roll 1938, which is classified from the coenotaxonomic point of view in the class Phragmitetea australis R. Tüxen et Preising 1942. The association was analyzed in terms of floristic composition, life forms, floristic elements, ecological indices and karyotype.

Key words: phytocoenoses, association, floristic composition, life forms, floristic elements.

INTRODUCTION

Chorology: the phytocoenosis of this association were mentioned in our country from Moldova (Mititelu, 1971, 1975; Barabaș, 1974; Mititelu et Barabaș, 1972, 1974, 1975; Mititelu et al., 1994; Dobrescu, 1981; Turenschi et Zanoschi, 1971); Muntenia (Dihoru, 1975; Popescu et al., 1984); Maramureș (Gergely et Rațiu, 1980); Transilvania (Ularu, 1969; Erika Schneider-Binder, 1975; Șuteu, 1973); Banat (Grigore, 1971a, 1971b; Vicol, 1974); Crișana (Pop, 1962).

From the floristic point of view, the researches carried out in the meadowlands from the lower basin of the Crișul Negru River provide dissipated data on some limited areas of the territory, and in the case of phytocoenological studies, the vegetation of this area is also less well known. The complex study of flora and vegetation is absolutely necessary.

Type of habitat: Natural Habitat of Community interest whose conservation requires the designation of Special Areas of Conservation (ASC), Natura 2000: 3150 Natural eutrophic lakes with *Magnopotamion* or *Hydrocharition* - type vegetation.

Code R5304: Danubian Communities with *Sparganium erectum*, *Berula erecta* and *Sium latifolium* (Doniță et al., 2005).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The phytocoenosis of this association populate the edges of the dams with permanent water retention near Cefa locality and the collector channels in the area of Inand and Homorog localities in the lower basin of Crișul Negru river, being included in the Crișurilor Plain, which is the central compartment of the Western Plain.

Framing the association to the corresponding cenotaxonomic units – alliance, order and class was made according to the traditional ecological and floristic systems elaborated by Tüxen (1955), Braun–Blanquet (1964), Borza et Boșcaiu (1965), Soó (1964-1980), as well as on the basis of the most recent works belonging to Mucina (1997), Rothmaler (1994, 2000), Borhidi (1996, 2003), Coldea et al. (1997); Sanda et al. (2008).

The study of the vegetal cover in the meadowlands from the middle basin of Crișul Negru River was made taking into consideration the phytosociological research method of the European Central School, based on the principles and methods elaborated by Braun–Blanquet (1964) and adapted by Borza and Boșcaiu (1965) to the particularities of the vegetation carpet from our country.

The taxa identified in the field have been recognized by specialty catalogues "Romania's Illustrated Flora" (Ciocârlan, 2009), in conjunction with the information provided by the "International Code of Botanical Nomenclature" (Code de Tokyo, 1993).

The association synthetic table was structured after the methodology proposed by Braun–Blanquet (1964) and developed by Ellenberg (1974); therefore, in the column header of the table for the association analyzed the following have been entered: the serial number of land surveys, altitude (m.s.m.), exposition, slope (°), area (m²), coverage of grass layer (%).

At the end of the table, the last two columns included the synthetic phytocoenological indices, constancy (K) and abundance–dominance index (ADm).

The constancy highlights the extent of coenotic fidelity of each species to the phytocoenosis environment of the association, according to the Braun–Blanquet et Pavillard methodology (1928). The abundance and dominance highlights the percentage of average coverage achieved by phyto–individuals of a phytocoenosis.

Establishment of the values for ecological indices, life forms, floristic elements and karyotype were made after the synthesis works elaborated by Raunkiær (1937), Braun–Blanquet (1951), Meusel et Jäger (1992), Ellenberg (1974, 1979), Ellenberg et al. (1992), Soó (1964-1980), Májovsky et Murin (1987), Sanda et al. (2003), Pop (1977, 1982), Ciocârlan (2009).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The phytocoenoses edified by *Sparganium erectum* form compact, well-individualized groups that develop in standing or flowing waters, with depths between 20 and 40 cm and occupy sample areas between 15-30 m².

The characteristic and dominant species is *Sparganium erectum* ssp. *neglectum*, with a general coverage of 72.5 ADm and maximum constancy (V), along with species characteristic of the alliance *Sparganio-Glycerion fluitantis*, of the order *Nasturtio-Glycerietalia*: *Glyceria fluitans*, *Veronica anagallis-aquatica*, *Myosotis scorpioides*, etc. and the class *Phragmitetea australis*: *Glyceria maxima*, *Stachys palustris*, etc. (Table 1).

Table 1

Sparganietum erecti Roll 1938

L.f.	F.e.	W	T	S.r.	2n	No. Land Surveys	1	2	3	4	5	K	ADm
						Altitude (m.s.m.)	100	100	104	104	106		
						Area (m ²)	30	20	15	15	20		
						Coverage of grass layer (%)	95	75	85	90	75		
Hh	Eua	5,5	3,5	0	D	<i>As. Sparganium erectum</i> <i>ssp. neglectum</i>	5	4	4	5	4	V	72,5
<i>Sparganio-Glycerion fluitantis</i>, <i>Nasturtio-Glycerietalia</i>													
Hh	Eua	5	3	0	P	<i>Myosotis scorpioides</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5
Hh-H	Cosm	5	3	0	P	<i>Glyceria fluitans</i>	+	.	.	+	+	III	0,3
H	Eua	4	3	3	P	<i>Epilobium hirsutum</i>	+	1	+	.	.	III	1,2
H-Hh	Cp-Bo	5	0	4	DP	<i>Veronica anagallis-</i> <i>aquatica</i>	+	.	+	.	+	III	0,3
Hh	Eua	6	3	4,5	P	<i>Glyceria plicata</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II	0,2
<i>Phragmitetea australis</i>													
Hh	Cosm	6	0	0	D	<i>Alisma plantago-aquatica</i>	+	+	+	+	1	V	1,4
Hh-G	Cosm	6	3	4	P	<i>Schoenoplectus lacustris</i>	.	+	+	.	+	III	0,3
Hh	Cp	5	3	4	P	<i>Glyceria maxima</i>	+	1	.	.	.	II	1,1
G-Hh	E	5,5	0	0	P	<i>Iris pseudacorus</i>	.	.	+	.	+	II	0,2
H(G)	Cp-Bo	4	3	4	P	<i>Stachys palustris</i>	+	+	.	.	.	II	0,2
G-Hh	Cosm	5	0	4	P	<i>Eleocharis palustris</i>	+	.	.	+	.	II	0,2
Ch	Eua	4,5	3	4	P	<i>Solanum dulcamara</i>	+	.	.	.	.	I	0,1
H	Cp-Bo	4	3	4	P	<i>Scutellaria galericulata</i>	+	.	.	.	.	I	0,1
Hh	Cp-Bo	4,5	0	4	P	<i>Rumex aquaticus</i>	+	.	.	.	.	I	0,1
<i>Magnocaricetalia</i>													
Hh	Eua	6	3	4	P	<i>Carex acutiformis</i>	.	+	2	+	.	III	3,7
Hh	Eua	5	4	4	P	<i>Carex riparia</i>	+	.	.	.	+	II	0,2
<i>Bidentetea tripartiti</i>													
H	Cp	4	4	4	D	<i>Rumex conglomeratus</i>	+	.	+	.	.	II	0,2
Th	Eua	4	3	0	P	<i>Myosoton aquaticum</i>	.	.	.	.	+	I	0,1
Th	Eua	4,5	3	0	P	<i>Bidens tripartita</i>	.	.	.	.	+	I	0,1
<i>Molinio-Arrhenatheretea</i>													
H-Hh	Cosm	4	3	0	P	<i>Lythrum salicaria</i>	.	.	.	.	+	I	0,1
H	Eua	4	4	4	D	<i>Juncus inflexus</i>	+	.	.	.	.	I	0,1
H-Hh	Eua	4,5	3,5	4	P	<i>Lythrum virgatum</i>	.	.	.	+	.	I	0,1
H	Cosm	4,5	3	3	P	<i>Juncus effusus</i>	.	.	.	+	.	I	0,1
H	Eua	4	3	0	P	<i>Symphytum officinale</i>	+	.	.	.	.	I	0,1
H	Cp-Bo	4	0	0	P	<i>Agrostis stolonifera</i>	.	+	.	.	.	I	0,1

Phytocoenological table of *Sparganietum erecti* Roll 1938 association, where: L. f. - life forms; F. e. - floristic elements; W - soil wet; T - temperature; S. r. - chemical reaction of the soil; 2n - karyotype; K - constancy; ADm - abundance-dominance; Hh - helohydatophytes; H - Hemicryptophytes, Th - Annual Therophytes, Ch - Chamaephytes, Eua - Eurasian, Cp - Circumpolar, Cosm - Cosmopolitan, E - European, D - diploidy, P - polyploidy, DP - diplo-polyploidy.

Place and date of surveys: 1 - 2 Dam with permanent water retention, Cefa locality (Bihor County) 11.08.2017; 3 - 4 Collector channel, Inand locality (Bihor County) 11.08.2017; 5 - Collector channel, Homorog locality (Bihor County) 11.08.2017.

An important cenotic role is played by the transgressive species from the *Bidentetea tripartiti* class: *Bidens tripartita*, *Rumex conglomeratus*, etc. and from the *Molinio-Arrhenatheretea* class: *Agrostis stolonifera*, *Juncus inflexus*, *Juncus effusus*, etc.

The life forms spectrum for the analyzed association (Fig. 1), attests the highest percentage of hemicryptophytes (42.3%), followed by helohidatophytes (38.46%), with annual geophytes and terophytes each having 7.69%.

Fig. 1 – The life forms spectrum of *Sparganietum erecti* association, where:
Hh – helohidatophytes, G – geophytes, H – hemicryptophytes,
Th – annual therophytes, Ch – chamaephytes.

The spectrum of the floristic elements (Fig. 2), indicates the higher weight of the Eurasian species (46.15%), followed by the circumpolar ones (26.92%) and the cosmopolitan ones (23.07%).

Fig. 2 – Floristic elements spectrum of the *Sparganietum erecti* association, where:
E – European, Eua – Eurasian, Cosm – Cosmopolitan, Cp – Circumpolar.

Analyzing the phytocoenoses of the association *Sparganietum erecti* from the point of view of the ecological indices (Fig. 3) it is found that, depending on the humidity factor, the mesohigrofile species (53.84%) predominate, followed by the hygrophilous ones (30.76%). In terms of temperature, micro-mesothermal species are dominant (61.53%), followed by euroterms (23.07%). Regarding the chemical reaction of the soil, the high percentage of the weak acid-neutrophil species (53.84%) is observed, followed by the euriionic ones (38.46%).

Fig. 3 – Diagram of ecological indices for the *Sparganietum erecti* association, where: W – soil wet, T – temperature, S. r. – chemical reaction of the soil.

The karyotype spectrum (Fig. 4) shows the dominance of the polyploid species (80.76%), followed by the diploids (15.38%) and the diplo-polyploids (3.84%), the diploidy index having the value of 0.19.

Fig. 4 – The karyotype spectrum of *Sparganietum erecti* association, where: D – diploidy, P – polyploidy, DP – diplo-polyploidy.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis results of the 5 surveys realised for the *Sparganietum erecti* Roll 1938 association, in that concerning the life forms, floristic elements, ecological indices and karyotype, shows that the floristic and cenotic composition of the association are well shaped and varied and our results are according with specialty literature.

Sparganietum erecti is a rare association ranked in Natural Habitat of Community interest whose conservation requires the designation of Special Areas of Conservation (ASC), Natura 2000: 3150 Natural eutrophic lakes with *Magnopotamion* or *Hydrocharition* - type vegetation, therefore we need to protect them for the preservation of their phytodiversity.

The evolution direction of the association is towards phytocoenoses of *Eleocharitetum palustris* and *Glycerietum fluitantis*.

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IL-6 AS A DIAGNOSTIC MARKER FOR THE INFLAMMATORY PROCESS OF ACUTE APPENDICITIS

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Abstract

The action of interleukin 6 (IL-6) on lymphoid and non-lymphoid cells is a modulatory mechanism of the body's immune and inflammatory responses. Although many of these functions overlap with those of type 1 interleukins (IL-1), such as the synthesis of acute phase reactants and fever, IL-6 also has anti-inflammatory effects. The IL-6-specific receptor (IL-6R) belongs to the (haematopoietic) cytokine receptor superfamily. IL-6R is a membrane protein complex consisting of two structural and functional subunits: a specific 80-kDa IL-6 binding protein (α chain) and a signal transducer, gp130 (b chain, a component for several types of receptors such as IL-11, IL-27, IL-31). Cytokine IL-6 is secreted as a polypeptide consisting of 184 amino acids, with a molecular weight of about 21 kDa, depending on the degree of glycosylation. Cytokines bind to specific membrane receptors on cells. IL-1 and TNF- α have as primary inducers the production of IL-6 and IL-8 and both occur systematically in acute appendicitis. IL-6 is the major cytokine mediator of the acute phase response and is produced by monocytes, macrophages and endothelial cells. IL-6 is a measure of systemically activated pro-inflammatory cytokines. The serum level of IL-6 also reflects the severity of the acute appendicitis and precedes the growth of the C-reactive protein by 24-36 hours. IL-8 is the secondary mediator of TNF- α -induced neutrophil activation.

Key words: interleukin, pro-inflammatory, neutrophils, acute appendicitis

INTRODUCTION

Reginald Fitz of Boston uses the term appendicitis and recommended surgical treatment of the disease. Chester McBurney described characteristic migratory pain as well as the surgical approach area located along an imaginary oblique line from the anterior superior iliac spine to the umbilical scar. Since 1940 the use of antibiotics, computed tomography, ultrasound and laparoscopic examination has resulted in decreased morbidity and mortality and increased diagnostic accuracy. Laparoscopic appendectomy was first reported by gynaecologist Kurt Semm in 1982, but it has gained wide-spread acceptance only in recent years.

The vermiform appendix is a rudimentary part of the large intestine. The average length is 8-9 cm, the outer diameter is 5-8 mm and the one of

the inner canal of 1-3 mm, a canal that continues with the cecum through the appendicular ostium that is provided with a fold of mucous membrane - Gerlach's valve. Its insertion site is located at the junction of the three taeniae coli, 2-3 cm distal to the ileocecal valve. The wall structure is identical to that of the cecum. In young people approximately 200 lymphatic follicles are present in the submucosa that is also called the "abdominal tonsil" (Zviedre et al., 2016). Blood supply is provided by the appendicular artery, derived from the ileocolic artery, the final major branch of the superior mesenteric artery. The appendicular artery is situated in the mesentery of the appendix. The veins accompany the artery and drain the blood into the superior mesenteric vein. The lymphatic drainage is done to the colic and ileocolic ganglia, but depending on the position of the appendix the lymph can be drained to the duodenum, gallbladder or ovarian ganglia. A very interesting element is that of the position of the appendix; while its base and the cecum are located in the right iliac fossa, its tip may be directed either upward or downward. The most frequent positions are the retrocaecal-retrocolic (75%) and the subcaecal-pelvic ones (20%) (Widdison and Karanja, 1993) while the meso-celiac, subhepatic, herniated ones are also described.

According to the colocalization theory, there is a premature fusion between the lysosomes and the zymogen granules, resulting in the phenomenon of crinophagy that triggers the activation of trypsinogen (Halang et al., 2002). Excessive trypsin (Halang et al., 2002) disrupts the protease-antiprotease balance by consumption of specific (PSTI) and nonspecific trypsin inhibitors (α 1-antitrypsin and α 2-macroglobulin). This will activate other zymogens (chymotrypsinogen, proelastase, phospholipase) as well as various protease systems (complement, kinin, coagulation and fibrinolytic factors) triggering a strong inflammatory reaction (Rivera-Chavez et al., 2003). The release of different mediators (platelet activating factor - PAF, cytokines, prostaglandins, leukotriene) stimulates the production of acute-phase proteins (endogenous antiproteases, C-reactive protein - CPR) and the activation of granulocytes and macrophages in the pancreas and peripancreatic level (Sack et al., 2006). Cellular degradation will result in the release of proteolytic and lipolytic enzymes (polymorphonuclear elastase-PMN-e), IL-6 generating free oxygen radicals in excess beyond the natural power of neutralization.

Sack et al., 2006 in the study on the role of inflammatory blood markers when diagnosing acute appendicitis in children revealed that secondary transport in the systemic circulation of many substances produced during the inflammatory reaction will lead to complications: cardiac circulatory failure, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), disseminated intravascular coagulation, acute renal failure, multiple organ

dysfunction (MODS). All these pathophysiological data enhance our understanding of the interest given in the dosage of biological markers (CPR, interleukins, PMN) (Sack et al., 2006).

Undoubtedly, the kinetics of the appearance of these markers represents a progress for early diagnosis and severity assessment, prognosis and rapid application of the appropriate therapeutic measures (Wang et al., 1996).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

A prospective study was used in order to achieve the proposed objectives: to determine the importance of the laboratory tests and to define interleukin-6 as an early predictive marker of acute appendicitis.

In this regard, a group of 90 patients diagnosed with acute appendicitis was created. All patients were hospitalized during 2019 in the surgical units of the County Emergency Clinical Hospital Oradea.

Determinations were made according to the following criteria:

- preparing the patient – fasting (in a fasting state);
- collected specimen - venous blood;
- collecting tube – vacutainer with sodium citrate 0.105 M (ratio sodium citrate/blood=1/9);
- collected quantity
 - as much as the vacuum allows; in order to prevent the partial coagulation of the sample, the proper mixing of the blood and anticoagulant was ensured by movements of tube inversion (5-6 gentle inversions);
 - causes of rejection of the evidence
 - vacutainer is not full (at least 90%);
 - hemolysed or coagulated sample, the sample collected in a tube other than the one with citrate;
 - processing required after collection - the sample was centrifuged 15 minutes at 2,500g;
 - sample stability - the sample is stable for 8 hours at room temperature;
 - the separated plasma is stable for 3 weeks at -20°C; > 1 year at -70°C. Prior to analysis, frozen samples were thawed rapidly in 3-5 min at 37°C. Defrosting at lower temperatures can cause cryoprecipitate.

Determining interleukin- 6

The major actions of interleukin 6 (IL-6) on lymphoid and non-lymphoid cells are modulatory mechanisms of the body's immune and inflammatory responses (Adkinson et al., 2008; Zvedre et al., 2016). Although many of these functions overlap with those of type 1 interleukins (IL-1), such as the synthesis of acute phase reactants and fever, IL-6 also

has anti-inflammatory effects. The IL-6-specific receptor (IL-6R) belongs to the (haematopoietic) cytokine receptor superfamily (Synevo, 2010). IL-6R is a membrane protein complex consisting of two structural and functional subunits: a specific 80-kDa IL-6 binding protein (α chain) and a signal transducer, gp130 (b chain, a component for several types of receptors, such as IL-11, IL-27, IL-31) (Richard et al., 2007; Robert et al., 2008). Cytokine IL-6 is secreted as a polypeptide consisting of 184 amino acids, with a molecular weight of about 21 kDa, depending on the degree of glycosylation (285). Like IL-1, IL-6 is secreted by macrophages, being also synthesized by T and B lymphocytes, fibroblasts and endothelial cells, keratinocytes, synoviocytes, chondrocytes, epithelial cells (Adkinson et al., 2008; Richard et al., 2007; Robert et al., 2008). Thus, IL-6 is produced in response to bacterial and viral infections, inflammation or trauma, rapidly reaching detectable plasma levels unlike many other cytokines (Robert et al., 2008). Cytokine IL-6 is considered the major mediator for the hepatic production of acute-phase reactants: fibrinogen, serum amyloid A, haptoglobin, C-reactive protein (Sack et al., 2006). Following exposure to IL-6, the liver decreases the albumin and transferrin synthesis, initiating processes of hepatocyte regeneration instead (Synevo Laboratory, 2014). IL-6 cytokine stimulates humoral and cellular immune responses by acting on both B and T lymphocytes. IL-6 plays a role in the differentiation and growth of the B cells and stimulates their production of immunoglobulins (Laborator Synevo, 2014). It also promotes T cell activation, growth and differentiation. It is involved in the pathogenesis of multiple myeloma, being used as a prognostic factor of the disease. IL-6 stimulates haematopoiesis (acts synergistically with IL-3), induces ACTH secretion and other pituitary hormones (prolactin, growth hormone, luteinising hormone) (Boucher, 2000). In addition to its pro-inflammatory effects, IL-6 also mediates several anti-inflammatory effects: while IL-1 and TNF mutually induce their synthesis as well as that of IL-6, IL-6 completes this inflammatory cascade as it inhibits the synthesis of both IL-1 and TNF and stimulates the synthesis of IL-1RA (Adkinson et al., 2008).

Recommendations for the determination of IL-6

Interleukin titres determined in various biological fluids may be used to diagnose immune disorders and to monitor treatments only when correlated with complementary clinical and paraclinical data (Laboratory Corporation of America, 2014).

Preparing the patient - fasting (in a fasting state) or postprandial (www.labcorp.com 2014)

Collected specimen - venous blood (www.labcorp.com 2014)

Collecting tube - vacutainer with no anticoagulants, with / without separator gel (www.labcorp.com 2014)

Collected quantity - minimum 0.5 mL serum (Synevo Laboratory, 2014).

Causes of sample rejection - intensely hemolyzed, jaundiced, lipemic or bacterially contaminated samples; samples that did not arrive frozen at the laboratory (www.labcorp.com 2014).

Processing after collection - the serum is separated by centrifugation as soon as possible after complete coagulation, and the sample shall be immediately frozen at -20°C; samples collected outside laboratory points shall be transported in the container for frozen samples (www.labcorp.com 2014).

Sample stability – the serum is stable for one month at -20°C; do not defrost/refreeze (Laborator Synevo, 2014).

Method - the immunochemical method with chemiluminescence detection (Laborator Synevo, 2014) **(CLIA)**

Reference values - <3.8 pg / mL (Synevo Laboratory, 2014).

Interpretation of results

Increased levels of the marker are found in:

- rheumatoid arthritis (www.labcorp.com 2014; Fionula et al., 2008).
- multiple myeloma: prognostic factor (Greer et al., 2004)
- autoimmune diseases – lymphomas (www.labcorp.com 2014)
- sepsis – AIDS (www.labcorp.com 2014)
- alcoholic liver disease (www.labcorp.com 2014)
- viral infections (www.labcorp.com 2014)
- transplant rejection (www.labcorp.com 2014)
- severe preeclampsia.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bioclinical examinations were recorded in 90 patients (33.5%), 45 women and 45 men, representing 30.2% of the female group and 37.5% of the male group.

As far as the biological markers are concerned, the progress made in the field of prognostic evolution of acute appendicitis is based on the current knowledge of the pathophysiological events that appear during the evolution of the disease (Atkinson et al., 1998). These markers are a priority in the current medical research due to their role in human pathology in general and to the fact that these bioactive compounds may become therapeutic targets. The ideal marker should be an objective indicator and non-observer-dependent, simple, fast and cheap, safe and non-invasive, not influenced by comorbidities, with a high positive predictive value and usable in the first 24-48 hours after the onset of the disease.

Graph 1. Distribution of cases by gender and IL-6

There are significant differences between the two genders, male and female, in terms of IL-6 ($p < 0.001$). Thus, the number of female patients with normal values of IL-6 is almost two times higher than the number of male patients (55.6% versus 28.9%) and the average value of acute appendicitis is within normal limits (425.0 pg /mL).

Interleukin 6 (IL-6) is a pro-inflammatory cytokine synthesized by a wide variety of cells, including the periacinar fibroblasts, under the action of $TNF\alpha$ and $IL-1\beta$. It is the major mediator of acute-phase protein synthesis. Serum concentration precedes the growth of CRP by 24-36 hours and evolves in parallel with it. The experimental evidence showed that IL-6 overexpression induces severe forms of acute appendicitis and its counteraction with monoclonal antibodies has protective effects. In acute appendicitis the increased values correlated with the complicated and lethal forms of the disease. Recently it has been reported that IL-6 is the best prognostic marker of respiratory failure. Despite all these shortcomings and contradictions, IL-6 remains one of the most widely used biological markers for the early detection of the severity of acute appendicitis.

CONCLUSIONS

The inflammatory markers appear in the serum later than the previous ones, the acute-phase proteins, C-reactive protein and ESR, but they present the advantage of monitoring the clinical evolution, offering complementary opportunities.

These biochemical parameters could help identify the “ideal marker”, which is why they should be evaluated prospectively, on large samples of patients that include significant percentages of severe cases.

In addition to the diagnostic role, these new markers may become therapeutic targets, their manipulation allowing the prevention or alleviation of severe acute appendicitis.

The hopes for the future are related to the markers of appendix injury and those of inflammation, in particular cytokines, provided that a dosing methodology that will make them useful in emergency cases is developed.

Genetic manipulation is a new promise in identifying the markers of severe acute appendicitis.

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SUBCONJUNCTIVAL HAEMORRHAGE IN HANGING

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Abstract

Hanging was first introduced in England after 450 a. Hr., being practiced until 1965 and was the most widespread method of execution during history and because of this reason they were classified as judicial and non-judicial. Hanging consists of a ligature with careful knot placed below the occiput and complete suspension of the entire body weight of the victim. Non-judicial are those that take place in homes and jails and are frequently due to incomplete suspension, with part of the victim's body laying on the ground.

Key-words: hanging, subconjunctivalhaemorrhage, knot

INTRODUCTION

Hanging is one of the main methods of life ending in the world and there is even a book written by a macedo-romanian doctor who revolutionized the international scientific world with his investigations and innovations about hanging. The book is about Mina Minovici (1868-1941), a forensic doctor who self experimented the mechanical autostrangulation effects of asphyxia.

The main counties in Romania where hanging is chosen as a main life ending method of death are those where people of Hungarian nationality are the majority. In most of the cases, people who want to suicide themselves through hanging make a knot or a double-ring which is convoluted around the neck and is made of a wire, a belt, a chain, a scarf or a rope (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Chain used for hanging.
Drawing made by Albisor (Romocian) Celestina

There are two positions of the body in hanging: the one in which the body is in complete suspension like in Fig. 2 and the other one in which the body is still in contact with the ground like in Fig. nr 3.

Fig. 2. Complete hanging (the body does not touch the ground).
Drawing made by Albisor (Romocian) Celestina

Fig. 3. Incomplete hanging (the body does touch the ground).
Drawing made by Albisor (Romocian) Celestina

The incomplete hanging is the most interesting and most used by women because is painful and the death is sudden because of the cerebral anaemia. If the knot is located at the posterior part of the neck than almost always the head has an anterior and down inclination, the chin being in contact with the chest. When the knot is located on the lateral part of the neck, the head will be tilted to the right or to the left. The stages of death through hanging are the loss of consciousness, spasms and muscular contractions and the last one is the death which ends the process. An important indicator for a lethal hanging is a subconjunctival haemorrhage even if it is not specific and it disappears with the occurrence of signs of putrefaction. Subconjunctival haemorrhage appears due to the raised venous/capillary pressure sufficiently to cause the haemorrhage of the face and neck above the level of ligature.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

We analyzed 86 people death in 2017 through hanging, complete and incomplete method. 13 chose to hang in an incomplete method and summarized 15%, while the rest of 73 chose the complete method and summarized 85%, Chart 1,2.

Chart 1 and 2. 13 people hanged in an incomplete method, summarizing 15% and 73 death through complete method, summing 85%

Those with complete method were separated into two groups: one consisted of those with subconjunctivalhaemorrhage and the second group without subconjunctivalhaemorrhage. The first group had 12 bodies in which subconjunctivalhaemorrhage was discovered after death and the second group had 12 bodies without any subconjunctivalhaemorrhage (Graphic 1).

Graphic 1. The two groups, with and without subconjunctivalhaemorrhage

In the incomplete hanging method, no body was identified as having subconjunctivalhaemorrhage.

CONCLUSIONS

Identifying a subconjunctivalhaemorrhage in patients whose death happened by hanging is a certain sign of a traumatic death and is considered to be a hallmark of asphyxial deaths, being in fact just a vascular phenomena related to mechanical factors, unrelated to asphyxia or hypoxia.

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MODERN TEACHING STRATEGIES IN TEACHING ROMANIAN LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE

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Abstract

The discourse on the reform of the current school refers, in particular, to the permanent renewal and improvement of the learning offer, which the system proposes to the student. In this sense, the aim of studying the Romanian language and literature during the compulsory schooling period is to train, progressively, a young man with a basic communication and literary culture, able to understand the world around him, to communicate and interact with his peers, to effectively integrate in the context of the future school career, respectively professional. The student must efficiently and creatively use his own abilities to solve concrete problems in daily life, to be able to continue the learning process at any stage of his life. Nowadays, the emphasis is on procedural learning, on structuring modern strategies and procedures for problem solving, exploitation and investigation, characteristic of the communicative activity.

Key words: interactive teaching methods, educational process, competences, methods, teacher, student, critical thinking, motivation.

INTRODUCTION

Romanian language and literature is a discipline through which the study aims to achieve specific objectives and competences, and the general aims would be:

Forming a system of attitudes, values and behaviors focused on: strengthening the interest for learning and self-education; awareness of the spiritual and ethical values conveyed through language and literature; understanding the meaning of language - and spiritual creation, in general - in shaping national identity and integrating them into the universal;

Formation of a set of knowledge regarding: language systems, as building blocks of efficient social communication; the diversity, the aesthetic value of the beletristic creations in the national and universal literature;

Formation of intellectual capacities regarding: optimization of the operations of thought and development of specific creativity;

The rational practice of the language in order to understand the structure and functionality of the language, as a unitary system, in permanent evolution;

The formation of cultural representations includes: developing the availability of reception of crisis, literary and non-literary messages ;

The acquisition of methods and techniques of intellectual work is progressively achieved by deepening the accumulated knowledge to which is added permanently new information.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Starting from the premise that the Romanian language and literature lesson must be a valuable one, from the perspective of the active-participative methods, of a formative type, in support of the development of the students' knowledge, it is appropriate to emphasize a first finding, which refers to the achievement of operational objectives. cognitive and affective, through specific didactic strategies: learning by discovery, heuristic conversation, "bunny" method, dials, didactic game, "ice breaking", brainstorming, Venn diagrams, experiment, case study, project learning, activity on teams, etc., methods aimed at achieving general competences

The teaching and learning methods specific to the Romanian language and literature are multiple.

Brainstorming - can be done on a topic that has to do with the topic of the studied text or its key elements. Starting from the answers received, you can create a bunch of ideas that synthetically group the students' answers.

Examples: What do you think of when you hear / read the word "fantastic", "romantic", etc.?

Name a feature that you think is important for the pastoral era.

The modern method of brainstorming, an active-participative group method, whose use in the didactic approach can last from 15 to 60 minutes, can be used successfully in the gymnasium, in the elaboration of free collective compositions, in approaching modern literary works, with finally open, in explaining polysemantism

Quintet - a creative method, in which in five verses a content of ideas is synthesized. You can add a drawing. The first verse is a key word about the discussion, being usually substantive. The second verse is made up of two words that describe the noun in question, being adjectives. The third verse is made up of three words that express an action, being, as a rule, verbs in the gerund mode. The fourth verse contains four words and expresses the feelings towards the subject. The fifth verse is a word that synthesizes those presented.

Mutual teaching: if students are put in the role of teachers, they have the opportunity to (re) learn what they thought they knew. When students teach their colleagues, they practice and develop their own way of arranging

teaching strategies. Mutual teaching can be done in groups of four to seven members and consists of the following:

- all participants have a copy with the same text. They distribute their tasks and text;
- all read the text and one of them summarizes it orally;
- asks the others a question based on the text they will try to answer;
- the student who "teaches" clarifies some things that are unclear to colleagues, at their request or on their own initiative;
- the students will predict together the content of the next fragment and the role of the teacher will be taken by another student in the group;

The steps the student must follow: summarize what he / she has read; ask a question to others about the paragraph read in order to clarify and understand it more clearly ; predict / anticipate what will happen in the next fragment;

Putting students in the position of teacher who teaches others diminishes teacher-student distance, creating an educational climate that is much more conducive to learning.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

From the number of methods presented and their descriptions, we must conclude that there are many ways to energize the education process and to remove the connotation of difficulties that the term of school education entails.

Centering on the student means using the student's experiential knowledge as an individual and creating conditions for sharing this knowledge with the other individuals who are trained or educated according to a mixed, individual and collective experience, thus increasing the degree of collective experience to all members of the group.

It is good for a teacher to know and apply as many teaching methods as possible to avoid devaluation of the method by repetition.

Therefore, active - participatory methods should be used with caution. But the methods should not be ignored because they energize the learning process and motivate the students .

CONCLUSION

Participatory methods require a large number of hours to prepare lessons from the teacher, design efforts, time efforts, large materials and special measures to reduce the risk of unforeseen situations that would destroy the entire activity. That is why the teacher must have several alternatives to approach the lesson. The lesson itself might be felt to be too short for the correct teaching scenario to unfold.

I believe that such modern methods of learning-teaching, used with discernment and only to the extent that traditional methods are not neglected, improve the communication between students and that between students and teachers, creating positive attitudes, at the level of the class involved in the activity. In addition, through these educational experiences, students prepare for life, for their future activity, learning useful things about teamwork, about responsibility, giving, seriousness, contributing to the common effort .

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INCIDENCE OF LYME DISEASE IN BIHOR COUNTY IN 2018-2019 IN COMPARED WITH 2012-2014

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Abstract

In this paper we shall establish the incidence of Lyme Disease in the county of Bihor between January 2018 to June 2019 and compare the acquired data to previous results obtained in a published study from 01.01.2012-01.10.2014. During this period, a total of 696 patients were consulted for a tick bite, of those patients, 132 have had a positive diagnosis of Lyme Borreliosis (19%) from who 32 have been hospitalized for Lyme Disease (24% of the confirmed cases).

*An increase in Lyme Borreliosis:19% in comparison with 15% in 2014 is observed without significant differences in terms of rural/urban distribution as well as in gender one. Most patients were diagnosed in the summer month June – July – August. Distribution by age shows an increase in the number of patients from 0 to 10 years old and older section, 51 years old upwards. Early diagnosis of Lyme disease is important to resolve current signs and symptoms, eliminate *B. burgdorferi* infection, and prevent later complications; therefore, education is important in preventing or mitigating disease.*

Key words: *Borrelia burgdorferi*, Western Blot, ELISA, tick bite

INTRODUCTION

Lyme disease is an emerging infectious disease caused by at least three species of bacteria belonging to the genus *Borrelia*: *Borrelia burgdorferi sensu stricto*, *Borrelia afzeli* and *Borrelia garini*. It is transmitted to humans by the bite of infected ticks belonging to a few species of the genus *Ixodes*. (Hess A, Buchmann J, Zettl UK, *et al.* 1999), (Hu MD, Linden 2009), (Mulleger RR, 2004), (Rapini, Ronald P. Bologna *et al.* 2007), (Puius YA, Kalish RA, June 2008), (Ryan KJ, Ray CG (editors), 2004). After inoculation of the bacteria at the skin level, following a tick bite, Lyme Borreliosis evolves schematically in three phases: The primary phase is essentially expressed through a cutaneous lesion spreading from the point of inoculation: the *Erythema Migrans*.

Typical symptoms include headache, fever and fatigue and a skin rash called erythema migrans. (Stanek G, Strle F, 2008). From the point of inoculation, *Borrelia* may also disseminate hematogenously and settle in several organs such as the heart, the brain, the articulations, which may in turn be areas of secondary clinical manifestations, observed a couple of

weeks following the initial contamination. In some cases the infection can spread to nervous system. (Samuels DS;Radolf, JD (editors), 2010), (Seltzer EG, Gerber MA, Cartter ML et al,2000). Various acute neurological problems, termed *Neuroborreliosis*, appear in 10-15% of untreated patients. These include facial palsy, which is the loss of muscle tone on one or both sides of the face, as well as meningitis, which involves severe headaches, neck stiffness, and sensitivity to light. Radiculoneuritis causes shooting pains that may interfere with sleep, as well as abnormal skin sensations. (Wang G, van Dam AP, Schwartz I et al, 1999). Mild encephalitis may lead to memory loss, sleep disturbances, or mood changes. (Steere AC, Sikand VK, Schoen RT et al, 2003).

Later, chronic clinical manifestations constitute the third phase of the disease, that appears generally after several years: *Acrodermatitis chronica atrophicans* (ACA); can occur in any age group but it is most common in adults, mainly those in their 40s or 50s., usually do not remember tick bite in their past. Patients who have had prior erythema migrans can be reinfected (meaning that the first infection has been successfully treated and they have a new infection with *B burgdorferi*). (Stricker RB,L. et al 2008).

The human contamination is superposed to the period of maximal activity of ticks, depending on the climatic conditions. It therefore occurs mostly between the beginning of spring and the end of fall.

It has been suggested in the recent years that the variations in climatic conditions subsequent to climate change (increase in global temperatures, shorter winters) may lead to an increase of activity and reproduction of ticks, leading to an increase in contamination.

The ticks that transmit Lyme disease usually transmit other tickborne diseases. (Auwaerter PG, Aucott J, Dumler JS, 2004), (Cairns V, Godwin J, 2005), (Chabria SB, Lawrason J, 2007), (Dandache P, Nadelman RB, 2008), (Edlow JA, 2007), (Fallon BA, Niels JA, 1994), (Fahrer H, Sauvain MJ, Zhioua E, Van Hoecke C, Gern LE, 1998), (Johnson RC, 1996).

The diagnosis of Lyme Disease is mostly based upon the clinical examination, Enzyme-linked immunoabsorbent assay (ELISA) test confirmed by Western blot test.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the hospital of Infectious Diseases of Oradea and the department of infectious diseases of Polyclinic hospital, we consulted the archives and registers from January 2018 to June 2019 included.

During this period, a total of 696 patients consulted for a tick bite and/or Lyme disease, and of those patients, 132 have had a positive

diagnosis of Lyme Borreliosis (19% of the total pool), and of those 132 patients, 32 have been hospitalized for Lyme Disease (24% of the confirmed cases).

Out of the 696 patients that consulted, 343 are men, and 353 are women. 272 of them are young patients, less than or up to 20 years old (39% of the total pool).

The chart above is the “Distribution of patients by age” of 2012 (Turda C., Csep A., 2012)

We can observe that the number of consults from young patients (up to 30 years old) between those two time periods is relatively close to one another (387 patients in 2012, versus 343 patients in 2018-2019).

Yet the number of patients from 0 to 10 years old has dramatically increased in 2018-2019 (204 patients versus 68 patients in 2012).

It is important to note that the older sections of patients (from 51 years old upwards) present an increase in 2018-2019 (155 patients), by comparison with 2012 (56 patients), whereas patients from 21 to 30 years old seem to have significantly reduced (71 patients in 2018-2019 versus 184 patients in 2012).

Gender distribution in 2012

During the study period of January 2018 to June 2019, out of the 696 consults at the Hospital of Infectious diseases of Oradea, 132 received a positive diagnosis for Lyme disease (around 19% of the total pool).

Distribution of Lyme disease 01/2018 - 06/2019

Out of those 132 confirmed cases, 32 patients were hospitalized (around 24% of the confirmed cases).

Hospitalized Lyme disease cases 01/2018 - 06/2019

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the study period of January 2018 to June 2019, out of the 696 consults at the Hospital of Infectious diseases of Oradea for tick bites 132 received a positive diagnosis for Lyme disease (19% of the total pool); it is worth noticing the increase in percentage of positive cases of Lyme disease.

The previous study from 01/01/2012 to the 01/10/2014 included 615 patients and revealed that 92 patients (15%) were positively diagnosed for Lyme Disease (Csep A., Turda C., 2014).

When comparing the values obtained in 2012-2014 with 2018- 2019 we may notice an increase in the total percentage of confirmed cases.

We can observe that the number of consults from young patients (up to 30 years old) between those two time periods is relatively similar, yet the number of patients from 0 to 10 years old has dramatically increased in 2018-2019, by comparison with 2012. It is important to note that the older sections of patients (from 51 years old upwards) present an increase in 2018-2019, by comparison with 2012, whereas patients from 21 to 30 years old seem to have significantly reduced in 2018-2019.

There are several hypothesis to explain those increases: there likely is a better triage and screening; secondly, it is important to notice the

important amount of younger patients, which could spend more time outdoors and might be more frequently screened, and have less knowledge about the first signs and symptoms of Lyme Borreliosis. Moreover, the elderly patients also have increased in proportion, which could be explained by a better understanding and knowledge about the disease, and therefore more frequent consults; or supposedly because grand-parents would accompany children in higher-risk areas (parcs, playgrounds...etc).

The monthly distribution of the disease remains similar from 2012-2014 to 2018-2019, with higher incidence within the late months of spring, and the summer months (with a special emphasis on June, July and August).

As it was expected, there are more cases of Lyme Borreliosis in patients from rural areas, than from urban areas (though rather subtle), this is easily explained by more frequent exposure to the outdoors (fields, animals, forests).

CONCLUSIONS

Through this comparative study, we have demonstrated an increase in Lyme disease over the course of a few years in the county of Bihor, even though the general education of patients about the disease is likely to have increased.

We know that insect repellents and pesticides hardly work on ticks, which could be a potential explanation for this increase. The absence of vaccine is also a likely cause. Some literature suggests that another cause for it is climate change: ticks thrive in warmer environments, and as proven over and over again, the planet is undergoing a dramatic warming for the past several decades, and is likely to continue.

Moreover, Lyme Borreliosis remains an under-diagnosed pathology, since the first stage of the disease isn't a constant (the ECM potentially being absent or unnoticed in about 30% to 50% of cases), and the second phase presents signs and symptoms which aren't specific, leading to a high rate of misdiagnosis. On top of it all, when the diagnosis is made, it isn't always reported (even though in many countries it is compulsory to do so) by a lot of general practitioners (since they often are the first ones exposed to Lyme disease patients). It is important to continue educating the general population, and medical professionals, about this pathology, as well as insisting with doctors about the importance of reporting it, narrowing down endemic areas, frequently examining pets and farm animals for ticks and their proper removal, in the hopes of reducing the zoonotic transmission.

Early diagnosis of Lyme disease is important to resolve current signs and symptoms, eliminate *B. burgdorferi* infection, and prevent later complications; therefore, education is important in preventing or mitigating

disease. Landscape and host management practices combined with the judicious use of an acaricide can provide excellent tick control with minimal risk or impact to the environment or other wildlife.

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THE ETIOLOGY OF BREAST CANCER, RISK FACTORS, PROTECTION FACTORS

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Abstract

The present paper aims to support the importance of knowledge of risk factors, of protection factors in the etiology of breast cancer and their influence in order to improve the quality of life of patients and increase healing chances.

Key words: breast cancer, etiology, risk factors, protection factors, genes, estrogen, quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is a condition with complex implications in evolution over the quality of life, it is characterized by an evolution with extremely high variability from one patient to another. It is admitted today that most breast cancers are dependent on hormonal factors that influence changes in breast-level from birth to advanced ages.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Knowledge has been analyzed until the present time of the etiology of breast cancer. The influence of hormonal factors, geneticsinheritances, premalignant lesions, cellular mutations of normal cells, suppressor genes, but also the influence of external factors are important to be known by professionals and patients, to be able to have tailored interventions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Certain aspects, such as protection factors, may change the likelihood of a person developing breast cancer or not, but there are also risk factors with which they cannot fight, age, gender, genetic inheritance.

1. Epidemiology

Breast cancer is a major public health problem, having an incidence in the European Union and a high mortality. In 2006, the annual incidence adjusted by age of breast cancer in the European Union (data from 25 countries) was 110,3/100.000 women, and the annual mortality through breast cancer was 25/100.000 women¹. Breast cancer is the most common neoplastic disorder in women, in our country, with a number of 4200 newly diagnosed cases and 2500 deaths per year². Although there is an increase in the number of new cases the mortality rate remains constant in the last 20 years³, more than half of the diseased are diagnosed in advanced stages and therefore the therapeutic costs are high and the results less good.

2. Etiology

The breast is an integral part of the female reproductive system with a role in breastfeeding, consisting of glandular tissue, fatty tissue and fibrome tissue. The breast is considered an interactive community in which the cells of the ducts and lobules interact and influence the fibrome tissue, the blood vessels and the surrounding fat, the most important component being the lactiferous ducts system, responsible for Lactation. The lactiferous ducts unite inside the breast in a common duct that opens up to the skin, being between 6 and 9 main ducts that open at the nipple level. At the end of the ductal system are lobules. Inside, the ductal system is lined with a layer of small cells that suffer changes, which appear to be involved in the appearance of breast cancer. The cells of adipose tissue that develop around canalicules and lobules are also specialized cells, correlated with ductal cells and lobular, influencing each other. The dysfunctions that occur at the correlation level between these cells create conditions for the development and growth of breast cancer.

At birth the breast is not fully developed, so in puberty when it develops it needs stem cells that are able to transform into another type of ductal cells or lobular, they will intervene in the period when the breast produces milk and when the breastfeeding period ends, these cells could become mutants, triggering cancer. During the monthly menstrual cycle, changes are produced in the ductal and lobular system, as well as the surrounding tissue, changes being influenced by the hormonal level. Breast transformation during lactation is coordinated by the level of estrogen,

1 Clinical recommendations for breast cancer, ESMO recommendations for diagnosis, treatment and follow-up, *Annals of Oncology* 20 (Supplement 4): iv10 – Iv14, 2009, doi: 10.1093/annonc/mdp114

2 Guilezan N, Diagnostic and Treatment guide, Oncology Committee

3 Ghilezan N, Vitoc C, Găfainanu MR, et al. Therapeutic methods and results in breast cancer, Romania 1990-1992. Multicentre Study of SRRO. *Radioter & Oncol Med* 1996; II, 3-4:1-7.

progesterone, prolactin and oxytocin. During pregnancy, the maturation of the lobules occurs, the type 4 mature lobulum is maintained during pregnancy and during lactation. Mature lobules are less vulnerable to cancer, immature structures being considered to be more susceptible to carcinogenesis, which would explain why early age pregnancies decrease the risk of breast cancer. At menopause fluctuations in estrogen levels and decreasing the level of progesterone attract a number of specific changes in which the mammary gland is involved. Women who present a higher level of estrogen and testosterone have a higher vulnerability towards breast cancer.

To develop and to thrive any cancer needs two fundamental elements: the first is a cell that for some reason, either hereditary or carcinotic, has undergone a mutation of an important part of the DNA, mutation that modifies its potential behavior; the second element is represented by the neighbouring cells that can positively or negatively influence cells with mutations, otherwise said the cancer is caused by a combination of genes altered by carcinogens and a favorable environment for growth and propagation.

The oncogenes and suppressive genes are involved in the development of cells and only if mutations are produced they become carcinogenic. One of the proto-oncogenes is related to the epidermal EGFR growth factor, useful during puberty when important development-related transformations are happening. One such factor is the epidermal growth factor 2 called HER-2/neu, or erB-B2, which may undergo a change in the type of amplification that can cause an accelerated growth and multiplication of a malignant cell in the vicinity.

The tempering of oncogenes and proto-oncogenes is performed by tumor suppressant genes that act as brakes in cell multiplication with mutations. Such a suppressant gene is p53 that prevents cells with an AND that has undergone mutations to divide. If the p53 gene is compromised the division of cells with mutations of AND it cannot be stopped. Molecular biology has highlighted two mutations occurring in BRCA 1 and BRCA 2 suppression genes, mutations that are responsible for the occurrence of hereditary breast cancer.

As with other localization of cancer, and in malignant tumors of the breast local dissemination (in the breast) is done by invasion, tumor cells infiltrating tissues along galactose canals and fascial septures to the surrounding fat, which gives The tumor's irregular appearance, starry, a special form of cutaneous infiltration is the "pating nodules", small tumor formations located in the dermal lymph nodes of the breast or exceeding the boundaries of the organ⁴. It is admitted that until the clinical discovery (1-2

4 Bălanescu I., Blidaru AL., Breast cancer, Angelescu N., Surgical Pathology Treaty, vol. 1

cm) or imaging (a few mm) of a breast cancer can pass several years, a breast cancer being curable when the diagnosis is put into the preclinical phases of its evolution⁵. However, approximately 7% of breast cancers have a very rapid evolution⁶, the disease is generalized in a few months. The local extension process is made either to the fascia of the pectoral muscle and the thoracic wall to which it can be fixed, either to the skin it invades, the characteristic signs of orange peel, edema, ulceration with superinfection and hemorrhage⁷.

3. Risk factors

- a) Female sex, the most important risk factor is even female sex.
- b) Age: the more we get older, the more our cells divide and more DNA errors can occur. Three-quarters of breast cancers are diagnosed after menopause. The risk of developing a breast cancer is almost 1:20,000 at the age of 25, but up to the age of 80, the risk reaches 1:8.
- c) Hormonal factors

Estrogen: the risk of developing a breast cancer increases the exposure to higher amounts of long time to this hormone. The risk is increased in women who have had their first menstruation at less than 12 years of age or in women in whose menopause has been installed at the age of 55 years or older. Studies have shown that women who have higher concentrations of estrogen in post-menopausal blood have a twice greater risk than women who have lower estrogen concentrations. Most major risk factors for breast cancer can actually be explained by their effect on hormones. Hormone replacement therapy is sometimes prescribed to relieve the symptoms associated with menopause. There are two main types: combination therapy, with estrogen and progesterone, and estrogen-only therapy. Multiple studies have shown that post-menopausal hormonal substitution therapy increases the risk of developing breast cancer, especially the combination of estrogen and progesterone. The largest clinical trials in this field were the "Women's Health Initiative", conducted in the United States of America, and "Million Women Study"-The study of a million of women-in the UK.

- d) Family history: Theoretically, if the mother or sister had breast cancer, a woman's risk of getting sick is double. However, more than 8 out of 10 women who have had cases of breast cancer in the family will never have this disease. This risk can be determined by an

5Rochet Y. - Cancer Gynecologiques et Mammaires, Flammarion medecine sciences, 1986.

6 Angelescu N., treatment of Surgical Pathology, vol. 1, Medical Publishing House, Bucharest, 2003

7 Angelescu N., treatment of Surgical Pathology, vol. 1, Medical Publishing House, Bucharest, 2003

inherited defect gene. There are two main genes involved in the genetic forms of breast cancer are BRCA1 and BRCA2. The risk of developing a breast cancer in people who have inherited one of these two "defects" genes varies between 45% – 85%, the direct inheritance of specific genetic defects such as mutations in the BRCA1 gene occurring in chromosome 17 (Locus 17q21), in 5-10% of all breast cancers⁸, the altered transmission of the BRCA 2 gene competes in the occurrence of breast cancer and especially in the occurrence of ovarian cancer⁹. This risk can be reduced by prophylactic surgery, with careful genetic evaluation and counselling, prophylactical treatment, careful supervision through mammograms and breast MRI.

Genes that accelerate cell division are called oncogenes. Proto-oncogenes are genes that normally help cells grow. When a proto-oncogenic mutates (changes) or if there are too many copies of it, it becomes an unhealthy gene, which can be activated permanently, so the cell grows uncontrolled, becomes oncogenic and can transform normal mammalar epithelial cell into a malignant one.

Tumor suppressant genes are normal genes that slow down cell division, repair DNA errors or intervene in apoptosis. When the tumor suppressant genes do not work properly, cells can grow uncontrolled which can lead to cancer. RB suppressant genes, NM23, p53, inhibit the proliferation process of tumor cells¹⁰. Certain mutations in DNA that "activate" oncogenes or "disable" tumor suppression genes can cause normal breast cells to become cancerous.

Hereditary transmission of breast cancer is very much discussed. It is acknowledged today that this issue should be seen from 2 points of view: the family aggregation syndrome involving a genetic predisposition dependent on interactions with the environment, family history of the Li-Fraumeni syndrome, the Cowdensyndrome, the Muir syndrome, ataxia-teleangiectasy and ovarian cancer, increase the possibility of developing breast cancer.

Inherited genetic mutations

Normal breast cells can become cancerous due to DNA changes (mutations). Some mutations in the DNA are inherited, mutations exist in every cell in the body and can substantially increase the risk of developing

8 Bălanescu I., Anghel Rodica- Breast cancer; Surgical Pathology; Under the redaction of Angelescu N., Celsius Publishing House, Bucharest, 1997.

9 Dickson R.B. Lippman M.E. - Advances in Cellular and Molecular Biology of Breast Cancer, Boston, 1996.

10 Angelescu N., Treatise on Surgical Pathology, vol. 1, Medical Publishing House, Bucharest, 2003

certain cancers. BRCA genes (BRCA1 and BRCA2) are tumour suppressant genes. Modification of one of these genes can be inherited familial. Genetic tests can identify some women who have inherited mutations in tumour suppression genes BRCA1 or BRCA2 (rarely other genes like PTEN or TP53). Mutations of tumor suppressant genes as BRCA genes are considered to have a "high degree of penetration" because they often lead to cancer. The genes involved can affect issues such as hormonal levels and metabolism.

Acquired genetic changes

These acquired mutations of oncogenes and / or tumor suppressor genes may derive from other factors, such as radiation or chemicals that cause cancer. Tests to detect acquired genetic changes can help physicians more accurately formulate the prognosis for breast cancer. For example, tests can identify those cases where the cancer cells have too many copies of the HER2 oncogene, cancers that tend to be more aggressive, but drugs that specifically target these cancers have been developed. The risk of developing breast cancer increases as it progresses in age. Breast cancer is more common among women over the age of 50, who have gone through menopause, 8 out of 10 breast cancer cases occur in women over 50.

- e) Personal history of breast cancer: a woman who has had breast cancer has a higher risk of developing another cancer in the same breast or in the other.
- f) Personal history of other diseases: breast cancer occurs more frequently in women who have previously suffered from other cancers: Hodgkin's lymphoma (especially at young ages and if treated by radiation), malignant melanoma, lung cancer, colorectal cancer, uterine body cancer, lymphocytic leukemia chronic.
- g) Benign breast disease: most benign (non-cancerous) breast diseases do not increase the risk of cancer. Depending on how dangerous they are, these diseases are divided into three categories:
 - i. Non-proliferative lesions - in which cells do not divide, do not grow, include: mastitis, fibrocystic mastopathy, ductal ectasia, steatonecrosis, single papilloma, lipomas.
 - ii. Proliferative lesions without atypia - the cells divide in excess, but they are normal, include: ductal hyperplasia, fibroadenomas, sclerosing adenosis, papillomatosis.
 - iii. Proliferative lesions with atypia - the cells divide excessively, and some no longer look normal, significantly increase the risk of cancer (~ 3 times). They include atypical lobular hyperlasia, atypical ductal hyperplasia, in situ lobular carcinoma. In situ lobular carcinoma is a disease in which abnormal cells grow, the presence of in situ lobular

carcinoma indicates an increased risk of developing cancer in either breast¹¹. In situ ductal carcinoma, on the other hand, is a form of early cancer that can turn into invasive cancer. However, only one in 6 women with lobular or ductal carcinoma in situ will develop breast cancer within 10 years.

- h) Density of the breasts: some women have more glandular and fibrous tissue, and their breasts have a higher density on mammograms, with more mammary cells present and the risk of developing cancer is increased up to 2 times.
- i) Smoking and alcohol consumption: alcohol consumption slightly increases the risk of developing breast cancer, smoking increases the risk, especially in women who smoke from a young age.
- j) Height and weight: older women have a higher risk of developing breast cancer, women who had a higher birth weight have a higher risk of breast cancer before menopause. Overweight or postmenopausal obese women also have an increased risk, overweight women also have increased levels of insulin in the blood, another hormone that seems to increase the risk.
- k) Social environment: women in Western countries may have an increased risk of developing breast cancer.
- l) X-ray exposure: exposure to radiation increases the risk of many cancers, chest radiotherapy for the treatment of Hodgkin's lymphoma, especially if done in childhood, can increase the risk of breast cancer.
- m) Assumed and unproven risk factors: trauma to the breast, antiperspirants, abortions, stress (breast tumors are not proven to be its consequences), breast implants (silicone implants most commonly associated with a rare form - lymphoma with large anaplastic cells), working in night shifts (slightly increased risk).

4. PROTECTION FACTORS

As risk factors increase the likelihood of someone getting sick of a certain disease, there are also protective factors that can help to lower this probability.

- a. Pregnancy is a protection factor. Breast cancer occurs more frequently in women who do not have children-or who bear the first child at an older age, a woman who has the first child over 35 years has a risk of 5 times higher to develop this disease against a woman who has the first child at 18 years.

¹¹Bălanescu I., Blidaru AL., breast cancer, Angelescu N., treatment of Surgical Pathology, vol. 1, Medical publishing house Bucharest, 2001.

- b. Breastfeeding – breastfeeding women have a lower risk of developing breast cancer, especially if they had the first child at a younger age.
- c. Physical activity-studies show that the movement (for half an hour, 5 times a week) decreases the risk of breast cancer by 20% (one-fifth), even a few walks at a more rapid pace may decrease the risk.
- d. Nutrition- it is estimated that we could avoid almost one in ten cases of cancer just by changing the diet. There are some conclusions: sugars, carbohydrates, fats especially saturated fat after menopause, can double the risk, lactates through their calcium content has a protective effect, fibers, fruits and vegetables contain many antioxidants, prevent damage to cells, soybeans and phytoestrogens, seem to slightly decrease the risk.

CONCLUSIONS

Breast cancer is characterized by an evolution of extremely high variability from one patient to another. It is admitted today that most breast cancers are dependent on hormonal factors that influence changes in breast-level from birth to advanced ages. Certain aspects, such as protection factors, may change the likelihood of a person developing breast cancer or not, but there are also risk factors with which they cannot fight, age, gender, genetic inheritance.

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THERAPEUTIC EDUCATION – NECESSARY MEASURE FOR ACHIEVING GOALS IN DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

Patients with diabetes mellitus rarely achieve glycaemic targets, generally defined as HbA1c < 7% despite adequate medication and advances made in the past decades regarding diabetes mellitus treatment. It is estimated that about 50% of diabetes mellitus patients achieve glucose control and that makes this category of population prone to microvascular and macrovascular complications such as diabetic retinopathy, diabetic neuropathy, myocardial infarction or stroke that have a debilitating impact on patients quality of life. Therapeutic education is defined as the measures taken by diabetes specialist in order that the patient gains the ability to understand his illness, the importance of a healthy lifestyle and acquires the skills necessary to adjust his diet, monitor his treatment and adjust it in order to prevent complications. The present paper explores the evidence from literature regarding the role therapeutic structured education for achieving the glycaemic, blood pressure and lipid target in diabetes mellitus patients.

Key words: diabetes mellitus, structured therapeutic education.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus complications are highly prevalent, the UKPDS study demonstrating that at the moment of diagnosis approximately 50% of patients have at least one microvascular or macrovascular complication (Liu et.al, 2010). Moreover the mortality of diabetic patients is usually determined by cardiovascular events, such as acute coronary syndromes, stroke, peripheral artery disease in approximately 80% of cases (Liu et.al, 2010). In the context of such disease burden much attention has been given to preventive measures. A good glycaemic control defined as HbA1c < 7%, adequate blood pressure generally defined as < 140/90 mmHg and a good control of blood pressure, LDL-cholesterol < 100 mg/dL (American Diabetes Association, Standards Of Medical Care In Diabetes-2018), are the goals that generally must be achieved by diabetes mellitus patients in order to reduce the risk of apparition and progression of complications.

However few patients achieve the goals in diabetes mellitus despite the discovery and general availability of new medications such as: GLP-1

agonists, SGLT-2 inhibitors, long acting insulins such as glargine and very short acting insulin. A study realized in USA in demonstrated that in fact of all these new therapeutic options the prevalence of patients that achieve glucose control is declining from 52.2% during the interval 2003-2010 to 50.9% during the interval 2011-2014 (Carls G. et al, 2017). Therefore if the pharmaceuticals measures are not enough for achieving the targets in diabetes mellitus, non-pharmaceutical measures need to be taken and the patient's education is one of them.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In our paper we analyse different studies that explore the impact on improving the diabetes mellitus patients education on the achievement of glycaemic, lipid and blood pressure targets, the analysed research is of high quality, review articles or meta-analysis indexed in PUBMED database.

The purpose of this paper is to define structured therapeutic education in diabetes mellitus, to explore its components, to determine how it can be provided to patients and to determine its efficiency. Also the purpose of the paper is to draw attention to the local administration to elaborate programmes for improving therapeutic education of diabetes patients in order to increase their quality of life, to reduce the costs associated with healthcare, to increase their productivity and decrease work absenteeism generated by diabetes complications.

In the study we also assessed the prevalence of glucose, blood pressure and lipid control in a cohort of patients with diabetes mellitus evaluated in the Clinical County Emergency Hospital of Oradea. 218 patients were retrospectively evaluated. For each patient were determined HbA1c, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure and LDL-cholesterol. Good glycaemic control was defined as HbA1c<7%, good blood pressure control was defined as blood pressure<140/90mmHg and ideal value of LDL-cholesterol<100mg/dL.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Structured therapeutic education is a key components of diabetes management and represents the measures and actions done by a specialist or a team of specialist trained in diabetes education addressed to the diabetic

patients that has the purpose to make them capable to manage their own disease and to make to necessary adjustment to achieve the therapeutic goals in order prevent or delay the apparition of complications.

This type of education is called structured because it follows a curriculum, the information is structured in a way that the patient gains knowledge and skills step by step and can adapt and apply in his life the principles that he learns. Every diabetes educational programme should be comprehensive, flexible, should respond to the patient needs both the clinical ones and the psychological ones (Yorke E. et.al, 2018). The curriculum of a structured education programme generally includes gaining information and knowledge regarding the following aspects of diabetes management:

- theoretical information – what is diabetes mellitus; what is hypertension and dyslipidaemia; what are the complications of diabetes mellitus and how they will impact the patient's life.
- information and skills regarding a healthy nutrition – what are the daily nutritional requirements; what is the proportion between carbohydrates, lipids and proteins in the diet; what are the categories of food that need to be weighted (bread, cereals, pasta, potatoes) and the ones that can be consumed in any quantity (vegetables); which are the healthy carbohydrates with low glycaemic index; which categories of lipids are recommended; how to calculate the quantity of carbohydrates consumed in a day; how to calculate the quantity of carbohydrates consumed at a meal and adapt the dose of rapid insulin to it.
- information and skills regarding physical activity – how many minutes of physical activity are recommended in a day; what kind of physical activity is recommended according to the patient's cardiovascular comorbidities; how to adapt the intake of carbohydrates to doing physical effort; how to adapt the doses of insulin to physical activity.
- information and skills regarding self- monitoring of glucose values – how many times a day should the glycaemia be measured if the patient is on long-acting insulin; how many times a day should the glycaemia be measured if the patient is on long-acting insulin and short-acting insulin; how to adjust the basal insulin dose according to basal glycaemia; what is the frequency of determination of HbA1c; how to utilize the insulin pump, how to adjust the basal rate, how to adjust the prandial bolus.
- information and skills regarding recognition of hypoglycaemia.
- information of skills regarding recognition of diabetes complications and diabetic foot prevention and care.

The complexity of such of a diabetic educational programme is illustrated in the above examples. However the benefits are undoubtable, the patient learns to manage his own disease in many directions such as nutritional therapy, exercise, foot care, lifestyle behaviour (Mokabel, F. M, 2017).

Therefore structured education is an activity centred around the patient and allows the patients to be active participants in their treatment (Golay, A et. al, 2008).

The efficacy of structured therapeutic education has been confirmed in many studies, but the most important evidence comes from metaanalysis. The educational programme can be individual or addressed to a group of patients, it can be done in ambulatory conditions or in the hospital. One study involved 998 patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus divided in two groups, one group, 498 patients, were assigned to a systematic health education model while 500 were assigned to a conventional model (Zhang, Y et.al, 2018). It is interesting in this study the modalities by which the education programme has been put in practice. Patients were educated monthly for two years, which means that the information can be adequately understood and by being reinforced it becomes part of the behaviour. The quality of the provided information in the study and the complexity of it make the study a model for such further educational studies. In the study (Zhang, Y et.al, 2018) patients benefited of: 1) image education – they were provided videos about diabetes mellitus and hypertension; 2) dissemination of informative materials; 3) nutritional therapy advice made easy with the help of a simplified plate composed of $\frac{1}{2}$ vegetables, $\frac{1}{2}$ meat and $\frac{1}{2}$ carbohydrates; 4) face to face lectures; 5) self-monitoring of glucose values; 6) screening for complications; 7) monthly evaluation of the therapeutic interventions; 8) improvement of the past measures according to the results of permanent monitoring. Compared with the group that received conventional education, the group that benefited from systematic health education had a value of HbA1c lower with 0.67%, LDL-cholesterol lower with 9.6mg/dL, systolic blood pressure lower with 10.83 mmHg and body-mass index lower with 0.23 kg/m². The differences regarding HbA1c, blood pressure, LDL-cholesterol were all statistically significant. Therefore the results confirmed the efficacy of a structured diabetes educational programme.

One meta-analysis (Yorke E. et.al, 2018) concluded, after analysing 36 studies that explore the efficacy of structured education in diabetes mellitus most of them including population of Caucasian origin, that structured therapeutic education is effective in improving glucose control and in reducing the risk of hypoglycaemia.

In our study 218 patients were evaluated regarding glucose, blood pressure and LDL-cholesterol control. Their mean age was 58.27 years, 51.38% were female, 68.26% lived in urban environment and 61.01% were obese. Regarding the glucose, blood pressure and lipid control in diabetes mellitus patients from Bihor County (Figure 1) it can be observed that the control of these risk factors is poor, but in accordance to the worldwide situation, as shown above even in USA only 50.9% of patients achieve glucose control.

Figure 1. Prevalence of glucose, blood pressure and LDL-cholesterol control in patients from Bihor County

CONCLUSION

Structured therapeutic education is a complex process that involves development of numerous abilities by the diabetic patient, it can be realized either individual or in a group, but most important is an effective measure for improving glycaemic control, blood pressure values and lipid parameters reducing this way the risk of apparition and progression of diabetic complications. In Bihor county prevalence of cardiovascular risk factors control in diabetes mellitus patients is reduced, but comparable to the global

situation, which demonstrates the need of local implementation of educational programmes for diabetes mellitus patients. Pharmacotherapy of diabetes mellitus is not sufficient for glucose control, it appears that against all innovations diet and physical effort remain as important for a good prognosis.

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EVALUATION OF THE PHARMACEUTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ARTIFICIAL TEARS

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Abstract

The eye is an essential organ, very sensitive and delicate. The diseases that can reach the eye are numerous, among them being with a quite high frequency a condition called dry eye syndrome or dry keratoconjunctivitis.

The objective of the study is to optimize an artificial tear formula and pharmaceutical characterization to be well tolerated when applied on the conjunctiva.

The use of artificial tears has a certain limitation, because human tears have a complex behavior, whereas artificial tears cannot completely replace them.

Special attention is paid to the preparation of ophthalmic preparations for obtaining drugs with good tolerability in the eye area. Tolerability is dependent on therapeutic efficacy, determining optimal bioavailability.

We obtained 6 formulas of artificial tears based on 940 carbomer neutralized with NaOH 10% and triethanolamine respectively.

After preparation, the pH, the refractive index, the density and the viscosity were determined for the artificial tears.

The formula containing 0.3% carbomer 940 shows the physical characteristics specific to the ophthalmic preparations specified in the compendial prevision.

Key words: ophthalmic preparations, artificial tears, carbomer 940

INTRODUCTION

One of the characteristics of the eyeball is the surface covered by the tear fluid, which the eyelids continuously display, preventing the drying of the exposed part of the air and facilitating the closing of the eyelids.

Dry eye syndrome is a disease of which a large part of the population suffers, its prevalence is between 5 - 35%, depending on the age group: 5.7% in women under 50; 9.8% women over 75; and 3.9% in men 50-54 years old; 7.6% in men over 80 years.(Cerenea P., 2002)

Thus, the quality of the vision and the daily activities are affected, being difficult to diagnose because there is no correlation between symptoms and signs; there are no standardized tests and well-defined

criteria for diagnosis.(Nilforoushan M.R et al., 2005)

Artificial tears were created to meet this irritant syndrome, which through their highly effective properties have given good results. (Calvao-Santos G.et al., 2011; McCann L.C et al. 2012) It is the most effective method in the treatment of dry eye.

The ocular mucosa has a special sensitivity that is accentuated during the treatment period, the ocular lesions have a strictly local specificity.(Hayati F et al.,2018)

These ocular pharmaceutical forms, must be formulated in such a way as to mimic natural tears, as far as their components and action are concerned.(Moshirfar M. et al., 2014)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Materials: The components used are of adequate purity, attested by analysis bulletins issued by the manufacturer: Carbomer 940 (Elton Corporation SA Romania), triethanolamine (Merck KgaA, Germany, lot K49471379), sodium hydroxide (CHEM 118109252, Nordic Chemicals SRL, Romania), ethyl alcohol (Coman Product Romaina, lot 27649). The water was purified by distillation to be of physico-chemical and sterile purity. (FR X, 2018; PhEur 9th, 2017)

Preparation of artificial tear formulas:

To achieve the proposed objective, respectively of obtaining an artificial tears formula, we developed and evaluated six formulas based on Carbomer 940, dispersed in hydro-alcoholic mixtures and neutralized with triethanolamine, respectively NaOH (Tabel 1).

Tabel 1.

Artificial tears formulas

Components	Artificial tears formulas					
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	N ₁	N ₂	N ₃
Carbomer 940	0,1 g	0,2g	0,3 g	0,1 g	0,2 g	0,3 g
Ethyl alcohol	2,00 g	2,00 g	2,00 g	2,00 g	2,00 g	2,00 g
NaOH 10%	-	-	-	1,00 g	2,00 g	3,00 g
Triethanolamine	0,1 g	0,2 g	0,3 g	-	-	-
Propyl p-hydroxy benzoate	0,01 g	0,01 g	0,01 g	0,01 g	0,01 g	0,01 g
Distilled water	100,00 g	100,00 g	100,00 g	100,00 g	100,00 g	100,00 g

Three solutions of different concentrations of triethanolamine were prepared (fomrula T1 concentration 0.1%, formula T2 concentration 0.2%, formula T3 concentration 0.3%) and three solutions with NaOH 10% (formula N 1 concentration 0.1%, formula N 2 concentration 0.2%, formula N3 concentration 0.3%).

After preparation, the artificial tears were conditioned in containers corresponding to the physical state (Lupuliasa D. et al., 2019; Popovici I. et al., 2011).

Characterization of the artificial tear formulation:

In the evaluation of artificial tears I appreciated physicochemical properties.

Measurements were performed at 33°C, which corresponds to the temperature of the ocular surface. (Acara D. et al, 2018)

The pH of the formulas was determined at room temperature with a pH-meter calibrated (model Inolab 7310 with electrode SenTix 81 Plus). The refractive index and density were measured with an Optika Abbe 2 WA Refractometer, respectively a calibrated ISOLAB picnometer, at 22°C.

To determine the rheological properties of the six tear formulas we used the Visco Ball viscometer, with a drop ball for transparent Newtonian liquids. All measurements were performed in triplicate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The formulations in which the neutralization with NaOH 10% was performed are presented as clear liquids, with a low viscosity (formulas N1, N2), and the formula N3 has a higher viscosity.

In the case of formulas neutralized with Triethanolamine (formulas T1, T2, T3) they are homogeneous, and the viscosity increases in increasing order of the concentration of triethanolamine.

In formula T1 we observe a slightly viscous liquid form, in formula T2 we notice an increase in viscosity, and in formula T3 we obtained a homogeneous and transparent hydrogel.

The refractive index determined with respect to the environment (air), is expressed as the ratio of the speed of light in the environment and the speed of light absorbed by the preparation.

The refractive index values of artificial tear formulas are presented in table 2.

Tabel 2

Characteristics of artificial tears

Formulas artificial tears	Refraction index	pH	Density (g/cm ³)
T ₁	1,3345	8,0	0,984
T ₂	1,3349	8,0	0,969
T ₃	1,3350	7,5	1,128
N ₁	1,3349	8,5	0,986
N ₂	1,3350	8,5	0,994
N ₃	1,3351	8,5	0,996

Density determinations were used to assess the viscosity of artificial tear formulas.

The pH value of the tear fluid is 7.4 (7.35 - 7.95); however, the pH values tolerated by ocivariate were experimentally determined to be between 7.5 and 9.5; slightly alkaline solutions being better tolerated by the eye than acidic ones.

The pH values of the artificial tears we obtain are included within these limits.

In assessing the viscosity of artificial tears, the dynamics of rotation and falling of the ball through the cylindrical tube were taken into account, slightly inclined and filled with the sample to be analyzed during the fall. [24]

The balls are borosilicate glass, Ni-Fe alloy, stainless steel with diameter and density specified in the technical data sheet of the viscometer. The viscosity values are included in the table 3.

Tabel 3

The rheological characteristics of artificial tears

Formulas artificial tears	Constance of the bile mPa.s. cm³/g.s	Fall time t(s)	Result
N₁	0,007	30,58	0,259
N₂	0,007	81	0,683
N₃	0,09	460	49,845
T₁	0,09	227	145,379
T₂	4,5	330	9995,53
T₃	4,5	335	9998,21

We mention that in the literature the tears have a viscosity that should not exceed the limit of 40-50mPa·s [2, 3], so the only artificial tear formula that meets this requirement is N3 having a viscosity of 49,845 mPa·s.

CONCLUSIONS

Artificial tears are used in irritant eye and dry eye syndromes, conditions in which the amount of water in the tear fluid decreases.

The results obtained in this study have shown that the formulation of artificial tears in situ based on carbomer 940 has properties suitable for ophthalmic topical administration.

Formula N3 due to the physical and rheological characteristics (viscosity of 49,845 mPa·s) has a better tear film recovery potential being better tolerated.

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STUDY ON THE SPREAD OF THE SPECIES PASSIFLORA COERULEA(THE PASSION FLOWER) AND THE USE OF THIS IN MEDICINE

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Abstract

Passion flower is a voluble plant cultivated for its pleasantly smelling, solitary flowers, stellated with a diameter of 5-9 cm colored in gray-green-whitish numerous filaments purple at the base, white at the middle and blue towards the tip.

The flowers last only one day, but this shortcoming is compensated by the abundance of flowers that appear daily during the mounts of May through October.

It originates from the tropical and equatorial area of the globe. In areas with adverse climatic conditions (when the minimum temperature drops in winter below the plant resistance limit) it is cultivated in vegetation pots with free maintenance during the hot period of the year and with introduction into protected spaces (apartments) during the cold season.

In our areapassion flower is scarce both as an ornamental medicinal plant and one of economic utility (edible fruits. This situation can also be attributed to the lack of planting material as a consequence of the low yield to multiplication.

Key words:passifloracoerulea, cuttings.

INTRODUCTION

The experiences regarding the propagation of passion flowering plants were carried out between 2017 and 2019 in the greenhouse of Sântandrei, Bihor.

The working hypothesis was that by using a cheap and easily obtainable substrate, by providing a favorable microclimate, through uniform and effective shading, performance can be achieved.

Passion flower infusion (leafy plant branches) is recommended for the treatment of insomnia. The tincture is used in the treatment of anxiety and nervous agitation, and the fruit for insomnia, nervous disorders and weight loss.

The infusion is prepared from a teaspoon of dried plant over which it is poured a cup of boiling water and left for fifteen minutes.

Passiflora is contraindicated for pregnant women, breastfeeding women and children under the age of two.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

For propagation, cuttings with a length of 8-12 cm were harvested, which were rooted in three different periods in two types of substrates (table 1)

Table 1

Experimental data on rooting cuttings of *Passiflora coerulea*
(medium values 2017-2019)

Variants	Rooted cuttings		$\pm$ Δ	The meaning of the difference
	Number	%		
V1 – cuttings put to root in sand in May	130	100	-	-
V2 – cuttings put to root in sand in July	145	112	15	*
V3 - cuttings put to root in sand in September	168	129	38	***
V4 – cuttings put to root in 50 % peat + beech sawdust in May	146	112	16	*
V5 – cuttings rooted in 50 % peat + beech sawdust in July	159	122	29	**
V6 – cuttings rooted in 50 % peat + beech sawdust in September	175	135	45	***

The cuttings were rooted at a distance of 5 x 5 cm and a depth of 6 cm, properly settling the substrate to remove the air spaces in the rooting area. During the rooting period the temperature ranged from 18-25⁰ C in air and 18-21⁰ C in substrate and humidity between 70-80% in air and 60-65% in substrate.

The light was directed by covering the cuttings with a green net.

After rooting the cuttings were planted in pots with a diameter of 12 cm, in celery soil 40%, peat 30%, food 10, leaf soil 10%, sand 10%.

For the differentiation of the variants, observations and determinations were made regarding the duration of the rooting period, the proportion of the rooted cuttings, the number of roots.

RESULTS AND DISSCUTIONS

The rooting period of the cuttings was on average 137 days on variant 1, 119 days on variant 2, 109 days on variant 3, 101 days on variant 4, 93 days on variant 5 and 83 days on variant 6.

The buds that took root in September took root in a greater proportion than those in July and May.

The number of rooted cuttings of the 200 rooted cuttings in each variant had average values of 17 pieces in variant 6 (cuttings rooted in 50 peat + beech sawdust in September), 168 pieces in variant 3 (cuttings put in rooted) in September), 159 pieces in variant 5 (cuttings rooted in 50 peat +

beech sawdust in July), 146 pieces in variant 4 (cuttings put in rooted in 50 peat + beech sawdust in May), 145 pieces in the variant 2 (cuttings rooted in sand in July) and 130 (cuttings rooted in sand in May) in the control variant.

The differences analyzed statistically are very significant between variant 6 (cuttings rooted in 50 peat + sawdust beech in September), variant 3 (cuttings rooted in sand in September) and variant 1, the witness (cuttings put to root in the sand in May).

Distinctly significant differences are found between variant 5 (cuttings put to the root in 50 peat + beech sawdust in July) and variant 1 the witness (cuttings rooted in sand in May) and significant between variant 4 (cuttings rooted in 50 peat + sawdust in May), variant 2 (cuttings rooted in sand in July) and variant 1 control (cuttings put it in the sand in May).

CONCLUSION

Passion flower is a very valuable medicinal and ornamental plant, quite scarce in our area, situation that is due to the lack of planting material.

The rooting time of the cuttings was 112-135 days.

The best variant both in terms of the number of rooted cuttings as well as the number of roots on the cuttings and their length and thickness was the variant 6 with cuttings rooted in September in 50% peat and 50 % beech sawdust.

Increasing the rate of multiplication by cuttings of the *Passiflora coerulea* species (passion flower) can be stimulated by using the appropriate substrate and the appropriate period (time) for cuttings.

The method elaborated in the nursery of Sântandrei (Oradea) can contribute to the extension in culture of this very valuable plant.

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NEURO-PSYCHIATRIC COMPLICATIONS OF ALCOHOL USE

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Abstract

The medical consequences of alcohol use are one of the most important public health problems. Alcohol has very important direct effects on different organs and tissues. In chronic alcohol users, important physiological and morphological changes occur, which is manifested by an abnormal response to alcohol, medicines, toxins and even to ordinary nutrients. Almost all tissues and organs are vulnerable to the effects of alcohol. Almost all medical consequences of alcohol use are reversible with abstinence. A serious effect of the state of intoxication is that it also promotes hypothermia and death through hypothermia.

Key words: alcohol consequences, hypothermia, public health problems.

INTRODUCTION

Alcohol is used at the same time as a psychoactive substance and food. Alcohol consumed in small quantities is enjoyed by those who appreciate the taste and aroma of the respective drink and those who drink at times. Between the transition from harmless consumption, made in moderate quantities to excessive alcohol consumption is a very small step. (Zilberman, 2005)

Alcoholism has innumerable effects both on the person concerned and on those around us, and we talk about effects that relate to the psychological sphere but also to physical effects. Alcohol abuse is the cause of most accidents, including car accidents, for example. One third of fatal accidents are related to alcohol consumption, not to mention the thousands of injuries that result each year.(Ewing, 1984)

Alcohol consumption, even in moderate amounts, greatly increases the risk of having unprotected sex, thus increasing the risk of illness. In some cases more complicated "effects" appear, from the sphere of unwanted pregnancy. (Fuchs, 1995)

Another unpleasant effect, dangerous for both the person and the others, is violence and aggression. Under the influence of alcohol

consumption you can misinterpret a remark or gesture, which can lead to aggressive behavior and violence. (Sobell, 1995)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Alcohol slows the function of the central nervous system; alcohol blocks some of the messages that should reach the brain thus altering the person's perceptions, emotions, movement, sight and hearing. (Begleiter, 1972) (Mekeres, 2017)

In moderate amounts, alcohol can help the person to be more relaxed and less anxious. In larger quantities alcohol causes major changes in the brain thus resulting in intoxication. People who have abused alcohol will lose their concentration, the ability to express themselves coherently or to maintain their balance; they want to be disoriented and confused. (Eckardt, 1998).

Depending on the person, intoxication can make the consumer extremely friendly and talkative or very aggressive and nervous. Reaction speed is dramatically decreased, which is why driving cars after drinking alcohol is prohibited. (Khan, 2007)

When very large amounts of alcohol are consumed within a short period of time, alcohol intoxication may result. Alcohol intoxication is exactly what its name says: the body becomes intoxicated with too much alcohol. (Mukherjee, 2013)

Violent vomiting is one of the first signs of alcohol intoxication; extreme sleepiness, unconsciousness, shortness of breath, extremely low blood sugar, palpitations and even death are the results of alcohol intoxication. (Höjer, 1996).

In the state of intoxication a number of changes occur. The psychic disposition goes from good mood to depression, upset and aggression; the initiative will go from stimulation to inhibition; social behavior is affected and will go from facilitating contacts to aggression.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Neurological complications of alcohol use are represented by alcoholic dementia, stroke, symptomatic epileptic seizures, cerebral disorders, etc.

Alcoholic dementia is improperly named as such by some authors because it is due, in addition to the direct toxic effect of alcohol, to multiple nutritional and vitamin deficiencies induced by chronic alcoholism, as well as to repeated cranio-cerebral traumas. It appears in chronic alcoholics (former heavy drinkers) after many years of social degradation and marginalization. (Cheng, 2017).

The most common strokes in alcoholics are hemorrhagic, embolic and thrombotic in nature and are due to the presence of hypertension, dyslipidemia, atherosclerotic disease and / or coagulopathies. The presumption of a coagulopathy may also be responsible for the increased incidence of subdural hematomas in those suffering from cranio-cerebral trauma. (Mekeres, 2017)

Alcohol seizures are usually widespread, appear without aura, shortly (6 - 8 hours) after discontinuation and may increase withdrawal. The chronic use of alcohol and its repeated interruptions lead to the lowering of the threshold of the onset of the commissions. The risk of committing seizures is proportional to the amount of alcohol administered. Alcohol intoxication leads to coordination disorders and modifies motor skills - balance disorders.

The cause of alcoholic neuropathy is still debated. It is assumed to include both direct action on nerve fiber and indirect action through poor nutrition. In severe cases the nerves that regulate the internal functions of the body may be affected. Symptomatology may include: numbness, pain in the limbs, muscle weakness, muscle cramps, heat intolerance, especially after exercise, impotence in men, urinary incontinence, difficulty in urination, constipation, diarrhea, nausea, vomiting, etc.

Alcoholic amblyopia can occur in people with chronic alcohol use. Symptomatology includes vision disorders, including scotches and decreased visual acuity starting with the central portion of the visual field. The disorder is caused by the toxic effect of alcohol on the optic nerve, leading to optic neuropathy. Because alcohol generates depletion of the entire body of nutrients, alcohol amblyopia is linked to thiamine deficiency, which results in damage to the optic nerve. Alcoholic amblyopia is reversible if treated with a proper diet and multivitamins, especially thiamine (vitamin B1). Untreated results in irreversible damage to the optic nerve and loss of vision. (Behbehani, 2005)

CONCLUSIONS

In chronic alcohol users, important physiological and morphological changes occur, which is manifested by an abnormal response to alcohol, medicines, toxins and even to ordinary nutrients.

Almost all tissues and organs are vulnerable to the effects of alcohol.

Alcohol addiction over time causes altered feelings and relationships with family members, disturbing interpersonal relationships at work and in the circle of friends, reducing feelings of responsibility, neglecting children's education, delaying and absent from work, accidents at work and traffic, delinquency, divorce, loss of home and work.

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